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**Modelling Digital Agriculture:
a Method and AI-Infused Tool for Living Labs**

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*My deepest thanks to everyone
who supported me with love and trust
along this journey*

Summary

Digital technologies and Artificial Intelligence (AI) are increasingly transforming agricultural practices by introducing advanced sensing, data-driven monitoring, and decision support systems. These innovations reshape technical infrastructures, farm processes, and stakeholder roles within the agri-food value chain, while also having implications for the natural environment. Understanding these transformations is therefore essential for designing digital solutions that contribute to more sustainable agri-food systems. Requirements Engineering (RE) provides well-established techniques for gathering and representing stakeholder needs through visual models. In particular, semi-formal notations are widely used to capture different perspectives, such as domain, goals, and process. However, there is still little empirical evidence on the application of requirements modelling in agriculture and, more broadly, in participatory innovation environments. Moreover, the use of RE approaches in these contexts raises an End-User Development (EUD) challenge: enabling domain experts to actively shape and appropriate the modelling artefacts.

This thesis explores how modelling with semi-formal notations can enhance knowledge exchange in agricultural living labs, i.e., networks of heterogeneous stakeholders addressing common challenges through participatory activities. The research involved 20 European living labs undergoing digital transformation. In these settings, stakeholders needed structured representations to illustrate how farm processes change after the introduction of digital technologies, thereby supporting communication and analysis. The research employed a design science methodology, spanning iterative cycles of design and validation within the living labs. The practical challenges arising from this context guided the literature review and informed the design of the proposed artefacts grounded in RE and EUD. Specifically, the thesis tackles four challenges: the use of semi-formal notations in agricultural living labs; the engagement of living lab stakeholders in both the creation and interpretation of modelling languages; the design of support for novice and non-technical modellers in alignment with their capabilities; and the role of AI-based support within the requirements modelling landscape for digital agriculture.

Two main artefacts were developed and evaluated within the living labs: *PoMeLO* (PrOcess Modelling in Living labOratories), a RE method for modelling socio-technical transformations in agricultural living labs, and *ModeLLer*, an AI-infused EUD modelling tool designed to support novice modellers.

The thesis contributes empirical insights into requirements modelling in participatory contexts and provides one of the first in-depth studies in the agricultural domain. It bridges RE and EUD, adopts a Human-Centred AI perspective, and delivers reusable artefacts that can support further research as well as the adoption of requirements modelling practices in sustainable digital innovation.

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Part I

Problem Investigation

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Digital Agriculture

Agriculture has a prominent role in shaping a sustainable digital future. In 2009, the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) projected that the world population could reach around 9 billion by 2050, implying a significant increase in food demand [80]. This expansion will occur under tight resource constraints, as food production already relies on extensive land use and high freshwater consumption [81]. Indeed, climate change already poses risks to crop yields, placing additional strain on food production [103]. To address this, the United Nations 2030 Agenda—through its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—stresses the need to shift towards sustainable food production systems by promoting agricultural practices that enhance productivity while improving resource-use efficiency and limiting environmental pressures [217]. In Europe, the European Green Deal [64] sets out a comprehensive strategy to steer the transition towards a more resource-efficient economy, promoting actions that contribute to sustainability objectives in alignment with the SDGs. More specifically, in the 2023–2027 period, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) provides the main policy framework through which the European Union translates sustainability objectives into agricultural action, combining support for farm viability and food security with measures addressing climate change, natural resource management, and the long-term vitality of rural areas through the implementation of national strategic plans [65].

Within this context, the automation of agriculture is increasingly framed as an enabling condition for progress towards “No Poverty (SDG 1)” and “Zero Hunger” (SDG 2), alongside objectives related to environmental sustainability and climate action. Specifically, the FAO’s annual report 2022 [81] discusses how agricultural automation can enhance agrifood systems, while also stressing the need of environmental-friendly practices and for an inclusive adoption so that benefits do not concentrate only on those already advantaged.

Digital agriculture is enabled by a set of technologies that have progressively improved the management and automation of farming processes. Core components include Internet of Things (IoT) devices, such as soil-moisture, nutrient, and microclimate sensors; connectivity and computing infrastructures, such as cloud platforms and edge computing; and data-driven methods, namely techniques based on big data and machine learning for diagnosis and prediction. These technologies can be integrated with

robotics and autonomous systems to conduct field operations. In practice, this translates into complex solutions such as precision irrigation based on soil and weather observation, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for crop monitoring, stress detection, and targeted spraying, and robotic weeding [83].

1.1.1 Digitalisation as Socio-Technical Change

The historical evolution of agriculture is described as a sequence of innovation waves leading to five consecutive *revolutions*. These range from early mechanisation, industrialisation, and input intensification to data-driven Agriculture 4.0, and now to Agriculture 5.0, where technical capabilities extend beyond optimisation to more sustainable, adaptive, and human-centred services across the overall food production chain [31, 84]. Consequently, there is a growing focus on technological adoption beyond the development of cutting-edge solutions. Indeed, the introduction of digital technologies in agriculture triggers a complex process of socio-technical change called *digitalisation* that radically transforms the context in which human activities are performed [183]. Agricultural digitalisation presents challenges with double-edged effects, generating potential winners and losers [73].

The socio-cyber-physical system perspective proposed by Rijswijk et al. [183] supports this framing by conceptualising digital agriculture as an interplay between social components (actors, institutions, norms, and power relations), cyber components (data, software, algorithms, connectivity), and physical components (land, crops, animals, machinery), thereby foregrounding the need to account for multiple dimensions when assessing impacts. Within this framework, the authors call for applying a responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach [44] to digital agriculture, using problematisation as a structured way to anticipate both benefits and drawbacks and to clarify the conditions under which digitalisation can lead to desirable outcomes.

In line with this, recent research has analysed the social and ethical impacts of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in agriculture. The findings highlight that, while there are potential benefits, there are also specific concerns. These include issues related to farmers' ownership and control of data, labour displacement, skill gaps, and the impact on the non-human world [106, 188, 189].

Building on this, increasing attention from both the scientific community and international institutions [82, 97, 179, 226] is focused on strengthening collaboration between technical and socio-economic expertise. This effort aims to combine technical robustness with assessment of social, ethical, environmental, and economic factors. In practice, this means involving experts and stakeholders throughout the process of design, deployment, and evaluation. By doing so, we can identify requirements early and mitigate any potential negative impacts.

1.1.2 Stakeholder Involvement in Technological Development

The Information Systems (IS), Software Engineering (SE) and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) communities have always been active in promoting user involvement, particularly through research fields such as Requirements Engineering (RE) and End-User Development (EUD) [20].

In recent years, this commitment has gained renewed momentum as researchers and practitioners increasingly deal with the design and deployment of digital systems that are ever more pervasive and complex, and whose impacts extend beyond purely technical performance. As a result, the emphasis on increased engagement with end users and stakeholders has emerged not only from external demands, but also from the internal needs of these fields [12, 33, 57].

The Karlskrona Manifesto for Sustainability Design [27] introduces sustainability as a core concern for software-intensive systems and, consequently, frames it as a systemic property necessitating a transdisciplinary common ground. Accordingly, the work lays the groundwork for a unifying framework in which different actors are involved, including software practitioners, researchers, associations, educators, customers and users.

RE is recognised as a key area to address sustainability concerns [28]. However, the literature highlights two main challenges for RE in this space. First, a commitment to sustainability requires moving beyond the elicitation of system goals—often the traditional focus of RE—and adopting a broader perspective that anticipates the effects a system may have on the environment in which it will be deployed [74]. Second, emerging smart contexts such as smart cities and smart rural areas broaden RE into a more participatory social setting, where users are increasingly involved as co-creators. It is therefore necessary to adapt RE practices to effectively support diverse stakeholders, whose motivation and availability may vary widely, compared to traditional RE contexts [60].

In parallel, recent research in HCI calls to revitalise participation so that communities can actively shape technological solutions, with researchers taking a more engaged role grounded in participatory action research [33]. Within this context, *food and sustainability* have been positioned as a “grand challenge” for HCI [165], with scholars arguing that sustainability-oriented technologies need to be developed through deeper engagement with real-world contexts, long-term relationships with practitioners, and collaboration with bottom-up social movements [165].

From a practical perspective, the widespread availability of technological tools—such as handheld devices—together with an increasing digital literacy has expanded the end users’ capabilities and their potential value in collaborating on the development of complex AI-based systems [75]. Consequently, end users are increasingly framed as active contributors who can take on roles of co-designers, active learners, and engaged citizens, and EUD approaches are promoted as a foundational basis for participatory work spanning software development, education, and sustainable societies [76].

1.1.3 Living Labs

An approach particularly suited to exploring and assessing how digital technologies shape practices, needs, and outcomes *in context* is offered by living labs. By definition, a “living lab” (LL) is a physical or virtual interaction space in which stakeholders form *public–private–people partnerships* [121]. LLs involve professionals, companies, public agencies, universities, research institutes, and citizens who adopt open and user-driven innovation principles to collaboratively develop, prototype, validate, and test technologies, services, products, and systems in real-life settings [99]. Two main factors characterise these environments: early user involvement in the innovation process and experimentation in real-world contexts [223].

The review study by Alavi et al. [13] traces how the concept of LL has evolved over time in HCI, showing that the early notion of the *living laboratory*—initially framed as an instrumented domestic setting for observing everyday activities—has progressively expanded towards broader, more participatory, and innovation-oriented deployments. In synthesising this evolution, the review identifies five recurring strands of LL use: (1) *Visited places*: controlled, lab-like environments that resemble real settings (e.g., a mock apartment) where participants visit for short sessions, enabling tightly managed testing and observation; (2) *Instrumented places*: real homes, workplaces, or public settings equipped with sensors and data-collection infrastructure to capture situated behaviour with high ecological validity; (3) *Instrumented people*: studies centred on people carrying or wearing instruments (e.g., smartphones, wearables), allowing data collection across multiple contexts and often supporting larger-scale or longer-term observation; (4) *Lived-in places*: long-term, inhabited environments (e.g., residential facilities, campuses) where research infrastructure is embedded over time, supporting longitudinal inquiry into how technologies are adopted, adapted, and integrated into daily routines; (5) *Innovation spaces*: co-creation and experimentation ecosystems, where multiple stakeholders collaborate to ideate, prototype, and iteratively refine solutions in real-life contexts, prioritising participation and practical relevance over experimental control. Overall, the review highlights a clear shift from “technology tested in instrumented setting” toward in-the-wild, longitudinal, and co-creative infrastructures, where LLs become not only a place for evaluation but also a means to structure collaboration and learning around digital innovation *in context*. LLs also became progressively institutionalised, especially in Europe, through the establishment of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). This network contributed to consolidating LLs as a recognisable organisational model beyond isolated experimental initiatives by fostering a community of practice and promoting shared principles such as multi-stakeholder collaboration, real-world experimentation, and active user involvement in innovation processes [198].

Agricultural LLs are commonly established in rural areas and involve farmers, technical advisors, knowledge intermediaries, technology providers, consumers, policymakers, and others. All participants carry out co-design activities to address common goals, in close collaboration with universities and research institutes. Examples of challenges discussed in LLs include sustainable and organic farming practices, such as initiatives supporting niche organic vegetable production in regional contexts, smart agriculture experimenting with advanced digital technologies, including digital twins. Other examples address innovation in the food supply chain, greenhouse gas mitigation strategies, and regional sustainability planning. LLs can also differ significantly in terms of scale, governance structures, and technological maturity [46]. Several studies have increasingly positioned LLs as a relevant open-innovation approach for environmental sustainability and rural development [26, 29, 46, 237]. Berberi et al. [29] examine the factors that affect LL effectiveness in agricultural sustainability transitions. Their analysis highlights a dual role for *communication* and *shared understanding*: both *shared understanding* vs. *lack of shared understanding* and *good* vs. *poor communication* can act as enablers when effectively supported, but become barriers when absent or mismanaged. This underscores the strategic role of these dimensions in shaping LL success.

1.1.4 The LLs of the CODECS Project

As part of the Horizon Europe (HE) programme, the research project “Maximising the co-benefits of agricultural digitalisation through conducive digital ecosystems (CODECS)” [1] engages stakeholders in evaluating the costs and benefits of agricultural digitalisation through interaction with 20 LLs across Europe.

The project runs from 2022 to 2026 with the overarching ambition to “*improve the motivation and the capacity of European farmers to understand and adopt digitalisation as an enabler of sustainable and transformative change*”¹. The various research teams involved in the project implement and evaluate different approaches to analyse the costs and benefits of digitalisation while directly engaging with the LLs. CODECS LLs are organised as 20 local networks across Europe, each rooted in an existing group of actors who are actively exploring digital technologies in agriculture².

Figure 1.1: Structure of CODECS Living labs, with the key actors involved and the three main components shaping the LL context: the focal action situation, the activities, and the digital solution.

The CODECS LLs, illustrated in figure 1.1, consist of a constellation of actors, with farmers key participants and the primary problem owners; accordingly, LL activities typically revolve around their needs and challenges. Depending on the setting, they may participate as individual farms, as well as through collective organisations such as

¹A complete overview of CODECS (grant agreement no. 101060179) can be found on the project website, <https://www.horizoncodecs.eu>. Last visited 5 February 2026

²A map of CODECS LLs is available at <https://www.horizoncodecs.eu/living-labs/>. Last visited 5 February 2026.

To orchestrate these analyses, CODECS has adopted Ostrom’s Social-Ecological Systems framework [147], a multi-level scheme of concepts and variables to describe systems in terms of actors, resources and capabilities. The framework enables comparison in the gathering of knowledge in multiple LLs and supports the analysis. The analysis covers several aspects, such as the role of digital resources (data, application systems, etc.), digital resource systems (platforms, infrastructures, clouds, etc.), digital governance systems (data sharing and use regulation), as well as actors and capabilities that are involved in the digitalisation process. For the purposes of CODECS research, we assume that the different components of a *focal action situation* leverage digital technologies for different outcomes.

At the project level, LL activities unfold in annual cycles alternating trainings, data collection and output. Each training session launches a new phase, after which LLs carry out field work at the local level involving stakeholders relevant to the *focal action situation*, then provide structured feedback to project coordinators for analysis and synthesis³.

1.1.5 Process Modelling in CODECS

One of the project activities within the Work Package 3 “*Analysis of Digital Ecosystems*” is Task 3.3, “*Farm Socio-Technical Process Modelling of Use Cases*” which focuses on representing how the introduction of digital technologies transforms farm processes. This task originated from a practical need: using standard, graphical representations to facilitate knowledge exchange across project participants and heterogeneous disciplinary perspectives. The representations should be understandable to all stakeholders involved in the LLs and useful for further impact analysis, e.g., cost-benefit analysis, carried out by experts in agricultural economics and social science.

To carry out this task, a research team at the Institute of Information Science and Technologies of the National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISTI) was involved since the early project setup in mid-2021⁴. The support of the team was required, given their expertise in model-based techniques applied in previous EU projects, e.g., LearnPAD [51].

To lay the foundation for the task, the research team conducted combined focus groups within the project consortium and performed field observations. First, two focus groups were carried out with the project coordinator, who had previously gathered ideas and requirements from 33 consortium partners through informal meetings; these sessions served to consolidate a first concept of the intended process-modelling approach and contributed to the project proposal submitted in September 2021 and subsequently approved by the European Commission in February 2022. Second, an observation study was carried out on July 19, 2022 through a one-day visit to a fruit farm in Tuscany, Italy, which is adopting a precision irrigation technology. The output of the visit was a textual report redacted by the agronomists who participated in the visit, describing the farm context, i.e., technology, stakeholders, and activities. The goal of the activity was twofold: i) understand a LL context that could be similar to those of CODECS; ii)

³A detailed description of LL coordination can be found on the project deliverable D8.6, https://www.horizoncodecs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/D8-6_ReportLivingLab_SetupResultsUpdateM36_30092025.pdf. Last visited 5 February 2026

⁴The author of this thesis was not yet part of the team during the project definition phase, as she joined CNR-ISTI as a post-graduate research fellow in July 2022.

understand what type of process-relevant information could be collected about a LL by domain experts without software engineering expertise, i.e., the typical profile who was expected to collect information to be later used for modelling, according to the initial concept of the approach. For clarification, Annex 1 [130] contains the report produced by one of the agronomists after the field visit and shared with the CNR team.

1.2 Research Challenge

The research problem addressed in this thesis originated from challenges raised within the CODECS project and was iteratively shaped by perspectives from the literature and interactions with the project LLs. Specifically, this thesis investigates four underexplored aspects of requirements modelling.

1.2.1 Research Gaps

(i) Use of semi-formal notations in participatory contexts. At the project level, there was an initial request to develop visual models to describe the transformation occurring in farm business processes after digitalisation. These representations were supposed to support communication among LL stakeholders and to enable subsequent socio-economic analyses (Task 3.3, “*Farm Socio-Technical Process Modelling of Use Cases*”). In this regard, RE makes extensive use of visual representations to systematically capture user needs and translate them into system requirements [166]. This line of work, commonly referred to as Model-driven Requirements Engineering (MoDRE) [18], leverages semi-formal notations, primarily Goal-Oriented Requirements Engineering (GORE) notations [98], as well as other structural or behavioural languages such as business process modelling notation [61]. Prior research in the agrifood sector has explored MoDRE strategies [21, 173, 201]. In addition, RE methods have been proposed to integrate complementary representations to analyse socio-technical systems from multiple perspectives [186]. However, MoDRE-based approaches that explicitly focus on the transformative aspects of agricultural digitalisation appear to have received comparatively limited attention. Moreover, evidence on the effectiveness of these modelling approaches, especially in participatory, non-industrial contexts, remains limited, suggesting the need for further empirical investigation.

(ii) Involvement of domain experts in modelling. A team of agronomists collaborating on the task expressed interest in actively participating in model development, with the intention of incorporating the modelling approach into their own practices. In this regard, the benefits of user involvement throughout the software development process have long been a key focus of RE research [8, 20, 62, 167]. Moreover, model-based approaches are among the most established techniques within the broad range of empirical practices that can be applied to enhance user participation [8, 23]. However, within the RE literature, studies reporting concrete applications of modelling in participatory contexts are limited, and digital agriculture remains underexplored.

From another perspective, EUD broadly concerns supporting non-professional programmers in the appropriation of software development practices [125]. However, within

the EUD literature, requirements elicitation and modelling have received less explicit attention than other stages of the software development process.

We argue that bridging RE and EUD may offer a useful lens for supporting domain experts in requirements modelling, thereby addressing this gap.

(iii) EUD approaches for novice modellers. Several studies examining practitioners' experience with MoDRE notations point to recurring challenges mainly regarding modelling tools (e.g., complex interactions, interoperability issues) and notations (e.g., difficulties in remembering the complete set of notation elements) [55, 193, 220]. These challenges also emerged during modelling in CODECS. The difficulties appear to stem mainly from poor usability of the modelling tools [11] and notation-related aspects such as low semantic transparency and poor visual expressiveness [152].

Beyond practical aspects, some studies remark on the cognitive effort required by modelling, especially for non-experts [126, 144]. Indeed, previous research has characterised modelling as a problem-solving activity, conceptually linking it with key computational thinking skills, such as abstraction and decomposition [34, 63, 144, 200, 231].

To address these challenges, recent studies have investigated the assistance needs of modellers, stressing the importance of enhanced modelling tools [126, 193], and have proposed user-centred solutions [115, 118, 232]. Furthermore, a growing body of literature explores user-assisting systems to provide context-aware modelling suggestions [14].

However, these approaches remain fragmented, often tied to specific modelling languages and developed mainly for either industrial or educational settings. Consequently, targeted support for novice modellers, particularly those with non-technical backgrounds, appears to remain underexplored.

(iv) AI-enhanced requirements modelling. Recent advancements in machine learning and generative AI have attracted growing attention to automated modelling in RE [191, 216, 234]. In particular, large language models (LLMs) are increasingly used to generate models from natural-language requirements [37, 71, 114], and the reverse direction has also been explored [111]. Beyond technical progress, Abrahão et al. [9] raise concerns that fully automated modelling may lead to reduced human control and biases originating from training data. On this basis, the authors highlight the need to adopt a Human-Centred AI (HCAI) perspective, thereby advocating for the design of AI-infused solutions that enable users to verify and refine model outputs [9].

Overall, current contributions remain largely technique-driven, and there is limited empirical evidence on how users may actually interact with such systems in practice. This points to the need for studies that clarify modellers' assistance needs and inform the design of more tailored AI-based functionalities for their support.

1.2.2 Research Questions

In summary, the gaps outlined above provide directions for empirical investigation and lead to the overarching research question: *How can MoDRE-based techniques support knowledge exchange in agricultural living labs addressing the challenge of digitalisation?*

Therefore, the thesis addresses the following research questions (RQs):

1. How can we carry out process modelling using semi-formal notations within agricultural living labs?
2. How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations?
3. How can we empower novice and non-technical stakeholders in requirements modelling?
4. How do domain experts experience requirements modelling with a block-based AI-infused tool?

1.3 Research Methodology

Given the “how” orientation of the overarching question, we structured the research as a design science project, following Wieringa’s methodology [227] to develop a *treatment*, i.e., one or more artefacts, that addresses the RQs.

We framed the project within two complementary contexts: (i) a *social* context, represented by the CODECS LLs in which the problem is situated and the treatment is validated under real-world conditions, and (ii) a *knowledge* context, grounded in existing literature, that motivates and informs design choices.

In line with the methodology, we distinguish between *design problems* and *knowledge questions*. Design problems concern the development of artefacts intended to improve the social context, while knowledge questions concern the empirical investigation of such artefacts and their effects. Accordingly, the research questions combine both perspectives. RQ1 and RQ3 are mainly framed as design problems. RQ2 and RQ4 are instead framed as knowledge questions.

The research, therefore, progressed through multiple engineering cycles to transfer the artefact into the LLs problem context, aiming to improve (i.e., “treat”) the identified conditions. Each cycle comprised three tasks, namely problem investigation, solution design, and treatment validation. Part of the treatment also progressed through implementation and evaluation tasks. These are reported in a dedicated section of the thesis (Chapter 6).

1.3.1 Design Science Overview

Figure 1.3 outlines the design science project. Note that four cycles iteratively spanned investigation, design and validation tasks, but to provide a comprehensive view of the thesis, we organise this overview by task, aggregating findings from multiple iterations. The remainder of this dissertation is therefore structured around the four RQs presented in 1.2.2.

Investigation The literature review was prompted by four high-level goals (shown in the yellow callouts at the top of the figure). These originated from the needs of the CODECS community and were iteratively refined based on insights from initial project

Figure 1.3: Overview of the design science project, structured within four iterations spanning problem investigation, solution design, artefact validation, implementation and evaluation.

interactions and feedback gathered during validation activities. These concern: (i) develop a stakeholder-friendly approach to represent process transformation in LLS, relying on standard modelling notations; (ii) actively involve domain experts—in particular agronomists participating in CODECS—in the creation and refinement of models, and consequently involve LL stakeholders in model interpretation; (iii) simplify modelling practices and empower end users by providing a modelling solution that lowers entry

barriers for non-expert modellers, enabling the process modelling practice to be adopted beyond the initial project context; (iv) integrate AI-based assistance strategies to enhance modelling and support novice modellers.

Accordingly, the analysis of the literature informed the four RQs presented and, in turn, initiated four corresponding design iterations—one for each RQ.

Design This task generated two artefacts: (i) a RE method, “*PoMeLO—PrOcess Modelling in Living labOratories*”, and (ii) an EUD tool, *ModeLLer*, where the capital “LL” refers to living labs. Each artefact was developed over two dedicated iterations, each focused on either generating an initial version or improving it. The RE method was built within a participatory action research methodology [127, 229], while the tool was informed by meta-design principles [77]. These methodological aspects are discussed further in dedicated sections throughout the dissertation. The following outputs were produced during the four iterations: 1) models and data collection procedure: a preliminary method, including a set of models and a procedure for data collection in the LL context; 2) a formalisation procedure that complements the method translating elicited knowledge into visual representations; 3) a block-based modelling tool for end users; 4) an AI-infused modelling tool, i.e., an extension of the tool with AI-based functionalities.

Validation This task concerned the empirical validation of the outputs produced in the design step. Specifically, it comprised: (1) assessment of the preliminary method through focus groups (n=3) with agronomists and LL stakeholders (n=15); (2) validation of the final method through a field experiment involving agronomist–modellers (n=4) and LL stakeholders (n=60) validating a case during a plenary project meeting; (3) validation of a prototype of the tool through (i) a cognitive walkthrough with experts in RE and HCI, and (ii) a user study with end users (n=30); and (4) validation of the improved tool through (i) a technical assessment of LLM capabilities for model-to-text transformations, and (ii) a Wizard of Oz study with agronomists (n=8).

Implementation As part of the process modelling activity carried out in CODECS, the RE method was implemented and transferred into the CODECS LLs (n=19, total stakeholders n~350). Concretely, this involved applying the data collection procedure across LLs, validating the collected information through plenary LL activities, and applying the formalisation procedure to produce representations of the elicited processes.

Evaluation Finally, an evaluation task combined (1) focus groups with LLs for model agreement, and (2) two TAM-based surveys to assess overall acceptance of the approach.

1.4 Contributions

This thesis provides contributions to both research and practice.

From a research perspective, it advances RE by proposing a method for eliciting and modelling requirements in agricultural LLs, supported by a dedicated tool and grounded in real-world LL practice.

Furthermore, it contributes to EUD and HCAI by designing and evaluating an AI-infused modelling system tailored to novice modellers, and grounded within CT frameworks for the design and assessment of EUD tools.

More broadly, the thesis helps bridge RE and EUD by providing one of the first empirical experiences of end-user requirements modelling in LL settings.

This research also reports empirical evidence on (i) the use of MoDRE languages in real-world contexts, (ii) the experience of domain experts in requirements modelling in their specific domain, and (iii) the forms of support that end users need when modelling with AI-assisted tools.

From a practice perspective, the work contributes reusable artefacts: 1) the RE method is released as a toolkit comprising a data-collection procedure, a formalisation procedure, and concise guidance for model interpretation; 2) the modelling tool is released as open source and can be adopted in LLs as well as in educational contexts; 3) the thesis makes available open datasets (Zenodo), including 19 Living Lab reports, 19 corresponding models produced in CODECS, and interaction logs from the tool evaluation.

Together, these artefacts and datasets enable replication and further applications of the method, support secondary analyses, and provide resources for both researchers (e.g., in SE and LL studies) and practitioners.

1.5 Publications

We list below the journal and conference papers that form the basis of this thesis published by the time of writing:

1.5.1 Journals

[JSS] (under review after first-round revision) Mannari C., Sportelli M., Meesala H., Okoye O. F., Lepore F., Bacco F. M., Brunori G., Malizia A., Ferrari A., “End-user Requirements Modelling: an Experience Report in Agricultural Living Labs”. In Special Issue “Social REsponsibility” in *Journal of Systems and Software*. Extension of paper [REFSQ25].

[BIT] Mannari C., Turchi T., Versino S., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Conati C., Malizia A., “Assessing Computational Thinking through Integrated Approaches: the Case of ModeLLer”. In Special Issue “End-User Development in the AI Era” in *Behaviour & Information Technology*. Extension of paper [IS-EUD25] (to appear).

[AGRSYS] Soma K., Brunori G., Giagnocavo C., Meulman F., Ryan M., Heredia Hortigüela R., Iliopoulos C., Paulus M., Ferrari A., Kilis E., Grando S., Bellon-Maurel V., Knierim A., Gobrecht A., Selnes T., Ortolani L., Bacco M., Mannari C., “Sustainable digitalisation - a system thinking approach for determining costs and benefits in the agri-sector”, *Agricultural Systems* 231 (2026) 104529.doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2025.104529 [204].

1.5.2 Conferences

[AVI26] Mannari C., Turchi T., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Conati C., Malizia A., “Designing Adaptive AI Assistance for Block-Based Modelling: A Wizard of Oz Study with Do-

main Experts”. In Proceedings of the 2026 International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces (AVI '26). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 41, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3811427.3811448> (2026) [142]

[IS-EUD25] Mannari C., Turchi T., Frosali C., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Conati C., Malizia A., “Assessing Computational Thinking Skills Through Artefacts: The Case of Mod-eLLer”. In: Santoro, C., Schmidt, A., Matera, M., Bellucci, A. (eds) End-User Development. IS-EUD 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 15713. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-95452-8_19. (2025) [140]

[REFSQ25] Mannari C., Sportelli M., Meesala H., Okoye O. F., Lepore F., Bacco F. M., Brunori G., Malizia A., Ferrari A., “End-user requirements modelling: An experience report from digital agriculture”. In: Hess, A., Susi, A. (eds) Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality. REFSQ 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 15588. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-88531-0_22 (2025) [137]

[MetroAgriFor24] Mannari C.; Sportelli M.; Okoye O. F.; Bacco F. M.; Ferrari A.; Malizia A., “Towards a toolkit for socio-technical process modelling in agriculture: a pilot study”. IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry (MetroAgriFor). (2024) [136]

[MetroAgriFor23] Mannari C., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Ortolani L., Lai M. B., Mignani C., Silvi A., Malizia A., Brunori G., “A methodology for process modelling in living labs to foster agricultural digitalisation”. 2023 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry (MetroAgriFor). (2023) [132]

1.5.3 Workshops

[MoDRE25] Mannari C., Turchi T., Bacco F. M., Malizia A., “Assisting Stakeholders in Class Diagram Interpretation with LLMs: a Work in Progress”. Submitted to the 15th International Model-Driven Requirements Engineering (MoDRE) co-located with 2025 IEEE 33rd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE). (2025) [139]

[MoDRE24] Mannari C.; Bacco F. M.; Spagnolo G. O.; “Towards a Method for Modelling Socio-Technical Process Transformation in Digital Agriculture”. 2024 IEEE 32nd International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW). IEEE (2024) [135]

[COPDA24] Mannari C., Anichini E., Bacco M., Ferrari A., Turchi T., Malizia A., “Mod-eLLer – Enabling end-users to model systems: a case study in digital agriculture”. Proceedings of the Eighth International Workshop on Cultures of Participation in the Digital Age: Differentiating and Deepening the Concept of “End User” in the Digital Age, co-located with the International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces (AVI 2024) Arenzano, Italy, June 4, 2024 (2024) [134]

1.5.4 Posters

[RE23] Mannari C., Anichini E., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Turchi T., Malizia A., “Mod-eLLer - a prototype to support requirements elicitation in co-design environments”. IEEE

31st International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE), Hannover, Germany, 2023, pp. 367-368, doi: 10.1109/RE57278.2023.00055. (2023) [131]

[REFSQ23] Mannari C., Bacco M., Spagnolo G. O., Malizia A., “Digitalisation of Agriculture: Development and Evaluation of a Model-based Requirements Engineering Process”. In: A. Ferrari, B. Penzenstadler, I. Hadar, S. Oyedeji, S. Abualhaija, A. Vogelsang, G. Deshpande, A. Rachmann, J. Gulden, A. Wohlgemuth, A. Hess, S. Fricker, R. Guizzardi, J. Horkoff, A. Perini, A. Susi, O. Karras, A. Moreira, F. Dalpiaz, P. Spoletini, D. Amyot (eds.): Joint Proceedings of REFSQ- 2023 Workshops, Doctoral Symposium, Live Studies Track, and Poster Track, Barcelona, Spain, April 17-20, 2023. (2023) [133]

1.5.5 Book Chapter

[PALGR] Mannari C., Sportelli M., Bacco M., Malizia A., Ferrari A. “Modelling Digital Transformation in Agriculture: BPM-based Method and Case Study”. In “Rural innovation ecosystems and agricultural transition: empirical insights, theoretical approaches, and governance challenges”, Palgrave (to appear).

1.5.6 Project Deliverables

[CODECS-DEL] Giagnocavo C., Heredia Hortigüela R. M., Olmedo Osuna L., Knierim A., Herrera B., Ferrari A., Mannari C., Bacco M., “Analysis of Digital Ecosystems”. CODECS Deliverable D3.2. (2025) [7]

[CODECS-DEL1] Giagnocavo C., Heredia Hortigüela R. M., Knierim A., Herrera B., Paulus M., Ferrari A., Mannari C., Bacco M., “Report on Digital Ecosystems draft M24”. CODECS Deliverable D3.1. (2024) [6]

[CODECS-DEL2] Soma K., Brunori G., Giagnocavo C., Knierim A., Vergamini D., Heredia Hortigüela R.M., Ferrari A., Mannari C., Bacco M., Selnes T., Ciravegna E., Ortolani L., Godaert R., Ryan M., “Sustainable Digitalisation: a Conceptual Framework”. CODECS Deliverable D2.1. (2024) [5]

We will highlight when a chapter or section is based on a published work.

The following other publications during the PhD studies do not contribute to the contents of this thesis:

- Lepore F., Vergamini D., Ortolani L., Mannari C., Ferrari A., Bacco F. M., Brunori G., “A Framework Integrating Agile Software Development Principles for Co-Design and Participatory Cost-Benefit Evaluation in Digital Agriculture.” IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry (MetroAgriFor). (2025) [124]
- Gezici G., Mannari C., Orlandi L., “The Ethical Impact Assessment of Selling Life Insurance to Titanic Passengers”. In CEUR WORKSHOP PROCEEDINGS (Vol. 3456, No. 3456, pp. 35-50). M. Jeusfeld c/o Redaktion Sun SITE, Informatik. (2023) [86]

- Lepore F., Ortolani L., Ferrari A., Fiorentini N., Mannari C., Bacco F. M., Brunori G., “Co-design and e-governance tools for sustainable land and water management in rural areas: the experience within the DESIRA H2020 project”. 2023 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry (MetroAgriFor). (2023) [123]

1.6 Overview of the Thesis Chapters

This section provides an overview of the thesis structure, outlining the relationship between chapters, research questions, and design science iterations.

Figure 1.4 offers a visual representation of this structure. The thesis is organised into four parts: Part I investigates the problem, Parts II and III present the core contributions focusing on the method and the tool, respectively, and Part IV concludes the thesis.

The narrative is structured to reflect the design science iterations and associated RQs. However, for clarity’s sake, the narrative flow prioritised the artefact and the studies conducted, resulting in some iterations extending across multiple chapters.

RQ1 and RQ2—that refer to the method—are addressed in Part II, with RQ1 addressed in Chapter 4 and RQ2 spanning Chapters 5 and 6. RQ3 and RQ4—that refer to the tool—are addressed within Part III, with RQ3 spanning Chapters 8 and 9, and RQ4 addressed in Chapter 10.

Iteration 1 is presented in Chapters 4 and 6, with Chapter 4 documenting the design and validation task and Chapter 6 reporting the implementation and evaluation. Similarly, Iteration 2 is presented in Chapters 5 and 6, with Chapter 5 documenting the design and validation task and Chapter 6 reporting the implementation and evaluation. Iteration 3 is reported in Chapters 8 and 9, with Chapter 8 documenting the design and first validation and Chapter 9 complementing the validation. Iteration 4 is reported in Chapters 8 and 10, with Chapter 8 documenting the design and Chapter 10 addressing the validation. This figure will be repeated at the beginning of the core parts to help orient the reader and highlight the portion addressed.

This chapter belongs to Part I, Problem Investigation, and serves as the introductory chapter. The remainder of the thesis is organised as follows:

Chapter 2 presents the literature review, including background and related works.

Part II focuses on PoMeLO, the RE method.

Chapter 3 provides an overview of Part II, summarising the research gaps and questions addressed in that part.

Chapter 4 addresses RQ1 by introducing the method and its methodological foundations, and reports the first validation round based on focus groups.

Chapter 5 addresses RQ2 by presenting the consolidated version of the method and reporting its second validation through a two-phase field experiment.

Figure 1.4: Overview of thesis chapters and mapping between chapters and RQs, iterations and chapters

Chapter 6 complements RQ₂, presenting results from the implementation and evaluation of the method.

Part III focuses on ModeLLer, the EUD modelling tool.

Chapter 7 provides an overview of Part III, summarising the research gaps and questions addressed in that part.

Chapter 8 addresses RQ₃, introduces the final version of the tool, and presents a cognitive walkthrough evaluation conducted on a prototype.

Chapter 9 complements RQ₃ by reporting the tool validation through a user study conducted within a CT framework.

Chapter 10 addresses RQ₄ by presenting the improved AI-infused version, a technical evaluation and a Wizard of Oz study with domain experts.

Part IV draws conclusions.

Chapter 11 discusses contributions and limitations.

Chapter 12 outlines future work.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter presents the background and related work that informed this thesis.

Figure 2.1 outlines its position within established research disciplines. The figure is not intended to provide a comprehensive taxonomy. Instead, its purpose is to offer a high-level orientation for the reader, indicating the fields and areas that most directly framed this contribution.

The review was grounded within HCI, SE, and IS. AI is characterised as a transversal field, enabling techniques adopted across diverse fields and application domains.

The contribution focuses on two main areas: MoDRE and EUD. MoDRE is a model-driven approach to RE that supports software development by using diagrammatic no-

Figure 2.1: Conceptual map of the research landscape of the thesis. Acronyms: CT = Computational Thinking, MBE = Model-Based Engineering, MDE = Model-Driven Engineering, MDD = Model-Driven Development, ITS = Intelligent Tutoring Systems, PD = Participatory Design, RS = Recommender Systems, VL = Visual Languages

tations to define, analyse, and manage requirements in a systematic manner [98]. EUD refers to a set of methodologies, tools, and techniques that enable non-professional developers to create, modify, or adapt software applications without requiring extensive programming knowledge [125].

In addition to its position at the intersection of MoDRE and EUD, this work also draws insights from relevant literature in related modelling fields. The areas most closely related to MoDRE include Model-Based Engineering (MBE) and Model-Driven Engineering (MDE), both based on the principle of using models as essential artefacts throughout the entire development process, with MDE further emphasising automation and model-to-code transformation via Model-Driven Development (MDD) [38]. Furthermore, Visual Languages (VL) contribute principles and techniques for addressing the design of model-based artefacts, including modelling notations [113]. Within HCI, Participatory Design (PD) primarily informs methods for engaging stakeholders in the co-design of model-based artefacts, such as participatory modelling. Additionally, Computational Thinking (CT) provides frameworks to assess and characterise modelling as an essential problem-solving skill set [230]. Finally, Recommender Systems (RS) [14] and Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) [108], two areas intrinsically connected to AI, provide concepts for adaptive support towards intelligent modelling assistants.

Modelling Research Communities

Various research communities study modelling from different angles, including engineering-driven model-based techniques, software development strategies, system-level conceptualisation and human-centred studies on diagram usage and understanding.

We report here the research communities that most strongly informed the thesis, presented in order of relevance to the current work.

MoDRE The model-driven RE community has articulated modelling-related concerns in a sustained way through the MoDRE workshop series, which has been running for several years, with the 2026 event being the 16th¹.

MoDRE was established as a forum to discuss how MDD can be meaningfully applied to RE. Contributions in the area repeatedly address balancing the flexibility needed to capture heterogeneous stakeholder needs with the formal rigour required for model analysis and transformations, and reconciling high-level abstraction with the information richness needed in practice. In addition, the workshop scope explicitly includes open challenges around making requirements modelling more participatory and collaborative, and around integrating emerging directions such as AI-enabled modelling into model-based RE workflows.

MODELS A complementary perspective is also drawn from the broader MDE community, most prominently represented by the Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS) conference, currently at the 31st edition². MODELS primarily targets modelling languages, tools and methods for model-driven software and systems engineering, contributing to model-related research with transferable principles

¹<https://www.modre.ece.mcgill.ca/> Last visited 5 February 2026

²<https://conf.researchr.org/home/models-2026/> Last visited 5 February 2026

and empirical insights, particularly on tool support, adoption, and practical modelling challenges. Although its primary focus is not RE-specific, many techniques and lessons—particularly regarding modelling workflows, tool support, and evaluation—can be transposed to MoDRE contexts. This community has recently shown growing interest in connecting model-driven discourse with the emerging low-code and no-code platforms paradigm, as reflected in the dedicated workshop on low-code development³. This venue explores how abstraction, automation, and AI-enabled assistance can broaden access to modelling and software construction.

Conceptual Modeling A further relevant community is Conceptual Modeling, historically associated with the long-running International Conference on Conceptual Modeling, also known as the Entity-Relationship conference, which has reached its 45th edition⁴. Conceptual Modeling focuses on describing the semantics of systems at a high level of abstraction, including structural aspects in terms of entities, relationships, and constraints. Over the years, the community has also contributed a wide range of modelling approaches for capturing various domains, often with an emphasis on semantic accuracy and conceptual clarity. Its research has influenced many modelling languages and techniques that are now commonly used in software and systems engineering serving as a relevant background community.

Diagrams In addition, the biennial conference *Diagrams* (International Conference on the Theory and Application of Diagrams)⁵, established in 2000, focuses on the cognitive and semiotic aspects of diagrammatic representations. Its contributions examine how people interpret and reason with diagrams, including the role of diagrammatic representations in supporting formal and computational reasoning.

2.1 Approach

The literature analysis was structured according to Wieringa’s design science methodology [227]. It was conducted at the beginning of each iteration to deepen the understanding of the research problem and position the work within the existing body of research. Additionally, it was revisited during the design phases to review related work, identify knowledge gaps, and ensure the proposed solution advances the state of the art.

The analysis was not conducted as a fully systematic review. However, it followed a structured procedure that was repeated in each iteration. Across iterations, the problem focus progressively shifted, as insights from treatment validation and newly emerging user needs refined the problem framing and, in turn, the literature to be consulted.

Since modelling covers interdisciplinary communities, it is difficult to find an effective search string. Therefore, a hybrid search strategy was employed that combined (i) a leading query derived from the initial problem under investigation; (ii) start sets of seed papers—primarily systematic mapping studies and other prominent works that were relevant to the research problem; (iii) snowball sampling that was applied to these initial sources.

³<https://lowcode-workshop.github.io/> Last visited 5 February 2026

⁴<https://conceptualmodeling.org/> Last visited 5 February 2026

⁵<https://diagrams-conference.org/> Last visited 5 February 2026

Research question	Seed papers
<i>RQ1—process modelling in LLS</i>	Horkoff et al., 2019 [98]; Van Der Aalst, 2011 [218]; Moody, 2009 [152].
<i>RQ2—agronomists modellers</i>	Barricelli et al., 2019 [23]; Bano and Zowghi, 2013 [20]; Fischer and Giaccardi, 2006 [77].
<i>RQ3—EUD modelling tool</i>	Barricelli et al., 2023 [22]; Kardan and Conati, 2015 [109]; Weintrop and Wilensky, 2015 [225]; Brennan and Resnick, 2012 [40].
<i>RQ4—AI-infused modelling</i>	Kourani et al., 2024 [115]; Saini et al., 2022 [191]; Mussbacher et al., 2020 [163].

Table 2.1: Initial seed papers selected for each research question.

This approach was inspired by prior work [143] that combined Scopus search and backwards-and-forward snowballing within a systematic mapping study. This hybrid strategy was reported as particularly efficient for retrieving relevant evidence in interdisciplinary contexts, where terminology and publication venues are more dispersed [160].

The database search was conducted using the Scopus literature search engine. The primary search query was formulated as follows:

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( ( "process modelling" ) OR ( "requirements modelling" ) OR ( "goal modelling" ) ) AND ( "agriculture" ) OR ( "agrifood" ) OR ( "food industry" ) )
```

The start sets of papers was selected in consultation with the supervisors at each iteration of the review process and comprised the studies presented in Table 2.1. Each research question was supported by a targeted literature cluster, progressively refined as empirical insights emerged.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were used consistently throughout both the database search and the snowballing steps.

Regarding inclusion criteria, the following criteria were applied:

- The paper should address at least one core theme of the thesis that is relevant to the current iteration (as the research focus shifted across iterations, this criterion was evaluated with respect to the iteration-specific problem framing).
- The paper should provide a substantive *primary* research contribution (e.g., framework, modelling method, tool, interaction technique, or empirical study), **or** constitute a *systematic secondary study* (e.g., systematic literature review or systematic mapping study) that synthesises evidence on the topic.
- For papers used to inform evaluation or user support design, the study should report empirical results with a well-defined method (e.g., user study, field study, case study, experiment) and basic validity/limitations discussion.
- The papers should be peer-reviewed (journal, conference, or peer-reviewed book chapter).
- Papers should be written in English.
- The papers should be accessible in full text.

Similarly, the exclusion criteria were defined as:

- Studies outside the scope of the iteration-specific research focus (e.g., modelling papers unrelated to RE/participatory approaches/EUD, or AI papers with no connection to modelling support or human use).
- Duplicates were removed, and each study was included only once (e.g., if a conference paper was extended into a journal version, only the most complete version was included).
- Papers lacking sufficient methodological or technical detail to assess the approach (e.g., unclear procedure, missing description of the artefact/tool, or insufficient reporting of the empirical study) were excluded.

We report here the outcomes of the problem investigation. For clarity, findings from the different iterations are synthesised into a single, integrated narrative. A background section introduces the key concepts derived from the literature review and provides context for the subsequent discussion of related work.

2.2 Background

Across the IS, SE and HCI fields, research on modelling has been particularly active since the early 2000s, mainly motivated by the diffusion of MDD techniques. Accordingly, we present the background through four streams of work that underpin the design science research in this thesis: (i) a theoretical stream that focuses on articulating definitions and establishing the theoretical foundations of modelling practices and notations by building on earlier cognitive theories; (ii) a technical stream, mainly grounded in MoDRE, covering notations and methods used for requirements elicitation and modelling; (iii) an EUD stream that brings together approaches that have progressively made modelling more accessible to end users; (iv) an AI-enabled modelling stream that reviews recent techniques that augment modelling at different levels by leveraging advances in machine learning and LLMs.

2.2.1 Modelling and Notations

In the modelling literature, there is general agreement that system modelling builds on internal conceptualisations, i.e., mental or conceptual models, that are externalised into persistent, manipulable representations. These external representations relocate parts of the internal model from the mind to the environment, thereby enabling cognitive actions that support computation by enabling inspection, revision, and shared reasoning [110, 194, 215, 239].

One influential characterisation of *model* is drawn from Stachowiak's General Model Theory, according to whom a model is a representation that satisfies three criteria: (i) *mapping*, in that it refers to an original, (ii) *reduction*, in that it reduces complexity by selecting only relevant aspects, and (iii) *pragmatic purpose*, in that it is constructed for a specific purpose and context of use [117]. From this perspective, a diagram can be understood as the graphical instantiation of a model [152].

Henceforth, throughout the thesis, the terms *diagram*, *visual model*, *graphical model*, and shorthand *model* are used interchangeably to refer to these kinds of representations.

According to Larkin and Simon [119], diagrams are a form of visual representations that differ from sentential—i.e., textual—ones because they preserve structural relations directly in the layout, enabling information at a given locality to be accessed simultaneously rather than sequentially, whereas sequentiality is typical in sentential format. This property can potentially reduce the cognitive effort humans typically expend when processing complex information [119].

Therefore, a substantial body of research investigated how visual models can support human reasoning by externalising abstract structures into perceptual cues that facilitate comprehension, reveal patterns, and reduce cognitive load [32, 144, 174, 206]. For example, prior work has shown that understanding graphical representations relies on specific reading skills that are acquired mainly through experience [144]. These skills include the capability to map visual elements to their underlying semantics and conventions [144, 174]. Within this line of work, Stapleton and colleagues explicitly call for further empirical studies examining how the choice of diagram type and its representational properties influences user performance [32].

Furthermore, the advantage of visual models has been linked—at least in part—to *dual coding* [152]. According to Paivio’s Dual Coding Theory [171], combining text and graphics is generally more effective than relying on either mode alone because verbal and non-verbal information are processed in partly distinct cognitive systems. When the same content is presented both verbally and visually, it can be encoded in both systems, increasing the likelihood of recall and comprehension; moreover, the presence of referential links between the two representations supports cross-cueing, i.e., the visual can trigger the verbal, and vice versa, strengthening understanding especially when the information is complex or unfamiliar.

Models are applied across all stages of software development, from requirements modelling [98] to the design of system functionalities and code development [38]. These representations are also widely used in practice by professional developers and expert analysts [220]. Many of these representations rely on semi-formal notations such as UML, BPMN, and SysML, i.e., modelling languages with a defined syntax and semantics. These differ from formal models, which rely on mathematically precise semantics that can support exhaustive verification, but may be less accessible to many stakeholders and harder to read in practice.

Therefore, a key advantage of models based on semi-formal notations is that they combine a human-oriented graphical representation with a machine-oriented textual encoding, i.e., an underlying code that captures the same elements and relations. This dual nature allows them to remain readable and communicable to humans while also being processable by machines—for instance, through parsing, consistency checks, and model transformations [38].

Moody’s Physics of Notations

Moody’s work on the Physics of Notations [152] has laid the groundwork for a scientific approach to visual notation design in SE and developed a theory for constructing and evaluating notations that is intended to be common to all modelling communities. The approach integrated theories from semiotics and perceptual psychology, including the

aforementioned cognitive theories, and empirical evidence about cognitive effectiveness of visual representations [153, 155].

Moody’s central claim is that visual notations are uniquely human-oriented artefacts whose primary purpose is to support communication and problem solving, and therefore must be optimised for cognitive effectiveness.

Moody distinguishes between semantics, i.e., what constructs mean, and visual syntax, i.e., how constructs are graphically represented, and argues that SE has developed mature methods for the former but lacks comparable principles for the latter. He therefore proposes a prescriptive theory for visual notations built on nine design principles.

Figure 2.2: Moody’s principles for designing cognitively effective visual notations presented through a modular honeycomb model.

Figure 2.2 presents these principles as originally proposed by Moody through a “honeycomb” modular structure. Each principle is expressed by a name associated with a theoretical definition, and is described through an empirical definition, explanation of design strategies, as well as exemplars and counter exemplars. The nine principles include: (1) *Semiotic Clarity*: there should be a 1:1 correspondence between semantic constructs and graphical symbols; (2) *Perceptual Discriminability*: different symbols should be clearly distinguishable from each other; (3) *Semantic Transparency*: use visual representations whose appearance suggests their meaning; (4) *Complexity Management*: include explicit mechanisms for dealing with complexity; (5) *Cognitive Integration*: include explicit mechanisms to support integration of information from different diagrams; (6) *Visual Expressiveness*: use the full range and capacities of visual variables; (7) *Dual Coding*: use text to complement graphics; (8) *Graphic Economy*: the number of different graphical symbols should be cognitively manageable; (9) *Cognitive Fit*: use different visual dialects for different tasks and audiences.

■ While these theoretical foundations justify the cognitive advantages of diagrammatic representations, empirical evidence on their effectiveness in participatory and non-expert contexts remains fragmented.

2.2.2 MoDRE

In RE, effective communication with stakeholders is essential to ensure that user needs are accurately captured and translated into system requirements [166]. This is particularly relevant in socio-technical contexts where domain expertise is crucial to develop systems that align with real-world needs [25]. Abelein and Paech [8] surveyed a broad range of empirical practices that can be applied to enhance user participation; among these are approaches that rely on models as central artefacts to structure communication, elicit requirements, and support analysis.

As an entry point into this body of work, Assar’s literature-based mapping of the MoDRE workshop series [18] provides a structured overview of how MDE has been leveraged within RE. A key insight of this mapping is the clear predominance of requirements representation as the primary research issue, with most contributions proposing new modelling languages—often domain-specific—or extending existing Object Management Group (OMG) standards to better capture requirements concerns. Furthermore, the review shows that MoDRE strategies are applied not only to model the *problem space*—as is typical in RE when using goal-oriented techniques [98]—but they also extend into the *solution space* to capture structural and behavioural aspects of the system to-be, therefore making extensive use of different MDD notations.

By leveraging the expressiveness of multiple notations, requirements modelling serves to refine system specifications and to ensure consistency, traceability, and alignment with stakeholders’ needs across the development process [38].

Goal-oriented Requirements Notations

As a subfield of MDE, Goal-Oriented Requirements Engineering (GORE) addresses socially related challenges and proposes goal models to represent system requirements derived from stakeholders’ goals [98]. In this context, a *goal* denotes a desired state of affairs that an actor aims to achieve. Goals are typically refined into sub-goals and can be operationalised into functional and non-functional requirements. Goal models are often represented graphically, employing frameworks such as iStar 2.0 [54] (formerly i* [233]), KAOS [88], NFR Framework [50], TROPOS [41], GRL [17], and URN [16].

While these approaches are often grouped under “goal modelling”, they do not treat goals in the same way: some are “goal-centred” and emphasise systematic goal refinement and assignment (e.g., KAOS), some are “quality- and trade-off-centred” and focus on softgoals and contribution reasoning for non-functional requirements (e.g., NFR Framework), and others are “actor- and intention-centred”, where goals are one intentional element among tasks, resources, and softgoals used to model responsibilities and social dependencies (e.g., iStar and Tropos). Specifically, iStar foregrounds actors’ interdependencies by providing constructs such as *actor*, *goal*, *quality* (softgoal), *task*, and *resource*. This supports reasoning not only about what is expected, but also about who is responsible, why particular alternatives are pursued, and how dependencies shape the system to-be [54]. Over time, the original i* proposals have evolved into a family of related specifications, often referred to as *dialects*, and extensions [233]. The current version, iStar 2.0 [54], from now on iStar, was introduced to improve conceptual clarity, consistency, and usability across applications and tools.

Tropos [41] builds on this actor- and intention-oriented perspective, but frames it

more explicitly as a software development methodology spanning the whole development process, from early requirements to architectural design and implementation. Building on the same intentional concepts as iStar, it supports the analysis of organisational contexts in the early requirements phase and the introduction of the system to-be in the late requirements phase, where responsibilities are delegated to software actors. This continuity of concepts across stages makes Tropos particularly suitable for contexts in which software systems must be derived from existing social and organisational dependencies, rather than specified only in functional terms.

Structural and Behavioural Requirements Notations

Beyond GORE, other MoDRE strategies focus on structural and behavioural requirements [18] by leveraging semi-formal notations such as UML [3], BPMN [2] and SysML [4]. These languages are all standardised by the OMG.

UML (Unified Modeling Language) is a general-purpose software modelling language providing multiple complementary diagram sets such as class, components, object diagrams for structure, and use case, sequence, activity diagrams for behaviour. UML remains especially prominent in SE research, where these diagrams are frequently used as artefacts for activities such as specification, analysis, and model-based techniques (e.g., testing, synthesis, consistency checking) [43].

BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation), is a specific type of system model that represents the sequence of activities, events, decisions, information flows, roles and resources involved in accomplishing a business objective. Business Process Modelling (BPM) is commonly enterprise-oriented with visual representation of how work is performed within an organisation, highlighting dependencies, inputs, outputs, decision points, and control flows. The representations enable a common understanding facilitating collaborative analysis, discussions, and decision-making. Business process models find utility across various domains, such as manufacturing, healthcare, finance, public administration, and logistics. Some practical applications include: process improvement by identifying bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and opportunities for optimisation; change management by visualising the impact on existing processes, identifying potential risks, dependencies, and required adjustments; compliance and governance, by mapping processes to regulatory frameworks, identifying areas of non-compliance and recommending necessary controls and monitoring mechanisms [218].

Finally, SysML (Systems Modeling Language) originated as a UML-based systems-modelling standard with dedicated constructs to represent requirements at system-level structures, thereby supporting MBE practices [224]. Building on this foundation, the SysML v2 standard—finalised by OMG in July 2025—introduces a novel model-centric definition (grounded in a dedicated kernel language, KerML) together with a standard API and services intended to improve automation and interoperability across tools and repositories [105].

Empirical Application of MoDRE

The systematic mapping study by Horkoff et al. [98] outlines that goal models have primarily been used in the early stages of RE to represent requirements interactions, trade-offs, and conflicts, with secondary applications in software adaptation, regulation,

and business intelligence. As GORE has been extensively studied and applied in the literature, the authors recommend that future research focus on testing and evaluating existing methods to enhance the practical applicability of GORE with better integration into real-world scenarios. This need is supported by evidence from a survey [145], indicating that many practitioners are either unaware of suitable GORE methods or uncertain about how to apply them. Furthermore, Assar’s study [18] points to the limited application of MoDRE in real-world case studies.

Broadening the lens beyond RE-specific contexts, several studies have examined MDE experiences from the practitioners’ perspective, primarily through investigations conducted in industrial settings [11, 55, 126, 220].

A major stream of contributions on the application of modelling to real-world contexts comes from Digital Twins, namely enterprise-modelling approaches used to develop digital artefacts that represent virtual counterparts of physical entities, enabling simulations and change-impact analyses in controlled digital environments [53, 178]. Although these settings differ from living lab (LL) contexts, and often result in highly technical solutions, they similarly highlight the need to engage domain experts who hold the situated knowledge required to support problem framing and decision-making.

From a practical perspective, the meta-review of empirical studies by Verbruggen and Snoeck [220] reinforces the role of modelling as a key instrument for RE, particularly to support alignment around stakeholder needs. Indeed, the study shows that practitioners primarily value modelling for communication with stakeholders, rather than as a direct driver of system development.

Furthermore, several studies indicate that although technically mature, the application of model-based approaches in real-world contexts still faces persistent challenges [11, 55, 219, 220]. Reported issues include poor usability and limited attention to user experience [11], fragmented collaborative practices [55], complexity of modelling tools and notations, and cognitive demand [220], prioritisation of technical decisions over socio-technical considerations, and limited alignment with practical needs [219].

Complementing this high-level view, Savary-Leblanc et al. [193] investigated through interviews the kinds of support that experts require during modelling. Their study revealed that modelling is often hindered by specific challenges such as maintaining consistency across models, managing complexity, and ensuring collaboration among stakeholders. Experts also highlighted the need for more guidance and adaptive tool support, particularly in contexts where multiple modelling languages must be coordinated.

Domain-specific Languages

To overcome challenges related to general-purpose languages (GPLs), researchers have introduced domain-specific languages (DSLs)—languages whose abstractions and notations are explicitly tailored to a particular domain. Such languages are proposed to bridge the gap between domain knowledge and technical implementation [113].

In the context of digital twins, this connection becomes particularly explicit: industrial platforms increasingly rely on machine-readable “twin models”, often expressed in DSL-like languages, to define domain vocabularies, entities, and relations in a form that can be instantiated, connected to data streams, and executed or analysed [53].

Since their initial diffusion alongside GPLs, empirical studies have investigated the application of DSLs, highlighting both the benefits and drawbacks of this practice [149].

On the one hand, industry users often reported that a well-designed DSL improves communication and shared understanding—by formalising domain jargon—, increases support for recurring tasks, and enables automation via generators and specialised tooling. At the same time, practitioners also highlighted recurring adoption barriers, including specialised training and high onboarding costs, and the long-term burden of evolving and maintaining the language, its generators, and editing tools [96].

■ Most empirical MoDRE applications remain embedded in industrial contexts with stable stakeholder structures, leaving open questions about their applicability in dynamic, multi-actor ecosystems such as LLs.

2.2.3 EUD

In their mapping study, Barricelli et al. [23] profile end users as specialists in their respective fields. They emphasise that successful EUD relies on providing tools and frameworks that reduce technical barriers and integrate seamlessly with domain-specific practices. Extending this perspective, Fischer [76] argues that, as digital tools have become widely accessible and opportunities to engage with technology have grown, the notion of the end user has become increasingly multidimensional, expanding beyond a developer-centred view focused on programming activities to include roles oriented toward design and assessment, such as co-designer, active participant, and engaged citizen.

EUD is supported by an established research community that, since the early formalisation of the notion [125], has convened biennially at the International Symposium on End-User Development (IS-EUD)⁶, which reached its 10th edition in 2025. More broadly, the benefits of user involvement throughout the software development cycle have long been a central research concern [8, 20, 62, 167]. As noted by Bano et al. [20], stakeholder engagement is associated with improved system quality and user acceptance.

EUD provides methods, techniques, and tools that enable non-professional users to take an active role in software development by creating, modifying, or extending software that addresses their needs. In the literature, EUD is positioned as an umbrella notion that encompasses two closely related practices: End-User Programming (EUP) and End-User Software Engineering (EUSE) [23].

EUP is typically regarded as the more established strand, focusing on enabling end users to construct programs for their own use; for instance, by creating macros that extend existing applications or by building small, purpose-specific artefacts such as spreadsheets to support everyday work practices. With the spread of professional software development, EUP increasingly targeted scenarios in which the developer and the user largely coincided.

EUSE complemented this perspective by embedding software engineering principles into these environments without requiring users to adopt formal engineering processes. Consequently, EUSE investigates approaches to support quality-related activities, such as error prevention, debugging, testing, and validation, while fitting these activities into end users' existing workflows.

Overall, the application of EUD in empirical contexts has been studied from integrated perspectives [23, 211]. Tetteroo and Markopoulos [211], specifically reviewed the

⁶<https://iseud.net/> Last visited 5 February 2026

research methods applied. Their work pointed to gaps in the empirical grounding and observed that although action research offers a naturalistic setting particularly suitable for evaluating EUD systems, there is a lack of such studies, and the use of case studies is likewise scarce. Extending this, Barricelli et al. [23] reviewed the EUD, EUP and EUSE literature surveying a broad range of techniques and implementation approaches. Based on their synthesis, the authors argued that future EUD research should engage more directly with the concrete work practices of end users and strengthen the evidence base by validating results through experimentation with domain experts [23].

In the literature review, we adopted this broad view of EUD and considered contributions from EUD, EUP, and EUSE, as well as studies that explicitly address the involvement of end users and stakeholders. Accordingly, EUD solutions may denote both the software artefacts created, modified, or adapted by end users, and the professional methods and tools designed to support their construction and adaptation.

To ground the empirical approach of the thesis, three foundational aspects of the EUD literature—also relevant to our modelling context—were explored: (i) *EUD techniques*, namely technical solutions that support end users to create, modify, and adapt software artefacts; (ii) *the meta-design paradigm*, examining how systems can accommodate users' evolving needs over time, moving beyond one-off solutionism through participatory approaches; and (iii) *evaluation approaches*, considering how EUD artefacts can be designed and assessed in ways that align with users' capabilities, going beyond the standard usability metrics commonly adopted in HCI.

EUD Techniques

By EUD techniques, we refer to the interaction styles and user interface metaphors through which end users manipulate software artefacts [23]. These include, for example, annotation-based, assertion-based, component-based, digital sketching, gesture-based, model-based, and others. In the review by Barricelli et al. [23], model-based strategies are also present among the proposed EUD techniques, alongside component-based solutions, which emerge as the most common, likely due to their emphasis on modular composition and reuse of building blocks [23].

More specifically, Kuhail et al. [116] surveyed visual programming approaches employed in EUD. They classified the approaches in four main categories—block-based, diagram-based, form-based, and icon-based—and analysed their interaction styles and application use cases. Results are consistent with the study by Barricelli et., showing that the literature is dominated by block-based and diagram-based solutions. Across categories, interaction is largely based in direct manipulation, notably through drag-and-drop mechanisms, frequently complemented by menu selection and form filling, which are used to locate components and configure their properties.

Block-based approaches Within this landscape, block-based approaches are mainly characterised by the jigsaw-like composition of program elements, composed according to specific constraints commonly designed to prevent syntax errors and reduce cognitive load by letting users focus on contents rather than on syntax rules. Blocks may represent either classic programming constructs (e.g., variables, loops, conditionals) [182] or higher-level domain components (e.g., interactive elements, sensors/services) [170], often with colour-coded inputs and outputs to guide composition and represent data flow.

Furthermore, the use of high-level abstractions to hide implementation details is a recurring design choice in block-based solutions.

A well-known example is the block-based environment Scratch, which enables users to code through compositional visual elements while minimising the need for prior technical training [182].

Figure 2.3: The Scratch block-based editor [182].

Weintrop and Wilensky [225] provided a perspective on the users' perception of block-based approaches through a longitudinal study with students who programmed both in Snap! (a Scratch-like blocks environment) and in Java. Insights revealed that blocks are generally viewed as easier because shape cues make combinations immediately visible, while drag-and-drop composition supports fast assembly and reduces errors. Blocks were also considered valuable memory aids, replacing the need to memorise syntax. At the same time, several drawbacks emerged: block-based programming was perceived as less powerful, more verbose and slower for larger programs, and sometimes inauthentic compared to "real" text-based coding.

Overall, block-based approaches have been shown to foster engagement and lower entry barriers for non-technical users [23]. However, most evidence comes from educational settings—partly because many visual programming approaches were developed for education [116]—yet this persists even when tools target other audiences. Further research is needed to improve ecological validity by evaluating these approaches with their intended end users in realistic contexts, when the tools are designed for such contexts.

Low-code and no-code development More recently, low-code and no-code development have emerged as industry-driven approaches, popularised through commercial

platforms, to accelerate software delivery by raising the level of abstraction and reducing manual coding. These approaches leverage MDE and MDD by providing visual environments (e.g., drag-and-drop editors, DSL-like building blocks) that minimise the need for hand-written code while supporting rapid application development [58]. Low-code development platforms (LCDPs) primarily target end users, who are also often referred to as citizen developers, and some are explicitly designed to maximise collaboration in mixed teams that include business analysts and professional developers [190]. In addition, recent analyses [196] clarify that LCDPs are frequently presented as cloud-based platforms covering the application lifecycle from design to deployment, and that they share several challenges with EUD [197].

The systematic literature review by Güresci et al. [94] explored the application of LCDPs for precision agriculture, reporting that LCDPs can significantly reduce development time and technical complexity by enabling rapid prototyping of data-driven farm applications and easier integration of IoT and cloud services even for non-technical users. The authors outline future research directions, including the improvement of user experience within these platforms.

The Meta-design Paradigm

Closely tied to EUD, meta-design emerged as a paradigm that views design as the outcome of complex interactions among multiple actors and processes [77]. This approach contrasts with views of design as a one-off activity carried out solely by professionals. Instead, it frames design as an ongoing process, shaped over time by user appropriation, system-user co-adaptation, and system extension.

A recurring implication in this line of work is that, since future uses cannot be fully anticipated at design time, meta-design shifts the focus from delivering finalised end-products towards creating open and evolvable socio-technical systems that let users bridge emerging mismatches at use time [78].

Within this context, two main requirements emerge for EUD systems developed through the meta-design paradigm: 1. the system shall be flexible to evolve at use time; 2. the system shall evolve to some extent at the hands of the users.

Seeding, evolutionary growth, and reseeded For developing software in line with meta-design principles, Fischer and colleagues proposed the Seeding, Evolutionary Growth, and Reseeding (SER) model [79]. Crucially, SER treats users as active contributors and designers in their own right, rather than as passive consumers. As illustrated in Figure 2.4, SER characterises system development as a recurring cycle that reflects how information systems evolve over time: an initial *seeding* phase, in which developers and domain experts collaboratively create a “seed” containing core functionality and domain knowledge; a phase of *evolutionary growth*, in which the system is extended in use through situated contributions and adaptations by users; and a *reseeding* phase, in which accumulated changes are deliberately reorganised, consolidated, and enhanced to restore coherence and enable further growth.

To summarise, meta-design can be articulated around five core principles:

1. *Cultures of participation*: foster sustained participation across multiple and evolving roles, enabling diverse stakeholders to contribute to shaping the socio-technical

Figure 2.4: The Seeding, Evolutionary Growth, and Reseeding (SER) process model for technological development [79].

system both at design time and at use time. Rather than separating design and usage phases, meta-design promotes an ecology of roles in which users, developers, domain experts, facilitators, and managers dynamically collaborate, progressively shifting control toward problem owners;

2. *Empowerment for adaptation and evolution*: complement participatory cultures with concrete mechanisms—tools, methods, processes, and support structures—that enable stakeholders to adapt not only the technical artefact, but also relevant organisational rules, social conventions, and work practices. Adaptation may occur through direct modification, close collaboration with developers, or through communicative cycles of incremental improvement across the socio-technical environment;
3. *Seeding, evolutionary growth, and reseeded*: conceive socio-technical systems as initially underdesigned “seeds” that provide basic structures, standards, and boundary objects, while intentionally leaving space for future elaboration. These seeds evolve through unplanned, situated contributions during use (evolutionary growth), and are periodically consolidated and reorganised in deliberate reflection phases (reseeding). Evolution is thus understood as an alternation between planned structuring and emergent change, affecting both technical components and social arrangements;
4. *Underdesign of models of socio-technical processes*: deliberately avoid over-specifying structures, workflows, and representations. Specify only what is critical (e.g., legal constraints, safety requirements, core standards), while allowing degrees of incompleteness, imprecision, and negotiability. Underdesign provides maps rather than scripts, enabling stakeholders to appropriate, reinterpret, and adapt models and processes in context, thereby accommodating contingency and emergent behaviour;
5. *Structuring communication* (“designing the in-between”): treat communication as a primary design concern. Provide facilitation strategies, walkthrough-oriented practices, and boundary objects (e.g., semi-structured models, scenarios, plans) that

make assumptions visible, integrate heterogeneous perspectives, support negotiation, and sustain co-evolution over time. Communication processes accompany both evolutionary growth and reseeding phases, ensuring that adaptation is reflective rather than accidental.;

Computational Thinking-grounded Approaches

Since its initial definition by Wing [230], Computational Thinking (CT) has been recognised as an essential skill set for problem-solving and innovation. A growing body of research highlights its importance across various disciplines [59, 66, 210, 231].

Many authors have concentrated on fostering and evaluating CT in the educational domain [100, 212], with empirical contributions on coding [40, 67] and game-based learning [48, 214]. Others have recently shifted the focus to CT in the workplace, where many individuals may lack the computational background necessary to adapt to the increasing demands of complex technological environments [22, 59].

This frames CT as a capability that requires support rather than a learning outcome. Within this scenario, EUD environments play a central role in enabling domain experts to effectively create, adapt, and use digital technologies to carry out their work [22].

Accordingly, evaluation approaches have emerged that complement traditional instruments and metrics such as usability and user acceptance scales, offering a more nuanced assessment of tools in relation to the capabilities and practical needs of their intended users [22].

Below, we outline the prominent works that contributed to the operationalisation of CT and to its application within EUD contexts.

Brennan and Resnick’s CT Framework Starting from the observation of students learning to code with Scratch, Brennan and Resnick [40] developed the idea that CT requires an evaluation from multiple, integrated dimensions. Consequently, they outlined an assessment framework based on the integration of different approaches, including project portfolio analysis, artefact-based interviews, and design scenarios (cf Fig. 2.5).

	Concepts	Practices	Perspectives
<i>Approach #1: Project Analysis</i>	presence of blocks indicates conceptual encounters	N/A	N/A (possibly by extending analysis to include other website data, like comments)
<i>Approach #2: Artifact-Based Interviews</i>	nuances of conceptual understanding, but with limited set of projects	yes, based on own authentic design experiences, but subject to limitations of memory	maybe, but hard to ask directly
<i>Approach #3: Design Scenarios</i>	nuances and range of conceptual understanding, but externally selected projects	yes, in real-time and in a novel situation, but externally selected projects	maybe, but hard to ask directly

Figure 2.5: Brennan and Resnick CT framework [40].

They discussed the respective strengths and limitations of each approach and illustrated their potential complementarity. In particular, the authors emphasised the value of examining both the produced artefacts and the underlying development processes, arguing that combining these perspectives enables a comprehensive assessment of CT.

The AAA Model Drawing on several years of teaching and tool-building experience with block-based programming, Repenning [181] proposed a three-stage model to frame the CT process. This model can be summarised as AAA—*Abstraction, Automation, Analysis* (cf. Fig. 2.6). *Abstraction* concerns problem formulation, that is, conceptualising a problem by identifying relevant objects and relationships. *Automation* refers to solution expression, where the solution is specified in a non-ambiguous form that a computer can execute, typically through programming. *Analysis* focuses on execution and evaluation: running the solution and examining its consequences, supported by feedback and visualisations that help assess whether the observed behaviour aligns with expectations. The model describes block-based paradigm as the combination of computer affordances, such as program analysis, visualisation, and real-time interfaces, with human abilities, namely users’ reasoning processes. Within this process, the author sustained the argument that block-based environments should be treated not merely as programming tools, but as CT tools extending support far beyond the syntax level, including semantic and pragmatic user support. To this end, Repenning describes mechanisms such as contextualised explanations as ways to support users during execution and evaluation, and more broadly to scaffold the full CT process rather than only replacing input coding.

Figure 2.6: Repenning’s AAA Model for the design of CT support tools [181].

Computational Thinking Skills The research conducted by Selby and Woollard [199] contributed to CT formalisation by proposing a set of five core skills including *abstraction* (focusing on the important information only and ignoring irrelevant details); *decomposition*, (breaking down a complex problem or system into smaller, more manageable parts); *algorithm design*, (developing a step-by-step solution to a problem); *evaluation*, (assessing whether a solution or algorithm works effectively and efficiently); *generalisation*, (extending a solution or approach to a wider range of problems).

The Computational Thinking Scale TSAI et al. [213] proposed the Computational Thinking scale (CTS), an operationalisation of Selby and Woollard’s CT skills (cf. Fig.

2.2.3) that can be measured through a questionnaire. The scale has been developed for the purpose of self-assessment of an individual's attitude to implement mental problem-solving strategies and consists of a 19-item questionnaire which captures participants' self-reported CT skills levels. Taking a process-oriented approach, it provides a framework for examining how individuals deal with complex problems by identifying essential elements, plan algorithmic strategies, break them down into simpler parts, and find effective solutions that can be reused in similar situations through pattern matching.

EUDability EUDability is a construct that was recently proposed to evaluate how effectively EUD environments support users' CT skills [22], by operationalising tool characteristics in relation to specific computational literacy skills, in alignment with Selby and Woollard's CT skills (cf. See. 2.2.3).

The framework leverages five dimensions to assess whether an environment structurally supports the cognitive operations required to formulate, express, and evaluate computational solutions. Each dimension is explicitly linked to a corresponding CT skill (cf. Fig. 2.7). *Concreteness* maps to *abstraction* and concerns the extent to which concepts are presented in intuitive, perceptible forms (e.g., visual representations, direct manipulation), thereby lowering abstraction barriers and helping users grasp and construct higher-level structures. *Modularity* maps to *decomposition*: environments should enable users to break down complex problems into manageable components (e.g., encapsulated blocks, separate entities, or rule units). *Structuredness* relates to the support for stepwise solution development, guiding users through coherent construction processes. *Reusability* connects to generalisation, allowing users to reuse, adapt, and share previously created artefacts or components, thus promoting transfer of solutions across contexts. Finally, *Testability* maps to evaluation, by providing mechanisms to execute, inspect, and verify outcomes, supporting iterative refinement. By articulating these mappings, EUDability provides a bridge between tool design features and CT capabilities. It allows researchers to analyse whether an environment merely enables artefact creation, or whether it actively scaffolds abstraction, decomposition, structured reasoning, reuse, and evaluation. In this way, the framework supports comparative assessment of EUD tools and helps identify which dimensions may particularly benefit users with lower prior CT proficiency, and which design elements may enhance CT development across different user profiles

Figure 2.7: The EUDability construct based on 5 dimensions aligned with CT skills [22].

■ Although most CT frameworks have been validated in educational contexts, their conceptualisation of abstraction, decomposition, and evaluation as measurable skills offers transferable lenses for analysing modelling practices in professional-oriented EUD domains.

2.2.4 AI-enhanced Modelling

Recent advancements in machine learning and generative AI have increased interest in techniques that enhance modelling. In reviewing recent literature, two recurring patterns emerge, which can be broadly classified into two categories: (i) *automated modelling* through content-level techniques, operating directly on modelling artefacts (e.g., model generation, completion, transformation, validation, and consistency checking); and (ii) *intelligent modelling assistants* that operate at the user level, supporting the modeller's activity through guidance, explanations, error prevention, and adaptive assistance.

Automated Modelling

In RE, modelling automation is mainly motivated by the need to reduce the effort associated with requirements modelling, an activity often perceived as time-consuming, error-prone, and cognitively demanding [191, 234]. In particular, most existing studies have focused on model generation from natural language input, exploring approaches to translate textual descriptions into code using LLMs [47, 71, 114] and machine learning techniques [191].

In most cases, these approaches are presented as back-end techniques [37, 71] and assessed mainly through technical performance metrics.

For example, Ferrari et al. [71] evaluated the use of GPT-3.5 to generate UML sequence diagrams from industrial requirements documents in natural language and assessed the generated diagrams using five quality criteria: (i) *completeness*, defined as the extent to which the diagram covered the content of all the input requirements with sufficient detail for stakeholder communication; (ii) *correctness* referred to as the coherence and consistency of the diagram with respect to the requirements; (iii) *adherence to the standard*, that concerned both syntactic validity and appropriate use of UML constructs; (iv) *degree of understandability*, referring to the overall communicative adequacy; and (v) *terminological alignment*, that measured the consistency between the terminology used in the diagram and that appearing in the AI-generated model.

Another example is the study by Klievtsova et al. [227] that has explored the opposite direction, namely the use of LLMs to generate textual explanations or descriptions from existing models to support stakeholders' understanding. The authors have assessed multiple LLMs, including different versions of GPT and LLAMA, in performing model-to-text transformation of business process models. The evaluation involved transforming process models into textual descriptions and assessing the outputs based on completeness, linguistic quality, and semantic accuracy.

In other cases, AI-based approaches are embedded in interactive user interfaces that support AI-enabled model creation from textual input [114].

Furthermore, commercially available diagramming tools such as Miro⁷, draw.io⁸, or DiagramGuru⁹ already incorporate LLM-based functionalities to allow users to generate models from natural language input.

An analysis of these innovations by Abrahão et al. [9] positions these technologies—generative AI in particular—as a major enabler for accelerating requirements work. However, they caution against viewing automation as a substitute, highlighting the centrality of the socio-technical core of RE. They argue that recent advancements in the field contribute to reshaping requirements elicitation, management, and documentation. Some examples include conversational support for elicitation, mining user feedback to surface emerging needs, automated documentation, and increased traceability between requirements and code. An example in agriculture is provided by Groen et al.’s crowd-based RE approach for digital farming [90], which explores in-situ requirements elicitation. The authors propose capturing requirements-relevant input directly from farmers through a speech-based feedback application embedded in the farming equipment.

These techniques demonstrate the potential of reducing the historically labour-intensive and error-prone nature of requirements management activities. At the same time, the authors [9] explicitly warn that faster and more automated requirements pipelines can amplify downstream pressure on design and delivery, resulting in reduced software quality and threatening human control. Moreover, AI may introduce bias and reduce oversight. Against this backdrop, they suggest carefully evaluating advantages and drawbacks and deriving implications for building *AI-infused systems* aligned with human-centred AI principles. In practice, this may involve embedding AI as an augmentation layer within the workflow and introducing explicit checkpoints for human review.

In line with this vision, previous research has examined the cognitive strategies used by modellers and conceptualised intelligent modelling environments where modellers collaborate with software agents that adapt dynamically to their behaviour, supporting and structuring their activities [144].

Intelligent Modelling Assistants

A recent interview study with practitioners confirmed that even experienced modellers are open to adopting software assistants to support their work. In particular, the modellers expressed specific needs for assistance in assessing model completeness, detecting inconsistencies, and receiving guidance on best practices, as well as support for using the tools effectively [193].

In response to the growing centrality of MDE and low-code platforms, recent research has sought to understand how modelling assistants can effectively support users throughout the modelling lifecycle [159, 162, 163, 192]. A first observation was that, despite increasing automation and tool sophistication, modelling remains cognitively demanding and error-prone, requiring structured assistance comparable to coding support in programming environments [159]. Among the strategies proposed to support modelling—spanning tools, techniques, methods, frameworks, guidelines, and language-level extensions—tool-based solutions are by far the most prevalent. These assistants

⁷<https://miro.com/>

⁸<https://www.drawio.com/>

⁹<https://www.diagramguru.com/>

are primarily designed to support model creation, evolution, validation, and consistency management, reflecting a strong orientation toward embedding assistance directly within the modelling environment [159]. Regarding target users, most proposals target software developers as the main users of these systems, while domain experts are less frequently addressed.

Furthermore, authors in [159] note that recent advances in AI are likely to reshape modelling assistance through increasingly automated and suggestion-based support.

Recommender Systems In line with this shift, recommender systems (RSs) have been proposed to provide personalised support in modelling environments [14]. Within these contexts, RSs have been primarily employed to assist modellers during model construction and extension, offering context-aware suggestions such as relevant modelling elements, reusable model fragments, constraint completions, or recommended next actions. These systems typically aim to reduce cognitive load, improve model quality, and accelerate modelling tasks by proactively guiding users through technically sound design choices.

In general, RSs are classified according to the strategy used to generate personalised recommendations. For example, content-based systems recommend items similar to those previously preferred by the target user, knowledge-based systems rely on explicit domain knowledge to model relationships between users and items, context-aware systems incorporate contextual factors—such as time, task state, or environmental conditions—to refine recommendations [14].

However, the analysis of existing RSs [14] revealed some gaps. Most RSs for modelling are embedded in desktop-based modelling software and provide highly technical recommendations, often tightly coupled to a specific modelling language or tool ecosystem. As a result, they primarily target experienced modellers rather than domain experts or novice users. In contrast, web-based recommenders and systems designed to assist users in creating new artefacts from scratch remain comparatively scarce.

Intelligent Tutoring Systems An alternative approach, drawing on Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS), is to provide adaptive hints based on users' observed behaviour. Rather than relying on predefined workflows or purely artefact-based recommendations, such systems tailor guidance to the modeller's evolving actions and inferred needs [108, 150]. The approach leverages interaction data to infer users' strategies and provide timely, context-sensitive support. Such behaviour-driven assistance has proven effective in exploratory learning environments, where different levels of expertise and heterogeneous interaction strategies are expected [85, 150].

Previous work has explored a personalisation mechanism driven by constraint-based modelling. This approach consists of two phases. In the first phase, a set of declarative constraints is established that captures fundamental elements of a domain—these are typically formulated as relevance and satisfaction conditions. In the second phase, learners' solutions are evaluated by detecting which constraints are violated and generating targeted feedback accordingly, without requiring the system to reconstruct the learner's exact problem-solving path [150]. The approach was applied to open-ended domain modelling tasks, and was integrated into web-based implementations. An example is the tool KERMIT [209], which supports the creation of entity–relationship models from

textual requirements, and COLLECT-UML [19], which teaches object-oriented analysis and design through UML class modelling. The tools diagnose structural and semantic issues via constraint violations and provide adaptive guidance during iterative refinement.

Within ITS research, adaptive support is commonly driven by a learner model. While constraint-based tutors operationalise the learner model through a hand-crafted set of domain constraints that capture correct principles and trigger feedback when violated, more recent experiments have investigated data-driven alternatives that build learner models from interaction behaviour without requiring an explicit constraint base. In particular, Kardan and Conati [109] proposed FUMA—Framework for User Modelling and Adaptation, which discovers behavioural profiles through clustering and then classifies new learners in real time to trigger adaptive guidance. FUMA consists of two main phases—*Behaviour Discovery* and *User Classification* (Fig. 2.8).

Figure 2.8: FUMA framework [108].

In the Behaviour Discovery phase (Fig. 2.8, top), interaction logs from prior learners are first transformed into feature vectors representing behavioural patterns. Clustering techniques are then applied to group students exhibiting similar interaction behaviours. The identified clusters are analysed by comparing their relative learning gains, enabling the detection of behaviour profiles associated with higher or lower performance. To characterise these profiles, association rule mining is employed to extract distinctive behavioural patterns for each cluster. Continuous features are discretised into bins to improve interpretability. Hyperparameters—such as the number of clusters, minimum rule support, and discretisation granularity—are optimised during training.

In the subsequent User Classification phase (Fig. 2.8, bottom), the labelled clusters and their associated behavioural rules are used to train a classifier-based student model. As new learners interact with the system, they are classified in real time into one of the previously identified clusters based on a membership score reflecting how closely their behaviour matches the learnt rules. Importantly, the system also identifies which specific behavioural rules triggered the classification. These rules can then activate targeted adaptive interventions aimed at reinforcing productive behaviours and mitigating detrimental ones.

FUMA has been applied to interactive learning environments, where the framework successfully identified two behaviour-based learner clusters with significantly different

learning gains. It classified unseen students with accuracies above 85%, outperforming several standard classifiers (e.g., random forests, SVMs), and adaptive versions of the simulations demonstrated improved learning outcomes compared to non-adaptive or randomly adaptive conditions [85].

Across this body of work, evaluations have been conducted mainly in educational settings through controlled experiments, including classroom deployments, learning-gain analyses, and interaction log studies. More recently, FUMA has extended this line of work by targeting CT skills acquisition via clustering-based learner profiling derived from interaction traces [161]. However, evidence remains largely confined to conventional learning environments, and applications or validation in non-educational contexts are still underexplored.

■ While modelling is a mature and well-established practice across the software lifecycle and beyond, the integration of AI into modelling remains a relatively recent and rapidly expanding research area. Current contributions are still dominated by technical performance metrics, with comparatively limited ecological evaluations of use in real contexts. At the same time, the risk of bias in AI-generated outputs calls for careful assessment and human-centred design.

2.3 Related Work

Given the thesis focus on digital agriculture, the review of previous work primarily targeted this domain prioritising empirical work conducted in agricultural and rural contexts. However, given the relatively limited number of studies in the primary sector, it also considered adjacent fields offering transferable concepts and evidence. These include agrifood, understood as the set of activities and actors spanning agricultural production and the broader food value chain, the food industry, and smart rural areas.

Moreover, to integrate insights on modelling practice and end-user tool support, the review was expanded via snowballing to other socio-technical domains. In addition, research from education—particularly on CT and learning-oriented tool support—was included, as it provides relevant constructs and evaluation approaches for EUD practice.

The related work section is organised into two complementary streams aligned with the artefacts developed within the design science framework: one grounding the RE methods specifically adopted in digital agriculture and related fields, and one informing the EUD tool through broader evidence on end-user support.

Within each stream, the discussion of related work is further structured around the RQs, so that each subsection motivates specific design choices and evaluation focus.

2.3.1 Modelling Methods for Agriculture and User Involvement

Case Studies Grounded in MoDRE (informing RQ1)

Many GORE approaches have been integrated with other modelling languages to strengthen requirements and design of user-centred solutions [98], with a few case studies in the agri-food sector [21, 173, 201].

The first relevant study found in the literature is by Perini and Susi [173], who applied the Tropos methodology (cf. Sec. 2.2.2) to the design of a decision support system for

integrated production in agriculture. In their study, the early requirements phase was focused on the analysis of the existing organisational context by modelling the main stakeholders, their goals, and their mutual dependencies, while the late requirements phase introduced the system to-be as a new actor to which selected goals, plans, and softgoals were delegated. The work was evaluated through a prototype of a pest management system, which was assessed by technicians and researchers to gather suggestions for further improvement.

Turning to the agrifood industry, Barata et al. [21] introduced a participatory goal modelling method that combined i^* and UML use case diagrams to manage overlapping standards in the food industry. The data was elicited in workshops where industry stakeholders actively contributed to the identification of goals, dependencies, and compliance requirements, ensuring that the resulting models reflected both regulatory obligations and organisational practices.

Similarly, Siena et al. [202] applied normative i^* modelling in a case study on food chain traceability. By extending i^* with concepts such as obligations and permissions, their method captured compliance aspects across organisational actors. The models were developed and refined through workshops with stakeholders from the food industry, ensuring their relevance to real traceability practices.

Beyond agrifood, Ruiz et al. [186] addressed process reengineering, i.e., the redesigning and improvement of organisational processes. They proposed GoBIS, a framework that explicits motivation and traceability of process changes in alignment with stakeholders' goals. The framework integrates intentional and operational models for information system analysis through the alignment between i^* models and communication-oriented business process models. The framework was complemented by an Eclipse-based tool for combining models and traceability, and a set of guidelines to derive a communication model from a given i^* model. The guidelines specify the metamodel mappings by indicating correspondences between i^* elements and communication model elements, such as communication events and message structure. GoBIS was evaluated through a controlled experiment and a focus group with master's students, comparing guideline-based derivation against participants' own criteria.

While the aforementioned studies rely on established MoDRE notations, a recent contribution by Groeneveld et al. [91] has proposed a DSL-based solution tailored to farm management information systems. The framework introduces a formal DSL to model agricultural processes, data flows, and system behaviours, aiming to support the specification and integration of functionalities in farm management systems. The intended users are primarily system designers and software developers, but the framework is also designed to facilitate communication with farm management experts who contribute domain knowledge.

Similarly, Scheerer et al. [195] explored the digital transformation of the farm-to-fork value chain in Germany. They developed conceptual process models to depict activities, digital interactions, and organisational change, applying a reverse perspective from catering back to organic crop production. These representations are primarily descriptive and visual, intended to stimulate discussion and reflection among researchers, practitioners, and value chain actors.

Summary of case studies grounded in MoDRE

- **What is known:** MoDRE combines complementary notations and has been previously applied in selected agri-food and process reengineering cases.
- **What is missing:** Limited evidence of application in LLs, participatory settings, and digital agriculture.
- **Why it matters:** In agricultural digitalisation, requirements are distributed across heterogeneous stakeholders, increasing the need for shared representations of process transformation.
- **How this thesis addresses it:** Proposes PoMeLO, a MoDRE-based method for modelling socio-technical transformations in agricultural LLs and validates it empirically across multiple cases.

Case Studies Grounded in EUD (informing RQ2)

A growing body of research in digital agriculture has shown their potential to enable end users—such as farmers and advisors—in creating or adapting digital applications for diverse purposes, such as real-time monitoring of environmental conditions and plant status [170, 205]. However, although most of these contributions incorporate EUD techniques, they are typically embedded within platform-based solutions [94] and often tailored to a highly specialised product in a technology-intensive context.

Beyond agriculture, some studies have proposed specific modelling strategies that explicitly address end-user involvement and support. An early contribution was provided by O’Neill and Johnson [169] who highlighted that, in the typical software engineering cycle, information is elicited from users, yet the subsequent analysis and modelling are conducted by developers *in isolation*, potentially leading to representations that reflect developers’ interpretations rather than users’ intentions. To address this gap, they proposed a methodology based on the integration of task analysis and participatory design by directly involving users as co-modellers of tasks and domains. The approach was structured as a two-stage iterative process carried out in collaborative sessions to construct graphical models depicting both the system *as-is* and the system *to-be*. The approach was validated through practical application in two software development projects, involving stakeholders with different organisational roles. In this case, the models were developed employing an exclusively graphical notation progressively refined and agreed upon with participants during the modelling sessions.

In contrast, Pérez et al. [172] proposed a method to support end-user participation within a more predefined MDD architecture supporting model-to-code transformation for smart home applications. Their approach leveraged a DSL through which users can express domain knowledge and structure modelling artefacts. The method defined a set of steps to delimit user-dependent properties and to establish mappings between user-level models and developers’ implementation tasks. However, the contribution mainly remained at the level of a methodological proposal, with limited empirical validation in real-world contexts.

More recently, Law et al. [120] attempted to bridge qualitative elicitation and standard process modelling by providing a transformation procedure that systematically derives BPMN models from qualitative interview data. Echoing concerns raised by O’Neill and Johnson [169], the authors identified a critical challenge: although interviews yield

rich, user-grounded qualitative insights, the subsequent transformation of these narratives into structured modelling artefacts remains highly susceptible to modeller's bias. To mitigate this issue, they proposed a structured manual transformation method aiming to reduce variability and subjectivity. The proposed process guided the systematic extraction of BPMN models from thinking-aloud interviews and consisted of three explicit steps of segmentation, classification, and modelling. A procedure operationalised text-to-model transformation through explicit rules. The empirical evaluation, carried out with a group of non-expert modellers trained with the procedure, demonstrated that participants using the method generated models more similar to each other and closer to expert ground truth, compared to a control group that modelled without the procedure. The experiment involved administrative office workers who described their habitual behaviours through interviews. The resulting BPMN models were then assessed through expert evaluation and comparison with expert-generated reference models.

Störrle [208] moved beyond the limited ecological validity of earlier work by conducting an action research study in the context of the German tax authorities, where tax clerks acted as end-user modellers. Software engineers provided coaching and methodological guidance to the end users who constructed and refined UML object diagrams through general-purpose drawing tools. After the early modelling stage by end users, the experts transferred the diagrams into formal tools. Through a participatory process, end users and expert modellers interacted iteratively to refine the models, ensuring consistency with the underlying data model, domain knowledge and integration into the development process.

■ Summary of case studies grounded in EUD

- **What is known:** EUD enables end users to build or adapt digital solutions; some methods involve users in modelling activities.
- **What is missing:** Limited empirical evidence on end-user modelling in real-world contexts, and many solutions remain platform-based or developer-driven.
- **Why it matters:** Direct involvement of domain experts can better capture domain knowledge in requirements representations and reduce the modeller's bias.
- **How this thesis addresses it:** Investigates end-user involvement in modelling and develops procedures and tools to support domain experts in model creation.

2.3.2 EUD Modelling Tools

Many of the modelling approaches discussed above are implemented either through general-purpose modelling environments or via specialised tool support, as for instance in Ruiz et al. [186]. Moreover, as outlined in the background section, a substantial body of work has considered the effectiveness of modelling tools from a user perspective [126, 193, 220], with also an emphasis on user-experience [11]. However, much of this research continues to primarily target professional modellers.

Other contributions more explicitly address the challenge of developing novel interaction paradigms and AI-enhanced mechanisms oriented to non-expert or novice modellers. These users are typically characterised as domain experts or early-stage practitioners.

AI-enhanced EUD Solutions (informing RQ3 and RQ4)

A recent work situated in low-code presented Polaris [177], a goal-oriented environment for robot programming. Polaris bridges an EUD approach with a goal-oriented programming paradigm. Instead of specifying low-level action sequences, users construct goal structures, with nodes representing desired world states and transitions encoding ordering or conditional constraints. Interaction takes place through a tablet-based graphical interface composed of a drawing area for specifying goals and transitions and an output area for inspecting the generated plan. Moreover, the tool integrates a symbolic AI planner that automatically converts user-specified goals into plans that are inspectionable and editable by users. The tool was evaluated in a controlled user study within a service-robot scenario in a caregiving use case, showing that exposing the generated plan through the visualiser improves plan quality and user understanding.

In the realm of process modelling, Kourani et al. [114] integrated generative AI capabilities to develop PromoAI, a LLM-driven automated modelling system. The tool supports the automated generation of business process models starting from textual descriptions in natural language. The interaction mechanism is conversational and text-driven: users provide a process description, which is transformed into a structured prompt through advanced prompt-engineering strategies, including role prompting, knowledge injection, few-shot examples, and negative prompting. The LLM is then instructed to generate executable Python code that constructs a representation using an intermediate language (POWL - Partially Ordered Workflow Language) that is subsequently transformed into standard notations such as BPMN and Petri nets. The tool supports user-driven personalisation by incorporating users' feedback to iteratively refine and adapt the produced models while also allowing the selection of the underlying LLM (e.g., GPT, Gemini) and its version. The tool was evaluated on benchmark process descriptions (e.g., online shop and hotel service scenarios), demonstrating that GPT-4 can generate sound and executable models with limited iterations, while also highlighting differences in performance across LLMs.

While Polaris and PromoAI primarily target specific modelling paradigms and application domains, Gentleman [118] adopts a more general-purpose approach, as this modelling environment can be used to produce domain-specific models. The interaction leverages projectional editing: users work through a largely textual interface, but each editing action directly updates the underlying model structure. This interaction style preserves the immediacy of typing while ensuring that the model remains well-formed, thereby reducing syntactic mistakes. Although it does not currently rely on AI techniques, the tool uses structural constraints to lower modelling errors and effort. The evaluation was conducted through controlled studies with participants from academia and industry, who reported improved efficiency and reduced mechanical effort in modelling tasks.

The tools described above aim to reduce the modelling effort while still engaging the users with semi-formal modelling artefacts and constructs. In contrast, FlexiSketch [232] adopts a more naturalistic, sketching-based interaction style building on pen-and-paper practices. The tool provides a blank canvas on tablets where users can sketch freely; the system interprets the sketches as node-and-edge diagrams and enables direct manipulation through touch/pen actions (e.g., selecting, dragging, merging, and editing elements). Furthermore, rather than relying on a predefined notation, FlexiSketch sup-

ports incremental semi-formalisation through metamodeling: users can assign types to symbols and links and define cardinalities for relationships. The sketches can be exported as structured graphs, together with the associated user-generated metamodel, enabling later refinement. FlexiSketch also includes a lightweight assistance mechanism consisting of a sketch recognition feature comparing newly drawn symbols against the type library defined by the user. Recognition suggestions are proposed to the user who can accept or ignore these suggestions. The approach was applied in RE settings via collaborative workshops, with students and practitioners working in small groups on tablets, where participants could choose or invent modelling languages and iteratively converge on shared notations. The evaluation highlighted the importance of early-phase communication and collaboration, as well as the emergence of shared language.

Summary of AI-enhanced EUD solutions

- **What is known:** Emerging tools lower modelling barriers via AI automation, constrained editing, or sketch-based modelling.
- **What is missing:** Limited attention has been paid to novice modellers and learning-oriented support, and empirical evidence involving domain experts remains scarce.
- **Why it matters:** Lowering modelling barriers is essential to enable domain experts to participate in modelling activities.
- **How this thesis addresses it:** Designs and evaluates ModelLer, a block-based AI-infused modelling tool tailored to novice modellers in participatory agricultural contexts.

Assessment Under CT Frameworks (RQ3)

A growing body of literature has explored CT assessment using diverse methodological approaches, including artefact-based evaluations and automated techniques embedded in digital tools. The scope and context of these studies are largely confined to education. A notable exception is the recent contribution by Barricelli et al. [24] that explicitly frames CT and tool evaluation within workplace-oriented EUD environments. The authors applied an evaluation approach based on the EUDability framework (cf. Fig. 2.2.3) in two healthcare case studies, combining tool assessment with the evaluation of users' CT skills. The evaluation of the tools was conducted by EUD experts using an inspection-based checklist that included items derived from the EUDability dimensions. CT skills were assessed by domain experts from the healthcare field using a self-reported questionnaire based on the TSAI's CTS (cf. Fig. 2.2.3). The combined evaluation revealed the suitability of the EUD tools for the target user groups in professional contexts.

An early example is the study of Koh et al. [112], who introduced a visual semantic evaluation tool designed to assess student-created games and simulations. The tool aimed to identify CT concepts embedded in students' projects by semantically analysing their development over time, thereby facilitating the detection of CT patterns and the potential transfer of skills from games to science simulations. While the focus was on the semantic analysis of the artefacts produced by the users, the approach implicitly involved the clustering of users based on their behaviour patterns.

With the widespread use of block-based programming environments such as Scratch, a substantial body of literature has emerged in educational settings, mainly investigating

the acquisition of CT.

Moreno-León [156] introduced Dr. Scratch, an automatic assessment technique for CT in Scratch projects based on the static analysis of programming constructs, such as abstraction, logical thinking, synchronisation, flow control, and data representation, extracted from projects generated in a programming challenge for students. The authors demonstrated strong correlations between tool-generated evaluations and expert judgments, providing evidence of the effectiveness of automated, artefact-based CT assessment. In a follow-up study [157], the approach was extended with data-driven learning paths for the development of CT in Scratch. By analysing large collections of Scratch projects and their associated CT scores, the researchers moved beyond simple evaluations. They identified progressive patterns of concept acquisition and demonstrated how automated assessment can be used to guide learners' progress and provide targeted feedback. Recently, an AI-powered version of the tool has been released, enabling tailored assessment of CT according to a specific project type, and AI-driven support through a recommender assistant based on LLMs [184].

Recent work on intelligent pedagogical agents [161] leveraged the FUMA framework (cf. Fig. 2.2.4) to support CT acquisition in learning settings where learners can legitimately follow multiple solution paths. Rather than relying on a fixed notion of correct behaviour, the approach models how users' problem-solving strategies evolve over time, using interaction traces to infer the learner's current strategy, difficulty points, and progression. This is particularly relevant for open-ended tasks, where the same goal can be reached through diverse decompositions, iterations, and refinements, making static rule-based tutoring limited. The evaluation showed that the framework can generate adaptive, data-informed hints that support CT acquisition, suggesting that useful guidance is possible even without a single correct solution.

Other studies addressed CT assessment through integrated approaches.

Israel-Fishelson et al. [104] explored CT assessment through multiple indicators, including solution attempts, completion time, concept utilisation, and solution originality, automatically extracted from interaction logs in a block-based programming environment for CT acquisition. Correlation and clustering analyses showed that these log-derived measures captured complementary and partially independent dimensions of CT. Overall, the study demonstrated that log-based analysis supported a formative, process-oriented assessment of CT, revealing measures often missed by summative approaches.

Much of the existing literature on CT has focused on procedural programming and the teaching of programming concepts, often through coding-centric activities and project-based learning [101]. In contrast, Moreno-León et al. [158] have explicitly investigated the relationship between modelling and CT. The authors studied the use of diagrams in educational settings, showing that engaging learners in diagrammatic modelling tasks supports the development of CT-related skills such as abstraction, problem decomposition, and systematic reasoning. Their results provide empirical evidence that modelling artefacts can serve not only as representational tools but also as vehicles for fostering and observing CT skills, reinforcing the relevance of model-based approaches for CT assessment.

■ Summary of case studies employing CT frameworks for assessment

- **What is known:** Approaches for CT assessment include artefact-based evaluations, log analysis, and intelligent tutoring systems, mainly in educational programming environments.
- **What is missing:** There is still limited research on CT assessment in professional contexts and modelling activities outside programming education.
- **Why it matters:** Modelling tasks involve core CT skills such as abstraction and decomposition. Assessing modelling under a CT lens can support the development of effective modelling tools.
- **How this thesis addresses it:** Uses CT frameworks to guide the design and evaluation of the EUD tool ModeLLer, thereby assessing CT application and user behaviour in a professional domain.

2.4 Summary

Our review of previous scientific works began by examining model-based approaches supporting digital transformation in agriculture within MoDRE and EUD fields. We subsequently broadened our scope to other socio-technical domains and studies reporting on user involvement and experiences with modelling.

We found that prior research has primarily concentrated on the agrifood sector combining GORE with complementary languages [21, 202], and more recent contributions propose agriculture-specific modelling languages [91]. We found a lack of application of MoDRE-based approaches focusing on the transformative aspects of agricultural digitalisation. Furthermore, although there is an explicit interest in applying RE approaches within agricultural LLs [60], to the best of our knowledge, we could not identify prior published work documenting requirements modelling in this specific context.

Overall, we highlight a growing interest in model-based applications in the agricultural domain [94, 170, 205], although the existing studies are predominantly focusing on software development platforms. Although EUD has primarily concentrated on empowering non-professional software engineers to create and extend software artefacts, we found a lack of contributions to requirements elicitation and modelling.

Beyond agriculture, previous studies have mainly targeted specific application domains [172, 177] and have been conducted predominantly in industrial settings [118].

Furthermore, empirical studies in natural settings are scarce in both areas.

Among the reviewed studies, some contributions move closer to our perspective, although they address related questions within different scopes. For instance, Ruiz et al. [186] address process reengineering by combining multiple modelling approaches and providing tool support; however, their work is primarily situated in organisational contexts, only marginally addresses end-user participation, and reports limited empirical application.

In contrast, O’Neill and Johnson [168] adopt a more end-user-oriented perspective, addressing technological development through a collective representation of the shift from a system as-is to a system to-be. Nevertheless, their representations are not grounded in established semi-formal notations, which limits their alignment with mainstream RE modelling approaches.

Störrle’s work [208] is the closest to ours in terms of end-user participation; however, it differs in two key respects: the evaluation focuses exclusively on one single aspect of the system representation, generating UML object diagrams, and the participants are domain experts from the tax authority domain. By contrast, our approach aims to encompass a broader modelling spectrum, integrating multiple facets of the complex digitalisation process, and is explicitly situated in the agricultural domain, with application in multi-stakeholder LL settings.

Regarding modelling support, prior research confirmed that modelling assistance is typically provided through dedicated tools [159], and a substantial body of work has explored the integration of AI techniques into these tools, particularly for automated model generation [191] and intelligent assistance features [193]. While these advances demonstrate the potential of AI-enhanced modelling environments, existing solutions already in the market offer limited support for iterative refinement and are more oriented towards expert modellers.

In contrast, more EUD-oriented support offered by tools such as FlexiSketch [232], PromoAI [114], and Gentleman [118] remained only marginally explored in real-world settings. More behaviour-driven assistance based on users’ interaction patterns—especially for novice modellers and in web-based contexts—has been explored primarily in educational settings [109, 150], leaving empirical application in real-world contexts largely under-investigated.

Part II

PoMeLO: a RE Method for Agriculture

Chapter 3

Overview of Part II

Figure 3.1: Overview of thesis chapters and their relation to RQs and design science iterations, highlighting the portion addressed in Part III.

This part addresses RQ₁ and RQ₂, which relate to the first and second iterations of the design research and led to the creation of the first artefact: *PoMeLO*, the RE method (cf. Figure 3.1).

3.1 Summary of Research Gaps

The community of CODECS living labs (LLs) had an initial request to develop visual representations to describe the transformation occurring in farm business processes after digitalisation. These representations were supposed to support communication among LL stakeholders and to enable subsequent socio-economic analyses. In this regard, RE makes extensive use of visual models to systematically capture user needs and translate them into system requirements [166] through MoDRE [18, 98]. Prior research in the agrifood sector has explored MoDRE strategies [21, 173, 201] and RE methods have been proposed in the industry to integrate complementary representations to analyse socio-technical systems from multiple perspectives [186]. However, MoDRE-based approaches that explicitly focus on the transformative aspects of agricultural digitalisation appear to have received comparatively limited attention, especially in participatory and open environments such as LLs.

Moreover, the application of modelling in LL contexts requires the active involvement of LL stakeholders to integrate the modelling approach into LL practices. This, in turn, implies a transfer of modelling skills from professional modellers to domain experts.

In this regard, although the benefits of user involvement throughout the RE process have long been a key focus of research [8, 20, 62, 167], within the RE literature, studies reporting concrete applications of modelling in participatory contexts are limited, and digital agriculture remains underexplored. From another perspective, EUD broadly concerns supporting non-professional programmers in the appropriation of software development practices [125], and model-based approaches are among the most established techniques within the broad range of empirical practices that can be applied to enhance user participation [8, 23]. However, within the EUD literature, requirements elicitation and modelling have received less explicit attention than other stages of the software development process.

■ Building on these issues, two research gaps can be identified:

1. There is limited empirical evidence on the application of MoDRE in real-world contexts, particularly in agriculture and participatory settings;
2. There is limited evidence on the direct involvement of end users in requirements modelling, both in terms of interpreting and creating models.

3.2 Research Questions

The gaps outlined above lead to the two research questions presented in this section, which are operationalised through multiple sub-questions. Figure 3.2 summarises the overall design, validation and implementation/evaluation tasks mapping sub-questions to the corresponding phase. The elements of the figure are referred to in the following paragraphs.

Figure 3.2: Visual summary of Part II - PoMeLO, addressing RQ1 *How can we carry out process modelling using semi-formal notations within agricultural living labs?* and RQ2 *How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations?*, with sub-questions mapped to the corresponding evaluation studies.

3.2.1 RQ1: How can we carry out process modelling using semi-formal notations within agricultural living labs?

This question is framed as a *design problem*, in line with Wieringa's methodology, as it concerns the development of an artefact. It is addressed through two sub-questions:

- RQ1.1: How can MoDRE techniques be applied in living labs for the representation of a process transformation?
- RQ1.2: To what extent does the PoMeLO method lead to understandable and effective representations of the process transformation?

To answer RQ1.1, we developed PoMeLO, a RE method composed of i) a set of models to describe all the elements of interest related to the process transformation occurring

after the introduction of digital technology within an agricultural context; ii) two structured procedures: a **data collection procedure**, to elicit requirements from LL stakeholders by capturing elements of the systems and relations, as well as impacts due to digitalisation; and a **formalisation procedure**, to create the models from the collected data.

To answer RQ1.2, the models produced as output of RQ1.1 were validated through a case study and **focus groups** conducted within the CODECS LLs, to collect feedback on the RE method and assess whether the resulting representations were useful and understandable.

Chapter 4 provides an answer to these sub-questions and concludes on RQ1.

3.2.2 RQ2: How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations?

In line with design science, RQ2 is framed as a *knowledge question* concerning the empirical investigation of stakeholders' experiences with the application of the method. We frame *modelling experience* as the set of perceptions, responses, and situated interactions that emerge when users engage with semi-formal languages, tools, and processes. This notion is conceptually grounded in Kalantari et al.'s recent proposal of *Modeler eXperience* (MX) [107], which builds on earlier work by Abrahão et al. [11] and extends the concept of user experience to the specific context of model-driven engineering.

Within this broader framing, we structure the evaluation of the method by combining evidence from stakeholders' performance in both model creation and interpretation with their reported perceptions. Specifically, in alignment with prior empirical work on RE modelling methods [10], we adopt the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [56], considering its three core constructs: Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU), and Intention to Use (ITU).

Therefore, RQ2 is explored within the LL context through four sub-questions:

- RQ2.1: To what extent are domain experts who are not RE specialists able to model requirements in their specific domain using the formalisation procedure proposed by PoMeLO?
- RQ2.2: To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO when exposed to a case external to their own living lab?
- RQ2.3: To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?
- RQ2.4: To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?

These questions address complementary aspects related to the LL stakeholders experience of applying PoMeLO, by considering model creation (RQ2.1), acceptance of the modelling notations when stakeholders interpret a case external to their own LL (RQ2.2), acceptance of the modelling notations when the representations refer to their own case (RQ2.3), and acceptance of the method after its overall application, thus considering both the data collection phase and the resulting models (RQ2.4).

Specifically, to answer RQ2.1 and RQ2.2, we performed a field study [207] within the validation task of the second iteration of the design science project. The study is divided into two phases (cf. Fig. 3.2): the first phase addressed RQ2.1 by investigating end users' ability to create models (**model creation**). A team of domain experts—specifically agronomists—applied the formalisation procedure included in PoMeLO (cf. Sec. 3.2.1) and created the graphical models in eight real-world cases.

The second phase addressed RQ2.2 during an interactive plenary session with 60 CODECS LL stakeholders (**model interpretation**). In this phase, the understandability of a selected set of models resulting from the previous phase was assessed, together with their PEOU, PU, and ITU.

Chapter 5 provides an answer to RQ2.1 and RQ2.2.

To address RQ2.3 and RQ2.4, we transferred PoMeLO to the practice by implementing the method within 19 LLs in the context of the CODECS project activities. We answered RQ2.3 through individual **focus groups** with selected LL stakeholders, discussing several aspects of the models developed, including understandability, usefulness and limitations of the representations. We answered RQ2.4 through two **surveys** administered to the LL stakeholders who participated in the focus groups. The first survey assessed the acceptance of the data collection procedure, while the second assessed the acceptance of the resulting models.

Chapter 6 provides an answer to RQ2.3 and RQ2.4 and concludes on RQ2.

Chapter 4

Development of the Method

This chapter is based on the workshop paper “Towards a Method for Modelling Socio-technical Process Transformation in Digital Agriculture”, Mannari C.; Bacco F. M.; Spagnolo G. O.; Malizia A.; Ferrari A. 2024 IEEE 32nd International Requirements Engineering Conference Workshops (REW). IEEE (2024)[MoDRE24] [135], and on the following publications: [AGRSYS] [204], [MetroAgriFor24] [136], [MetroAgriFor23] [132], [REFSQ23] [133], [CODECS-DEL] [7].

Figure 4.1: Visual summary of chapter 4, highlighting the portion that addresses: *RQ1.1 How can MoDRE techniques be applied in living labs for the representation of a process transformation?* and *RQ1.2 To what extent does the PoMeLO method lead to understandable and effective representations of the process transformation?*

4.1 Overview

This chapter introduces the first design science iteration, motivated by a request from the CODECS living labs (LLs) to develop visual models of the transformations occurring in farm business processes after digitalisation. In doing so, we address the research gap concerning the limited empirical application of semi-formal models in participatory agricultural contexts. While MoDRE provides a rich repertoire of visual notations to capture goals, processes, and system components [98], its application to the analysis of digital transformation within agricultural LLs remains underexplored. In particular, there is limited empirical evidence on how such techniques can effectively support the representation of process transformation (cf. Ch. 3).

To tackle this challenge, the chapter investigates RQ1: *How can we carry out process modelling using semi-formal notations within agricultural living labs?*

This question is addressed through two sub-questions:

- RQ1.1: How can MoDRE techniques be applied in living labs for the representation of a process transformation?
- RQ1.2: To what extent does the PoMeLO method lead to understandable and effective representations of the process transformation?

Figure 4.1 maps how these questions are addressed.

To answer RQ1.1, we developed PoMeLO, a RE method composed of 1) a set of diagrams to describe all the elements of interest related to the process transformation occurring after the introduction of digital technology within an agricultural context; 2) two structured procedures: one to elicit requirements from LL stakeholders by capturing elements of the systems and relations, as well as impacts due to digitalisation; and one to create the diagrams from the collected data.

To answer RQ1.2, the models produced as output of RQ1.1 were validated through a case study and focus groups conducted within the LLs of the CODECS consortium, to assess whether the resulting representations were useful and understandable.

■ Compared to prior participatory modelling approaches, PoMeLO: 1) operates in multi-stakeholder LLs, 2) integrates goal and process modelling, 3) introduces a formalisation layer, 4) is validated across multiple sites.

4.1.1 Methodology

This section presents the methodology adopted for the design and validation of the method. To clarify the meaning of *method*, we adopt Brinkkemper's definition:

A method is “an approach to perform a systems development project, based on a specific way of thinking, consisting of directions and rules, structured in a systematic way in development activities with corresponding development products” [42].

Accordingly, the proposed method includes a set of modelling notations, the modelling procedure, the underlying rationale, the activities to be performed, and the artefacts produced during the process.

Action research

To come to a consolidated artefact consisting of useful and understandable diagrams and straightforward procedures, we followed an action research methodology [187]. More specifically, our approach aligns with two traditions: *technical* action research [229] and *participatory* action research [127]. The first emphasises the iterative design and evaluation of an artefact in real settings, aiming to solve a practical problem while generating transferable knowledge. The second foregrounds the active involvement of participants as collaborators in the research process. In participatory action research, the researcher takes an active role within the studied community or organisation, collecting and analysing data with the dual purpose of influencing the situation and generating knowledge [127]. Prior work addressing a similar dual challenge has been positioned as *participatory technical* action research, combining the in-situ application of an artefact with sustained stakeholder involvement throughout the research process [70].

In our context, the method was developed through multiple iterations alternating refinement and validation, with the aim of eliciting and consolidating requirements to progressively fine-tune the artefacts.

Participants Throughout this process, the author of the thesis interacted regularly with the supervisors—professors and researchers in computer science with expertise spanning IS, SE, RE, HCI, and agritech and also members of the CODECS project—as well as with researchers from CNR-ISTI contributing complementary expertise on formal notations. The work also involved a team of agronomists and economists from the Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment at the University of Pisa, and LL stakeholders with diverse backgrounds and levels of experience. Further details on the sample characteristics of these participant groups, including demographic information and participant numbers, are reported in the sections describing the validation activities (Sections 4.3.1 and 5.1.1).

Pilot studies A first pilot study was developed outside the CODECS project to anticipate and align with the project timeline. The case is based on an Italian LL working on the integration of a smart irrigation system on a pear orchard. Subsequently, two case studies were carried out with selected LLs within CODECS: Case 1, based on Pecorino Toscano, an Italian LL focusing on the introduction of a farm management information system within a cheese-making process, and Case 2, Agrifood Technology, a Belgian LL dedicated to drone technologies for crop monitoring. These cases enabled the progressive testing of the set of models and guidelines, respectively, ahead of their broader deployment in project activities. Case 1 is presented in Sec. 4.2 and 4.3, whereas Case 2 is examined later in Chapter 5.

Activities The interactions took place through internal meetings, focus groups, on-field visits, and plenary sessions within project activities. This process involved multiple actors with complementary roles: RE researchers developed and refined the modelling artefacts, while agronomists and LL stakeholders provided feedback that informed successive iterations and improvements.

During the internal meetings, the CNR team assessed the syntactic rigour and formal consistency of the diagrams, ensuring their alignment with the underlying notations.

These assessments were carried out during regular weekly remote meetings of approximately one hour, which have been held throughout the project since the beginning of CODECS. In specific phases of the method development, agronomists from the University of Pisa and other experts from CNR-ISTI also took part in these meetings.

During the design process, a formal requirements document was created. This document is available in Annex 2 [130]. At this stage, no consolidated metamodel was defined, as the practical orientation of the work prioritised testing the modelling notations in practice. Nevertheless, Section 4.2 presents the constructs adopted in the approach, which were used consistently across all cases.

Focus groups In particular, focus groups with agronomists and selected LL stakeholders were organised to assess the understandability and usefulness of the representations. The sessions were conducted as one-hour remote semi-structured group discussions, guided by a common protocol. Each session included an introduction to the modelling notations and a presentation of the diagrams by the author of the thesis, followed by a discussion in which the agronomists took turns to comment on their comprehensibility, effectiveness, and usefulness within the LL context. Members of the CNR team intervened when needed to exchange further clarification. Revised versions of the models were then shared with participants after the focus group to gather final feedback through email. More details are provided in Section 4.3.

Thematic analysis

The feedback collected in the focus groups was analysed through thematic analysis of the transcripts, following Braun and Clarke's approach [39]. Given the practical need to reach results within a relatively short timeframe, no analyst triangulation was performed. The coding was carried out by the author of the thesis, and subsequently reviewed by the supervisors to check its understandability and consistency with the transcripts.

For each type of diagram, namely UML, iStar and BPMN, two main questions were discussed related to the *understandability* and *effectiveness* of the representations. Moreover, a third question about the *completeness* of the representation supported the discussion about missing elements and led to improved versions of the diagrams.

Understandability refers to the clarity and accessibility of the diagrams to a wide range of stakeholders, including LL contact points, researchers from different domains and relevant actors involved in the process evaluation.

Effectiveness refers to the ability of the representations to serve their intended purpose in facilitating process assessment and communication. Completeness refers to the extent to which the diagrams accurately and comprehensively capture the essential entities, relationships, and layers concerning the dimension represented.

At this stage, we did not yet rely on TAM, as the main objective of the focus groups was to collect requirements for improved versions of the method rather than to assess its acceptance. The discussions were therefore kept broad and exploratory, with the aim of eliciting participants' spontaneous reactions, perceived difficulties, and suggestions for refinement.

4.2 Design (RQ1.1)

The method consists of three artefacts: (i) a set of selected MoDRE notations; (ii) a data collection procedure to collect the data required to create the models; (iii) a formalisation procedure to develop the representations.

4.2.1 MoDRE Notations

The method integrates the foundations of process modelling with a socio-technical lens, producing three complementary types of diagrams, each providing a distinct perspective on the process transformed by digitalisation. The process transformation is emphasised by qualitatively highlighting the differences in the process *as-is* (before the introduction of a digital technology) and in the process *to-be* (after the introduction of a digital technology). To ensure completeness, the process transformation focuses on three complementary dimensions—domain, goal, and process—, which are represented through different notations:

- **Domain:** the UML class diagram provides an overview of the domain in which the process is situated, i.e., actors, resources, tools, and infrastructures involved in the process to-be and the relationships among them [3, 43].
- **Goal:** the iStar diagram models the goals of the process to-be focusing on the intentional, social, and strategic dimensions [54, 233];
- **Process:** the BPMN diagram [2, 51] represents the detailed flow of the process, including actors' tasks, procedures, and communications. Multiple diagrams are developed to represent both the process as-is and the process to-be. An overlapping visualisation allows comparisons between the overall process before (as-is) and after (to-be) the introduction of digital technology.

The iStar and UML diagrams only focus on the process to-be in order to simplify the overall representation, considering that the core models to visualise the process transformation are the BPMN diagrams.

Selection rationale These notations were selected opportunistically by the author of the thesis, in agreement with the supervisors, after examining the relevant modelling literature (cf. Sec. 2.2.2). The rationale for this choice was based on the concepts the notations convey, their relative maturity, and the availability of adequately documented tools, including web-based ones.

The selected notations were deemed complementary for representing socio-technical process transformations. As a prominent notation for process modelling, BPMN was selected to provide an operational view of the transformation. In the context of this thesis, however, this level of representation needed to be complemented with representations of the social and organisational aspects of the digital transformation in agriculture. For this reason, iStar was adopted to support discussion on the roles and interests affected by digitalisation. Furthermore, given the need to support cost-benefit assessment at a sufficiently granular level, UML class diagrams were used to represent the static structure of the system, including relevant domain entities.

Case Study Pecorino Toscano LL

This section presents the final versions of the diagrams through a case study.

Fig. 4.2 illustrates parts of the diagrams developed in Case study 1 - Pecorino Toscano. The models depict the transformation of the cheese-making process due to the introduction of the FMIS for monitoring milk production. The models shown here focus specifically on the agronomist involved in the process, interacting with the FMIS. The complete set of models, including both the preliminary and final versions, is available in Annex 3 [130].

Figure 4.2: Models representing part of a milk production process transformed by the introduction of a farm management information system.

In Fig. 4.2a, the iStar diagram represents the goals, activities and relationships of the agronomist. The agronomist is represented by means of an icon over its boundary. Within the boundary, there are the agronomist's inner goals (orange elements), such as *increase milk*, *optimise feed* and *protect animal health*. These goals are all pursued through the task *elaborate food ratio* (blue elements). Moreover, another agronomist's goal is to *save time*, which they address using a tool, a PetScan Bluetooth (grey element). Outside the boundary, there are additional goals are included, and corresponding dependency links. For example, the goal *optimise work management* is fulfilled through the use of the FMIS, shown in a distinct boundary that represents the system. Overall, from the representation can be derived the advantages, or the drawbacks, gained by the agronomists through the use of the digital technology. Furthermore, the model aims to support reflection on the strategic interactions among actors accessing the system, the roles of the various stakeholders, and the management of data across the value chain.

Fig. 4.2b contains a portion of the UML class diagram with a detailed view of the class *Agronomist* and neighbouring elements, *Veterinarian*, *Pet scan bluetooth* and *App*. The new classes introduced by digital technology are in light blue. Within the *Agronomist*'s class are described the activities performed by the actor, namely *assign food ratios*, *provide data*, *update FMIS* and *access data*. The relations with labels and terminal arrows provide information about the kinds of relationships that the actor has with neighbouring elements. For example, the agronomist exchanges data with the app through a bi-directional relation (*exchangeData*), while they monitors the animals interacting with the Pet scan Bluetooth (*monitorAnimal*). This type of model provides a static view of the process, offering insight into the domain in which it is situated, how it is structured, how its components interact, and how digitalisation may affect a wide range of actors and resources. By highlighting the entities involved and their relationships, the diagram clarifies the underlying network of relations and identifies the elements of the process that are reshaped or newly created by the introduction of digital technology.

Fig. 4.2c is an overlap of two BPMN models focusing on the pool of the agronomist: a first diagram describing the process carried out by the agronomist before the introduction of technology (process as-is), and a second diagram representing the new process introduced by the digital infrastructure (process to-be). The new participants, activities and gateways introduced by the technology are in blue; in green the activities and gateways that do not change; in red the activities and gateways that are not present anymore. The picture represents the agronomist's daily process, which consists of two main parallel flows: the farm visit and work planning. During the farm visit, several tasks remain unchanged, for example, *visit scheduled farms*, *request animals information*, and *annotate animal facts*, with the latter involving a communication flow with the farmer. Other tasks are newly introduced, such as *scan animals*, while some tasks are removed, such as *notify vet*, which is replaced by *update FMIS*. Moreover, the diagram includes two additional flows representing the former communication exchanges between the agronomist and the veterinarian, and with the milk analysis laboratory, all of which are now fully replaced by access to the FMIS. By depicting the process as-is and the process to-be the representation makes explicit the transformation undergone by this actor highlighting the principal points of change in their daily process, fostering discussion and decision-making.

Overall, the combined use of BPMN, UML, and iStar offered by the method enables

moving from process representation to requirements specification, supporting the identification of both functional and non-functional requirements (FRs/NFRs). Specifically, the BPMN diagram is the primary source for FRs, as it represents the detailed flow of the process. Furthermore, by comparing the process *as-is* and *to-be*, it becomes possible to derive FRs concerning the system functionalities needed to support the new tasks introduced by the digital solution. In addition, the UML class diagram complements this view by helping specify the entities that the system shall manage and the relations that shall be maintained among system components and actors. From this representation, FRs can be further refined in terms of the data objects manipulated by the system and the associations among domain entities. At the same time, the diagram provides a clearer understanding of the domain boundaries and the socio-technical configuration within which requirements are situated. Lastly, the iStar diagram can help identify NFRs relating more broadly to the value and conditions of use of the digital solution in the LL contexts. By modelling actors' goals, dependencies, and tasks, the diagram supports the derivation of FRs, as well as NFRs connected to qualities such as *time efficiency*, *improved working conditions* and *environmental sustainability*.

Notations adaptation

The final set of models was obtained through multiple iterative refinement cycles conducted via internal meetings and focus groups with LL stakeholders (cf. Sec. 4.3). The feedback collected in each session was incorporated into successive revisions until a consolidated set of representations was obtained. This consolidated version was then adopted as the reference set applied across the CODECS LLs (cf. Ch. 6).

For convenience, Table 4.1 summarises the constructs applied in the models. Although, as already noted, no explicit metamodel was defined at this stage.

Diagram	Constructs
Domain—UML class diagram	Class, direct association, aggregation
Goal—iStar diagram	Actor, goal, task, resource/tool
Process—BPMN diagram	Pool, task, message, parallel gateway, exclusive gateway

Table 4.1: Constructs applied in the RE method

Across all the selected notations, targeted adaptations were introduced to maximise understandability. Specifically, the number of constructs was reduced, a small and consistent visual vocabulary was privileged, and colour was used to emphasise key elements. These choices were guided by principles from Moody's theory [152] (cf. in particular Graphic Economy in Sec. 2.2.1), which have also been reaffirmed by more recent empirical research [107].

UML For the UML diagrams, we employ an essential set of constructs from domain diagrams, e.g., a subset of class diagrams, including the construct *aggregation* to represent the digital technology. In representations of digitalisation, this element is central for making the structure of the technology explicit and understandable to all LL stakeholders. All the digital entities are also highlighted in light blue to maximise perceptual discriminability (cf. Moody's Theory in Sec. 2.2.1). The position of these elements is

likewise meaningful, as they are typically placed in a central upper area of the diagram to further emphasise their relevance.

iStar For the iStar diagrams, a modified visual style was adopted by introducing actor icons and revising the appearance of selected symbols to produce more user-friendly representations and improve semantic transparency (cf. Moody's Theory in Sec. 2.2.1), as previously done by other authors [45]. This solution aligns with prior work on the cognitive effectiveness of visual notations, highlighting recurring usability issues in goal-oriented notations and motivating notation tailoring to mitigate them [153]. Furthermore, we adopt the convention of placing the technology at the centre of the representation and the actors around it. Actors and technology are represented in a similar manner, namely within an actor boundary, with the distinction that the technology is not assigned its own goals. For the sake of simplicity, we do not employ qualities. Instead, we use three categories of goals: goals internal to actors, which belong to the strategic rationale view; goals between actors; and goals between actors and technology, which belong to the strategic dependency view. In these dependency relations, the dependum is always formulated as a goal, so as to preserve the focus on the underlying motivation of the relationship.

BPMN For the BPMN diagrams, we use task types to increase semantic transparency (cf. Moody's Theory in Sec. 2.2.1). In particular, we employ the task types *send*, *receive*, *manual*, *service*, and *user*. Since the process is described at a higher level of abstraction, e.g., with a relatively coarse granularity, the *user* task type is used for mixed tasks, which often aggregate multiple activities. We also employ annotations, in line with the principle of dual coding (cf. Moody's Theory in Sec. 2.2.1), to explain qualitative aspects that are not directly captured by the notation constructs. We use one diagram to represent the process *as-is* and another to represent the process *to-be*. Process transformation is then visualised through an overlapped view, in which the two representations are superimposed and differentiated by colour. The adopted colours follow an intuitive code-like logic: red for removed elements, blue for new ones, and green for elements that remain unchanged.

Conceptual bridges across modelling languages The three selected notations are related through common concepts that act as bridges across the representations. For example, actors in iStar may correspond to participants represented as pools in BPMN and to classes in the UML class diagram; similarly, digital tools may appear as resources in iStar, classes in UML, and system-enabled activities in BPMN. These conceptual correspondences support traceability across the models and help connect the structural, strategic, and operational views of the same process transformation. While these views represent different types of content, they exploit the specialisation of each modelling language to capture distinct constructs. At the same time, since the models are managed separately, maintaining consistency across them may become challenging and requires careful alignment during modelling and validation. This reflects a trade-off in the method, which does not aim for strong formal consistency across models, but rather prioritises stakeholder communication and the flexible exploitation of each modelling language according to its representational strengths.

Selection rationale

4.2.2 Data Collection Procedure

To develop diagrams that are accurate and representative of the perspectives of the various stakeholders involved in the LLs, the method requires the collection of process-relevant data from the actors involved in the transformation. Common RE practices typically rely on interviews conducted by expert analysts to elicit data and requirements [166]. However, in the multi-stakeholder setting of CODECS, this approach was not completely feasible due to the high number of LL involved, their geographical dispersion, and the fragmented nature of the actors and activities to be covered. Starting from this traditional baseline, we therefore adapted the elicitation approach to align with project timelines and operational constraints, with the aim of defining a systematic and reusable procedure applicable across heterogeneous LL contexts.

To this end, a data-collection procedure was designed, based on a set of guidelines and dedicated reporting templates. The guidelines and templates are available in Annex 4 [130].

To facilitate LLs in discussing process transformation and in systematically collecting the information required for modelling, three alternative templates were designed. These are differentiated based on the state of digitalisation.

Three possible states of digitalisation have been identified. The states are Zero Digital, Digitalising, and Digitalised:

- *Zero Digital*: this is a state in which the technology has not been identified yet. Starting from an evaluation of the current process in terms of assets, resources and capabilities available, the LL explores alternative solutions to solve the problem statement based on the adoption of different technologies. LLs are invited to consider that they are in a Zero Digital state also if some technologies are used in their process, but the specific digital solution they are interested in to solve the problem statement has not been identified yet.
- *Digitalising*: In this state, a digital solution to solve the problem statement has been identified but not yet adopted. This occurs when the technology is available but not stable yet, or not fully adopted. For example, the LL could be in the process of introducing the technology within a restricted group (e.g. a demo farm), or a prototype has been developed and tests are being carried out. In this context, the LL is able to compare the process today (i.e., before the introduction of the digital technology) and after the introduction of the digital technology, by trying to envision the process in the future.
- *Digitalised*: in this state, a digital solution to solve the problem statement has been purchased or developed by the LL. This occurs when, after a first period of in-field testing, the technology has been adopted within the LL. In this context, the LL is able to evaluate the technology and compare the process today (i.e., after the introduction of the digital solution), and before the introduction of the digital solution, by trying to recall the process in the past.

Table 4.2: Question groups in the guidelines for data collection, their intended use and example.

Question group	Purpose	Running example
Introductory questions	Understand the LL context and the core problem addressed (or to be addressed) through digital technology. Support reflection on the <i>state of digitalisation</i> and guide the selection of the most appropriate reporting template.	Pecorino Toscano LL can be positioned in the <i>Digitalising</i> case (technology selected and prototyped, not yet introduced).
Description of the digital technology	Describe the selected digital technology and the rationale for its selection. In <i>Zero Digital</i> cases, support reflection on candidate technologies and guide the identification of the most appropriate option for the LL context.	In Pecorino Toscano LL, the main technology is an FMIS aimed at facilitating information exchange among actors and improving monitoring.
Process after the digital technology	Capture how the process appears when the digital technology is (or will be) in place. The questions are organised into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Goals, actors, and resources</i> • <i>List of actions</i> 	Description of actors and resources highlighting what was added in the process (e.g., an app introduced, a software provider) and lists of actions carried out by actors with the technology in place.
Process before the digital technology	Capture how the process appeared when the digital technology was not (or is not yet) in place. The questions are organised into: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Actors and resources</i> • <i>List of actions</i> <p>Emphasise additions/removals of actors, resources, and activities due to digitalisation by comparison with the process after</p>	Description of actors/resources highlighting what was added/removed (e.g., an app introduced, paper sheets removed) and description of activities before digitalisation.

Accordingly, the guidelines define three alternative procedures, each tailored to a state of digitalisation and associated with a corresponding data-collection template to be completed.

The templates are editable documents containing the questions explained in the guidelines. They contain approx 12 questions asking to describe both the process before (as-is) and after (to-be) the introduction of the digital solution, as well as other information useful for the different models. Table 4.2 summarises the template content, organised into relevant question groups.

4.2.3 Formalisation Procedure

The design of the formalisation procedure was driven by two main objectives: 1) to streamline the approach for applying general-purpose notations within the specific context of agricultural digitalisation, and 2) to explain the notations and offer practical shortcuts that support non-expert requirement engineers during the modelling process. This design choice is inspired by previous work that translated modelling knowledge into practitioner-oriented guidelines, emphasising stepwise instructions and usability-oriented adaptations to facilitate adoption beyond expert modellers [186].

To develop modelling guidelines that are sequential, structured, and suitable for non-technical profiles, a modelling procedure was derived by reverse-engineering the steps followed to produce the cases studies.

The guidelines are practice-oriented, designed as a reference manual organised into several sections to support the creation of consistent models across LLs. It provides explicit step-by-step instructions for transforming the narrative descriptions contained in the LL reports into formal model elements—goals, actors, tasks, resources, tools, and relations—and connecting them according to the rules of each notation.

Since the next chapter reports the field study used to validate the guidelines, the detailed step-by-step procedure is presented there for clarity and to keep the description aligned with its empirical application (cf. Chapter 5).

4.2.4 Answer to RQ1.1: *How can MoDRE techniques be applied in living labs for the representation of a process transformation?*

MoDRE techniques can support communication among interdisciplinary stakeholders by providing complementary visual perspectives on socio-technical transformation. The design solution consists of a RE method that integrates UML, iStar, and BPMN to capture complementary perspectives on socio-technical transformation—respectively domain, stakeholder goals, and process workflow. By combining these notations, the method enables stakeholders to reason in an integrated manner about system components, strategic motivations and dependencies, and process changes. To produce diagrams that are accurate and representative of the diverse perspectives of LL stakeholders, the method includes a structured procedure for collecting process-relevant data from multiple actors involved in the transformation. Moreover, to streamline the application of the modelling notations within the specific domain of agricultural digitalisation and to make them accessible to non-expert modellers, the method incorporates a formalisation procedure that provides stepwise guidance and practical shortcuts.

4.3 Validation (RQ1.2)

This section reports the validation of the models based on one case selected among the first cases developed. Within the action research process, model validation was consolidated through a more extensive assessment involving a broader group of stakeholders. This was necessary because the models constitute the primary artefact and communication output of the project and were intended to be implemented across all CODECS

LLs. For this reason, focus groups were conducted to simulate the forthcoming CODECS activities and to collect feedback under conditions closer to the real project context.

4.3.1 Case and Subject Selection

The Consorzio Pecorino Toscano—the Italian LL based in Manciano, Tuscany—was selected as the case study for validation. The rationale for this choice was its geographical proximity, which provided the opportunity to conduct on-site visits, and the possibility of establishing close collaboration and communication with the large group of agronomists from the University of Pisa involved in the LL.

The LL Pecorino Toscano focuses on the activity of sheep breeding and pecorino cheese production. The LL is working on introducing a smart farming solution in the cheese production process. The activity is built around the co-design of a Farm Management Information System (FMIS) including a series of technologies aimed at supporting the work at various levels. The final system will grant interoperability among several technologies, such as a mobile application to monitor animals' health status, food ratios and milk production; smart collars to protect animals against wolves; and a blockchain-based system for farm-to-fork traceability. A prototype of the app is currently in use by technical advisors, while additional components are under evaluation. Participatory activities are being carried out in the LL for the co-design and evaluation of the digital technology.

Data collection and formalisation As this was the first case developed, the data collection did not yet follow the proposed procedure in a fully structured way. Rather, this case contributed to setting up and refining the procedures themselves. The author of the thesis and the CNR team visited the LL multiple times dedicating half a day to interacting with a group of around 20 people, including farmers, researchers, the farmers' cooperative representatives, the consortium of producers, the cheese-making factory, and the technical advisors working closely together with the farmers. Local administration such as the municipality of Manciano and the Tuscany Regional Administration are also participating in some LL activities. The first visit to the cheese-making farm in Manciano and to a sheep breeder was on November 11, 2022; this was followed by another meeting with the LL team in Manciano, on February 24, 2023, and a meeting at the Department of Agricultural Economics of the University of Pisa on May 26, 2023. After the meetings, the agronomists produced additional material, i.e., an informal diagram depicting all the elements of interest for the LL.

Data collected in this phase aimed at describing the system structure, the digital process currently under development, and the change with respect to the traditional process.

Based on the input data, the author of the thesis created the formal diagrams, and the CNR team revised them and provided feedback according to their expertise. The phase of internal revision was completed on October, 6, 2023 and led to 4 main changes to better comply with the grammar of the notations and user experience.

Feedback Collection The diagrams were used to further clarify certain aspects of the system in focus groups with the agronomists. Three focus groups were organised with three different groups on October 23, 2023 (FG1), November 24, 2023 (FG2), and

December 4, 2023 (FG3) respectively. Four participants took part in FG1 (P1, P2, P3, P4); the group was composed of three females and one male, one expert in agricultural economics (P1), one in animal production (P2) and two software engineers with expertise in formal notations (P3 and P4). Six participants participated in FG2 (P5, P6, P7, P8, P9, P10): three females and three males, three experts in agricultural economics (P5, P6, P7) and three software engineers (P8, P9, P10). Five participants took part in FG3 (P11, P12, P13, P14, P15): four females and one male, two practitioners, i.e., an agronomist (P11) and a vet (P12) who are the technical advisors involved in the LL, one expert in animal production (P13) and two software engineers (P14 and P15).

The software engineers were the same in the focus groups and the discussion was moderated by the author of the thesis. During the focus groups, together with the revision of the diagrams, questions were asked about the comprehensibility, effectiveness, and completeness of the representations. The focus groups were recorded and transcribed for analysis.

The evaluation led to substantial changes in the diagrams. In FG3, which was held with practitioners, an improved version of the diagrams was discussed, which was the outcome of the feedback received in FG1 and FG2.

4.3.2 Focus Groups Results

This section presents the results obtained from the thematic analysis of the transcripts of the three focus groups, following the methodology described in Sec. 4.1.1. Quotes supporting the identified themes, together with the focus group transcripts, are available in the supplementary documentation of the [MoDRE24] study [129].

Table 4.3 contains a map of the identified themes, which are discussed in the following, while completeness is discussed as an additional dimension in Sec. 9.3.

Note that when interacting with LL stakeholders, we referred to *domain* models as *structure* models, that is, models representing the *structure* of the process in terms of actors, resources, and relationships. This terminology was adopted to avoid burdening stakeholders with additional concepts requiring additional explanation beyond the core concept of *process*. For this reason, *domain models* may also appear in the form of

Table 4.3: Thematic map

<i>Questions</i>	<i>Themes</i>
UML Understandability	Useful colouring, Hard symbols interpretation
UML Effectiveness	Useful for comparison, Reuse and adaptation
iStar Understandability	Keep the representation simple, Hard symbols interpretation
iStar Effectiveness	Monitoring policies and interoperability
BPMN Understandability	Linearity, Useful colouring, Consistency, Hard symbols interpretation
BPMN Effectiveness	High level of detail on the process workflow, Multiple objectives of the representation, Immediate detection of advantages
Methodology	Tool for analysis, Effectiveness of visual representations, Reuse of the models, Procedure for co-creation of the diagrams

structure models in the feedback and related documentation.

1) Domain Diagram UML

UML Understandability The feedback on understandability confirmed that participants in all the focus groups generally agreed that the diagram was clear. In particular, P1 and P2 expressed their appreciation for the *useful colouring*, referring to the use of light blue to highlight classes representing technology. This requirement was suggested by a domain expert in a preliminary focus group based on the previous case study. The request was to put more emphasis on technology and identify with different colours the digital from the non-digital. During the evaluation, the domain expert, who also took part in FG1, confirmed the effectiveness of the new solution and the other participants unanimously agreed.

Despite the positive feedback, some difficulties emerged regarding *hard symbols interpretation*. Some participants found it difficult to interpret specific elements of the notation, such as the different types of association connectors (i.e., aggregation, composition) or the direction of some arrows in direct associations. As in the previous theme, difficulties in distinguishing attributes and methods inside the classes had already emerged during the validation. This suggested avoiding class attributes and opting for a simpler representation with class names only (cf. Fig.4.2b). Thus, to maximise the understandability of this diagram while minimising the readers' effort, a simplified version was produced, consisting solely of boxes with class names, and main operations performed by the class. This version with improved readability was presented in FGs and evaluated positively. An advanced version with expanded boxes is available for stakeholders interested in deeper analyses.

UML Effectiveness In general, the participants agreed that the diagram is “very effective” (P5) and “very useful” (P1). To assess effectiveness, participants considered potential usage scenarios for this type of diagram in the context of the planned LLs activities. Specifically, all participants in FG1 commented that having a standard representation is *useful for comparison*. Referring to process modelling activities carried out in parallel in different LLs, P1 stated: “It could be useful for every one of us to see the differences among LLs”. After analysing the diagram, P1 also suggested that the representation could be potentially subject to further *reuse and adaptation* by specific actors: “The consortium could use the same diagram in different situations”.

2) Goal Diagram iStar

iStar Understandability Generally, participants confirmed that they could understand the notation and provide feedback on the diagram. The participants agreed to *keep the representation simple*. In fact, being the goal model focused on strategic aspects, the representation should be limited to a small set of actors who are internal to the process. Moreover, P14 suggested: “We could deviate a bit from the standard of the notation in favour of readability”. This diagram was globally evaluated as clearer than the UML diagram, however some participants encountered difficulties with understanding certain symbols. This resulted in the theme *hard symbols interpretation*. For example, additional clarification was requested in all FGs to explain the difference between goal

and quality. Although in an additional iteration after FG1 and FG2 we tried to simplify the notation and decided to represent the goals and qualities in more distinct styles the confusion persisted in FG3. After carefully evaluating the feedback, we decided to avoid the distinction between the two concepts and use only a more general abstraction of “actor goal” encompassing both goals and qualities. The new version is represented in Fig. 4.2a.

iStar Effectiveness The diagram was evaluated as extremely useful for early discussion on strategic aspects, and participants highlighted that the goals could be useful for *monitoring policies and interoperability*. P1 and P2 asked to add a boundary with the public institution responsible for the Animal Registry with a main dependum task “Share animals data.” By adding this element, the group aimed to highlight that it is extremely important to collaborate with public institutions to ensure interoperability between the FMIS and the Animal Registry in the process to-be. To confirm this, P4, specified “This kind of representation related to the goals helps to establish if there are potential conflicts between the actors,” which could be particularly useful for policymakers.

3) Process Diagram BPMN

BPMN Understandability Participants agreed that the representation is very clear and the single views are *consistent* with each other (P3).

P5 appreciated the *linearity* of the diagrams: “These representations with straight lines are clean and very understandable.” Furthermore, participants discussed the theme *useful colouring*. In fact, they particularly appreciated the overlapped representation enabled by the use of different colours. P2 said: “I really like the idea of using the colours, I think this is very intuitive.” P11, despite appreciating the use of colours for representing the transformation, claimed that they had difficulties distinguishing the blue elements from the green ones and suggested reflecting on the use of alternative colours. Furthermore, the theme *hard symbols interpretation* emerged again in FG3. In fact, both participants had difficulties in understanding the meaning of the gateways. Moreover, P12 said: “I don’t pay attention to the small icons inside the boxes containing the actors’ tasks.”

BPMN Effectiveness All participants appreciated the overlapping view (cf. Fig. 4.2b) and evaluated it as particularly effective in presenting the process transformation. The participants agreed that the process diagram presents a *high level of detail on the process workflow* and actors’ tasks. Referring to the multiple views developed, each one depicting an actor’s pool, P1 commented: “The process is seen from the perspective of the agronomist, then from the point of view of the vet, from the farmer, from the factory. . . they are all there, well done.”

Reasoning on possible usage scenarios, P5 highlighted the *multiple objectives of the representation*: “These representations are very effective and can support the design of the service helping to decide how to distribute tasks among actors and how to manage a service in a different scenario; for example, we could have the same process with different actors involved and different task distribution.” Furthermore, P1 confirmed that the diagram supports the *immediate detection of advantages*. In fact, having a view of

the process from the perspective of every single actor is useful for the detection of important features: “presenting the single point of view, the diagram really shows who has the costs, who has the benefits. In the end, it will emerge thanks to these diagrams.”

4) Process Modelling Method

A final time slot in the focus groups was dedicated to a common discussion about the proposed method. Participants confirmed that the global modelling is very complete, effective and detailed. Furthermore, during the discussion about some scenarios of application of the diagrams, the main theme was to adopt process models as a *tool for analysis*, especially oriented to reflect on costs and benefits. Moreover, participants also agreed on the *effectiveness of visual representations*. During the discussion in FG1, it emerged that visual representations have the main advantage of being synthetic and immediate. P1 said: “Visual representation is a good support for memory and is more effective than reading a textual document, which is a more time-consuming activity.” In the same FG, it was discussed the theme of the *reuse of the models*, understood as the application of a model developed within a context to a new similar context. The aim could be to assess which changes are necessary to introduce the technology in the new context. One last concern was related to the need to set up a common *procedure for co-creation of the diagrams*. The discussion started in FG1 with the following question by P1: “Will the other LLs do the diagrams on their own?” All of the participants agreed that creating diagrams for LLs could be a challenging task, and experts in the notations are required. During the meeting, the participants discussed the initial proposal of a procedure based on guidelines for LL contact points and a template for data collection.

4.3.3 Discussion

Effectiveness and Understandability The outcome of the thematic analysis confirms that, generally, the participants evaluate the modelling languages as effective and understandable. The overall feedback on the method is positive, confirming the willingness of the participants to use the method as an analysis tool and a companion to technology demonstration. Furthermore, the active participation of the practitioners in FG3 confirmed that the diagrams can be employed to foster information exchange and discussion, and ultimately elicit domain knowledge.

Completeness The representations facilitate stakeholders in identifying incompleteness issues, thus fostering discussion and leading to more representative models. During the discussion of the UML class diagram, an initial question asked participants if they were able to find all actors, resources and relations that are part of the domain. They were suggested to consider that this kind of model can be extended to the representation of the wider system, including both internal and external actors. Several participants agreed that the representations, while already comprehensive, could be further enhanced with *more complete elements*. In fact, participants reported that some elements or relations were missing. For example, it was decided to add a link between the software agency, the agronomist, and the vet. This relation was considered relevant to highlight the information exchange during the co-development of the mobile application and to

provide the analysts with a clear indication of the actors directly involved in the design of the system. Then, moving the discussion to the iStar diagram, participants were asked to ensure that all the relevant stakeholders, goals, tasks, and dependencies were adequately represented in the model. Despite the feedback being globally positive, participants found that some resources or tasks were missing, and some elements needed to be better specified. For example, a goal mismatch was reported in the boundary of the vet and it was agreed to replace *milk productivity* and *milk quality* with *animals health*, being the first seen as a consequence of the latter.

Limitations A limitation emerging from FG1 and FG2 was related to evaluating the BPMN diagrams. In both focus groups, the process diagrams were evaluated as extremely interesting, providing very detailed views of the process workflow at the actor's level, and helping to identify the risks and advantages of process transformation. However, it was not possible to collect precise feedback, as the evaluation team did not include the practitioners directly involved in the process. Thus, a third focus group (FG3) was organised with practitioners who were able to provide accurate information on activities, frequency and relations among actors both about the process as-is and the process to-be. This confirms that to reach a holistic representation of a process we should include a feedback loop with *all* representatives of the LLs, including practitioners.

A major concern emerging from the analysis is the need to familiarise with the notations to understand the diagrams thoroughly. This is especially the case of the UML diagram, which is perceived as the most effective in representing the potential extent of the transformation, but at the same time is regarded as the most challenging to understand. On the one hand, agronomists accept the effort to learn the proposed notations with the result of enlarging the scientific body of knowledge shared by the community of practices involved in the LLs. On the other hand, a negotiation has been carried out by the CNR team and the agronomists to simplify the notation, while maximising the completeness of the representations. A tension between understandability and completeness frequently emerged. In fact, as already discussed in 9.2, some participants found difficulties in decoding fine-grained symbols on the diagrams. At the same time, analysing a diagram from multiple perspectives contributes to increasing the number of elements in the representation. This point was discussed while examining the UML diagram, and some participants suggested creating multi-layer representations, i.e., having multiple models that focus on different levels of a system. For example, there can be models that represent the minimal elements of the system, as well as specialised models that focus on a subset of the system. Additionally, complementary models can represent different states of the system, such as the set-up and fully operational stages.

Solutions There is no single solution to the tension between understandability and completeness, and we have been working on tackling the problem from different angles. In some cases, the solution was to maintain the symbols and rely on the legend as a support tool for users. In other cases, the evaluation group decided to maximise the readability of the diagrams by avoiding the use of advanced symbols, also in line with recommended practices [51]. The authors also introduced additional conventions in the representations. For example, in the iStar diagram, in addition to the use of an aesthetically enhanced notation, it was decided to represent the technology introduced in the

system within an actor boundary placed in a central position. This was to emphasise the technological components which are at the centre of the transformation. In general, multiple iterations helped to improve the diagrams and find optimal solutions applicable to the whole method.

4.3.4 **Answer to RQ1.2: *To what extent does the PoMeLO method lead to understandable and effective representations of the process transformation?***

Evidence from the focus-group validation indicates that PoMeLO leads to representations that are understandable and effective. Participants confirmed that the models accurately capture key actors, goals, and process transformations, while also enabling the identification of refinements and missing elements. The overlapping BPMN views were particularly appreciated for making digital transformation visible, and the goal models supported reflection on dependencies and strategic alignment. Although some challenges emerged—especially regarding notation complexity and the trade-off between completeness and readability—the iterative refinements confirmed the feasibility and practical usefulness of the method in real LL contexts.

4.4 Conclusions

In this final section, we discuss the threats to validity and draw conclusions on RQ1 (*How can we carry out process modelling using semi-formal notations within agricultural living labs?*), highlighting the research implications emerging from this iteration. These implications inform subsequent refinements of the method and motivate further cycles of the design science research.

4.4.1 Threats to Validity

This section discusses issues of the validity of this study, divided into construct validity, internal validity and external validity.

Construct validity The constructs considered in the validation include *understandability*, which assesses how accurately the meaning of the representations is conveyed; *effectiveness* of the method, which measures the usefulness of the representation for information exchange; and, to a lesser extent, *completeness*, which evaluates any missing elements in the representations. The definition of these concepts have not been detailed to the participants, which could have led to misunderstandings. However, we argue that the answers received show a correct comprehension of the concepts, which suggests that this threat is sufficiently limited.

Internal Validity The selection of representation languages was based on preliminary requirements, and by pragmatic decisions. Different results may be obtained with different languages. The feedback was captured by the people who proposed the method, which could have caused a Hawthorne effect. To mitigate this, we asked the participants

to be honest with their reflections, and the issues identified suggest the threat is limited. The thematic analysis is inherently subjective and was performed by the author of the thesis. To mitigate subjectivity, the supervisors reviewed the themes.

External Validity According to case-based generalisability [228], we argue that our results can apply to other LLs in the agricultural domain that are similar to our case, i.e., concerned with the production of food, and characterised by the presence of a preliminary prototype of a novel technology.

4.4.2 Summary

Findings from the first iteration of the design science research conducted in this thesis indicate that MoDRE languages, when applied through a structured method, are understandable and effective in representing the multiple perspectives involved in process transformation within agricultural digitalisation. The validation provides novel empirical evidence on the application of MoDRE in agricultural LLs—an underexplored setting for MoDRE. Within this context, our design choice to integrate multiple notations, namely UML, iStar, and BPMN, builds on earlier solutions proposed and evaluated primarily in industrial socio-technical settings, where combining complementary languages has been shown to capture strategic, and procedural dimensions more effectively [21, 186]. This contribution shows that this MoDRE solution remains effective also when transferred to agricultural LLs, thereby extending the external validity of prior work to a non-industrial context.

Notably, during the validation phase, the LL stakeholders—a team of researchers and practitioners from the agricultural domain—were able to engage in discussion and contributed refinements upon first exposure, without requiring extensive explanation of the modelling languages. This suggests the suitability of MoDRE for participatory modelling contexts, which have typically relied on more informal approaches [168, 232].

In particular, our direct experience with LLs revealed three complementary aspects. First, within our empirical context, we encountered conditions consistent with those described in LL literature, i.e., LLs are characterised by strong time constraints and the central involvement of domain experts whose primary work lies outside the LL activities [121]. These conditions are also well recognised in EUD research, which emphasises that methods and tools must accommodate practitioners' background and skills, and limited time [23]. Second, when stakeholders are given the opportunity to engage with the models, they show a clear willingness to appropriate the method and take ownership of the models, explicitly expressing their intention to edit and create models themselves. This also aligns with common EUD approaches, which emphasise empowering stakeholders to act as co-creators by adapting and evolving artefacts to fit emerging needs instead of relying exclusively on professionals [76]. Third, from the validation through focus groups emerged the dynamic nature of models: rather than being perceived as static artefacts, they functioned as “living documents”, evolving alongside the LL context itself. As additional stakeholders were involved in the discussion, the models were enriched with complementary viewpoints. This confirms their role—as defined in the RE literature—as shared artefacts that support requirements elicitation and negotiation [166].

Accordingly, we argue that operational solutions for supporting requirements modelling in LLs can be grounded in EUD principles and practices. Specifically, our direct experience with LLs motivated the adoption of RE and EUD approaches for data collection and formalisation: embedding in the method practical guidelines for data collection and modelling—so that domain experts can participate effectively and progressively become autonomous in producing and updating the models.

At the current design science iteration, a more extensive validation of the method is necessary. Specifically, while the diagrams were shown to a relatively limited group of stakeholders within their specific LL context, the method should be assessed in more ecological settings and across a larger number of real-world cases.

The following chapters addresses this challenge. Specifically, Chapter 5 reports the application of the formalisation procedure by a group of agronomists, followed by the validation of a selected case during a plenary meeting with LLs, while Chapter 6 reports the application of the method to the CODECS LLs.

Implications for AI Support At this stage of the research, an initial idea of supporting LLs through AI-based techniques had already emerged. In particular, the internal validation activities suggested the opportunity to provide a tool for model creation that integrates AI-powered functionalities to facilitate and accelerate modelling tasks.

However, given the limited evidence on the application of MoDRE approaches in contexts comparable to ours, it is necessary to first explore how LL stakeholders actually interact with requirements modelling and what they concretely need from these technique. Consistent with prior work in industrial contexts [193], this implies prioritising an understanding of users' practices, expectations, and constraints before designing AI assistance.

This chapter has provided an initial step towards establishing AI-based support for modelling in LL contexts, highlighting the feasibility of relying on semi-formal notations. By externalising key aspects of agricultural digitalisation into representations that are both human-interpretable and machine-interpretable, MoDRE-based models can serve in LLs as a shared language to support analysis, decision-making, and design.

■ RQ1 recap

This chapter has provided an answer to RQ1: *How can we carry out process modelling using semi-formal notations within agricultural living labs?* Process modelling in agricultural LLs can be carried through a RE method combining complementary semi-formal notations, namely UML, iStar, and BPMN, within structured elicitation and formalisation procedures. The findings show that, when suitably adapted and facilitated, this combination is understandable and effective for representing socio-technical process transformation in agricultural digitalisation contexts.

Chapter 5

End-user Requirements Modelling

This chapter is based on the paper: “End-user Requirements Modelling: an Experience Report in Agricultural Living Labs”, Mannari C., Sportelli M., Meesala H., Okoye O. F., Lepore F., Bacco F. M., Brunori G., Malizia A., Ferrari A., submitted to the Special Issue “Social REsponsibility” in Journal of Systems and Software and currently under review [JSS], as an extension of [REFSQ25] [137].

Figure 5.1: Visual summary of chapter 5, highlighting the portion that addresses: *RQ2.1 To what extent are domain experts who are not RE specialists able to model requirements in their specific domain using the formalisation procedure proposed by PoMeLO?*, *RQ2.2 To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO when exposed to a case external to their own living lab?*

5.1 Overview

The previous chapter presented the first design science iteration, which resulted in the proposal for the RE method and a first evaluation through focus groups conducted in a pilot case.

This chapter addresses the challenge of actively involving domain experts in requirements modelling within digital agriculture, motivated by the need to support their appropriation of the method. While RE has long emphasised the value of user participation [20], and model-based approaches are recognised as powerful instruments to support stakeholder involvement in RE [166], concrete applications of modelling in participatory socio-technical contexts remain limited—particularly in the agricultural domain. At the same time, EUD research has focused on empowering non-professional programmers [23], yet it has paid comparatively less attention to requirements elicitation and modelling activities (cf. Ch. 3).

To address this challenge, the chapter introduces RQ2: *How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations?*

This question is articulated into multiple sub-questions (cf. Ch. 3). This chapter addresses the following:

- RQ2.1: To what extent are domain experts who are not RE specialists able to model requirements in their specific domain using the formalisation procedure proposed by PoMeLO?
- RQ2.2: To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO when exposed to a case external to their own living lab?

Fig. 5.1 maps how these RQs are addressed, distinguishing two complementary dimensions of stakeholders' experience with requirements modelling: model creation and model interpretation. These two dimensions were investigated through a two-phase field experiment [207]. In the first phase, we investigated end users' ability to create models (*creation* dimension). A team of domain experts—specifically agronomists—applied the formalisation procedure which is part of the RE method, and created graphical models in iStar, UML, and BPMN in eight real-world cases. In the second phase, we assessed a selected set of models resulting from the previous phase during an interactive plenary session with 60 CODECS living lab (LL) stakeholders (*interpretation* dimension).

■ Compared to prior studies, this field study: 1) engaged domain experts not only as model interpreters but also as active contributors to model creation, and 2) examined the use of semi-formal notations in the natural setting of a cross-disciplinary plenary meeting, supporting participants in becoming familiar with a case through the modelling artefacts.

5.1.1 Methodology

This section presents the methodology adopted in the study.

Field experiment

A field experiment involves introducing specific interventions into a natural, pre-existing setting, enabling the assessment of techniques or practices under realistic conditions [207]. Its main strength lies in its high ecological validity, as behaviours and outcomes are observed in real-world contexts—although manipulated by the researchers. At the same time, the approach is exposed to contextual variability, which may influence measurement precision or transferability.

Participants

Three groups that are part of the CODECS consortium were directly involved in the field experiment: a team of RE/SE experts, i.e., the author of the thesis and the supervisors, a team of agronomists and LL stakeholders. The first group developed the modelling guidelines. The agronomists applied the guidelines. The agronomists are researchers with 3 to 4 years of experience in agricultural economics and agritech, while the software engineers have between 7 and 18 years of research and practical expertise in RE and EUD. The third group, composed of 60 LL stakeholders, was engaged in model interpretation. This group consists of a heterogeneous community from 33 organisations across 18 European countries, spanning multiple research profiles (e.g., agronomists, economists, social scientists) as well as practitioners (e.g., farmers, technical advisors, technology providers), united by the common challenge of conducting joint research on agricultural digitalisation. In addition to these participants, a broader group of LL stakeholders—amounting to approximately 200 individuals—led by LL coordinators, contributed to data collection by providing the reports used as input for modelling.

Procedure

Figure 5.2: Overview of the study structure.

Figure 5.2 outlines the study structure, comprising three phases with interconnected steps. We refer the reader to the specific sections, where additional figures provide a detailed view of each phase with inner activities and outcomes.

Phase I—Model creation, presented in Section 5.3.1, was carried out in two steps. In **Step 1—Modelling guidelines development**, the author of the thesis and the su-

pervisors developed modelling guidelines tailored for end users (cf. Section 5.2). In **Phase 2—Guidelines application**, the agronomists applied the modelling guidelines, using data provided by LLs (cf. Section 5.3.1). Details of Steps 1 and 2 are illustrated in Figure 5.3. This part of the study answered RQ2.1 through artefact-based analysis. Additionally, the direct observations from the modelling sessions provided source material for the lessons learnt.

Phase II—Model interpretation, presented in Section 5.3.3, aimed to assess a modelling case with a large group of stakeholders. In **Step 3—Plenary interactive session**, the LL stakeholders validated one case resulting from the previous step through an interactive session conducted during a plenary project meeting (cf. Section 5.3.3). In **Step 4—Post-plenary survey**, a survey was administered to the participants to validate the feedback (cf. Section 5.3.3). The overall workflow for Steps 3 and 4 is represented in Figure 5.4. This part of the study answered RQ2.2. Specifically, the plenary session captured performance-related evidence of the understandability of the models as well as qualitative insights from LL stakeholders. This informed the design of the subsequent survey, with questions aligned to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The on-field experience contributed to the lessons learnt.

Finally, **Phase III—Lessons learnt**, presented in Section 5.3.5, reports the 15 *lessons learnt* by the agronomists and the requirements engineers from the overall experience. Figure 5.10 contains an overview of the lessons.

Thematic analysis

The feedback collected in the plenary session (cf. Phase II, Step 3—Plenary interactive session) was analysed through thematic analysis of the transcripts, following Braun and Clarke’s approach [39]. One of the agronomists involved in the study (the fifth author of [JSS]) performed an initial round of coding. The author of this thesis then reviewed and harmonised the codes by mapping them onto the TAM dimensions [56], namely Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Intention to Use (ITU), which were subsequently used to design the survey (cf. Phase II, Step 4—Post-plenary survey).

5.2 Design

The modelling guidelines are embedded within the formalisation procedure, which constitutes the third artefact of the PoMeLO method. Their development through action research was introduced in Section 4.2.3. In the following, we provide an overview of the structure of the guidelines document.

The guidelines are illustrated in a 22-page document shared in Annex 5 [130]. The document provides instructions for converting the narrative descriptions in the LL reports into diagrams.

The introduction defines the purpose of the modelling activity within the project CODECS and includes a glossary of common terms clarifying the main concepts. The core of the guidelines describes the three diagrammatic notations. For each notation, the document includes legends and running examples. A dedicated section introduces the recommended modelling tools. The requirement engineers selected LucidSpark for iStar

diagrams, StarUML for UML class diagrams, and Camunda Modeler for BPMN. These tools were preferred for their accessibility, intuitive interfaces, and ability to export in standard exchange formats (e.g., XMI and BPMN-XML), which supports future integration with the modelling environments and other analysis tools. For iStar, where code export is not possible due to the custom graphical style, a template file was created to ensure consistency of icons, actor boundaries, and goal hierarchies. For all the notations, the document provides links to templates for immediate use, guiding users in how to open, duplicate, and adapt each file.

The procedural section details, in numbered lists, how to construct each diagram type—from selecting actors and goals to exporting high-quality images. For every modelling step, the document specifies which parts of the LL report should be consulted (e.g., [DIGITAL SOLUTION], [ACTORS PROCESS AFTER], [ACTIVITIES PROCESS BEFORE]), the type of information to extract, and how to represent it in the diagram. Tables 5.1 and 5.2 summarise the procedure, using the placeholder [TITLE] to denote the corresponding section title in the report. The iStar procedure (cf. Table 5.1, first part) comprises six steps, beginning with the identification of relevant actors and goals in the reports, followed by the abstraction of tasks from activity descriptions, and culminating in the creation of different types of connections among the created elements. Similarly, the UML procedure (cf. Table 5.1, second part) guides the modeller in identifying and representing the technological system, its components, and the relevant actors and resources, as well as in defining the relationships among them through labelled associations that represent concrete interactions (e.g., access data, exchange information). Finally, the BPMN procedure (cf. Table 5.2) supports the modeller in creating three com-

Table 5.1: Summary of formalisation procedure for iStar and UML models

Goal Diagram - iStar

- Actors** - Select actors from [ACTORS PROCESS AFTER] and create an Actor boundary.
 - Select technology from [DIGITAL SOLUTION] and create an Actor boundary (Technology boundary); possibly place it at the centre of the diagram.
- Goals** - For each actor select goal list from [RATIONALE] and [ADVANTAGES].
 - Classify and create goals. Place goals in internal, actor-actor or actor-technology positions. Express goals through a short sentence containing a verb.
- Tasks** - For each actor select main activities relevant to strategic aspects from [ACTIVITIES PROCESS AFTER] and abstract tasks. Place tasks inside the actor's boundaries.
- Tools** - Select technological resources from [RESOURCES] and [SOLUTION]; create and place tools inside the actor's boundaries, below the correspondent task.
- Connections** - *Tool-task*: for each tool, add a link between the tool and its corresponding task with the arrow directed from the tool to the task.
 - *Task-goal*: for each task add a link between the task and its corresponding goal with the arrow directed from the task to the goal.
 - *Actor-actor goal*: for each actor-actor goal, add a link connecting the two actor boundaries and the goal. The arrow should be directed from the active actor, e.g., the actor performing actions to fulfil the goal, to the recipient actor. If the actors share the same goal, put the arrow in both directions.
 - *Actor-technology goal*: for each actor-technology goal, add a link connecting the actor boundary to the technology boundary with the arrow directed from the actor to the technology.

Structure Diagram - UML

- Classes** - Select the technological system from [SOLUTION] and represent it as a class.
 - Identify components (hardware and software) of the tech. system from [SOLUTION] and [RESOURCES]; represent them as class and link with aggregation, (i.e., diamond).
 - Select actors from [ACTORS] and resources from [RESOURCES] and represent them as classes.
- Connections** - *Actor-technology/Actor-resource*: Add a link between the classes based on [PROCESS AFTER]. Add a label on the link with the action performed by a class actor using a technology or resource class. The arrow direction should go from the actor to the technology or resource.
 - *Actor-actor*: if actors have direct interactions, add a link between the actors based on [PROCESS AFTER]. The arrow direction should go from the active actor to the passive.

Table 5.2: Summary of formalisation procedure for BPMN models

Diagram 1 - BPMN process after

Actors - Select actors from [PROCESS AFTER] and create a pool for each actor. Select technology in [SOLUTION] and create a pool.
Start/End process - Add a start event and an end event inside each pool. Add a text annotation on the start event and indicate the execution frequency.

Tasks - Select the activities in [PROCESS AFTER] and create a sequence of connected tasks inside each actor boundary and within the start and end event. Optionally, assign a type to each task choosing among: manual, system, receive, send.

Connections - Identify send tasks and create a link starting from the send task to the corresponding recipient's receive task / pool. In case the send task triggers the beginning of the recipient's process, transform the start event of the recipient into a message start event and connect the send task.

- Add a label on the dotted line with the object of the activity.

Gateways - *Parallel gateways*: from [PROCESS AFTER] extract activities that are executed in parallel and place a parallel gateway before the first task executed to create multiple paths. Add a task or a sequence of tasks to each path. Repeat the gateway after the last tasks.

- *Exclusive gateways*: from [PROCESS AFTER] extract activities that are executed optionally and place an exclusive gateway to create multiple paths. Add a task or a sequence of tasks to each path. Add a label on the gateway explaining the condition and add a label on each path explaining the verification of the condition. Repeat the gateway after the last tasks.

Annotations - Add annotations on tasks to express additional information in [PROCESS AFTER].

Diagram 2 - BPMN process before

Actors - Copy in a new file the model(s) created in Diagram 1: BPMN process after

- Delete the pools of actors that were not in [PROCESS BEFORE].

- Delete or edit the technology pool according to the info in [SOLUTION].

- Select actors from [PROCESS BEFORE] that are not in [PROCESS AFTER] and create new pools. Add start and end events inside the pool.

Tasks, connections, gateways - Select activities from [PROCESS BEFORE] and edit the pool of each actor with corresponding tasks, relationships, gateways and annotations following the instructions provided in Diagram 1: BPMN process after.

Diagram 3 - BPMN process overlap

- Copy in a new file the model(s) created in Diagram1: BPMN process before. Paste the content of Diagram2: BPMN process after. Place Diagram2 next to Diagram1 and compare the two processes.

- Colour in green all the elements of Diagram1 that do not change in Diagram2.

- Colour in red all the elements of Diagram1 that are no longer present in Diagram2.

- Copy-paste all the new elements from Diagram2, colour in blue and overlap to Diagram1.

- Remove Diagram2.

plementary representations: the process after (to-be), the process before (as-is), and the process overlap. For as-is and to-be diagrams, it describes a systematic workflow for selecting actors and abstracting tasks from the reports, and representing process start and end, placing sequential and parallel activities, message exchanges, and conditional paths. For the overlap, it provides operational instructions to juxtapose the two representations, carry out visual comparison and highlight additions, removals, and unchanged elements through a standardised colour-coding scheme.

5.3 Validation

This section presents the empirical study structured into three interconnected phases (Fig. 5.2), each addressing a complementary dimension of stakeholder engagement with modelling. The first two sub-sections focus respectively on model creation and model interpretation, while the third summarises insights into lessons learnt.

5.3.1 Model Creation (RQ2.1)

Figure 5.3 illustrates the overall workflow of the model creation activity, highlighting the inputs, outputs, and collaborative steps involved in model development and in deriving

Figure 5.3: Detailed workflow for model creation

the lessons learnt. The activity began with the **development of modelling guidelines** by the requirements engineers, using as input the Case study 1 - Pecorino Toscano (introduced in Chapter 4.2). The modelling guidelines were then applied by the agronomists during the first round of modelling (**Modelling Round 1**). This phase used as input four cases selected from **LL reports (cases 1-4)**, each assigned to a different agronomist. The output consisted of initial versions of the models for all four cases (**Models v1 case 1-4**). Afterwards, the requirements engineers revised the cases (**Revision Round 1**, with input **Models v1 case 1-4**), then the two groups gathered for a **feedback** session that led to the production of the final versions of models for the four initial cases (**Models v-final case 1-4**). The activity continued with a second iteration: a second round of modelling (**Modelling Round 2**) was carried out by the agronomists using as input four additional **LL reports (cases 5-8)**, the resulting models were revised by the software engineers (**Revision Round 2**, with input **Models v1 case 5-8**) and discussed during a **feedback** session, leading to final versions (**Models v-final case 5-8**). Results and feedback led to the **lessons learnt**. All artefacts generated during this phase are available in the supplementary material of the paper [JSS] [138].

Input Data: LL Reports

Among the cases developed, eight were selected for inclusion in this validation. These cases concern technologies such as UAVs, IoT, image processing, and FMIS. They were chosen according to the agronomists' backgrounds and research interests and to ensure case and EU region diversity. Table 5.3 provides a summary of the cases.

Application of the Modelling Guidelines

The modelling activity was conducted in two rounds. The first round began on 14th June 2024, when the requirements engineers organised a two-hour remote meeting to

Table 5.3: Summary of LL reports used as input data for modelling

<p>Case 1—Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for grape harvesting</p> <p>The case examines an agroecological vineyard located in Italy. This 10-hectare farm, with 3.3 hectares dedicated to organic and biodynamic-certified vineyards, operates under strict fertiliser and pesticide limits. Climate change has reduced both yield and wine quality, challenging the farm's competitiveness. In response, the farm has adopted digital technologies, including UAVs and sensor data, to optimise grape harvesting based on quality. UAVs enable staged harvesting by processing higher-quality grapes first. New actors, such as technicians operating the UAVs and creating fertility and vigour maps, now play a role in the grape harvesting process. Maps accessible via mobile software assist the farmer in coordinating the harvest and improving grape selection, ultimately enhancing wine quality.</p>	
<p>Case 2—Ultra-High-Resolution RGB imagery for early detection of potential outbreaks</p> <p>The case concerns a Living Lab in Belgium focused on reducing chemical plant protection products in arable farming. The LL promotes targeted applications using ultra-high-resolution RGB images for early detection of pests, diseases, and weeds. The LL is currently testing a prototype that integrates multiple sensors, UAVs for image collection, robust AI models, and data processing software for accurate detection and mapping of potential outbreaks. A task map is then generated to support site-specific spraying.</p>	
<p>Case 3—Remote agricultural monitoring and advisory system (RAMAS)</p> <p>The case focuses on RAMAS, a Farm Management Information System developed within a Living Lab in North Macedonia to support efficient and data-driven farming. The system acts as a centralised hub and data repository, integrating advanced technologies such as IoT devices, UAVs, satellite imagery, and soil analysis reports to support the cultivation of barley, corn, hazelnuts, and vineyards. The platform can be accessed by farmers and advisors, improving communication, enhancing resource efficiency, and addressing the limitations of manual record-keeping.</p>	
<p>Case 4—Electronic milk meters and DSS for sheep breeding</p> <p>The case looks at digitalisation in sheep breeding for the production of Roquefort PDO cheese in a French Living Lab. The proposed solution integrates multiple technologies: a) electronic milk meters with flow sensors to monitor milk production; b) a self-moving automatic feed distribution system; and c) sensors for humidity and temperature monitoring. The aim is to support farmers in optimising feeding according to productivity and physiological attributes, providing a decision support system.</p>	
<p>Case 5—Grassland management using drone technology</p> <p>This case involves an Estonian Living Lab that uses drone technology to help farmers monitor grasslands and develop tailored management plans. The system integrates drones for aerial data collection, processing software to generate detailed maps, an open-access platform for viewing and interacting with spatial layers, and cloud storage. This solution addresses limitations of National Geospatial Services, such as low resolution and limited coverage, by providing farm-specific information for personalised seminatural grassland management planning.</p>	
<p>Case 6—Spraying drone systems</p> <p>The case concerns an experimental field at the Agricultural University of Athens, where a Living Lab evaluates drone-based spraying systems. The main goal is to assess spray quality and spray drift under different operational conditions. Field trials involve UAVs applying treatments in vineyards while testing variations in flight altitude and speed to determine their influence on spray distribution and off-target movement.</p>	
<p>Case 7—Greenhouse management using Plataforma iVeg</p> <p>This case focuses on a Living Lab in Almería, Spain, evaluating Plataforma iVeg, a management and decision-support system for small family-run greenhouse businesses. The platform serves as a unified data management tool, integrating information from third-party datasets and multiple existing market technologies. It enhances interoperability by standardising data formats and providing users with an integrated view of greenhouse operations.</p>	
<p>Case 8—Data interoperability for pig farm management</p> <p>The case refers to the French Living Lab LIT Ouesterel, which is testing PigLink, a digital platform designed to improve data sharing and interoperability in pig farming. The system addresses inefficiencies such as fragmented management systems and repeated manual data entry by using standardised web APIs, connected equipment, and farm management software. The platform supports dashboards for monitoring breeding indicators and enables benchmarking of animal health, welfare, and productivity across farms.</p>	

Table 5.4: Summary of data collection, modelling and revision. Abbreviations: Av = average, I = interview, FG = focus group, VIS = visit, WS = workshop, res. = researcher, adv. = advisor, farm. = farmer, inst. = institution, prod. = producer, tech. = technology provider, pol. = policymaker, cus. = customer

Case	Data collection	Models	Revision
1	Report: 14pp Stakeholders: 20 (res., farm., tech., cus.) Activities: I (7), VIS (7)	iStar: 44 el. UML: 19 el. BPMN 72 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 3 UML: Err. 0; Warn. 4 BPMN: Err. 1; Warn. 2
2	Report: 16pp Stakeholders: 12 (farm., tech., pol., adv.) Activities: I (6), FG (1), VIS (4), WS (1), D (2)	iStar: 123 el. UML: 63 el. BPMN 402 el.	iStar: Err. 3; Warn. 7 UML: Err. 1; Warn. 1 BPMN: Err. 2; Warn. 4
3	Report: 16pp Stakeholders: 12 (res., adv., farm., tech., pol.) Activities: I (1), FG (4), VIS (1), WS (1), M (3)	iStar: 43 el. UML: 24 el. BPMN 50 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 6 UML: Err. 1; Warn. 4 BPMN: Err. 1; Warn. 3
4	Report: 17pp Stakeholders: 22 (res., adv., farm., inst., prod., tech) Activities: I (3), FG (2), VIS (1)	iStar: 86 el. UML: 30 el. BPMN 130 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 7 UML: Err. 1; Warn. 4 BPMN: Err. 1; Warn. 2
5	Report: 23pp Stakeholders: 20 (res., adv., farm., tech) Activities: I (4), FG (3), VIS (6), WS (1)	iStar: 58 el. UML: 28 el. BPMN 168 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 1 UML: Err. 2; Warn. 1 BPMN: Err. 2; Warn. 1
6	Report: 31pp Stakeholders: 12 (res., adv., farm., tech., pol.) Activities: FG (2), WS (1), M (1)	iStar: 45 el. UML: 34 el. BPMN 207 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 1 UML: Err. 0; Warn. 2 BPMN: Err. 1; Warn. 2
7	Report: 14pp Stakeholders: 22 (res., adv., farm., inst., tech.) Activities: I (1), FG (1), VIS (1), WS (1), M (4)	iStar: 63 el. UML: 26 el. BPMN 188 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 1 UML: Err. 0; Warn. 1 BPMN: Err. 1; Warn. 2
8	Report: 17pp Stakeholders: 65 (res., adv., farm., inst., cus., prod., tech., gov.) Activities: I (2), FG (1), VIS (3)	iStar: 65 el. UML: 36 el. BPMN 144 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 1 UML: Err. 0; Warn. 1 BPMN: Err. 0; Warn. 3
Av.	Report: 19pp Stakeholders: 24 Activities: I (3.5), FG (2), VIS (3), WS (0.5)	iStar: 66 el. UML: 33 el. BPMN 170 el.	iStar: Err. 1; Warn. 3 UML: Err. 1; Warn. 2 BPMN: Err. 1; Warn. 2

present the guidelines to the agronomists, assign them a LL report as modelling case, and agree on a timeline. The agronomists used the guidelines to produce the models based on the reports. The models were then revised by the requirements engineers for syntactic errors—the models were subsequently validated for completeness with the LL coordinators in focus groups, and the outcomes of this validation will be reported in future work. Feedback meetings were held on 5th July and 11th October 2024, involving all participants who discussed the models and exchanged viewpoints on their experiences. This concluded the first round of modelling. Joint writing sessions were then organised to summarise the lessons learnt. The second round of modelling began on 24th January 2025, with the assignment of a second case to the agronomists. As in the previous round, the agronomists developed new models, and the requirements engineers revised them. A final discussion meeting was held on 14th March 2025. The round concluded with writing sessions in April, May and June 2025 for finalising the lessons learnt, ensuring that insights from both iterations were consolidated.

Results

Table 5.4 summarises information on the data collection and presents results from modelling and revision activities. Cases 1-4 refer to the first round of modelling, while cases 5-8 to the second. The reports serving as input data for model creation were generated

by LL coordinators, who engaged with LL stakeholders through multiple data collection activities, such as interviews, focus groups, and workshops. This phase involved approximately 200 stakeholders. The models were quite detailed and extensive, with an average of 66 elements for iStar, 33 for UML, and 170 for BPMN. The revision distinguished between errors (i.e., formal syntactic and semantic mistakes diverging from the standard of the notations, e.g., use of the wrong type of symbols) and warnings (i.e., less severe issues associated with stylistic reasons, e.g., overlapping lines). Table 5.4, col. Revision, reports unique instances of these issues—each type of systematic error is counted once. We notice that these are limited, with only 1 to 3 types of errors per diagram, and an average of 1 error across all cases. Notably, both errors and warnings decreased in the second iteration, with errors remaining between 0 and 1, and no more than 3 warnings.

5.3.2 Answer to RQ2.1: *To what extent are domain experts, who are not RE-specialists, able to model requirements in their specific domain?*

The artefacts produced by the agronomists indicate that domain experts without prior RE experience were able to apply the modelling approach effectively, using the constructs proposed by the procedure. The expert revision confirmed that the models were syntactically correct, with only a few formal errors and minor stylistic warnings. These findings show that non-RE specialists can effectively model requirements when they are supported by a structured modelling procedure.

5.3.3 Model Interpretation (RQ2.2)

The *model interpretation* phase of the validation study took place in the context of the CODECS second-year general assembly, held online on 12th December 2024. The activity was designed by the requirements engineers, who met in multiple internal meetings in the weeks preceding the plenary to define objectives, constraints, structure and contents, and technical setup. In the days leading up to the plenary, the team finalised the materials and performed a dry run of the whole session.

The session was structured to account for project constraints, including the strict agenda with limited time and multiple work packages to present, the online format, and the interdisciplinary audience.

Figure 5.4 outlines the overall activity, highlighting the feedback-collection steps carried out within both a plenary and a post-plenary session. One case produced in RQ1 was selected as input (**Selected case**). In the plenary session, a **quiz** was first conducted to introduce the notations and verify the understanding of the models (cf. Section 5.3.3). Afterwards, participants individually explored the models and answered two **open-ended questions** (cf. Section 5.3.3). The post-plenary session built upon the results of the plenary. The feedback collected was analysed to derive statements which were retrospectively mapped to the TAM dimensions (**TAM-based statements PEOU - PU - ITU**), which were subsequently incorporated into the **survey** (cf. Section 5.3.3). From the results and feedback, findings were obtained that contribute to the **lessons learnt**. Data and results are available in the repository of paper [JSS] [138].

Figure 5.4: Detailed workflow for model interpretation

Plenary Validation of Models

The plenary session consisted of an interactive activity on Mentimeter that lasted 50 minutes in total. The audience was divided into two breakout rooms, Room 1 and Room 2, with 28 and 32 participants, respectively. The allocation to rooms was randomised by the platform used to host the online meeting (Microsoft Teams). Each breakout room was managed by a presenter supported by a moderator. All facilitators were authors of the paper [JSS]. In Room 1, the 1st author (i.e., the author of the thesis) presented with the 5th author moderating, while in Room 2, the 2nd author presented with the 4th moderating.

The case assessed during the session was Case 2 - Agrifood technology (the case corresponds to *Case 2 - Ultra-High-Resolution RGB imagery for early detection of potential outbreaks*, presented in Section 5.3.1), which had been selected from the set of cases developed by the agronomists. The models are available in Annex 6 [130]. The rationale for this choice is multiple: first, to concentrate the audience on the same case; second, this case was newly developed and had not been previously disseminated, thus controlling for prior familiarity and standardising respondents' baseline knowledge¹.

Quiz on Understandability The quiz lasted 25 minutes. Following an active learning approach [69], the presenters guided attendees through the questions, while the moderator facilitated real-time polling. The presenters began by showing a legend, followed by a slide containing the model and the questions. After a question was answered, the solution was given before moving to the next question. To support this activity, a simplified version of the models—with views optimised to fit on a slide and remain readable without zooming—was specifically prepared.

Questions Ten questions were asked: three for each notation, plus an additional question addressing the BPMN overlap (cf. Fig. 4.2c). Table 5.5 outlines the questions with associated objectives. The question types were multiple choice, with a maximum of three options, or true/false, and were designed to verify several aspects related to the understandability of the models. Although intentionally designed to be accessible for an entry-level audience, the quiz items targeted granular aspects, such as interpreting associations or aggregations in UML class diagrams, associating goals to actors in iStar, and tracing start, end points, and flows in BPMN. For example, one question (cf. Q9

¹The sole exception concerned the coordinator of the LL, who had previously reviewed the models and was therefore instructed not to take part in the quiz

Table 5.5: Overview of plenary quiz questions.

Question	Model	Text	Type	Objective
Q1	UML	Who are the actors?	multiple choice	Identify actors across classes
Q2	UML	The farmer is the only actor who accesses forecast from the weather service	true/false	Comprehend associations
Q3	UML	Which digital technologies are part of the ultra high resolution RGB imagery system?	multiple choice	Comprehend aggregations
Q4	iStar	Which are the farmer's tasks?	multiple choice	Identify tasks
Q5	iStar	The drone pilot's goal is to:	multiple choice	Identify goals
Q6	iStar	Who has the goal to minimise the plant protection products (PPPs) usage?	multiple choice	Associate goals to the corresponding actors
Q7	BPMN	What are the tasks performed by the farmer?	multiple choice	Associate tasks to the corresponding actor
Q8	BPMN	The VRA sprayer is used only in case of pest potential outbreak	true/false	Comprehend exclusive gateways
Q9	BPMN	Which process flow is correct?	multiple choice	Comprehend process flow
Q10	BPMN	Which of the following statements is correct?	multiple choice	Comprehend process change

in Table 5.5) asked to indicate the correct process flow depicted in the process model in BPMN by choosing between alternative descriptions. This required participants to focus on the model and analyse it by interpreting the position of tasks and the flows of information exchanged among the actors.

Open-ended questions After the quiz, participants accessed a board on MIRO with the complete case and autonomously analysed the models for 10 minutes. Then, the group engaged in a 15-minute open-ended discussion by answering two additional questions on Mentimeter. Responses consisted of brief, anonymous comments displayed in real time by the moderator.

Questions The following open-ended questions (OQs) were asked:

- *OQ-1: What were the difficulties encountered in reading the models?* OQ-1 asks participants to reflect on the difficulties they had just experienced while interpreting the notations.
- *OQ-2: How would you use these models for?* OQ-2 invites participants to indicate, according to their personal profile and background, how they would envision using the models in their own work.

The questions were designed to maximise feedback within the limited time and large audience. We deliberately used stakeholder-oriented prompts that required no conceptual explanation or sustained focus. Subsequent analysis enabled us to map the responses to more granular TAM-based dimensions, namely PU, PEOU, and ITU.

Results from the Plenary Session

In this section, we present the main results of the plenary interactive session. Further discussion of this phase is provided in the lessons learnt.

Figure 5.5: Quiz results

Results from the Quiz To provide a clearer overview of the quiz results, we present data aggregated across both breakout rooms. The participation rate, calculated as the proportion of answers out of the 60 participants in the session, ranged between 53% and 62%, with distribution of participation similar across the three notations, and no major differences between questions.

Figure 5.5a presents the results aggregated by modelling language, distinguishing the proportion of correct and incorrect answers. UML achieved the highest proportion of correct responses at 90%, while BPMN and iStar followed with 82% and 79%, respectively.

Figure 5.5b details the results per question, highlighting variability across items within each modelling language. For UML, correctness ranged from 71% to 100%, for iStar from 70% to 88%, and for BPMN from 72% to 94%.

Overall, results show that participants performed well, with an overall average of 84% correct responses across the three model types, individual scores consistently above 70%, and satisfactory participation rates.

Results from the Open-ended Questions A total of 65 responses to the open-ended questions were collected, with 35 in the first question and 30 in the second question.

Answers were analysed by means of a thematic analysis (cf. Sec. 5.1.1). Most of the emerging themes informed the structuring of the subsequent survey, serving as triggers for the design of its question statements, while only a minority were excluded when judged too domain-specific or beyond the scope of the analysis.

Table 5.6: Themes extracted from open-ended questions and corresponding survey statements

Theme		Statement	
t1	Structure model easy	+	PEOU-1 The structure model is easy to understand
			PEOU-2 The structure model can be used with farmers
t2	Goal model easy	+	PEOU-3 The goal model is easy to understand
			PEOU-4 The goal model can be used with farmers
t3	Training useful	+	PEOU-5 The training helped to clarify the models
t4	Legend useful	+	PEOU-6 The legend is sufficient to understand the models
t5	Difficulties for farmers	-	PEOU-7 Farmers would find the models difficult to understand
t6	Activity model complex	-	PEOU-8 The activity model is the hardest to understand
			PEOU-9 The activity model is more oriented to researchers
t7	Training needed	o	PEOU-10 A training with a facilitator is essential to understand the models
t8	Legend needed	o	PEOU-11 The legend is necessary to understand the models
t9	More colour code needed	o	PEOU-12 More colour coding could improve the models understandability
t10	Understanding digitalisation processes	+	PU-1 The models can be applied in different digitalisation contexts
			ITU-1 I would use the models to identify process changes
t11	Basis for future tool development	+	PU-2 The models are useful to develop technologies tailored to farmers' needs
t12	Instruments for socio-economic analysis	+	PU-3 The activity model is helpful as a preliminary tool for assessing costs and benefits
			PU-4 The models can support decision making
			PU-5 The models are useful to support LCA (life cycle assessment)
			PU-6 The models are useful to understand relationships among actors
			ITU-2 I would use the models to compare different living labs
t13	Communication with stakeholders	+	ITU-3 I would not use the models with farmers
			ITU-4 I would use the models with advisors
			ITU-5 I would use the models with technology providers
			ITU-6 I would use the models with different stakeholders

Table 5.6 presents 13 selected themes (t1-t13) and the associated survey statements. The polarity of each theme is indicated by a plus (+) or minus (-), denoting whether it was interpreted as expressing positive or negative feedback. Neutrality is indicated with zero (o). The themes t1-t9 were derived from the first question, leading to the formulation of statements PEOU-1 to PEOU-12. Themes t10-t13 concern the second question, leading to the formulation of statements PU-1 to PU-6 and ITU-1 to ITU-6. The correspondence between themes and survey statements is not one-to-one. Some themes resulted in multiple statements, as deemed necessary to capture granular aspects of participants' views and to scaffold contrasting opinions emerging from the comments. We refer the reader to Section 5.3.3 for a description of the survey statements and the results.

The themes are presented below, along with illustrative quotes from participants' comments.

Answers to OQ-1 *What were the difficulties encountered in reading the models?*

Comments to the first question reflected a generally positive perception of the models. Several participants reported no difficulties, describing the notations as “clear” or “complex but understandable”. Among the positive themes, the *structure model easy* (t1) and the *goal model easy* (t2) emerged, with the UML and iStar viewed as easier to grasp, with one respondent explicitly noting that “the structure model [i.e., the domain model] and goal model are suitable for use with farmers”. This perception should be read in light of the relatively streamlined goal-modelling notation adopted in PoMeLO, and

not as a general comparison between the modelling notations. *Training useful* (t₃) also emerged, as reflected in comments such as “after the training, no particular difficulties encountered”. The *legend useful* (t₄) was further mentioned as an element that facilitated understanding, with one commenting: “Having the legend on the side helps a lot and then there are no difficulties for reading the models”.

Negative themes arose regarding BPMN, particularly with *activity model complex* (t₆). Comments included phrases like “more for scientists”, “too detailed”, and “farmers rapidly lose interest—too many arrows and bubbles”. More broadly, several remarks underlined the *difficulties for farmers* (t₅) in engaging with the notations.

Beyond positive and negative comments, several responses led to neutral themes, providing constructive feedback to improve the overall approach. Some participants emphasised the importance of *training needed* (t₇) to become familiar with the notations. In addition, *legend needed* (t₈) was regarded as essential for interpretation, while *more colour code needed* (t₉) was suggested to further enhance readability.

Answers to OQ-2 *How would you use these models for?*

Answers to the second question indicated that the models were primarily perceived as tools for *understanding digitalisation processes* (t₁₀): “to have a more clear idea of the transformative process linked to digitalisation”.

The significance of the models as a *basis for future tool development* (t₁₁), particularly for creating technologies that meet farmers’ needs, was also recognised: “To develop technologies tailored to farmers’ needs”.

Moreover, the models were viewed as analytical tools, with participants commenting on their potential as *instruments for socio-economic analysis* (t₁₂), for decision-making support and understanding strategies adopted by practitioners: “to understand decision making of farmers”. The models were also proposed in connection with analytical frameworks, such as life cycle assessment, or techniques such as digital twins: “Goal: to understand the multiple goals. Structure [i.e., the domain model]: to help us in Life Cycle Assessment LCA. Modelling activity: to build digital twins”.

Finally, regarding a possible use for *communication with stakeholders* (t₁₃), some comments were more sceptical about direct interaction with farmers: “not [for use] with farmers, but rather for interactions between advisors and technology designers.”

Post Plenary Survey The survey was distributed to participants to validate or challenge the insights gathered in the plenary session.

The questions ask to rate 24 statements using a 5-point Likert scale. The “Statement” column in Table 5.6 contains the statements associated with TAM dimensions. It includes 12 items related to PEOU (PEOU-1 to PEOU-12), addressing aspects such as ease of use of the different notations for various user groups, the role of training and facilitation, and the importance of visual aids like legends and colour coding. Additionally, there are 6 items focusing on PU (PU-1 to PU-6), covering the models applicability across digitalisation contexts, their value in supporting technology development, and their use in multiple socio-economic analyses. Finally, 6 items focus on ITU (ITU-1 to ITU-6), evaluating the willingness to adopt the models for interaction with different stakeholders, as well as for LL comparison and assessment of digitalisation.

In addition, a first set of questions covering demographics, professional background, and prior modelling experience was included, as well as a final question allowing for

Figure 5.6: TAM average values

additional open-ended comments.

Results from Survey The survey was administered to participants after the plenary via an online questionnaire distributed through Google Forms. In total, 19 participants responded.

The following demographic information were collected: with respect to gender, participants included both male and female respondents (47% female, 53% male); regarding age, most participants fell within the 30–39 and 40–49 year ranges, with fewer in the under 30 or 50+ ranges; in terms of professional background, the group comprised primarily researchers and LL coordinators (68%), alongside advisors and other stakeholders (32%); educational backgrounds were distributed across Agronomy (42%), Economics (26%), Social sciences (21%), and Agritech (11%).

Regarding previous experience with modelling notations, participants reported basic familiarity, mainly acquired through previous activities in CODECS, with only a minority reporting more advanced expertise. Among the three languages, UML class diagrams were the most familiar, while BPMN models were the least familiar.

Figure 5.6 presents the aggregated TAM results showing that participants perceived the models as moderately easy to use ($PEOU \approx 3.3$), while they expressed a higher level of perceived usefulness ($PU \approx 3.8$). The intention to use ($ITU \approx 3.5$) the models is mostly positive. Since 3 indicates neutrality, all three aggregated scores exceed the neutral point, showing a generally positive perception across the three TAM dimensions, albeit without markedly high values.

PEOU - Perceived Ease of Use

Results related to PEOU are shown in 5.7. The figures display the distribution of responses to all PEOU items, ranked by level of agreement.

Figure 5.7a presents the positive statements (PEOU-1 to PEOU-6). Among the six items rated, the highest level of agreement was observed for PEOU-5 and PEOU-6, indicating that brief training improved understandability and that the legend was sufficient for reading the models. Statements related to the understandability of single models,

(a) Positive statements on PEOU

(b) Negative and neutral statements on PEOU

Figure 5.7: Survey results for PEOU statements ranked by agreement score

such as PEOU-4, PEOU-1 and PEOU-3, were still agreed by the majority of respondents, although the agreement was less strong. In contrast, low levels of agreement emerged for PEOU-2, which relates to the understandability of the structure model for practitioners—specifically farmers, leading to a higher proportion of neutral or critical responses.

Figure 5.7b presents the negative or neutral statements (PEOU-7 to PEOU-12). The strongest agreement was obtained by PEOU-11 and PEOU-7, highlighting the need for a legend for understanding the models and that farmers would face interpretation challenges. Moderated levels of agreement were also expressed for PEOU-9, highlighting that the activity model is indicated for an academically trained audience; PEOU-10, in-

dicating the need for training; and PEOU-12, remarking the need for more colour coding to understand the models. In contrast, lower agreement was found for PEOU-8, indicating differing opinions about the effective complexity of the activity model.

PU - Perceived Usefulness

Figure 5.8 shows the agreement rate for statements PU-1 to PU-6 ranked by agreement rate: In this case, no distinction was required between positive and negative statements, as participants provided positive feedback regarding this dimension during the plenary session. The agreement was particularly high the statements related to using the models for analysing actors' strategic relationships (PU-6), and using the models in various digitalisation-related contexts (PU-1), both above 90%. Low levels of agreement—although still above 50%—were found in the statement related to the use of models for LCA (PU-3).

ITU - Intention to Use

Figure 5.9 displays the distribution of responses ranked by level of agreement to statements from ITU-1 to ITU-6, related to the intention to use the models for comparing LLs, for assessing digitalisation and with different stakeholder groups. The highest levels of agreement were observed for ITU-4 and ITU-5, indicating the respondents would use the models more likely with advisors and technology providers, respectively. Both statements received 84% agreement from participants. High agreement rates were obtained by ITU-1 and ITU-6, indicating the willingness to employ the models for identifying process change and with multiple stakeholder profiles. More neutral and critical responses were recorded in ITU-2 and ITU-3, indicating divergent attitudes towards using the models for LL comparison and directly with farmers.

Open-ended comments Seven participants provided free-text remarks in the final question. The majority expressed *appreciation for the explanatory session*, which was

Figure 5.8: Statements on PU ranked by agreement

Figure 5.9: Statements on ITU ranked by agreement

considered a helpful introduction to the diagrams. At the same time, multiple respondents highlighted that the *models would be difficult to interpret without facilitation*, especially for farmers, and suggested to *adopting icons or illustrations to maximise understanding*. This feedback reinforces the results emerging from the quantitative responses.

5.3.4 Answer to RQ2.2: To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO when exposed to a case external to their own living lab?

Results indicated a generally positive level of acceptance of models created with PoMeLO when stakeholders are exposed to a case external to their own LL, across all three TAM dimensions: the models were considered understandable (PEOU), useful (PU), and potentially usable in practice (ITU), albeit with some conditions related to audience and facilitation.

Regarding PEOU, participants reported no major difficulties and no noticeable differences across the notations. However, they recognised the benefits of receiving a brief training and having a legend for improving comprehension. This perception was further confirmed by results from the quiz conducted in the model interpretation phase (cf. 5.3.3), where stakeholders were able to interpret all three model types—UML, iStar, and BPMN—successfully, with UML class diagrams being the most readily understood. Overall, while no particular concerns would be expected when discussing the models with a research-oriented audience or with technical profiles, interpretation challenges—especially for UML and BPMN—might emerge in practice-related settings, such as at the farm level. In this regard, the comparatively positive perception of iStar may also be linked to the relatively streamlined goal-modelling notation adopted in PoMeLO. This suggests that non-RE specialists can interpret semi-formal models, although preliminary refinement and training on the notations may be needed, tailored to the intended use and audience.

Regarding PU, the LL stakeholders found the models useful and, after interacting with them, suggested a range of digitalisation-related uses. In particular, the models were seen as valuable for strategic analysis, such as supporting decision-making and clari-

fying relationships among actors, and for implementation purposes, such as informing technological development.

Regarding ITU, the LL stakeholders demonstrated a generally positive intention to use the models in LL activities. They confirmed their intent to apply the models for the primary intended use in the project—identifying process change. Moreover, they expressed interest in using the models in multi-stakeholder contexts, and with practitioners, particularly with advisors and technology providers. However, they had more reservations about using them for direct communication with farmers and for LL comparison.

5.3.5 Lessons Learnt

This sub-section concludes the validation activity by outlining the insights derived from the overall experience, presented as a set of 15 lessons learnt.

The lessons learnt reflect the viewpoints of the requirements engineers and agronomists involved in model creation and are informed by the outcomes of model interpretation. Their derivation followed a structured process conducted through several group meetings and individual sessions. The teams first engaged in debriefing meetings to identify emerging insights, followed by the drafting of preliminary lesson statements. These drafts were iteratively refined using a shared document, where team members discussed and complemented the lessons. Finalisation occurred through joint writing sessions. Since these individuals are also the authors of the paper [JSS], we do not provide specific quotations from the discussions. Instead, we present the team's synthesised and collectively agreed-upon reflections.

Figure 5.10 contains an overview of the lessons categorised in topics. Under the topic *Learning to model*, lessons L1-L3 emerged about the kinds of support end users require, the learning approaches, and the progressive familiarity gained through practice. Under the topic *Modelling strategies*, lessons L4-L6 are presented, highlighting how domain expertise can compensate for incomplete information, how peer discussion supports clarification, and how visual effectiveness is often prioritised over formality. The topic *Challenges encountered* groups lessons L7-L9 concerning the perceived difficulty of abstraction, modelling as a bias-prone activity, and the demand for easy-to-use and open-source modelling tools. The topic *Understandability of notations and representations* brings together lessons L10-L12, reporting how end users can achieve a shared understanding by interpreting semi-formal notations, the specific challenges posed by each notation, and the trade-off derived from terminological choices. Finally, the *Utility of the modelling approach* category introduces L13-L15, which address the perceived usefulness of the modelling approach within the specific context of agricultural digitalisation and LLs, as well as the effort involved in manual modelling as a foundation for potential future automation.

Learning to model

L1 – Practice-oriented guidelines enable end users to model complex requirements The agronomists received only an initial illustration of the modelling guidelines, and then they were given the guideline document. The agronomists confirmed that

Figure 5.10: Overview of the lessons learnt categorised in topics

they were able to follow the instructions provided without encountering major obstacles. They remarked on the effectiveness of the guidelines, especially for their practice-oriented structure, and the presence of examples. The document is seen as beneficial for understanding the objective of the activity, the principles of the languages, and the specific steps for systematically creating the diagrams². The success of the experience is highlighted by the complexity of the models produced in terms of the number of elements, and by the limited number of errors. On the other hand, the agronomists agree that a preliminary hands-on session under the guidance of the requirements engineers could have helped them reduce the learning effort.

💡 This lesson underscores end-user ability in requirements modelling and formal accuracy even in complex socio-technical contexts like agricultural LLs. It highlights that the practice-oriented guidelines proposed, which are arguably simple and do not require a deep knowledge of the languages, can lead to successful modelling.

L2 – End users have different learning approaches The agronomists shared their strategies for addressing the modelling task. While they used the modelling guidelines as a primary reference, they adopted different approaches according to their learning preferences and attitudes: some relied solely on the documentation following a learning-by-doing method and waiting for the revision by the requirements engineers; others supplemented the guidelines with additional explanations of the notations, such as the

²This opinion may be affected by the Hawthorne effect, as the authors of the paper (cf. paper [JSS]) are also those who developed the guidelines, and the agronomists may not feel comfortable in expressing negative judgments. However, they are well aware that this activity is oriented to validate the approach and that negative opinions can be beneficial to improve it.

video tutorials on BPMN offered by the Camunda platform, also to understand more theoretical principles behind the modelling languages. This is in line with observations from Felder [68], who emphasises that aligning teaching methods (e.g., methodology-oriented, practice-oriented) with learning styles (e.g., active vs reflective, sequential vs global) can improve learners' engagement and comprehension.

💡 By supporting diverse learning methods, we can help end users effectively perform the modelling task. This highlights the need for adaptable training resources that complement the modelling guidelines.

L3 – Modelling proficiency improves with practice The agronomists reported that the second round of modelling was easier with increased confidence in applying the notations. The learning effect was evident across all modelling languages, as shown by the reduced number of errors across cases 5–8, particularly in iStar and UML models, which showed consistently low or zero errors (cf. Table 5.4, col. Revision). The modellers reported that the need to consult the guidelines decreased, as they had become familiar with the notations. However, some observed that the interval between sessions made it necessary to review the instructions, especially for BPMN, given the large number of elements that are not easy to remember. Others mentioned that they also referred to the documentation for learning features they had missed in the first round. This is in line with Moody's theory [152], which argues that notations with large symbol sets and low semantic transparency increase the cognitive effort required for learning and recall.

💡 Modelling becomes easier with familiarity of the notations and practice, although occasional reference to the documentation remains to recall specific symbols and learn new constructs.

Modelling strategies

L4 – Domain expertise can fill the gaps of incomplete information elicitation Participants highlighted that their background in agronomy helped them understand the reports from the LLs and fill in the gaps where information was missing or inconsistent. Challenges primarily arose while extracting granular information for the BPMN models. Since the number of stakeholders involved in the elicitation activities was substantially high, incompleteness in the reports may be due to tacit knowledge issues, i.e., the LL coordinators did not include information that was assumed to be obvious, given their knowledge of the LL. Furthermore, LL coordinators complained about the fine-grained level of detail required by the reporting templates, which was, however, deemed necessary to achieve meaningful and complete diagrams. This is in line with previous research highlighting the difficulty in reaching clarity and understanding in elicitation interviews [72] with additional challenges in the agricultural domain [60, 90]. Other approaches focus on technology-intensive crowd RE techniques to enhance data collection, e.g., with mobile apps for farmers [90]. In our case, the gaps were filled by the domain expertise of the modellers—a goal that the requirements engineers involved

admit they could not have achieved. Although this does not rule out further validation with stakeholders, the involvement of domain experts can speed up the process of reaching a consensus on the requirements. Our contribution aligns with Störrle's [208] insights, highlighting the positive effects of empowering domain experts in participatory modelling.

💡 Domain expertise is crucial when modelling in specific technical fields, as someone with less relevant knowledge may struggle to fill the somewhat inevitable gaps in the elicited requirements.

L5 – End users can resolve doubts by resorting to their peers The agronomists decided to work autonomously rather than in joint work sessions. However, whenever they faced challenges—whether in interpreting particular aspects of the reports or in utilising the modelling tools—they turned to peers who could complement their specific knowledge with additional viewpoints and expertise. This highlights that establishing a team of peers is particularly useful for modelling. As noticed by Abrahão et al. [11], collaborative modelling tools could further enhance modelling speed and accuracy.

💡 Successful modelling benefits from teamwork, where different perspectives, skills, and insights are integrated to address gaps in knowledge and ensure a comprehensive understanding.

L6 – End users prioritise visual effectiveness over formality From the evaluation of the models, a general formal accuracy was observed, albeit the representations contained some recurrent issues (cf. Table 5.4, col. Revision). These included conceptual errors in the use of elements of the notations, element redundancy or cohesion, verbosity and use of non-standard names and styles. Notably, the models were delivered without end users seeking clarification from the requirements engineers or expressing doubts about the outcome. During the follow-up discussion, the agronomists confirmed that they were sometimes aware of the deviations and provided different motivations, e.g., personal preferences and use of symbols that were considered more aesthetically appropriate, although semantically incorrect. They also highlighted that they were first interested in expressing their understanding in the most visually effective way, and secondarily to adhere to the formal rules. The agronomists also remarked that relying on the final revision by requirements engineers for the technical soundness of the models enhanced their confidence in modelling.

💡 End users are not afraid of making mistakes, prioritising effective visualisation over formal correctness. This suggests that iterations with requirements engineers are necessary to balance expressiveness with formality.

Challenges encountered

L7 – Abstraction is regarded as the most challenging task The agronomists generally found the modelling activity to be time-consuming, requiring an average of 12

hours, spread across multiple sessions with breaks. Although the guidelines allowed them to speed up the practical tasks, they declared that the most challenging part of modelling is related to interpretation and abstraction, consisting of making clear-cut choices about relevant information and finding the right words to name elements in the diagrams. They agree that this activity requires mental effort and flexibility, necessitating constant revision to achieve coherence in the representation. Abstraction is a key computational thinking skill [230]; it often requires specific training and experience, which may not traditionally be part of an agronomist's background.

💡 While practical aspects of model creation can be supported with guidelines and tools, the task of abstracting information is the most challenging demanding cognitive effort and computational thinking skills.

L8 – The modeller can introduce bias, thereby affecting the resulting model

When reflecting on the modelling practice, the team recognised that the activity itself was prone to bias. The modellers identified several points where personal opinions and interpretive choices could influence the representations, such as the selection of elements from the reports, naming, and positioning. This tendency emerged across all three types of models, affecting how the process could ultimately be perceived. This observation aligns with phenomena discussed in the literature, where cognitive biases such as confirmation, anchoring, or representativeness [151] are recognised as influencing requirements elicitation [235]. In our case, the agronomists suggested validation with peers and stakeholders as the most effective mitigation strategy to foster more balanced and collectively grounded representations.

💡 Models may contain bias due to the modeller's flexibility in data selection and interpretation. Validation with peers and stakeholders helps achieve more balanced representations.

L9 – End users demand easy-to-use and open-source modelling tools The agronomists reported that, when using the suggested tools and templates for drawing diagrams, they encountered obstacles at various levels. The process involved downloading and configuring various general-purpose tools, some of which were difficult to use, e.g., StarUML. Furthermore, there were limitations with the free versions and not all tools provided the comprehensive support needed to fully implement the procedure, e.g., for BPMN overlaps. In response to these challenges, an agronomist opted to use a licensed drawing tool that he was more familiar with—i.e., PowerPoint. In the second round of modelling, some agronomists adopted alternative tools—i.e., draw.io, to overcome previous limitations. Similar challenges were also experienced in the study by Störrle [208] that proposed the use of PowerPoint for early modelling with domain experts. Moreover, previous research [11] highlighted the need to improve the user experience of modelling tools for diverse user groups. On the other hand, this experience highlights the adaptability of the proposed procedure to different tools, even those not specialised in modelling.

💡 The modelling procedure is sufficiently flexible to be implemented with different tools. However, modelling platforms should be open and adaptable to users with different skills. This would reduce technical barriers and better support end users in focusing on the modelling task.

Understandability of notations and representations

L10 – Visual models expressed in semi-formal notations support shared understanding Although tailored for remote plenary context, the models presented to the LL stakeholders were sufficiently detailed, incorporating notation-specific constructs. Results from the quiz show that participants were generally able to interpret them correctly (cf. Sec. 5.3.3), thus gaining a shared understanding of the complex socio-technical process of transformation under analysis. The subsequent feedback session proved the acceptance of the models and the stakeholders' engagement towards the session, strengthened by the direct relevance of the representations to their research and professional interests. Overall, this experience outlines the potential of semi-formal notations as tools for supporting social modelling practices [221] such as participatory decision analysis, where models act as boundary objects to structure dialogue and support joint decisions among diverse stakeholders.

💡 End users can successfully interact with visual models expressed in semi-formal notations. Furthermore, these representations contribute to shared understanding and foster plenary debates, especially when these are applied within the stakeholders' specific areas of interest.

L11 – Every notation brings its own set of challenges The end users interacted with three modelling languages—UML, iStar, and BPMN. Based on the experience of the modellers, some found iStar diagrams difficult to create and read, particularly due to the non-linear connections and the need for careful interpretation of goals and dependencies. Others considered UML models complex to create, especially to ensure lines did not overlap when managing relations. BPMN models offered a contrasting experience: easier to *read* due to their straightforward, procedural flow, but harder to *create* because of the inherent complexity of agricultural processes and the large number of notation elements. Divergent perceptions also emerged in responses to the post-plenary survey, where the questions on perceived ease of use received the most mixed responses, confirming that user feedback was not uniform and perception is inherently subjective (cf. Figure 5.8). Further evidence from the quiz offers insights into which notations challenged users the most. The iStar models resulted in the highest number of incorrect answers (21%), followed by BPMN (18%), while UML showed fewer errors (10%). However, the items with the highest error rate (around 30%) were observed across all three notations, indicating that each language can pose specific challenges (cf. Figure 5.5).

💡 There is no preferred modelling language by end users. Each notation has a different objective and brings its own set of challenges which are perceived differently.

L12 - Terminological choices influence the understandability of models by diverse audiences The agronomists reported that while the guidelines effectively supported the graphical aspects of the models, they felt less assisted in managing the textual information. This lack of guidance resulted in uncertainty, especially when the report included information at varying levels of detail or mixed technical jargon. Consequently, the modellers had to make clear decisions about which terms to include in the labels or whether to use explanatory notes. These choices were made with consideration for the final destination of the models and the intended audience.

Terminological choices become crucial in model creation, frequently leading to trade-offs: whether to employ more general vocabulary to ensure broader interpretability or more specific terms to capture the precise meaning of concepts within the domain. This is in line with Moody's notion of cognitive effectiveness [152] and further supported by empirical findings from Mendling et al. [148], highlighting that linguistic decisions can significantly affect how easily modelling languages are interpreted by stakeholders.

💡 Lexical choices shape how easily modelling languages can be interpreted by a broad range of stakeholders. The modeller has to keep in mind the final destination of the models when deciding on the wording.

Utility of the modelling approach

L13 – Requirements modelling helps to see the wide picture of agricultural digitalisation The agronomists agree that the modelling activity helped them to better understand the connections among digital technologies, social actors, and environmental resources. The models make clearer the socio-technical nature of digital transformation and its impacts in terms of activities, actors, and resources to be added or removed from agricultural processes because of the adoption of technology. In the plenary session, participants identified and agreed on three main contexts for applying the models: communication, socio-economic analysis, and the design of user-centred technologies (cf. Sec. 5.3.3). As a future step, the project team plans to use the representations to support cost-benefit analysis, and estimate the sustainability of the solution.

💡 Models can be valuable tools for domain experts to explore, understand, and analyse digitalisation in ways that are directly relevant to their work, also enabling reflections on the impacts of technical solutions.

L14 – Modelling helps capture the dynamic nature of living labs The plenary discussion led to reflections on the adoption of models within the agricultural LLs. Some participants found the models to be valuable analytical tools for examining digitalisation in greater depth. Others suggested using these representations to facilitate discussion with stakeholders, applying continuous adaptation to enhance understanding and reflect the dynamic nature of LLs (cf. Sec. 5.3.3). This highlights that models can serve both as static artefacts capturing a specific state of knowledge, and as evolving documents that change as stakeholder perspectives shift.

Overall, this feedback confirms the potential contribution of requirements modelling to methods and tools for agricultural LLS, and more broadly to participatory innovation environments, addressing the lack of structured methodological approaches noted in previous studies [26, 60, 189].

💡 Visual models are living artefacts that adapt to the dynamic nature of LLS, continuously reshaped by stakeholder interaction and contextual changes.

L15 – End-users aspire to greater automation in model creation While the agronomists recognised the benefits of requirements modelling, they also pointed out the time and effort required by manual modelling. This highlights a challenge widely discussed in the literature, motivating recent research applying generative AI techniques to support model creation [234]. Along these lines, the team recognised that automation could significantly reduce the effort, even for non-expert modellers. Automation was seen as beneficial for handling operational tasks such as element generation, layout management, and syntactic control, for maintaining cohesion between models, and explanation of notation elements. Conceptual tasks support was also envisioned, such as suggesting elements or portions of processes. At the same time, the agronomists were cautious about complete automation, regarding the modelling activity itself as valuable for its interpretive nature, fostering reflection and shared understanding. This position aligns with perspectives in RE literature, recognising models not only as representations of a wide range of artefacts produced throughout the RE process, but also as elicitation tools, prompts for further information gathering and reflection [166].

💡 End-users express interest in automating parts of the model-creation process while maintaining control over the modelling practice itself and its interpretive dimension.

5.4 Conclusions

In this final section, we discuss the threats to validity and draw conclusions on the user study highlighting the research implications emerging from this iteration. These implications inform subsequent implementation of the method and motivate further cycles of the design science research.

5.4.1 Threats to Validity

This section discusses issues of the validity of this study, divided into construct validity, internal validity and external validity.

Construct validity The constructs considered in the study are modelling ability (how easily non-RE experts can apply semi-formal modelling notations), understandability (the extent to which the representations can be correctly and easily interpreted by the stakeholders), perceived usefulness (the degree to which the models are regarded as valuable in the context of LLS) and intention to use (the stakeholders' willingness to adopt the models into the LL practices). Due to the exploratory nature of the study and the

real-world, field-based modelling context, we opted to observe end users in their natural project environment prioritising ecological realism over experimental control. As a result, some operational decisions concerning how the constructs were measured, how different variables are aggregated, and how well those variables represent the constructs that they are supposed to operationalise may limit construct validity. To mitigate this, the accuracy of the measurements was strengthened, wherever feasible, through the integration of multiple evaluation methods, e.g., performance-based analysis and participants perception and through iterative cycles of model creation and revision. The modelling ability was assessed through expert evaluation, which is inherently subjective, though a common practice in similar studies. Certain simplifications in the design of the TAM questionnaire—such as the absence of reverse-coded items and fixed item order—may represent potential threats to construct validity, as they can affect the precision with which the questionnaire captures the intended theoretical constructs. To mitigate this risk, the selection and formulation of the survey items, still informed by user feedback, were guided by the background knowledge of the authors (cf. paper [JSS]), ensuring that the questions remained meaningful to participants and semantically appropriate. Moreover, the questionnaire included negatively worded statements to reduce systematic response bias. In future work, we intend to further assess the constructs under different circumstances—for example, by discussing a case within a broader timeframe and more focused discussion space, and involving smaller groups. We also aim to provide empirical evidence of the approach usefulness through the further application of the notations in real settings.

Internal validity Potential biases may have arisen from the interaction between agronomists and LL participants and the requirements engineers during the modelling and interpretation phases. The facilitation provided by the requirements engineers may have influenced participants perceptions or performance, and the fact that feedback was collected by the same engineers who proposed the approach may have introduced a Hawthorne effect.

Moreover, several factors could have influenced the observed outcomes. First, although the study involved participants who were not experts in RE, the outcome is closely tied to the expertise and motivation of the individuals involved, who were strongly committed to the success of the experiment. In particular, participants' familiarity with digital tools, their motivation to adopt the modelling approach, and contextual factors such as time availability may have affected their performance and perceptions. Moreover, participants were embedded in the CODECS ecosystem, which may have influenced their perceived acceptance and engagement with the modelling approach. These contextual influences are inherent to field experiments and may reflect the diversity of real-world settings. We mitigated these risks by providing the same training material to all participants, standardising the modelling procedure, and triangulating the results with evidence-based analysis and qualitative observations. Furthermore, the entire modelling experience—including the selection of notations, the structure of the guidelines document, the resulting artefacts—builds upon the selected modelling languages. Different results may be obtained with a different method. Second, the thematic analysis leading to the TAM-based items, although providing transparency on how the measurements were derived, is inherently subjective and influenced by the open-ended questions

and the context in which the questions were administered during the plenary session. To mitigate subjectivity, the analysis was performed by the first author, and the fourth and fifth authors reviewed the themes. Moreover, some items were adapted or added by the research team to better reflect the study context, while others were excluded when considered redundant or misaligned with the constructs under investigation. However, different outcomes may emerge with diverse cases presented and participants involved. To mitigate these risks, all feedback sessions followed a shared discussion script and participants were encouraged to provide honest reflections. The nature and specificity of the issues reported—summarised in the form of lessons learnt—suggest that the threats remain limited.

External validity The study was conducted with a number of LL representatives within a specific project and domain (agricultural digitalisation). Therefore, according to case-based generalisability [228], we argue that our results can apply to other LLs in the agricultural domain, whereas the generalisability of the results to other contexts or user groups may be limited. Nevertheless, the LLs represent diverse actor compositions, providing a heterogeneous sample that increases the transferability of the findings to other multi-stakeholder, participatory modelling contexts.

5.4.2 Summary

The second iteration of the design science research conducted in this thesis reported an experience on the application of the modelling procedure in eight real-world cases. Through a field experiment we observed stakeholders from LLs interacting requirements with modelling in two phases: model creation and interpretation. Findings show that non-RE experts were able to apply the modelling guidelines, and that LL stakeholders were able to engage with the modelling languages and recognised them as valuable within LL practices.

Furthermore, the lessons learnt contribute to the literature with empirical insights into how stakeholders can be effectively engaged in requirements modelling, a task typically carried out by requirements engineers.

Regarding model interpretation, the results and feedback confirmed the effectiveness of the method in ecological settings. This experiment complemented the validation conducted in the first iteration (cf. Sec. 4.3) by extending the assessment to a project plenary context involving a large and heterogeneous group of actors (60 participants). Moreover, by presenting a previously unseen case external to the specific LL context represented by the plenary participants, it provided further evidence of the effectiveness of the notations “at-first-exposure”. The models worked as shared focal objects that oriented participants’ attention towards a common reference point while still conveying contents with a sustained level of complexity. Taken together, these results suggest that the artefact has reached sufficient maturity to be applied across the CODECS LLs. The next chapter presents its implementation and the corresponding evaluation activities, extending the range of application cases and involving a broader set of LL stakeholders in modelling.

Regarding model creation, the experience highlighted the feasibility of having models developed by end users; however, it also outlined a range of challenges. These include

the sustained cognitive effort involved in creating and interpreting the modelling languages and the constraints of general-purpose tools. Both aspects have been consistently reported in prior empirical studies [126, 144]. In line with the broader modelling literature [14, 144, 191, 192], these empirical findings provide a rationale for the development of dedicated, user-oriented modelling tools capable of assisting novice modellers. Addressing these aspects in the specific context of agricultural LLs would help lower entry barriers for non-expert modellers, foster appropriation, and strengthen the practical impact of modelling. Part III of this thesis is therefore devoted to the design and validation of such a tool.

Implications for AI Support The model creation experience provided insights into how agronomists approached modelling. The feedback they provided (see, for example, Lesson Learnt 15 in 5.3.5) highlighted specific challenges emerging in model creation, particularly in relation to cognitive effort, syntactic correctness, cross-view consistency, and layout management. This aligns with previous empirical studies with practitioners that similarly reported tensions between conceptual modelling and the difficulties posed by the modelling environment [126]. At the same time, the agronomists appreciated the requirements modelling activity itself as valuable for its interpretive nature, fostering reflection and understanding.

These findings motivate the exploration of AI-infused functionalities [9] to support core modelling tasks such as abstraction and decomposition, for instance by suggesting modelling elements, checking consistency, and facilitating interpretation.

Building on this empirical evidence, this design science iteration provided further insights towards establishing AI-based support for modelling in LL contexts.

The insights gained can be synthesised into six design implications.

First, the AI should function as a collaborative assistant rather than an autonomous modeller. It should provide selective automation, rather than full automation. The agronomists expressed interest in delegating operational and repetitive tasks—e.g., element generation, layout optimisation, syntactic validation, and cross-model alignment—while retaining control over higher-level interpretive and conceptual decisions.

Second, as models are recognised as valuable artefacts for analysis and decision-making, this reflective dimension of modelling should be preserved also in the model creation phase. Accordingly, the tool should support incremental and suggestion-based interaction—an approach that is widely adopted in recommender systems for model-based development [14], where developers are guided through proposals that can be accepted, rejected, or refined rather than being replaced by fully automated outcomes. Instead of generating complete models, the system could propose candidate elements, relationships, or process fragments based on partial inputs, allowing users to accept, modify, or discard suggestions.

Third, the AI features should ensure transparency and explainability. Given that modelling serves as both a representational and elicitation activity, AI-generated suggestions should be accompanied by explanations (e.g., why a dependency is proposed, or how a process fragment was inferred). This is crucial to maintain trust and support learning.

Fourth, the tool should provide cognitive support, such as progressive disclosure of complexity, templates, syntactic and semantic validation feedback. These functionalities

would lower abstraction barriers while keeping users engaged in the modelling logic.

Fifth, it should maintain human interpretive primacy. Consistent with RE literature framing models as elicitation artefacts [166], the AI system should augment, rather than replace, the interpretive and dialogical aspects of requirements modelling.

Taken together, these characteristics point towards an AI-infused modelling assistant that supports operational efficiency and cognitive load reduction, while preserving modelling as a reflective, participatory, and knowledge-building practice within LLs.

🔖 This chapter provided:

1. Empirical evidence of MoDRE adoption by non-technical domain experts;
2. A characterisation of modelling as a socially mediated cognitive activity;
3. The identification of friction points in semi-formal notation use;
4. Requirements for tool support.

Chapter 6

Method Implementation and Evaluation

This chapter is partly based on the book chapter “Modelling Digital Transformation in Agriculture: BPM-based Method and Case Study”, Mannari C., Sportelli M., Bacco M., Malizia A., Ferrari A. Palgrave (in press) [PALGR] and on the project deliverable [CODECS-DEL] [7].

Figure 6.1: Visual summary of chapter 6, highlighting the portion that addresses: *RQ2.3 To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?* and *RQ2.4 To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?*

6.1 Overview

The previous chapter began to address RQ2 (*How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations?*) by validating the PoMeLO method through a field study conducted during the second design science iteration. This study focused on stakeholders' experiences with model creation and interpretation, specifically examining the feasibility of involving domain experts in requirements modelling and stakeholders with no prior RE expertise in validating the resulting models within a real-world context of a project plenary meeting. However, it did not evaluate how the modelling languages would be perceived in a more focused environment, specifically when applied within participants' own living lab (LL) contexts (cf. Ch. 3).

Therefore, this chapter complements RQ2 through the second group of sub-questions:

- RQ2.3: To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?
- RQ2.4: To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?

Fig. 6.1 maps how these RQs are addressed. To answer the questions, we implemented and evaluated the method in 19 LLs of the CODECS project.

To answer RQ2.3, we evaluated the method through individual focus groups conducted with LLs. Each LL focused on a unique case within its specific local context. We interacted with LL coordinators and selected participants.

To address RQ2.4, we assessed both the data collection process and the models by conducting two surveys based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [56]. These surveys were administered to the LL coordinators responsible for the data collection phase, as well as to the participants in the focus groups.

■ The large-scale implementation of the PoMeLO across 19 LLs provides empirical evidence of: 1) scalability of MoDRE in participatory contexts, 2) methodological robustness under heterogeneous conditions, 3) acceptance across disciplinary boundaries, and 4) operational sustainability beyond initial pilot settings.

6.1.1 Methodology

This section is structured into two parts: the approach adopted for the method implementation and the methodology used for the evaluation.

Implementation approach

A systematic procedure was adopted to implement the method within the LLs. Fig. 6.2 illustrates the five main steps of this process: data collection, reporting, check, formalisation, and agreement.

Data Collection. The procedure begins with the data collection through farm visits, interviews, focus groups, and workshops. This activity is planned to be managed directly by the LLs, in accordance with the guidelines for data collection (cf. Sec. 4.2.2).

Figure 6.2: Step-by-step procedure adopted for implementing the method in the LLs

Reporting. The LL coordinators synthesise the collected material into reports filling the templates included in the guidelines for data collection. This reporting phase transforms heterogeneous qualitative information into a semi-structured document describing actors, goals, resources, and process tasks.

Check. The reports are reviewed using a checklist to ensure that the information is complete and consistent (checklist template is available in Annex 7 [130]). In this step, additional clarifications from the LLs may be required. Therefore, based on the checklist, a document containing questions for the LLs is created.

Formalisation. Once reports are checked, the models are formalised through the application of the modelling guidelines (cf. Sec. 4.2.3). This activity involves developing the complete set of models: UML, iStar, and BPMN.

Agreement. The resulting models are presented to the LLs in dedicated evaluation focus groups. These sessions take the form of individual meetings with LL representatives.

Evaluation methodology

We present the methodology adopted to evaluate the two RQs. Across focus groups and surveys, the evaluation examined stakeholders' perceived acceptance of the overall method as applied in CODECS, including both the data collection procedure and the resulting models. Furthermore, qualitative evidence from the focus groups was triangulated with the survey findings on the models.

Focus groups (RQ2.3) The evaluation of the method primarily occurs in the agreement phase (cf. Fig. 6.2). Individual focus groups are organised with the LLs to evaluate the resulting models. These one-hour remote meetings involve a restricted group of LL representatives and are focused on the evaluation of the specific case of each LL. A few days before each focus group, the models were shared with participants together with a quick reading guide (cf. CODECS Quick Guide Process Modelling document in Annex 8 [130]), which they were invited to consult in advance so as to arrive at the meeting better prepared for the discussion.

Protocol. The focus groups followed a common protocol that was consistently applied across all LLs. The feedback was structured around five key aspects: (1) *understand-*

ability, namely the extent to which the models are easy to understand; (2) *completeness*, namely whether the information represented is perceived as complete and accurate; (3) *usefulness*, namely the perceived usefulness of the models and the overall RE method; (4) *intention to use*, namely how stakeholders envisage potential uses of the models; and (5) *limitations*, namely the weaknesses or constraints emerging from participants' experience. While *understandability* (1), *usefulness* (3), and *intention to use* (4) are directly aligned with TAM constructs PEOU, PU and ITU, respectively, *completeness* (2) and *limitations* (5) serve project-specific objectives and provide additional elements to reinforce the overall feedback. Questions on *understandability* (1), *completeness* (2) and *usefulness* (3) are asked for each type of modelling language, whereas the remaining aspects are addressed considering the modelling approach as a whole. The focus group protocol, including the supporting documentation, is available in Annex 8 [130].

Data analysis. Given the breadth of the material collected, amounting to approximately 18 hours of focus group recordings, and the tight timeline of the project, we adopted an AI-supported thematic analysis approach. This approach draws on recent literature that has highlighted the value of generative AI in supporting qualitative analysis [238]. We selected ChatGPT (version GPT-5.4 Thinking) for coding and ranking.

As the focus groups were already structured, we adopted a semi-open coding strategy, combining predefined high-level themes with the inductive refinement of subthemes emerging from the data [35], and adapted this process to interaction with the LLM.

We summarise our approach in six steps. 1) All transcripts were anonymised. 2) Through a first prompt, we provided the LLM with contextual information about the study and the RE method under discussion. 3) Through a second prompt, we instructed the LLM to code and to associate each code with a finer-grained theme aligned with 16 TAM-based high-level themes. These included: <Structure model understandability strengths>, <Structure model understandability challenges>, <Goal model understandability strengths>, <Goal model understandability challenges>, <Activity model understandability strengths>, <Activity model understandability challenges>, <Structure model usefulness strengths>, <Structure model usefulness challenges>, <Goal model usefulness strengths>, <Goal model usefulness challenges>, <Activity model usefulness strengths>, <Activity model usefulness challenges>, <Overall models usefulness strengths>, <Overall models usefulness limitations>, <Intention to use the models strengths>, <Intention to use the models limitations>. This process was conducted incrementally, prompting the analysis of one transcript at a time. After each transcript was analysed, the author of the thesis manually reviewed a sample of the LLM output. This revision, which was not conducted according to a systematic protocol, was used to check the plausibility of the assigned codes, their correspondence with the original transcript, and their alignment with the previously defined codecs. Note that, in defining the high-level themes for the prompts, we adopted terminology aligned with the wording used in the transcripts. Specifically, *structure model* was used to refer to the *domain model*, and *activity model* to the *process model*. 4) Through a third prompt, the resulting codebook was homogenised across focus groups by merging overlapping theme labels and aligning terminology. Given the large amount of data, this was done progressively in groups of 2-3 transcripts. 5) Through a fourth prompt, themes were ranked by frequency. 6) Finally, the author of the thesis carried out a further round of aggregation by manually refining the themes.

TAM surveys (RQ2.4) To reinforce the qualitative feedback of the focus groups, two TAM-based surveys using a 5-point Likert scale were administered to participants.

Survey on data collection. The first survey concerned the data collection process and was administered to the LL coordinators who managed the data collection after the *reporting* step (cf. Sec. 6.1.1). The questions are reported in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Questions TAM survey on data collection

1	PEOU	It was easy to come out with answers.
2	ITU	I think I will reuse the procedure in the future when dealing with the analysis of process transformation.
3	PEOU	I made a lot of effort to think about actors, resources and activities.
4	ITU	I would recommend the use of this procedure.
5	PU	The procedure helped us to better realise the impact of the digital transformation.
6	PU	I found the question on the transition useful to reflect on the steps taken.
7	PEOU	It was challenging to recall the process before digital solution.
8	PU	The procedure followed did not help to describe the process transformation.
9	ITU	I would apply a different procedure if I had to repeat a similar activity.
10	ITU	I had to highly adapt the questions when collecting data directly from stakeholders.

Survey on models The second survey focused on the models and was administered to participants after the focus groups conducted during the *agreement* step (cf. Sec. 6.1.1). The questions are reported in Table 6.2.

Table 6.2: Questions TAM survey on models

1	PEOU	It was easy to read the models
2	PU	The models are NOT useful to understand the impacts of the digital solution (negatively worded).
3	ITU	I would recommend the use of models to represent the process transformation.
4	ITU	I would use the models in discussing aspects related to the digital solution with different stakeholders.
5	PU	The models help understand how the introduction of a digital solution can transform a process.
6	PEOU	It was easy to interpret the process transformation.
7	PU	The models have the potential to drive the analysis of costs and benefits.
8	PU	Using the models would NOT bring benefits to assessing the impacts of digitalisation.
9	PU	I believe the models would NOT help my living lab in assessing the impacts of the digital solution.
10	PEOU	The models are NOT easy to understand.

6.2 Implementation

The implementation across the CODECS LLs took place between October 2022 and June 2025. In the following, we present the results of this task, spanning the process from data collection to formalisation (cf. Sec. 6.1.1).

6.2.1 Results from data collection

We summarise results from the data collection phase in Table 6.3. For each case, the table reports the LL name and country, a description of the smart farming technology central to the digitalisation process, information on the report documentation, and the number and types of stakeholders involved in the data collection activities. Cases 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9, 13, and 16 are the same as those presented in Chapter 5; they are nevertheless reported here for completeness.

Annex 9 [130] contains the complete documentation produced during this phase. Specifically, it includes the first version of the reports, the completed checklists, the

Table 6.3: Summary of data collection step. Abbreviations: agron. = agronomist, adv. = advisor, breed. = breeder, contr. = contractor, coop. = cooperative, farm. = farmer, fin. = financing institution, FG = focus group, gov. = government representative, I = interview, M = meeting, pol. = policy maker, prod. = production, ret. = retailers, tech. = technician, VIS = farm visit, WS = workshop

Case	Digital Technology	Data collection
1 - LL Pecorino Toscano Italy	Farm Management Information System integrating animal-health and milk-production data for sheep farming and Pecorino cheese production support.	Report: 16pp Stakeholders: 20 (res., farm., tech., breed.) Activities: I (4), FG (1), WS (1), M (2)
2 - LL AgriFood Tech Belgium	Drone-based pest/disease detection using ultra-high-resolution RGB imagery to generate task maps for variable-rate spraying and reduce pesticide use.	Report: 16pp Stakeholders: 12 (farm., tech., pol., adv.) Activities: I (6), FG (1), VIS (2), WS (1), D (2)
3 - LL Smart Villages Slovenia	IoT vineyard monitoring system supporting vineyard monitoring and planning of organic treatments through sensors, gateways, and the ThingsBoard platform.	Report: 21pp Stakeholders: 12 (res., adv., farm., tech., pol.) Activities: I (1), FG (1), M (6), WS (1), VIS (1)
4 - LL: RAMAS, North Macedonia	Farm management/advisory information system supporting farmer-agronomist decision making through field data, sensors, gateways, satellite/UAV and web application.	Report: 16pp Stakeholders: 12 (res., adv., farm., pol., NGO) Activities: I (1), FG (4), VIS (1), WS (1), M (3)
5 - LL Spraying drones Greece	Drone-based aerial pesticide spraying in vineyards, including flight planning, inspection, monitoring, and targeted application support.	Report: 31pp Stakeholders: 9 (res., adv., farm., pol., agr.) Activities: FG (1), WS (1), M (1)
6 - LL Greenhouse Lab Serbia	Greenhouse monitoring system using sensors, network, and Agrosense platform to support greenhouse production monitoring and advisor-farmer interaction	Report: 16pp Stakeholders: 17 (res., adv., farm., pol., tech.) Activities: FG (1), VIS (1), WS (2), M (7)
7 - LL Grassland Management using Drones Estonia	Grassland management using a drone-based system with photogrammetry/GIS maps to monitor grassland and support management planning.	Report: 23pp Stakeholders: 20 (res., adv., farm., tech.) Activities: I (4), FG (3), VIS (6), WS (1)
8 - LL Artificial Irrigation Slovakia	AI-based irrigation management system integrating field and irrigation data into one platform for farm-level irrigation decisions	Report: 6pp Stakeholders: 12 (res., adv., farm., inst., tech., pol., ret.) Activities: I (1), WS (2), VIS (3), M (1)
9 - LL Agroecology Almeria Spain	Platform for greenhouse monitoring: integrates IoT/sensor data, supports field technicians and farmers, standardises data, and helps optimise treatments and system management.	Report: 14pp Stakeholders: 22 (res., adv., farm., inst., coop. tech.) Activities: I (1), FG (1), VIS (1), WS (1), M (4)
10 - LL AgDiBi Germany	FarmLab: IoT/AI soil sensing and mapping system supporting real-time soil monitoring and fertilisation planning by demo farm manager and technology operator.	Report: 13pp Stakeholders: 13 (res., farm., tech., inst., pol., contr.) Activities: LL meeting (5), I (2), FG (1)
11 - LL APPETIT Poland	Platform supporting local food markets, linking farmers/producers, organisers and customers across virtual and physical market activities	Report: 34pp Stakeholders: 23 (res., adv., farm., inst., tech., pol., cus.) Activities: I (4), FG (24), VIS (1), WS (2)
12 - LL Orchard Manag. Czechia	Irrigation management with sensors, LoRaWAN/network, cloud platform, digital twin, and remote water monitoring for farm decision support	Report: 18pp Stakeholders: 18 (res., farm., inst., tech., pol., gov.) Activities: I (2), FG (1), VIS (3), WS (1), M (1)
13 - LL LIT OUESTEREL France	Data-space for pig breeding, enabling data flow/interoperability between equipment, services, farmers, and technical advisors.	Report: 17pp Stakeholders: 65 (res., adv., farm., inst., cus., prod., tech.) Activities: I (3), FG (2), VIS (1)
14 - LL Soil Scanner Tech Hungary	Soil scanner system supporting soil monitoring and site-specific fertilisation decisions by farmers and advisors.	Report: 20pp Stakeholders: 15 (res., adv., farm., pol., inst.) Activities: I (1), FG (1), WS (2), M (4)
15 - LL Living Lab Latvia	Multiple online marketing platforms and tools supporting grassland-product branding, promotion, and sales between farmers, retailers, and consumers.	Report: 15pp Stakeholders: 15 (res., adv., farm., inst., prod., tech., pol., cus.) Activities: I (3), FG (2), VIS (3), WS (2), M (2)
16 - LL Occitanum sheep France	Connected milk meters and advisory software supporting farmer and milk-inspector monitoring of milk production and animal health in sheep farming.	Report: 17pp Stakeholders: 22 (res., adv., farm., inst., prod., tech.) Activities: I (2), FG (1), VIS (1), WS (1), M (2)
17 - LL Organic Table Grape Italy	DSS-supported precision irrigation system for organic table grape farming using weather station, sensors, app, networked monitoring, and remote control.	Report: 14pp Stakeholders: 20 (res., farm., pol., adv. tech.) Activities: I (1), M (3), VIS (1)
18 - LL Digital Tools and Platforms, Scotland	Digital tools, online platforms, social media, email, CCTV, and vending machines used by small farmers for promotion, sales, traceability, and farm visibility.	Report: 27pp Stakeholders: 16 (res., farm., pol., adv. prod.) Activities: FG (1), VIS (3), WS (1), M (1)
19 LL - CloughJordan Food Hub Ireland	Open source digital farmers market, to reduce waste of time and resources by farmers.	Report: 13pp Stakeholders: 20 (res., farm., pol., NGO, prod.) Activities: I (2), VIS (1), WS (1)

question documents, and the revised version of the reports. Not all LLs completed the full documentation set: the first version of the report was completed by 19 out of 20 LLs, while the revised version after the checking phase was completed by 13 out of 18 LLs. This was not due to the research team, but rather to the broader project context, which involved multiple parallel requests and activities. As such, this should be considered part of the real-world conditions under which the method was applied.

Zenodo Archive of Living Lab Reports [10.5281/zenodo.16372574](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.16372574). The 19 final reports are available through a public repository on Zenodo. This is to comply with open-science principles of transparency and reusability promoted by EU-funded research.

6.2.2 Results from formalisation

The results from the formalisation phase consist of the set of models created by the CNR team and collaborators. Following the formalisation procedure (cf. Ch. 5), the complete set of UML, iStar, and BPMN diagrams was produced across the different LLs.

Zenodo Archive of Process Models [10.5281/zenodo.16372882](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.16372882). The models are stored within a publicly accessible Zenodo repository. The archive comprises 19 sets of graphical models, organised into folders, each dedicated to a single case.

6.3 Evaluation

We organise the presentation of the results from the evaluation phase around the two instruments used to answer the RQs: focus groups and surveys.

6.3.1 Results from focus groups (RQ2.3)

The focus groups, which represented the final agreement step (cf. Sec. 6.1.1), were conducted as individual remote meetings with 18 LLs between December 2024 and June 2025. A total of 39 participants were involved, with group sizes ranging from 1 to 4 participants. Each meeting included the LL coordinators and key informants from the LLs who were interested in discussing the models. Additionally, each focus group involved 2 to 4 members of the CNR team, with the author of the thesis acting as moderator and another colleague serving as note-taker.

Annex 10 [130] contains the material produced during the focus groups, including transcripts of the meeting records, slides, tables, and documentation related to the thematic analysis.

Table 6.4 contains a synthesis of the focus groups. For each focus group, it reports the date, the LL involved, number and profiles of participants, and the main takeaway lessons synthesised according to the three TAM dimensions: PEOU, PU, and ITU.

Table 6.4: Synthesis of Evaluation Focus Groups with LLs with description of Case and Takeaway Lessons in terms of PEOU, PU and ITU

Case	PEOU	PU	ITU
FG#1 - 2024-12-03, LL: Pecorino Toscano, Italy Participants: 6 (1 animal prod., 2 agron., 2 agritech, 1 RE)	Generally understandable for socio-economic analysts, but complex; simplified versions needed for broader LL audience.	Useful for documenting the process, tracing changes over time, supporting evaluation, and informing service design.	Positive mainly for expert analysis, reporting, and methodological support; more limited for broader stakeholder use unless simplified.
FG#2 - 2024-12-04; LL: AgriFood Tech, Belgium; Participants: 4 (2 agritech, 1 RE)	Readable and help identify actors, resources, workflows, and changes; goal symbols less intuitive and farmer simplification suggested.	Models useful for clarifying roles, overlaps, process changes, and technology adoption logic, and for explaining the solution to farmers and other stakeholders.	Participants would use the models for communication and overview, especially simplified versions; actual uptake in LLs depends on clearer cost-benefit evidence and affordability.
FG#3 - 2025-1-31; LL: Smart Villages, Slovenia; Participants: 4 (1 econ., 1 electr. eng., 1 agritech)	Easy enough to read once participants had reviewed the guidelines; the main difficulty was distinguishing actors from resources and recalling notation conventions over time.	Useful to represent demo-farm use case, clarify process changes, and communicate different levels of detail, especially for explaining technology structure and process logic.	Participants would use different models for different audiences: simpler for farmers, more detailed for developers, to support mobile app design and technical discussion.
FG#4 - 2025-2-21; LL: RAMAS, North Macedonia; Participants: 4 (3 agronomists, 1 agritech)	Overall understandable; some views hard to know where to start from, and the transformation/activity view needed clearer guidance, colours, and resolution.	Useful for clarifying actors, interactions, goals, process changes, and for supporting technology assessment and later analysis; especially valuable as an overview of how the technology works and where impacts/improvements may emerge.	Positive intention to use, communication and analysis aid; suggested using the models to explain the web application, supporting technologies, agronomist/farmer roles, and to support future assessment activities, though with refinement for more detail.
FG#5 - 2025-2-21; LL: Spraying drones, Greece; Participants: 3 (1 economist, 2 agritech)	Clear and straightforward, especially the structure and activity views, though some symbols, messages, and technical terms needed explanation.	Useful to explain the process, support operator guidance, compare before/after changes, and communicate the system to externals; the goal model less useful.	Use especially the activity model as a guideline/checklist for operators and the structure model for explanation, but with simplification or presenter support.
FG#6 - 2025-3-04; LL: Greenhouse Lab, Serbia; Participants: 5 (5 agritech)	Domain and process models generally understandable, thanks to colour coding and clear actor relations; goal model less intuitive.	Models useful for clarifying roles, visualising process changes, supporting understanding of the digital solution, comparing outcomes through clearer KPIs.	Positive: participants saw value in using the models for discussion, revision, and future evaluation of the LL process.
FG#7 - 2025-12-04; LL: Drones for grassland, Estonia; Participants: 4 (2 landscape manag. 2 agritech)	Models understandable overall, some elements hard to read without a legend and clearer arrows/labels; GIS interaction needed clearer representation.	High usefulness both for clarifying a complex process and for communicating it to farmers or new LL members; visuals judged clearer than text alone.	Reusing the models in future communication and even in a scientific article, once revised collaboratively.
FG#8 - 2025-04-02; LL: Artificial Irrigation, Slovakia; Participants: 4 (2 agronomy, 2 agritech)	Moderate to low for non-technical users: models were seen as abstract, detailed, and sometimes too complicated on first reading.	High for researchers/developers and for analysing process change: useful to clarify roles, integrate data from separate systems, and support future AI/ML-based decisions.	Conditional intention to use: willingness exists if models are revised to be more concrete, stakeholder-specific, and clearer about practical and cost-benefit implications for farms.
FG#9 - 2025-04-03; LL: Agroecology Almeria, Spain; Participants: 4 (2 agritech, 1 agronomist, 1 economist)	Mixed. Participants could read the models but understanding was hindered by unclear grouping of heterogeneous resources, missing legends, and abstract visual structure; the goal model was easier.	Positive. Participants said the models could help explain complex technologies, support workshops, clarify benefits and process transformation, and be useful especially for stakeholders needing LL overview.	Cautiously positive. They would use the models, especially with explanation and legends; the activity model seen as most suitable for farmers and workshop communication, while some models may be too abstract if shown without guidance.

Case	PEOU	PU	ITU
FG#10 - 2025-04-29; LL: AgDiBi, Germany; Participants: 2 (1 agribusiness, 1 agritech)	Models overall understandable, especially the goal and activity models; structure harder to read because it lacked a clear starting point and some elements were ambiguously positioned.	Useful for clarifying technical elements, actor roles, process changes, and how the system enhances fertilisation planning with more timely and ad hoc information.	Willingness to use them for discussing and refining the process, while also indicating that some visual refinements would improve usability.
FG#11 - 2025-05-19; LL: APPETIT, Poland; Participants: 3 (3 agricultural economics)	Relatively simple and understandable, but some elements needed clearer annotation.	Useful to discuss platform goals, collaboration, market organisation, barriers, and adaptation across different local-market configurations.	Positive: they said they would try the model on their cases, refine them, and use them as exploratory tools with partners.
FG#12 - 2025-5-21; LL: Orchard Manag., Czechia; Participants: 3 (2 agronomist, 1 agritech)	Clear and concrete, especially by technically experienced participants, some notation details needed refinement; creating models without theoretical background considered difficult.	Useful for understanding system structure, process transformation, and discussing digitalisation; not sufficient alone for impact evaluation unless complemented with clearer criteria, timelines, and some simplification of tasks and roles.	Overall positive: participants judged the material clear and “ready, and were willing to review it further and provide follow-up feedback, especially for communication and refinement purposes.
FG#13 - 2025-06-06; LL: LIT OUESTEREL, France; Participants: 3 (2 social science, 1 agricultural economic)	Overall understandable, especially goal; ease of use depends on adding a legend, short titles/explanations, and clearer labels for non-technical stakeholders.	Useful for communication and analysis: structure model helps discuss ecosystem positioning, goal model explains motivations, activity model highlights workflow changes.	Positive but conditional: participants would use different models for different audiences; a simplified/interactive version more suitable for farmers suggested.
FG#14 - 2025-06-10; LL: Soil Scanner Tech, Hungary; Participants: 2 (2 agritech)	Modelling representations seen as complex, especially for farmers and advisors.	Value for scientific communication, dissemination, and partly for describing impacts and process changes.	Intention to use is conditional: participants would use it mainly for research/coordinator purposes, and for practice only if simplified and tailored to the target group.
FG#15 - 2025-06-17; LL: Living Lab Latvia; Participants: 3 (2 social science, 1 agritech)	Understandable, especially structure and colour-coded transformation views, reading required explanation/legend; some symbols, arrows, and granularity not immediately clear.	Useful mainly for clarifying ecosystem roles, interactions, and digital transformation, especially for outsiders/research audiences; less useful for policymakers or directly for practitioners.	Limited intention to use within day-to-day LL activities; they would consider using mainly the structure model for presenting the ecosystem to outsiders, not the full set routinely.
FG#16 - 2025-06-23; LL: Occitanum sheep, France; Participants: 4 (2 agronomist, 1 agricultural economics)	Generally understandable; more zoom needed, legend support, and clearer elements distinction; activity model hardest because of its granularity and dynamic complexity.	Useful for discussing completeness, identifying missing software/data relations, comparing digitalised vs non-digitalised situations, delimiting system boundaries for life-cycle assessment.	Positive but conditional: they were open to refining the models further; especially for more detailed analytical uses.
FG#17 - 2025-7-02; LL: Organic Table Grape, Italy; Participants: 4 (2 agritech, 2 RE)	Generally understandable and coherent especially by participants familiar with the case; some terminology needed refinement.	Useful for clarifying roles, monitoring, decision support, quality-oriented production, and discussing cost–benefit trade-offs.	Intention for structured farms pursuing quality and innovation; adoption seen as less feasible for smaller or less prepared farms lacking skills, capital, or organisation.
FG#18 - 2025-07-02; LL: Tools and Platforms, Scotland; Participants: 4 (2 agritech, 2 RE)	Overall understandable, especially the colour coding and flow view, some arrows hard to interpret, and qualitative aspects hard to represent.	Useful to stimulate reflection, clarify complexity, support discussion, and provide an external mirror of LL practices, though contextual explanation needed.	Suitable mainly for coordinators/researchers rather than direct use with farmers; a simplified version could be more usable in future LL communication.

Thematic analysis

As described in the methodology section (cf. Sec. 6.1.1), transcripts were analysed through a thematic analysis with themes aligned to TAM constructs. Accordingly, we present and discuss results based on these dimensions. The codebook is available in Annex 10 [130] (folder 3, thematic analysis).

PEOU—Perceived Ease of Use Table 6.5 reports themes on PEOU. These are associated with a first group of high-level themes concerning both positive and negative aspects of model understandability (<*Structure model understandability strengths*>, <*Structure model understandability challenges*>, <*Goal model understandability strengths*>, <*Goal model understandability challenges*>, <*Activity model understandability strengths*>, <*Activity model understandability challenges*>).

We present the themes that were most consistently agreed upon across the focus groups, together with their corresponding representative quotes.

Domain model (UML class diagram)

The UML class diagrams were generally perceived as understandable representation, mainly because they supported *visibility of key elements*, which emerged as the most recurrent theme across the focus groups. Participants were often able to recognise core actors, resources, technologies, and their relations at a glance, suggesting that the model effectively conveyed the structural components of the LL context “Yeah, there is advisor. There is farm owner, policy maker, research institute, tech provider, local farmer association. Those are actors” (FG#6, P1). Closely related to this, a second frequently reported strength was the provision of a *clear overview*, as several participants noted that the diagram offered a synthetic yet informative picture of the overall report and helped make the process structure easier to grasp “It’s pretty nice develop because you have translated from the text to a diagram and it’s really nice and it’s really understandable” (FG#4, P1). Other positive themes included the model ability to support the *recognition of the technological architecture*, to *make the complexity of the case more visible*, and to *create a positive first impression*. In a few cases, participants also remarked that the *representation fitted their specific LL context* well.

At the same time, the feedback also highlighted some limitations. One of the most recurrent challenges concerned *terminology issues*, with participants sometimes suggesting specific terms that should be replaced for greater clarity “So for the spray nozzles, I would also suggest instead of calibrating which you do not accidentally calibrate the nozzles, you calibrate the spraying system.” (FG#5, P1). In addition, some participants pointed to *visual complexity*, observing that the density of information or the number of connected elements could make the model harder to read, especially to find a starting point “For me, I was kind of lost to see. If I have to read the map from the bottom or the top. And there are many links” (FG#13, P2). A further recurring issue concerned the *hard interpretation of fine-grained symbols*, as some participants struggled in interpreting certain specific elements of the notation, such as arrow directions in associations: “The question I had was the connection between the grassland product label and the map environment... it could be the other way around” (FG#15, P1). Other themes concerned *visual accessibility issues*, the *need for a legend*, the *need for a clearer reading path*, *color semantics issues*, and the *need for stronger visual differentiation* among model elements.

Goal models (iStar diagram) The iStar diagrams were appreciated for *visibility of*

actors and goals “Yeah, well, I can see that you’ve put some icons to represent some of the key stakeholders” (FG#16, P1) and for providing an *actor-centred narration* “The farmers is at the center. They manage grasslands and plant grazing” (FG#7, P1). Furthermore, several participants described this model as *generally comprehensible* and *rich in detail*, noting that *shapes and colours supported differentiation* among elements, while in some instances specifying that its *interpretation became clearer when accompanied by explanation*.

Regarding challenges, several participants reported *hard interpretation of relations and arrows*, for example that the direction of arrows are sometimes confusing or not immediately evident, especially in complex models with many interconnected elements: “Because it’s so complex, it’s not always possible to kind of see where the lines are going and which direction they’re going in and that kind of thing, but I think it has captured a lot” (FG18, P1).

Additionally, other recurring challenges concerned the *need for a legend*, the *hard interpretation of goals because of their abstract nature*, and *low readability when the model became visually dense*. Some participants also noted that *non-linear lines were not always clear*, or reported *confusion between goals and tasks*. Further issues included the *time and effort required* to inspect the model, the perception that it may be *too technical for newcomers*, the *limited intuitiveness of its visual grammar*, and the *low visual salience of goals*.

Activity models (BPMN diagram and overlaps)

The BPMN was appreciated for its *clear process flow*, with participants able to recognise tasks easily, “My opinion, the model is really clear to read it.” (FG#3, P2). Moreover, participants appreciated that the BPMN made the *transformation visible*, helping them see how activities unfold and how the process changes across steps “I think it is a clear way to present all the changes that happened after introducing the solution, especially because of the colors and the symbols with like I said before, the letter in the different colour it made things pretty clear for me even though I know what. Happening, but it’s it was still easy to to read” (FG#2, P1). Several also remarked that the *notation is understandable*, suggesting that the symbols and conventions were generally easy to interpret “The hand was representation of the manual activities. The closed envelope is something that he sends and the open one is that he receives task” (FG#3, P1). Other positive themes concerned the visibility of *information exchange* between actors or system components, as well as the fact that *colour coding was helpful* in supporting interpretation. Finally, in some cases participants considered the BPMN *clearer than other models*.

Regarding challenges, the most recurrent issue concerned *notation interpretation issues*, as several participants reported that some symbols or graphical conventions were not immediately clear and required additional effort to interpret “The fact that the dotted line means communication is not something I would suspect by myself to be honest” (FG#5, P1). A second recurring theme was that *excessive detail reduces readability*, with participants noting that the richness of the representation could at times make the process harder to follow visually “It can be hard to check everything because there is lot of information inside, for example who’s sending data. Who can receive data?” (FG#12, P1). In addition, some participants remarked that the model *needs explanatory context*, meaning that its interpretation became easier when accompanied by verbal explanation or prior familiarity with the case. Another challenge concerned the *hard interpretation*

of *removed activities*, as participants were not always able to immediately understand how no longer performed activities were represented in the diagram. Other negative themes concerned more general *visual readability issues*, the *need for a legend*, and, in a few cases, *limited clarity in how the transformation itself was represented*.

PU—Perceived Usefulness Table 6.5 reports themes on PU. These are associated with a second group of high-level themes concerning positive and negative aspects on usefulness, discussed both at the level of single model and overall models (<*Structure model usefulness strengths*>, <*Structure model usefulness challenges*>, <*Goal model usefulness strengths*>, <*Goal model usefulness challenges*>, <*Activity model usefulness strengths*>, <*Activity model usefulness challenges*>, <*Overall models usefulness strengths*>, <*Overall models usefulness limitations*>).

We present the themes that were most consistently agreed upon across the focus groups, together with their corresponding representative quotes.

Domain model (UML class diagram)

The UML class diagrams were mainly appreciated for supporting *stakeholder communication*, which emerged as the most recurrent positive theme. Participants often viewed this model as useful for discussing the case with different actors and for making the structure of the socio-technical setting easier to communicate “Anytime when we have new stakeholders, for example, on some events like demo events or the workshops, we can use the structure model to help us to explain the focal action situation and the technology implemented” (FG#3, P1). A second recurrent theme concerned the provision of a *system overview and technology integration*, as the model helped situate the digital solution within the broader context of actors, resources, and technical components “This model actually describes the digital solution” (FG#1, P2). Participants also noted that the model *clarifies roles and relations*, making explicit who is involved and how the main entities are connected “I would say that the actors are clearly defined. The relations are defined the nature of relation is defined. It’s, I would say structural model. Defines this” (FG#6, P1). Other positive themes included its capacity to *support cost-benefit reasoning*, to *position the solution in context*, and, in a smaller number of cases, to *support technical discussion*, as well as being considered useful for *presentation to external audiences* and for *research and dissemination*.

At the same time, one of the most recurrent limitations was that its *usefulness depends on the audience*, with participants noting that the model may be more valuable for some stakeholders than for others “I think the first one is most irrelevant for the technology provider... in the end he has already something like that because he’s more or less designing the innovation” (FG#10, P1). Additional themes, although each emerging only in isolated cases, concerned its *limited analytical depth*, its *limited added value for insiders* already familiar with the case, and the fact that *readability limits practical use* in some situations.

Goal models (iStar diagram)

The iStar diagrams were especially appreciated because they *support stakeholder engagement and reflection*, prompting discussion and helping participants reason about goals, perspectives, and the motivation behind the technological innovation “When it’s visual like this, they are more keen to answer and to look at it” (FG#16, P1). Another highly recurrent theme was that they *explain motivations behind technology use* “I could

Table 6.5: Themes on PEOU of models extracted from thematic analysis

Model	Theme	Focus Group and Participant		
Domain model	+	Visibility of key elements	FG#1 (P1); FG#2 (P1); FG#3 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#6 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#9 (P1, P2); FG#12 (P1); FG#14 (P1); FG#15 (P1); FG#16 (P1); FG#18 (P1)	
		Clear overview	FG#1 (P2); FG#2 (P1); FG#4 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#8 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#13 (P1); FG#13 (P1); FG#16 (P1)	
		Recognition of technology architecture	FG#10 (P1); FG#13 (P1)	
		Complexity made visible	FG#18 (P2); FG#18 (P1)	
		Positive first impression	FG#17 (P1)	
		Representation fits the case	FG#3 (P1)	
	UML	-	Terminology issues	FG#3 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#7 (P1, P2); FG#8 (P1); FG#9 (P1, P2); FG#11 (P1); FG#17 (P2)
			Visual complexity	FG#8 (P1); FG#10 (P1); FG#6 (P1); FG#13 (P2)
			Hard interpretation of fine-grained symbols	FG#15 (P1); FG#16 (P1); FG#13 (P2)
			Visual accessibility issues	FG#1 (P1); FG#2 (P1); FG#18 (P1)
			Granularity issues	FG#16 (P1); FG#18 (P2)
			Need legend	FG#6 (P1); FG#13 (P1); FG#16 (P1, P2)
			Need for clearer reading path	FG#4 (P1)
			Color semantics issues	FG#13 (P1)
		FG#12 (P1)		
Goal model	+	Visibility of actors and goals	FG#1 (P1); FG#2 (P1); FG#3 (P1); FG#3 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#6 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#11 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#14 (P2); FG#15 (P1); FG#16 (P1); FG#16 (P1)	
		Actor-centred narration	FG#4 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#17 (P1);	
		General comprehensibility	FG#9 (P2); FG#13 (P1); FG#17 (P1); FG#17 (P1)	
		Rich detail	FG#18 (P4); FG#18 (P1)	
		Shape and color differentiation help	FG#13 (P1); FG#1 (P1); FG#10 (P1)	
		Understandable with explanation	FG#8 (P1)	
	iStar	-	Hard interpretation of relations and arrows	FG#8 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#14 (P1, P2); FG#8 (P1); FG#10 (P1); FG#7 (P3); FG#18 (P2); FG#18 (P1)
			Needs initial orientation	FG#4 (P1); FG#13 (P1); FG#16 (P1); FG#11 (P2); FG#17 (P1)
			Need for legend	FG#7 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#15 (P1); FG#11 (P2)
			Hard interpretation of goal due to abstract concept	FG#14 (P2); FG#15 (P3)
			Low readability due to density	FG#1 (P2); FG#16 (P1)
			Need for simplification	FG#3 (P1, P3)
			Non linear lines unclear	FG#5 (P1)
			Confusion between goals and tasks	FG#2 (P1)
Requires time and effort to inspect	FG#12 (P1)			
		FG#13 (P1)		
		FG#6 (P2)		
		FG#2 (P1)		
Activity model BPMN	+	Clear process flow	FG#8 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#3 (P1, P2); FG#5 (P1); FG#6 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#4 (P1, P2); FG#14 (P2); FG#15 (P1); FG#13 (P1); FG#17 (P1); FG#11 (P2); FG#13 (P1); FG#10 (P1)	
		Transformation is visible	FG#1 (P1); FG#2 (P1); FG#16 (P1); FG#18 (P3); FG#17 (P1); FG#2 (P1); FG#3 (P1); FG#7 (P3); FG#12 (P1); FG#13 (P1)	
		Notation is understandable	FG#3 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#10 (P1)	
		Information exchange is visible	FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#6 (P1)	
		Colour coding helpful	FG#5 (P1); FG#6 (P1); FG#18 (P2)	
		Clearer than other models	FG#9 (P2); FG#18 (P2)	
	-	Notation interpretation issues	FG#3 (P1); FG#1 (P1); FG#4 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#5 (P1)	
		Excessive detail reduces readability	FG#1 (P3); FG#7 (P3); FG#12 (P1); FG#16 (P2)	
		Needs explanatory context	FG#18 (P3); FG#6 (P1); FG#10 (P1)	
		Hard interpretations of removed activities	FG#18 (P3); FG#17 (P1); FG#18 (P1)	
		Information exchange is hard to read	FG#5 (P1); FG#14 (P1)	
		Colour coding confusing	FG#7 (P1); FG#13 (P2)	
		Visual readability issues	FG#5 (P1); FG#12 (P1)	
		Need for legend	FG#5 (P1); FG#15 (P1)	
		FG#4 (P1, P2)		

Table 6.6: Themes on PU of models and overall method extracted from thematic analysis

Model	Theme	Focus Group and Participant
Domain model UML	Useful for stakeholder communication	FG#3 (P1, P2); FG#14 (P2); FG#15 (P1); FG#16 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#6 (P2); FG#2 (P1); FG#8 (P1)
	System overview and technology integration	FG#8 (P1); FG#9 (P1); FG#10 (P1); FG#1 (P2); FG#7 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#1 (P3); FG#7 (P1)
	Clarifies roles and relations	FG#6 (P1); FG#2 (P1); FG#10 (P1); FG#11 (P2); FG#18 (P2); FG#5 (P1)
	Supports cost-benefit reasoning	FG#17 (P1, P2); FG#7 (P1)
	Helps to position the solution in context	FG#13 (P1); FG#17 (P1)
	Supports technical discussion	FG#13 (P1)
	Useful for presentation to externals	FG#15 (P1)
	Useful for research and dissemination	FG#14 (P1)
	Usefulness depends on audience	FG#8 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#13 (P1); FG#14; FG#2 (P1)(P2)
	Limited analytical depth	FG#5 (P1)
Limited added value for insiders	FG#15 (P1)	
Readability limits practical use	FG#10 (P1)	
Goal model iStar	Supports stakeholder engagement and reflection	FG#16 (P1, P2); FG#1 (P1, P2); FG#11 (P1); FG#13 (P1); FG#11 (P1); FG#7 (P3); FG#7 (P3); FG#1 (P2)
	Explains motivations behind technology use	FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#14 (P2); FG#15 (P1); FG#4 (P1); FG#6 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#18 (P1)
	Supports analysis and decision-making	FG#3 (P1, P3); FG#17 (P1)
	Links objectives to actions	FG#10 (P1); FG#13 (P1)
	Clarifies responsibilities	FG#8 (P1)
	Makes economic rationale visible	FG#17 (P1)
	Needs explanation to be used	FG#3 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#18 (P4)
	Limited fit for some audiences	FG#3 (P1, P3); FG#16 (P1)
	Abstract nature of goals limits practical uptake	FG#2 (P3)
	Needs complementary analysis	FG#1 (P3, P5)
Less useful than other models	FG#5 (P1)	
Missing temporal dimension limits usefulness	FG#18 (P4)	
Needs simplification	FG#5 (P1); FG#15 (P1)	
Activity model BPMN	Supports process analysis and impact discussion	FG#1 (P2); FG#4 (P1); FG#14 (P1); FG#16 (P2); FG#17 (P1); FG#13 (P2); FG#13 (P1); FG#18 (P2); FG#11 (P2); FG#17 (P1); FG#12 (P1)
	Communicates process change	FG#2 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#6 (P1); FG#8 (P1); FG#9 (P2, P3); FG#10 (P1); FG#15 (P2); FG#10 (P1)
	Supports technical development	FG#13 (P1); FG#8 (P1); FG#3 (P1, P2)
	Can be extended or adapted	FG#11 (P1)
	Provides impact overview	FG#13 (P1)
	Makes the added system visible	FG#10 (P1)
	Limited representation of impacts	FG#1 (P6); FG#2 (P1); FG#12 (P1); FG#14 (P2); FG#6 (P1)
	Needs facilitation or expert mediation	FG#16 (P2); FG#5 (P2);
	Need adaptation for audience	FG#1 (P2); FG#3 (P1)
	Excessive complexity may reduce usefulness	FG#1 (P3); FG#2 (P1)
Cannot support cost-benefit evaluation alone	FG#13 (P1)	
Need additional notation for improvements	FG#18 (P1)	
All models	Useful multi-model communication set	FG#3 (P1, P2, P3); FG#1 (P2); FG#4 (P1); FG#8 (P2); FG#9 (P1, P2); FG#18 (P2, P3); FG#4 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#2 (P1)
	Perceived practical value	FG#13 (P1); FG#8 (P1); FG#9 (P2); FG#13 (P1); FG#10 (P2); FG#12 (P1); FG#11 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#1 (P5); FG#1 (P2)
	Supports cost-benefit assessment	FG#2 (P1); FG#16 (P2); FG#16 (P2); FG#6 (P1)
	Clarifies complex processes	FG#12 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#17 (P1)
	Supports participatory work	FG#1 (P2); FG#5 (P1); FG#16 (P1); FG#10 (P1)
	Useful for research and dissemination	FG#14 (P2); FG#15 (P1); FG#5 (P2)
	Supports requirements-oriented reflection	FG#12 (P1); FG#7 (P3)
	Bridges dense text into organised representations	FG#15 (P3)
	Can reduce data collection effort	FG#6 (P3)
	Transferability beyond the case	FG#17 (P1)
	Visual form is engaging	FG#14 (P1)
	Preparation effort is required	FG#9 (P2); FG#10 (P1); FG#3 (P1, P3); FG#1 (P2); FG#15 (P1)
	Distance from everyday practice	FG#1; FG#8; FG#14; FG#15
	Model creation is difficult	FG#6; FG#12; FG#12
	Audience-dependent usefulness	FG#5 (P2); FG#8 (P1)
	Need legend and notation guidance	FG#16; FG#5
	Representation remains partial	FG#2 (P1, P2)
	Tension between complexity and simplification	FG#11 (P1); FG#18 (P1)
	Needs larger or higher-resolution views	FG#4 (P1)
	Needs simplification	FG#5 (P1)
Requires domain knowledge	FG#4 (P3)	
Requires iterative collaboration	FG#7 (P3)	

see the orange box which is in this sense the the objective, the goal. And maybe the motivation of each actor and how they can access the digital platform to get this goal” (FG#9, P2). In some cases, participants also remarked that the model *supports analysis and decision-making* “This model could be used with policy makers and other actors who are more in the decision making process to understand how the different actors can relate with technology and what can be their interests” (FG#3, P3), *links objectives to actions, clarifies responsibilities, and even makes the economic rationale visible*.

However, certain limitations also emerged. A first recurring issue was that the model *needs explanation to be used*, as its practical usefulness often increased when accompanied by verbal interpretation or facilitation “Having some context around each of these would be quite important before anybody nitpicks at it” (FG#18, P4). Participants also noted a *limited fit for some audiences*, especially when practitioners were not used to reasoning at a high level of abstraction “The goal model is maybe more difficult for someone who is more in the practice of the process like farmers or advisors who are more interested in the process flow and in the task” (FG#3, P3). Other themes suggested that the *abstract nature of goals limits practical uptake*, that the model *needs complementary analysis*, or that it was sometimes perceived as *less useful than other models*. Additional concerns referred to the fact that the *missing temporal dimension limits usefulness* and that the representation may *need simplification*.

Activity models (BPMN diagram and overlaps)

The BPMN models were primarily appreciated because they *support process analysis and impact discussion*, helping participants inspect the transformation in operational terms and reason about how the introduction of the solution affects activities and flows “If a proper before-and-after scenario analysis is carried out, in my opinion the farm manager will be convinced and will move forward without problems (FG#1, P1). Closely related to this, another recurrent positive theme was that the model *communicates process change*, making visible how the process is modified before and after the adoption of the technology “I think this transformation process is well depicted through these colours so we can see what was before and what’s added” (FG#15, P1). Some participants further pointed out that BPMN *supports technical development*, “The last one is mainly for me, for the people that are developing, that are trying to understand what is the impact and to survey with probably other tools if the impact is positive or not. It is a tool to manage the development” (FG#13, P1). Moreover, others note the this model can *be extended or adapted, provides an impact overview, and makes the added system visible*.

At the same time, participants also reported some limitations. One recurring concern was that the *limited representation of impacts*, suggesting that the model may not capture all relevant consequences of the transformation “I would emphasise more real the impacts... the impact is on the income of the farmer, on the nutrient use... optimising fertilisers, reducing risk, that is also an impact” (FG#14, P2). Other participants noted that the BPMN model *needs facilitation or expert mediation*, and that it may *need adaptation for the audience*. Further themes concerned the fact that *excessive complexity may reduce usefulness*, that the model *cannot support cost-benefit evaluation alone*, and that it may *need additional notation for improvements*.

Overall models

Considering the models as a whole, participants most frequently appreciated them as a *useful multi-model communication set*, highlighting the complementary value of com-

binning different representations to discuss the case from multiple angles “It can be also used with the farmers and if somebody else new joins into LL it... can be explained very clearly through the diagram” (FG#7, P1). Another highly recurrent theme concerned the *perceived practical value*, with several participants emphasising that the models could support concrete reasoning and discussion around the LL transformation “If we want to use it in a dissemination scope or something like this to describe. The activities in our LL” (FG#5, P1). Additional positive themes indicated that the models *supports cost-benefit assessment* “They can show the cost and benefits in a concise way. The most important factors will be will be shown here” (FG#2, P1) and *clarifies complex processes* “This graphical representation of process modelling for the LL is very helpful because we have such a complex situation... this is very straightforward and simple” (FG#7, P1), as well as *supports participatory work*. In some cases, models were also described as useful for *research and dissemination*, for *requirements-oriented reflection*, and for *bridging dense textual material into organised visual representations*. Other themes suggested that the representations *can reduce data collection effort*, have *transferability beyond the case*, and that their *visual form is engaging*.

At the same time, participants also pointed to a number of limitations. The most recurrent one was that *preparation effort is required*, “The limitation is that it requires the reader or the audience to actually go through the steps and actually learn to read the model” (FG#15, P1). Another common theme concerned a *distance from everyday practice*, as some participants felt that the models do not always align closely with the routine ways in which practitioners describe or analyse their work “I don’t really see how these models could be used in the context of the LL activities... I think this has more use in the context of research, like applied research” (FG#15, P1). Other recurring limitations included the fact that *model creation is difficult*, that usefulness can be *audience-dependent*, and that the models may *need legend and notation guidance*. Additional themes concerned the fact that the *representation remains partial*, a *tension between complexity and simplification*, the *need for larger or higher-resolution views*, the *need for simplification*, the fact that they *require domain knowledge*, and that they *require iterative collaboration*.

ITU—Intention to Use Table 6.7 reports themes on ITU. These are associated with a third group of high-level themes concerning positive and negative aspects related to the intention to use the models (<Intention to use the models strengths>,<Intention to use the models limitations>). We present the themes that were most consistently agreed upon across the focus groups, together with their corresponding representative quotes.

The most recurrent positive theme concerned the intention to *use the models internally over time*. Many participants expressed an interest in reusing the models within their own organisation or LL activities, “We would try to probably look at your BPMN model and try to add some process... and see in what way we can modify a little bit this distinction between the farmer and the producer” (FG#11, P1). A second recurring theme was *selective planned model reuse*, as some participants indicated that they would reuse only some of the models depending on their needs and context “You would use it even with farmers and advisor if it was much more simple...” (FG#14, P2). Other positive themes suggested that the models *would be used for research or expert contexts*, had *potential for communication and dissemination reuse*, and showed a *strong intention for analytic use*. In a few cases, participants also referred to an *intended use for communica-*

Table 6.7: Themes on ITU of the overall models extracted from thematic analysis

Model	Theme	Focus Group and Participant	
All models	+	Intend to use internally over time	FG#1 (P1, P2); FG#3 (P1); FG#9 (P1, P2); FG#2 (P1); FG#8 (P1); FG#4 (P1); FG#5 (P1); FG#7 (P1); FG#17 (P1); FG#11 (P2); FG#16 (P1); FG#11 (P1); FG#1 (P2); FG#12 (P2)
		Selective planned model reuse	FG#3 (P1, P2); FG#14 (P2); FG#15 (P1); FG#13 (P1)
		Would use for research or expert contexts	FG#14 (P1); FG#16 (P2); FG#7 (P1)
		Potential communication and dissemination reuse	FG#5 (P2); FG#15 (P1)
		Strong intention for analytic use	FG#2 (P1); FG#6 (P1)
		Intended use for communication with specific audiences	FG#10 (P1)
		Better suited to technical stakeholders	FG#12 (P1)
	-	Selective adoption depending on audience	FG#3 (P1, P2); FG#14 (P2); FG#16 (P1); FG#8 (P1); FG#10 (P1); FG#18 (P2); FG#12 (P1); FG#11 (P2); FG#12 (P1)
		Current workload limits reuse	FG#16 (P2); FG#2 (P1); FG#7 (P3); FG#14 (P2); FG#16 (P1); FG#3 (P1)
		Needs adaptation before reuse	FG#4 (P4); FG#13 (P1); FG#15 (P1)
		Use depends on incentives and organizational embedding	FG#1 (P2); FG#2 (P1); FG#11 (P2)

tion with specific audiences or observed that the models may be better suited to technical stakeholders.

At the same time, the prospective reuse of the models was often described as conditional. “One of the most recurrent limitations was *selective adoption depending on the audience*” (FG#3, P2), with participants noting that reuse would vary according to the stakeholders involved and the communicative purpose of the models “I would use this for explanation. For explaining the process to anyone, this one and not the rest” (FG#5, P1). Another frequent theme concerned the fact that *current workload limits reuse*, suggesting that time pressure and competing priorities may hinder the practical adoption of the method even when it is perceived as valuable “We had to prepare to some extent in order to be able to have a successful communication” (FG#3, P1). Other limitations indicated that the models *needs adaptation before reuse* and that its use may *depend on incentives and organisational embedding*, pointing to the importance of fitting the approach into existing practices.

6.3.2 Discussion

We discuss the outcome of the thematic analysis based on the three TAM dimensions considered in reporting the results, namely PEOU, PU and ITU, and by relating the emerging findings, a posteriori, to selected principles of Moody’s theory (cf. Sec. 2.2.1).

PEOU The findings on PEOU show that all three model types are overall understandable to LL stakeholders, but also that ease of use was not uniform across them.

The domain model (UML) appeared to be the most effective in providing an immediate structural overview, as participants could often identify actors, resources, technologies, and relations at a glance. This suggests that representations grounded in tangible entities are more readily accessible to non-technical stakeholders.

By contrast, the goal model (iStar) was appreciated for the use of icons and colours and for making actors and goals immediately visible. This can be related to the principle of perceptual discriminability, as the use of differentiated visual shapes and cues appears to have supported participants in distinguishing key modelling elements. However, the domain model also emerged as the most cognitively demanding to interpret when reading the diagram as a whole. This is probably related to the abstract nature of goals and

the difficulty of interpreting relations and arrows in visually dense diagrams.

The activity model (BPMN) occupied an intermediate position: it was often regarded as clear and intuitive in representing process flow and transformation, especially thanks to colour coding and explicit task sequencing. These positive aspects may be interpreted principle of perceptual discriminability. At the same time, its readability decreased when the amount of detail became too high or when notation-specific conventions (e.g., gateways, task icons) were unfamiliar, indicating that such discriminability became harder to sustain in visually dense or less transparent representations.

Taken together, these results suggest that ease of use depends not only on the semantic transparency of the notation itself, but also on the granularity of the information depicted resulting in the visual density of the diagram and the type of different different symbols used. In this sense, the findings confirm the importance of simplification and explanatory support, e.g., through an introductory guidance or a legend. Notably, participants who had reviewed the quick guide (cf. Sec. 6.1.1) in advance seemed to demonstrate greater confidence and awareness when reading and discussing the models during the focus groups, whereas those who had not had the opportunity to consult it appeared to experience more difficulty in orienting themselves within the diagrams.

PU The outcomes on PU suggest that the three model types were mostly perceived as complementary.

The domain model (UML) was mainly perceived as useful for communication, as it helped participants explain the socio-technical context, make actors and relations explicit, and position the digital solution within the broader LL context.

The goal model (iStar) added a more reflective and strategic layer, supporting reasoning about motivations, responsibilities, and stakeholder perspectives, especially in discussions involving coordination or decision making.

The activity model (BPMN), in turn, was perceived as the most operationally useful, since it made process transformations visible and supported discussion of concrete changes introduced by the technology.

At the same time, the limitations reported across all three models qualify their usefulness. Their value was often described as dependent on the audience and on the availability of facilitation or explanation, both aspects are connected to PEOU. Overall, the findings support the view that a multi-notation RE approach can provide meaningful practical value in complex socio-technical contexts such as agricultural LLs. This value appears to depend on the extent to which the models are adapted to LL stakeholder needs, as well as on how effectively expressive richness is balanced against the time and cognitive effort required for interpretation.

ITU The results on ITU suggest that the models were perceived as an approach whose future uptake depends on how well it fits concrete organisational purposes and stakeholder profiles. A first relevant point is that intention to use emerged most clearly at the level of the overall model set, indicating that participants recognised value in the combined modelling approach. At the same time, this intention was rarely unconditional: participants tended to frame reuse as selective, audience-dependent, and contingent on simplification, adaptation, and available time. This is relevant because it shows that adoption in practice is shaped less by abstract appreciation of the models and more by

their perceived communicative fit within real work settings. In this sense, the findings are coherent with the evaluation of the PU dimension: the models appear promising as boundary objects for analysis and discussion, but their transfer into routine practice requires calibration to users' expertise, purposes, and workload. The stronger intention to reuse in research and analytic settings also suggests that the models are currently more readily adoptable where abstraction is already part of professional practice. At the same time, their use was also viewed positively in settings involving farmers and mixed practitioners groups, provided that the representations were suitably simplified or adapted to the audience.

6.3.3 Answer to RQ2.3: *To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept models created with PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?*

The evaluation of the models across 18 focus groups with the CODECS LLs that had implemented the method, together with the subsequent analysis through the TAM framework, makes it possible to examine stakeholders' perceptions of the models along the complementary dimensions of PEOU, PU, and ITU.

Overall, participants considered the models understandable (PEOU), although with differences across notations and application cases. The domain model was generally the easiest to grasp, as it provided an immediate overview of tangible domain entities. The goal model, by contrast, was perceived as the most cognitively demanding because of its more abstract focus and non-linear visual structure. The activity model was often regarded as clear, especially thanks to the sequential layout and the use of colour coding in representing process transformations. At the same time, across all the three model types, readability decreased when the representations became too detailed, since greater visual density increased the cognitive load and the effort required to interpret the diagrams.

In terms of usefulness (PU), stakeholders valued above all the complementarity of the three models proposed, with each notation contributing a distinct perspective to the understanding of the LL case, that is, the domain model for identifying the main actors, resources, and relations, the goal model for making explicit motivations, interests, and dependencies, and the process model for representing the workflow and the changes introduced by the digital solution. Overall, the models were seen as useful for analysis and discussion in LLs. At the same time, the feedback revealed that usefulness of the models depends on the expected audience and context of use, as well as on the availability of facilitation to support their interpretation.

Regarding the intention to use (ITU), participants showed a generally positive but conditional willingness to reuse the models. They were mainly valued for internal analysis, research, and communication purposes, but often suggested selective reuse depending on the model type, audience, and context.

6.3.4 Results from TAM Surveys (RQ2.4)

Survey on data collection

The TAM survey on data collection (cf. Sec. 6.1.1) was integrated in the reporting templates for producing the LL reports (cf. Annex 9 [130], folder LL reports, version 1). Out

of the 19 LL reports, 18 included the compiled survey.

Figure 6.4 reports the results, with questions aggregated by TAM dimensions for the data collection phase. The results suggest relevant differences across constructs. Usefulness (PU) received the strongest support, with 64.8% of responses in the positive category and 13.0% in disagreement, indicating that participants generally considered the data collection procedure valuable for their work. Intention to Use (ITU) showed 38.9% of positive responses, contrasting with limited disagreement (20.8%), while showing the highest share of neutral answers (40.3%). This suggests a certain degree of hesitation about future adoption. In contrast, Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) emerged as the weakest dimension, with nearly half of the responses (48.1%) falling in the disagreement category and only 31.5% being positive, pointing to notable efforts related to the implementation of the data collection.

Figure 6.4 provides a granular view of the responses at the level of single questions (Q), grouped by constructs and ranked by agreement rate.

Q1—*It was easy to come out with answers.* Responses were mixed, though slightly positive overall. A total of 7 participants agreed (38.9%) and 1 strongly agreed (5.6%), suggesting that nearly half found it easy to come up with answers. At the same time, 4 disagreed (22.2%) and 6 were undecided (33.3%), indicating that for a substantial proportion of respondents the procedure was not entirely straightforward.

Q2—*I think I will reuse the procedure in the future when dealing with the analysis of process transformation.* Most participants expressed a positive intention to reuse the procedure in the future: 11 agreed (61.1%). However, 3 disagreed (16.7%) and 4 were undecided (22.2%). Overall, this suggests a generally favourable perception of the procedure's future applicability.

Q3—*I made a lot of effort to think about actors, resources and activities (negatively*

Figure 6.3: Results from TAM survey on Data collection with questions aggregated by constructs PEOU, PU, and ITU.

Figure 6.4: Results from TAM survey on Data collection with questions grouped by constructs PEOU, PU, and ITU with reversed codes for negatively worded items.

worded). After reverse-coding, the item can be read as *It was easy to think about actors, resources, and activities*. The responses indicate a predominantly negative evaluation of ease: 8 fell in the disagree category (44.4%) and 8 in the strongly disagree category (44.4%), while only 2 fell in the agree category (11.1%). This suggests that thinking about actors, resources, and activities was generally experienced as demanding.

Q4—*I would recommend the use of this procedure*. Responses were mainly neutral to positive. A total of 6 participants agreed (33.3%), while 9 were undecided (50.0%) and 3 disagreed (16.7%). This suggests some openness to recommending the procedure, although many respondents remained cautious or uncertain.

Q5—*The procedure helped us to better realise the impact of the digital transformation*. The responses were overall positive. Eight participants agreed (44.4%) and 2 strongly agreed (11.1%), indicating that more than half found the procedure helpful in understanding the impact of the digital transformation. At the same time, 5 were undecided (27.8%), 2 disagreed (11.1%), and 1 strongly disagreed (5.6%), suggesting that this benefit was not equally evident to all respondents.

Q6—*I found the question on the transition useful to reflect on the steps taken*. This item received one of the most positive evaluations. A total of 11 participants agreed (61.1%) and 2 strongly agreed (11.1%), while only 1 strongly disagreed (5.6%), 1 disagreed (5.6%), and 3 were undecided (16.7%). This suggests that the transition-related question was widely perceived as useful for reflection.

Here is the parallel rewritten version with the **reverse-coded interpretation made explicit**:

Q7—*It was challenging to recall the process before digital solution* (negatively worded). After reverse-coding, the item can be read as *It was easy to recall the process before the*

digital solution. Responses remained quite distributed. In the reversed distribution, 6 responses fall in the disagree category (33.3%) and 1 in the strongly disagree category (5.6%). At the same time, 5 fall in the agree category (27.8%), 1 in the strongly agree category (5.6%), and 5 are undecided (27.8%). Overall, this suggests heterogeneous experiences across respondents in recalling the pre-digital process.

Q8—*The procedure followed did not help to describe the process transformation* (negatively worded). After reverse-coding, the item can be read as *The procedure helped to describe the process transformation*. The responses indicate an overall positive evaluation: 10 fall in the agree category (55.6%) and 2 in the strongly agree category (11.1%), while 4 are undecided (22.2%) and 2 fall in the disagree category (11.1%). This suggests that most respondents perceived the procedure as helpful in describing the process transformation.

Q9—*I would apply a different procedure if I had to repeat a similar activity* (negatively worded). After reverse-coding, the item can be read as *I would use the same procedure if I had to repeat a similar activity*. Most responses remained concentrated in the undecided category (10, 55.6%). In the reversed distribution, 4 fall in the agree category (22.2%), while 3 fall in the disagree category (16.7%) and 1 in the strongly disagree category (5.6%). This suggests uncertainty about whether the same procedure would be preferred in the future, with no clear tendency emerging.

Q10—*I had to highly adapt the questions when collecting data directly from stakeholders* (negatively worded). After reverse-coding, the item can be read as *The questions could be used with little adaptation when collecting data directly from stakeholders*. Responses were mixed. In the reversed distribution, 5 fall in the disagree category (27.8%) and 2 in the strongly disagree category (11.1%), indicating that for several respondents substantial adaptation was required. At the same time, 5 fall in the strongly agree category (27.8%), while 6 are undecided (33.3%). Overall, this suggests considerable variability in the extent to which the questions could be applied directly without adaptation across contexts.

Survey on models

The TAM survey on the models (cf. Sec. 6.1.1) was administered online after the focus groups and completed by 25 respondents (16 males, 9 females) out of 39 invited participants, resulting in a response rate of approximately 64%. Most participants were in the 35–44 (12) and 25–34 (7) age ranges, with smaller groups in the 45–54 (3), 55–64 (2), and 18–24 (1) categories. The majority of respondents were researchers (20), with others identifying as project managers, ICT providers, advisors, and representing a variety of LLs across Europe. Backgrounds were diverse, with the most common being Agronomy (9), Computer Science (4), Agritech (3), and Social Science (3), along with individual representatives from fields such as Management, Engineering, and Landscape management. Survey responses are available in Annex 9 [130] (cf. folder 4 TAM survey models results).

Figure 6.5 displays the results for the models, with questions aggregated by TAM dimensions. The results show a clearly positive assessment across all three constructs. Usefulness (PU) received the strongest endorsement, with 76.8% of responses in the positive category and only a minority of participants in disagreement (4.8%), suggesting that participants largely recognised the practical value of the models. Understandability (PEOU) was similarly well rated, with 74.7% positive responses and a few negative ones (5.3%), indicating that the models were generally considered understandable. Intention to Use was also positive overall, with 68.0% agreement, although it showed a somewhat

Figure 6.5: Results from TAM survey on Models with questions aggregated by constructs, PEOU, PU, and ITU.

Figure 6.6: Results from TAM survey on Models with questions grouped by constructs, PEOU, PU, and ITU.

larger share of neutral (24.0%) and a relatively higher share of negative responses (8.0%**) compared with the other two constructs.

Figure 6.6 displays the results, with single questions grouped by TAM dimensions and ranked by agreement rate.

Q1—*It was easy to read the models.* Most participants (19, or 76%) found the models easy to read, with nearly half agreeing (12) and over a quarter strongly agreeing (7). No respondents expressed disagreement, suggesting the models were generally accessible. However, 6 remained neutral (24%), leaving some room for further simplification.

Q2—*The models are NOT useful to understand the impacts of the digital solution (negatively worded).* A large majority (22, or 88%) disagreed (15) or strongly disagreed (7) that the models were not useful for understanding impacts, confirming that most participants found the models helpful, indicating high PU. Only a small minority were undecided (3, or 12%).

Q3—*I would recommend the use of models to represent the process transformation.* Most participants (17, or 68%) would recommend using the models, while almost a quarter (6, or 24%) were undecided. Only a small number expressed disagreement (2, or 8%).

Q4—*I would use the models in discussing aspects related to the digital solution with different stakeholders.* Similarly, a majority (17, or 68%) would use the models with stakeholders, with only 8% in disagreement and 24% undecided (6).

Q5—*The models help understand how the introduction of a digital solution can transform a process.* Most respondents (20, or 80%) agreed that the models help in understanding process transformation, with very few undecideds (16%) or disagreeing (4%).

Q6—*It was easy to interpret the process transformation.* A strong majority (17, or 68%) found it easy to interpret process transformation using the models, though almost a quarter were undecided (24%), and 2 disagreed (8%).

Q7—*The models have the potential to drive the analysis of costs and benefits.* More than half (14, or 56%) saw potential for the models to help with cost-benefit analysis, but almost a third were undecided (8, or 32%), and a minority disagreed (3, or 12%).

Q8—*Using the models would NOT bring benefits to assessing the impacts of digitalisation (negatively worded).* Most respondents (21, or 84%) rejected the idea that the models would not bring benefits, confirming positive perceptions of their value. Only 3 remained undecided (12%) and 1 completely agreed.

Q9—*I believe the models would NOT help my living lab in assessing the impacts of the digital solution. (negatively worded).* The majority (19, or 76%) disagreed (12) or strongly disagreed (7) with this negative statement, supporting the idea that the models are considered helpful. However, 5 remained undecided (20%) and 1 agreed (4%).

Q10—*The models are NOT easy to understand (negatively worded).* Most participants (20, or 80%) disagreed (44%) or strongly disagreed (36%) that the models are hard to understand, though a small group found them challenging (8%) and 12% was undecided.

6.3.5 Discussion

The survey results aim to complement the qualitative findings by showing how the two main components of the method, namely *data collection* in LLs and the *resulting models*, were perceived across the TAM dimensions. Overall, the results show a consistent pattern: the *data collection* procedure was recognised as useful, but was experienced as comparatively demanding and less readily reusable, whereas the *resulting models* were evaluated much more positively across all dimensions, including usefulness, understandability, and future intention to use. This contrast is relevant for clarifying both the contribution and the limits of the method.

Survey on data collection

For the data collection phase, participants appear willing to acknowledge the value of the procedure even when they do not experience it as especially easy or lightweight. In terms of TAM, PU clearly outweighs PEOU, with respondents largely recognised that the procedure helped them reflect on process transformation, especially in relation to understanding impacts and reasoning about transition steps. At the same time, the lower PEOU scores suggest that this value comes at a cognitive and practical cost. Reconstructing socio-technical processes, identifying actors, resources, and activities, comparing the situation before and after digitalisation, and involving stakeholders in a participatory elicitation process required time and effort. This is reflected in the mixed answers to questions on ease, recall, and adaptation.

This is further confirmed by more cautious results on ITU for the data collection procedure. The relatively large share of neutral answers suggests that respondents did not reject the procedure, but were uncertain about whether they would adopt it again autonomously in future contexts. This hesitation can reasonably be interpreted as linked to the effort required to apply the procedure and the contextual nature of LL work.

At the same time, the item-level results suggest a more nuanced picture. Some activities were perceived as especially effortful, such as thinking about actors, resources, and activities (Q3), while others were positively appreciated for their reflective value, in particular the question on the transition (Q6). Overall, this indicates that the procedure was able to elicit meaningful information, even though applying it still requires effort. This effort appears to be partly inherent to elicitation itself, as RE literature describes it as a complex activity shaped by tacit knowledge, stakeholder communication, and socio-technical complexity [72, 240]

Survey on models

The survey on the models presents a more homogeneous pattern. Here, all three TAM dimensions are positive, with especially high scores for usefulness and understandability. This suggests that once the knowledge elicited in the data collection phase is transformed into external representations, stakeholders perceive clear benefits.

Specifically, the models are perceived as useful (PU), helping participants understand the impact of digital solutions, interpret process transformation, and support discussion with different stakeholders. This is particularly significant in the context of LLs, where knowledge is distributed across actors with different backgrounds and roles.

The positive evaluation for PEOU on the models suggests that the representational choices adopted in the method were largely successful in making the models understandable to participants without a specific RE expertise. This supports the argument that, with appropriate simplifications and facilitation, semi-formal models can serve as effective boundary objects in socio-technical analysis.

The intention to use (ITU) results for the models are positive as well, although slightly less strong than PU and PEOU. This gap suggests that appreciating the value and readability of models does not automatically translate into a firm commitment to future use. Future adoption likely depends on contextual conditions, such as whether stakeholders have time and concrete occasions to reuse the representations in their own practice. In this sense, intention to use may remain the most demanding dimension, because it

reflects not only immediate perceptions of the artefact but also expectations about long-term integration into work routines.

Furthermore, the survey on the models also provides a triangulation of the qualitative evidence collected through the focus groups (cf. Sec. 6.3.1). The TAM results converge with the qualitative findings in several respects: PU emerged in participants' appreciation of the models as supports for understanding, reflection, and communication; PEOU was reflected in the perceived readability of the representations, especially when supported by simplifications and guidance; and ITU was consistent with the more cautious but still positive orientation expressed in the discussions, where participants recognised the value of the models but also stressed the importance of context, audience, and facilitation for their continued use.

Findings on the overall method

Taken together, the two surveys support a general interpretation of the method. The greatest friction appears in the elicitation process, while the greatest perceived value emerges in the resulting models. This suggests that the method is successful in producing outputs that stakeholders appreciate, even if the process of arriving at those outputs required considerable effort. Notably, the more positive evaluation was associated with the models, that is, the final outputs with which stakeholders mainly engaged as interpreters rather than as direct producers. By contrast, the data collection phase, in which stakeholders were more directly involved in coordinating, recalling, and structuring information, was perceived as more demanding. This pattern further reinforces the interpretation that modelling is inherently effortful, particularly in its upstream elicitation and formalisation phases, even when its results are ultimately seen as valuable and usable.

6.3.6 Answer to RQ2.4: *To what extent do living lab stakeholders accept PoMeLO after the application of the method to their own living lab?*

Results from the TAM surveys indicate a differentiated level of acceptance of PoMeLO by LL stakeholders who applied the method to their own specific case. Acceptance was assessed by examining two complementary artefacts: the data collection procedure and the set of models. Across these two artefacts, acceptance emerged as stronger for the models than for the data collection procedure itself. This suggests that stakeholders clearly recognised the value of the method overall, while also experiencing some parts of its application as more demanding.

In terms of PU, the method was generally well accepted across both the artefacts. The data collection procedure was already perceived as valuable, but usefulness emerged even more strongly for the resulting models. This confirms that the method was successful in producing representations perceived as relevant for LLs.

Regarding PEOU, acceptance was more uneven. The data collection procedure emerged as the weakest dimension, pointing to the effort required to elicit and structure the process-related information. By contrast, the models were rated positively in terms of ease of use. This suggests that, although the elicitation phase required time and effort

and this may have affected the PEOU dimension, the formalised outputs were generally perceived as accessible and usable once produced.

Finally, ITU was positive overall but more cautious than usefulness, especially for the data collection phase. For the procedure, many neutral responses suggest hesitation about reusing it autonomously in future contexts, likely because of the effort and adaptation required. For the models, ITU was clearly more positive, showing that stakeholders would be more willing to recommend them and use them in discussions with others. Overall, the method can therefore be considered accepted to a good extent, particularly in terms of usefulness and in relation to the models, while its main limitation concerns the ease and practical sustainability of the data collection procedure.

6.4 Conclusions

In this final section, we discuss the threats to validity and draw conclusions on RQ₂ (*How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations?*), highlighting the research implications emerging from this iteration. These implications motivate further cycles of the design science research.

6.4.1 Threats to Validity

This section discusses the main threats to validity of the evaluation based on the focus groups and the two post-session surveys, organised into construct, internal, and external validity.

Construct validity The evaluation of acceptance was framed through the TAM dimensions of PEOU, PU, and ITU. These concepts were not formally defined to participants, which could have led to some misunderstandings. Overall, the responses suggest a sufficiently coherent understanding of the constructs, which limits this threat. Regarding PEOU, in this study, it was mainly framed as *understandability*, that is, the ease with which participants could read the models and identify relevant elements and relations. To mitigate this threat, during the focus groups we explicitly asked participants both to interpret the models and to report their perceptions, thereby grounding their judgments in an actual exercise of identification and explanation.

Internal validity Several threats concern the way the data were collected and analysed. First, the focus groups were conducted by members of the research team who had also designed the method and produced the models. This may have introduced a Hawthorne effect, with participants being more inclined to provide favourable feedback. We mitigated this by explicitly inviting participants to discuss limitations and difficulties, and indeed critical remarks emerged across both focus groups and surveys. Second, the evaluation took place after an iterative collaboration with the LLs in the action research, so perceptions of the method may have been influenced not only by the representations themselves, but also by the broader interaction with the researchers. Third, the thematic analysis of the focus groups is inherently interpretive. Moreover, the coding process was supported by AI, which may have introduced additional bias in the interpretation and classification of excerpts. To mitigate this threat, AI was used only to

support the initial coding, while the author of the thesis revised and homogenised the codes. To reduce subjectivity, coding was structured through a predefined TAM-based analytical frame, refined iteratively, and reviewed by the supervisors. Finally, survey results are based on self-reported perceptions and a limited number of respondents, which may affect reliability.

External validity The study was conducted within 18 agricultural LLs of the CODECS project, covering heterogeneous countries, technologies, and agri-food contexts. This variety strengthens the relevance of the findings within the agricultural LL setting. However, the results cannot be generalised statistically to all participatory settings or all modelling approaches. Rather, following case-based generalisability [228], we argue that the findings are transferable to contexts that are similar to ours: multi-stakeholder agricultural innovation settings in which semi-formal representations are introduced to support reflection on socio-technical process transformation.

6.4.2 Summary

This chapter has provided insights from the implementation and evaluation of PoMeLO within 19 CODECS LLs.

The application of the RE method indicated that the proposed method is adaptable to diverse contexts and varying levels of technological maturity, confirming its flexibility within heterogeneous LL contexts. The focus groups conducted with the LLs consolidated the ecological validity of the insights obtained in the previous iteration (cf. Ch. 5), while also contributing further knowledge on stakeholders' experience of interacting with semi-formal notations.

Results from the focus groups and the TAM survey on the models confirmed the overall acceptance of the method, especially showing that LL stakeholders clearly recognised the usefulness of the models. At the same time, some results of the TAM surveys appeared comparatively weaker—most notably those related to the data collection procedure—and recurring feedback pointed to the perceived complexity of certain aspects of the notations. These findings suggest that modelling requirements at this level of detail may still benefit from the presence of expert modellers. This is also coherent with the intended use of the method, that is to combine the technical rigour of MoDRE with domain experts' situated knowledge, in order to elicit requirements that are comprehensive and actionable for analysis and subsequent system development. In this sense, the method proves effective; however, its autonomous adoption by LLs may require additional support mechanisms.

At the time of writing, the work within the CODECS project is still ongoing, with current activities focusing on the use of the models for cross-case comparison and as a support for cost–benefit analysis. This continued application further indicates the practical value and transferability of the artefact beyond isolated case studies.

The feedback from the focus groups confirmed the main insights already emerging from RQ1 (cf. Ch. 4), that is, with the proposed RE method, the semi-formal models can be both understandable and useful in the LL contexts. Their evaluation across the 18 CODECS LLs made it possible to consolidate the preliminary feedback obtained in the earlier validation and to extend the analysis by identifying the themes that recurred

most consistently across cases.

Overall, participants considered the models understandable, although some difficulties emerged, especially when dealing with more abstract semantics and denser visual structures. At the same time, important limitations emerged, as PU and ITU depended strongly on the audience, the level of abstraction, and the availability of guidance or facilitation, suggesting that these dimensions are closely intertwined with PEOU. This finding is consistent with prior research grounded in Moody's Method Evaluation Model (MEM), which positions ITU as being influenced indirectly by PEOU and PU [154]. In practice, this indicates that the models are promising boundary objects for analysis and discussion in LLs, but their broader adoption requires simplification, adaptation to stakeholder profiles, and a careful balance between expressive richness and interpretive effort.

Implications for AI Support Beyond the application of the method within the specific context of the CODECS LLs, these findings provide initial motivation for further work in requirements modelling. Specifically, we build on an insight emerging from the method application: the modelling activity can be demanding and often benefits from expert facilitation. Yet, technical profiles are not consistently available in LLs, which, unlike companies, operate with less clearly defined and more fluid roles [121]. As a result, coordination can be ensured by figures who do not necessarily have specialised IT competencies.

To address this challenge, a low-floor–high-ceiling approach—implemented through a dedicated EUD-oriented strategy—could help extend MoDRE-based practices within LLs. Such an approach should pursue three complementary goals: (i) lowering operational barriers of requirements elicitation and modelling, (ii) supporting more autonomous modelling practices, and (iii) reducing dependence on specialised RE expertise, while still enabling a gradual transition towards advanced RE practices when needed.

Within this context, the solution proposed in this design science project is a modelling tool dedicated to novice users, supported by AI-based functionalities to facilitate key modelling tasks. We argue that such a tool could help mitigate some of the limitations that emerged in the data collection procedure, particularly the effort required for elicitation and reporting. By supporting the elicitation phase directly, the tool could reduce the burden of text-based data collection and provide immediate feedback on the representations.

We remark that this entry-level tool is not intended to *replace* the method; rather, it aims to *enrich* it and increase its adoption. The overarching objective is to make requirements modelling feasible in settings where RE experts are not fully available, or they need support of domain experts to achieve a full understanding of the application domain and its requirements, or domain experts cannot commit sufficient time to learn modelling notations and conventional tools. This can be pursued by offering multiple pathways through which stakeholders can appropriate requirements modelling practices and progressively engage with more advanced techniques.

■ RQ2 recap

This chapter and the previous one addressed RQ2: *How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations?* The experience of applying PoMeLO for model creation and interpretation in several real-world contexts suggested that requirements modelling is feasible also for domain experts and that this process can lead to representations that are understandable and useful for gaining an understanding of digital transformation in agricultural LLs.

At the same time, stakeholders highlighted two aspects as crucial for the future adoption of the method. First, representations need to be tailored to different contexts and audiences, and appropriately facilitated. Second, the practice of model creation itself should be simplified through more user-friendly approaches and tools, so as to reduce the effort required for requirements elicitation and modelling.

Part III

ModeLLer: an AI-infused Tool to Assist Novice Modellers

Chapter 7

Overview of Part III

Figure 7.1: Overview of thesis chapters and their relation to RQs and design science iterations, highlighting the portion addressed in Part III.

This part addresses RQ₃ and RQ₄, which relate to the third and fourth iterations of the design science research and led to the creation of the second artefact: *ModeLLer*, the EUD modelling tool (cf. Figure 7.1).

7.1 Summary of Research Gaps

The design and implementation of the RE method addressed in the first two iterations of this design science research (cf. Part II) have contributed evidence on the use of MoDRE in living lab (LL) contexts.

The empirical findings suggest that, to advance the uptake of requirements modelling in real-world participatory settings, additional enabling support may be needed to facilitate model creation. In this respect, although our investigation primarily involved non-expert modellers and was conducted in LL contexts, many of the observed insights are consistent with findings from prior modelling research, which, in contrast, has mainly focused on industrial settings and professional modellers [10, 126, 163, 193, 220]. Indeed, prior research has identified recurring challenges, particularly related to tool usability and notation-specific issues [10, 126, 152, 193]. These challenges may constitute entry barriers for end users and early-stage modellers [144, 193, 232] (cf. Sec. 2.2.2).

From an end-user perspective, EUD makes extensive use of the model-based paradigm to support end users in the specification and adaptation of computational artefacts [23], including in agricultural contexts [170] (cf. Sec. 2.3.1). At the same time, EUD proposes refined evaluation approaches that attend both to tool characteristics and to the actual computational thinking skills (CT) of end users [22, 40] (cf. Sec. 2.2.3). However, these contributions have mainly focused on leveraging models for software development, such as in low-code platforms (cf. Sec. 2.3.2), while comparatively little attention has been devoted to the development of dedicated EUD tools for requirements modelling.

Furthermore, a growing body of work investigates AI-enhanced modelling solutions, including automated modelling [234], intelligent assistants [163], and modelling-specific recommender systems [14] (cf. Sec. 2.2.4). Alongside these technical developments, recent research has raised concerns about fully automated approaches to RE [9] and has advocated HCAI perspectives [15]. Yet these perspectives are fragmented and have rarely been applied to the support of novice modellers in real-world contexts.

■ From these challenges, we derive two research gaps:

1. Existing tool support to requirements modelling is developed primarily for industrial or educational settings, leaving the support of novice and non-technical modellers underexplored;
2. AI-based solutions to modelling remain fragmented and technique-driven, and there is an incomplete understanding of the assistance needs of novice modellers from an empirical perspective.

7.2 Research Questions

The gaps outlined above lead to the two research questions presented in this section, which are operationalised through multiple sub-questions. Figure 7.2 summarises the overall design and validation, mapping sub-questions to the corresponding evaluation study. The elements of the figure are referred to in the following paragraphs.

Figure 7.2: Visual summary of Part III - ModeLLer, addressing RQ3 *What functionalities should a modelling tool for novices provide to support the computational thinking skills involved in modelling?* and RQ4 *How do domain experts experience requirements modelling with a block-based AI-infused tool?*, with sub-questions mapped to the corresponding evaluation studies.

7.2.1 RQ3: How can we empower novice and non-technical stakeholders in requirements modelling?

In line with design science, this research question is framed as a *design problem*, as it concerns the development of an artefact to support novices in requirements modelling.

We address this question by bridging insights from EUD and modelling literature and applying a Seeding Evolutionary Growth Re seeding (SER) iterative method grounded in meta-design (cf. 2.2.3) to design a new artefact: *ModeLLer*, an AI-infused, web-based modelling tool featuring a block-based editor. The question is articulated into four sub-questions that inform the iterative design of the tool:

- RQ3.1: How easy is it for a user to model requirements with the ModeLLer prototype?
- RQ3.2: Does an artefact-based assessment of ModeLLer reveal insights into computational thinking skills?
- RQ3.3: Do users' computational thinking profiles influence their perceived workload when modelling requirements with ModeLLer?
- RQ3.4: To what extent can interaction log analysis inform the design of intelligent suggestions mechanisms aimed at supporting users' computational thinking skills while using ModeLLer?

To answer RQ3.1, we preliminary evaluated a **prototype** of the tool through a **cognitive walkthrough** with experts. The evaluation confirmed that a block-based approach is feasible and provided insights for redesigning the tool.

Chapter 8 introduces ModelLer and provides an answer to RQ3.1. For clarity, the chapter describes the final version of the tool, including the AI-based functionalities, while acknowledging that its development was iterative and progressively informed by the evaluation studies.

To address RQ3.2 to RQ3.4, we developed the first stable version of the tool (**Tool v1**), which includes additional functionalities and initial support for AI assistance. This, in turn, enabled us to conduct a **user study** involving 36 participants, including 6 experts in HCI and RE and 30 end users, who performed a modelling task using the tool. We framed the study within the CT framework of Brennan and Resnick (cf. Sec. 2.2.3) to obtain a nuanced assessment of the tool in relation to users' modelling capabilities.

To answer RQ3.2, we combined three dimensions of evaluation: an assessment of the tool provided by EUD experts, a self-assessment of CT skill levels by participants, and the artefacts produced with the tool.

To answer RQ3.3, we investigated whether users' CT profiles relate to perceived workload during requirements modelling with ModelLer.

To answer RQ3.4, we analysed interaction logs and observed behaviours, relating them to users' CT profiles to derive insights into the use and potential value of the AI-assisted features.

Chapter 9 provides an answer to RQ3.2, RQ3.3 and RQ3.4 and concludes on RQ3.

7.2.2 RQ4: How do domain experts experience requirements modelling with a block-based AI-infused tool?

In line with Wieringa's methodology, RQ4 is framed as a *knowledge question*, focusing on the empirical investigation of users' experience with the proposed artefact.

This question is articulated in three sub-questions:

- RQ4.1: To what extent can large language models perform model-to-text transformation?
- RQ4.2: To what extent do users follow the suggestions provided by the system?
- RQ4.3: How do the agronomists perceive the AI-based assistance offered by ModelLer?

To answer RQ4.1, we first conducted a **technical evaluation** of LLM capabilities for model-to-text transformation prior to including these functionalities within the tool.

Given the positive outcome, we extended the tool with AI-based functionalities designed in line with HCAI principles [15] and CT frameworks [181] (**AI-infused Tool v2**). Specifically, we integrated LLM-based features, including a component for model-to-text transformation, and extended the tool support for intelligent assistance.

To answer RQ4.2, we conducted a study with agronomists who performed a task with the tool, while a **Wizard of Oz** protocol was used to simulate system suggestions.

To answer RQ4.3, we carried out post-test interviews with the agronomists to further elicit and clarify their assistance needs.

Chapter 10 provides an answer to RQ4.1 to RQ4.3 and concludes on RQ4.

Chapter 8

Design and Key Functionalities of ModeLLer

This chapter is based on two papers: i) “Designing Adaptive AI Assistance for Block-Based Modelling: A Wizard of Oz Study with Domain Experts”, Mannari C., Turchi T., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Conati C., Malizia A. In Proceedings of the 2026 International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces (AVI ’26) (2026) [AVI26] [142], ii) “ModeLLer – Enabling end-users to model systems: a case study in digital agriculture”, Mannari C., Anichini E., Bacco M., Ferrari A., Turchi T., Malizia A. Proceedings of the International Workshop on Cultures of Participation in the Digital Age, co-located with AVI 2024 [COPDA24] [134].

8.1 Overview

This chapter introduces the third design science iteration, motivated by the outcomes of the application and evaluation of the method reported in Part II. Specifically, the empirical findings indicate that additional support may be necessary to facilitate requirements modelling in real-world participatory settings. Based on insights from the literature, we found that RE methods have commonly been accompanied by dedicated tool support [159, 186] and that, more broadly, modelling tools have been widely investigated in the literature [220]. However, existing requirements modelling tools are primarily oriented towards industrial and professional modellers, while support for novice and non-technical users remains comparatively underexplored (cf. Ch. 7).

To address this challenge, the chapter investigates RQ3: *How can we empower novice and non-technical stakeholders in requirements modelling?*

This question motivated the design of a new artefact, *ModeLLer*: an AI-infused, web-based modelling tool that features a block-based editor. To guide the iterative design of the tool, we have broken this question down into several sub-questions (cf. Ch. 7). This chapter addresses the following:

- RQ3.1: How easy is it for a user to model requirements with the ModeLLer prototype?

To answer RQ3.1, we developed a **prototype** of the tool, and we evaluated it through a **cognitive walkthrough** with experts. The evaluation confirmed that a block-based

approach is feasible and provided insights for redesigning certain features of the tool.

This chapter is divided into two parts. The first part, Design (cf. Sec. 8.2.2), describes the final version of the AI-infused modelling tool, while acknowledging that its development was iterative and progressively informed by the evaluation studies. The second part, Cognitive Walkthrough (cf. Sec. 8.3), addresses RQ3.1. The following chapter will address the remaining sub-questions, complementing RQ3.

■ Compared to prior requirements modelling tools, ModeLLer: 1) draws on EUD principles through a block-based approach that reduces the notational burden on users, 2) is delivered as a web-based tool requiring no installation, 3) supports multiple modelling notations, 4) incorporates a domain-specific language to support requirements elicitation, and 5) is AI-infused in line with a HCAI perspective.

8.1.1 Methodology

This section is structured into two parts: the methodology adopted for the design of the tool and the methodology used for the prototype validation.

Tool Design

In designing the tool, we combined methodological approaches from EUD and HCAI. First, we adopted meta-design [77]—specifically drawing on the SER methodology (cf. Section 2.2.3)—that frames design as an ongoing, participatory process in which users can appropriate, extend, and evolve the system over time.

Second, to inform the tool, we leveraged computational thinking (CT) frameworks. Specifically, the design was grounded in Repenning’s AAA model [181], which provided a conceptual foundation for the design of our system within a three-stage CT process (cf. Section 2.2.3).

Third, for the AI-assisted features, we followed HCAI practices [15], treating AI as an augmentative component within an AI-infused system and prioritising transparency, user control, and opportunities for users to inspect, verify, and refine outputs. Specifically, we opted for components to support users’ cognitive activities without replacing their role in shaping the model.

During the design process, a formal requirements document was created. This document is available in Annex 11 [130].

Validation

Fig. 8.1) outlines the activities carried out to address RQ3.1, *How easy is it for a user to model requirements with the ModeLLer prototype?*. Specifically, a prototype version was designed and initially evaluated through a cognitive walkthrough with RE and HCI experts [128].

Cognitive walkthrough evaluations allow for a preliminary assessment of learnability and usability from the user’s point of view. The evaluation was conducted as a workshop, where a group of expert evaluators collectively stepped through a predefined task sequence from a novice user’s perspective, discussed each action, and assessed learnability using the four standard walkthrough questions: (1) Will users try to achieve the

Figure 8.1: Visual summary of tool design and validation iterations, highlighting the portion that addresses: RQ3.1 *How easy is it for a user to model requirements with the ModeLLer prototype?*

right result? (2) Will users notice that the correct action is available? (3) Will users associate the correct action with the result they’re trying to achieve? (4) After the action is performed, will users see that progress is made toward the goal? [164].

8.2 Design

The main objective of ModeLLer is to enable users with no expertise in semi-formal notations to create standard diagrams. The main idea behind the tool is to minimise notational burden while preserving the interaction with the semi-formal notations.

Therefore, a primary design choice is to support model creation through a block-based editor. The rationale behind this choice is that block-based environments have been extensively used in programming education and have proven effective in supporting learning, reducing syntactic errors, and fostering engagement among novices [225].

The tool is accessible online as an open-source application¹, and the project repository on GitHub² also includes a short demo video illustrating the main functionalities.

8.2.1 System Architecture

Figure 8.2 provides an overview of the web-based architecture of the tool, organised into a front-end and a back-end. In the **front-end**, the **user interface** (on the left of Fig. 8.2) follows a component-based architecture implemented through **Golden Layout** [87], a

¹The tool can be accessed at: <https://unipisa.github.io/blockly-modeller/>, last visited 19 March 2026

²The repository can be accessed at: <https://github.com/Unipisa/blockly-UML-modeller>, last visited 19 March 2026

JavaScript multi-screen layout manager for webapps. Within this, the **workspace** supports user interaction and includes *Blockly* [89], a JavaScript library for block-based programming, and two AI-based custom-developed components, namely **contextual hints** and **textual instructions** (described in Sec. 8.2.3). The workspace is connected to the **front-end services** (at the center of Fig. 8.2), whose **code-to-diagram** component transforms the created block structures into semi-formal model specifications, which are then passed to the **rendering libraries** to generate the corresponding diagrams. These services rely on the JavaScript libraries **bpmn-js** [36], for rendering BPMN diagram, and **piStar** [175], to visualise the iStar diagram. An **export and download** service is also provided to save the generated artefacts. Specifically, **JSON** is used to export the Blockly workspace and the iStar diagram, **XMI** to export the UML, and **XML** to export the **BPMN**. This pipeline also generates the **output models** returned in the user interface, namely **UML**, **BPMN**, and **iStar**, together with the AI-based **diagram reader**.

In the **back-end**, an infrastructure deployed on **Render** [180] (at the bottom right of Fig. 8.2) hosts supporting services such as **PlantUML** render server [176] and manages the access to the **Groq API** [92]. **Groq** (on the top right of Fig. 8.2) provides access to an **LLM** (i.e., openai/gpt-oss-20b model), which receives three prompts including **prompt hints**, **prompt instructions**, and the **prompt diagram reader** (described in Sec. 8.2.3). These functions return AI-generated support to the front-end. The **Better Stack** telemetry service [30] collects **interaction logs** through the **log mechanism** embedded in the front-end services. These logs are aimed to support a future **recommender system** (RS), located in the machine learning area, aimed at generating adaptive suggestions based on user interactions (cf. Sec. 8.2.3).

8.2.2 Design and User Interface

The design of ModelLLer is grounded in Repenning’s AAA model. Within our tool, we operationalised the three CT stages as follows:

- *Abstraction*, a set of blocks, accessible through a toolbox panel, supporting users in identifying relevant domain concepts. In the context of digital agriculture, the core entities may be represented through actors, activities, natural resources, digital tools, etc.
- *Automation*, a jigsaw-based mechanism of dragging-and-dropping blocks on the workspace, enabling the users to arrange custom block structures under certain constraints.
- *Analysis*, through the simultaneous visualisation of output diagrams, enabling users to inspect, interpret, and assess the resulting models.

Fig. 8.3 presents the tool interface, which is organised into two main areas. The *Input area*, located on the left, contains the workspace featuring the block-based visual editor, while the *Output area*, on the right, displays the diagrams generated in real time based on the block structures created by the user. These block structures are simultaneously transformed into different diagrams.

Figure 8.2: Web architecture of the tool. The front-end comprises the user interface including a Blockly-based workspace, output models and AI support, as well as code-to-diagram services and rendering libraries to generate the diagrams. The back-end comprises the services supporting AI-based assistance and a logging mechanism for the recommender system.

Block-based Visual Language

The block-based editor provides a toolbox to explore and select blocks, and a workspace where they can be assembled through a guided, prompt-driven procedure.

Although Blockly provides a set of pre-defined blocks, these are generic and primarily intended for programming tasks. Therefore, custom blocks were created, as illustrated in Fig. 8.4, to provide users with a DSL language [113] tailored to the digital agriculture context. The DSL introduces modelling constructs that reflect key entities of socio-technical farming systems, including *Actor*, *Activity*, *Digital Tool*, *Digital Component*, *Tool*, and *Natural Resource*. Each block encapsulates semantically meaningful properties (e.g., attributes, activities, motivations, aggregation, specialisation) and guides users through structured fields and predefined relationships.

The language is conceptually grounded in the entities of the Ostrom framework [147] adopted in CODECS living labs (LLs) (cf. 1.1.3), which informs the representation of actors, resources, and interactions within collective action settings.

Block labels are enhanced with colours and icons to maximise affordance, leveraging the principles of dual coding to support more intuitive recognition and understanding [152].

Figure 8.3: Modeler interface, organised into two main areas: the *Input area* (on the left) with the block-based editor and the *Output area* (on the right), where UML, BPMN, and iStar diagrams are generated in real time from the user-defined block structures. Download buttons allow exporting the workspace and generated diagrams in various formats. The interface consists of multiple rearrangeable windows, allowing for the isolation of a single modelling language.

Models Generation and Export

All blocks dropped onto the workspace are simultaneously translated into UML, BPMN, and iStar code. These notations were selected in line with the method described in Part II, as they provide complementary perspectives capturing domain (UML), processes (BPMN), and goals (iStar). Output diagrams are automatically generated through a client-side rendering pipeline (cf. Sec.8.2.1).

The editor includes import and export buttons to support model reuse and interoperability. The output components (on the right) allow users to download export files in various formats, including source formats, i.e., XMI, XML and JSON, as well as vectors and raster images of the diagram. These files can be imported into other modelling software that supports the notations and edited in future sessions, ensuring continuity and compatibility across tools. The block-based editor allows users to export and import the workspace file in JSON for future sessions within the tool.

As outlined in Fig. 8.3, the creation of a model starts following the questions contained on the preset blocks appearing on the initial setup of the workspace. The preset blocks contain labels with basic questions aiming at eliciting the UML classes. The initial questions are: 1. *Who are the actors involved in the process?* and 2. *Which are the resources?* Exploring the toolbox based on the categorisation provided (i.e. actors, activities, natural resources, tools, digital tools etc.), the user can select a block.

Figure 8.4: Blocks available in ModeLLer, corresponding to the visual language for modelling digital agriculture.

Blocks can be added to the workspace through drag and drop. Once an actor block is added to the workspace, the user is asked a new question: 3. *What are the activities carried out by the actor?* The user is asked to provide information on activities performed following this pattern: an \langle actor \rangle performs an \langle activity \rangle using \langle resource \rangle to \langle motivation \rangle .

Component-based Layout

The component-based interface layout allows users to rearrange the workspace and output areas. In the initial setup, the editor is positioned on the left and the output components on the right.

The layout is single-page, featuring several resizable and rearrangeable windows. This modular structure allows users to adapt the view according to their modelling needs and makes it easy to manage future extension of the tool, such as adding new domain-specific block sets, enabling or disabling output languages, and including new layout components for modelling support.

Future versions may broaden coverage beyond agriculture, enabling reuse across other socio-technical contexts.

8.2.3 AI-based Functionalities

We grounded the design of the AI-based support in Repenning’s AAA model (cf. 8.2.2). In integrating specific AI-based functionalities, we introduced four components, each supporting a specific stage while preserving user control:

Contextual Hints (Abstraction stage) A component with a call-to-action for asking suggestions for model extension based on the current state of the model. An LLM receives as input a piece of code generated by the tool, e.g., a PlantUML describing a class diagram, and returns a message with suggestions for extension (Fig. 8.5a).

Textual Instructions (Automation stage) A natural-language input field enables users to build or edit models by providing instructions in plain text. The input text is interpreted by an LLM and translated into corresponding *create*, *delete*, and *edit* operations, which are executed through the API of the block-based modelling language to update the view accordingly (Fig. 8.5b).

Diagram Reader (Analysis stage) An LLM performs a model-to-text transformation of the underlying code at each update of the workspace. The resulting textual description presents the generated models in non-technical terms, supporting users in reflecting on whether the resulting representation aligns with their intended meaning and domain knowledge (Fig. 8.5c).

Pop-up Notifications (All stages) An RS assists the modellers by providing notifications aligned with each stage of the CT process, based on the actions performed. The system relies on a client-side logging mechanism and a server component that collects and processes interaction data during modelling sessions. These data are used to trigger rule-based, context-sensitive pop-up messages, enabling recommender behaviour during user sessions.

(a) Contextual Hints

(b) Textual Instructions

(c) Diagram Reader

Figure 8.5: AI-based functionalities integrated in the tool: (a) Contextual Hints provide suggestions for model extension; (b) Textual Instructions enable natural-language model manipulation; (c) Diagram Reader generates non-technical descriptions of models.

8.2.4 User-AI Interaction Flows

Figure 8.6: User–AI interaction flows model mapped to system architecture. The blue path connected by solid lines represents an interaction that is entirely controlled by humans. In contrast, the dotted lines indicate potential human-AI interactions. The different colours—green, red, pink and orange—represent various AI-based functionalities.

The result of these integrations, depicted in Fig. 8.6, is an AI-infused system that enables users to selectively access AI-based support while retaining control over modelling actions.

Components architecture

Figure 8.6 presents AI-infused system, on the top of the architecture presented in Figure 8.2, highlighting the three stages of the CT process enriched with the AI functionalities.

On the left, the end user interacts with the **component-based interface** structured into three CT-aligned phases: Abstraction, Automation, and Analysis.

In the **Abstraction** phase, users explore blocks, supported by AI-generated contextual hints.

In the **Automation** phase, users construct the model within a drag-and-drop workspace, either manually manipulating blocks or optionally providing textual instructions. These instructions can be sent to generative AI to be converted into blocks, supporting partial automation of modelling actions.

In the **Analysis** phase, the resulting diagram is rendered, and an AI reader component supports user in interpreting the model.

At the centre, the **blocks-to-diagrams** module translates block-based specifications into code (e.g., UML/PlantUML, BPMN, iStar) and produces the visual model shown to the user.

On the right, **generative AI** provides three optional forms of assistance, accessed via dedicated prompts: (i) converting textual instructions into blocks, (ii) providing hints to extend or refine the diagram, and (iii) explaining the diagram to support interpretation and validation.

At the bottom, a telemetry component records **interaction logs** generated during modelling. These logs feed a RS, which analyses user behaviour and triggers pop-up notifications within the interface.

At the current stage, the RS is being developed on top of a logging infrastructure to provide targeted support to users while they perform modelling actions. The system includes a client-side logging mechanism and a remote server component that collects and processes interaction data during modelling sessions. These data are currently used to trigger rule-based, context-sensitive pop-up messages, enabling the simulation of recommender behaviour during user sessions (e.g., through a Wizard of Oz (WOz) setup).

Future developments will incorporate machine learning techniques to enable more adaptive and personalised recommendations. However, the design of such a RS requires a deeper understanding of the kind of support users need during interaction with the tool.

Interaction flows

Figure 8.6 also provides an overview of the User-AI interaction flows made possible by the tool. Interaction flows are represented through coloured connections: solid lines depict human-controlled actions, while AI-mediated interactions are shown as dashed flows. The blue path linked with solid lines represents an interaction that is 100% under human control, while the dotted lines present possible human-AI flows. The interaction starts from the *abstraction* stage, where the user explores the **Toolbox with blocks** (icon tractor), then moves to the *automation* stage, in which the user interacts with the **Drag-and-drop workspace** (icon puzzle) to assemble block structures. These structures are translated into the corresponding semi-formal diagrams according to transformation rules defined by the developers (grey circle with symbol \langle / \rangle within the *Blocks to diagrams* area at the centre of the diagram). Code is then visualised through **code-to-diagram** libraries (white rhombus) and returned to the user in the form of **diagram** within the *analysis* stage. The AI-based features are integrated at various stages of the CT process and provide optional interactions, resulting in a hybrid human-AI flow.

A mechanism of **contextual hints** is available within the **abstraction** stage (green dotted path). When the user presses the hint button, a prompt is sent to the LLM with the model code as input. The LLM then returns suggestions that can influence the user's decisions regarding block selection and composition. For example, a hint may suggest: *“Within your precision irrigation mechanism, add an actuator that enables irrigation to start automatically.”*

An input field for **textual instructions** is available within the **automation** stage (red dotted path). The user can enter a textual request, which is sent to the LLM. The LLM

interprets the instruction by translating it into blocks and compositions. A developer-defined control layer then converts this generated structure into corresponding portions of the Blockly workspace. These blocks are returned to the user, who can further inspect and modify them. For example, a request such as “Extend the model by adding a technical advisor” may result in the creation of a new actor block interacting with the farmer and providing a set of suggestions.

Within the *analysis* stage, a *reader* component is provided (pink dotted path). While the blocks are being composed, the component is triggered from the automation stage, sending a prompt to the LLM that asks for an explanation of the diagram in non-technical language. The component returns a natural-language description that accompanies the visual representation and may influence the user’s interpretation of the model.

Finally, based on the interaction logs recorded by the system (within the telemetry component), a **recommender system** component is envisaged to provide targeted suggestions across all stages (orange dotted path). In the study, this functionality was not yet fully implemented and was instead simulated through a Woz setup serving suggestions in the form of **pop-up notifications**.

Multiple sequences of interactions collectively constitute the enacted modelling process, giving rise to different patterns of Human-AI interaction. These patterns will be examined in greater detail in Chapter 10.

8.3 Cognitive Walkthrough (RQ3.1)

Figure 8.7: Structure of the ModelLer prototype

This section introduces the validation of the tool by presenting the first evaluation study, in which a prototype was assessed through an expert-led cognitive walkthrough.

Figure 8.7 shows the state of the tool at the time of validation. The ModelLer prototype already included a block-based visual editor and supported the creation of domain models, specifically UML class diagrams. It also allowed for the export of the resulting structure as an XMI file, which could be imported into UML design software³. Among

³ModelLer Prototype: https://unipisa.github.io/blockly-modeller/demo_v1

the three types of models proposed by the method, namely UML, iStar, and BPMN (cf. Ch. 4), UML was chosen because it represents the most prominent modelling notation in the research baseline [43] and because domain models constituted the most representative starting point for stakeholder involvement in requirements definition, as also observed in prior work [37].

8.3.1 Workshop

A remote workshop (cf. Sec. 8.1.1) was carried out with cross-functional evaluators to identify aspects of the interface that could be difficult for users. The evaluators, three males and a female, aged between 35 and 45, are experts in the following areas: formal languages; visual languages; web design; agricultural technology. Guided by a facilitator, the review team walked through four main actions enabled by the modelling tool and answered a set of predetermined questions. The facilitator shared the screen and demonstrated the relevant functionalities to the group. For each action, the experts engaged in a brief discussion and agreed on a common answer before moving on. Table 8.1 summarises the actions analysed and the consensus answers provided by the experts for each question.

ACTION 1: Identifying blocks in toolbox The first action analysed by the group of experts was the *identification of blocks* within the toolbox. Overall, the experts agreed that “Finding blocks is simple and intuitive. The menu divided into different categories guides the user towards the identification of the blocks”. By clicking on the label of the chosen category, the system responds by opening a panel containing the blocks of the selected category. In this way, the user receives clear feedback to have performed the correct action.

ACTION 2: Construction of the model in workspace The second action analysed by the experts was the *graphic construction of the model*, i.e. dragging the blocks into the workspace and fitting them together. Also for this action, the review team has expressed itself overall positively. The presence of a fixed block in the work area, containing the phrases *Insert actors* and *Insert resources* with space underneath for inserting something,

Table 8.1: Results from the cognitive walkthrough evaluation of ModeLLer prototype

EVALUATION	Will users try to achieve the right result?	Will users notice that the correct action is available?	Will users associate the correct action with the result they're trying to achieve?	After the action is performed, will users see that progress is made toward the goal?
ACTION 1: Identifying blocks in toolbox	Yes, from experience	Yes, from experience	Yes, a prompt or label matches action	Yes, there is connection between user goal and system response
ACTION 2: Construction of the model in workspace	Yes, from experience	Yes, they would see a call-to-action	Yes, a prompt or label matches action	Yes, there is connection between user goal and system response
ACTION 3: Creation of advanced structures	No	Yes, they would see a call-to-action	Yes, a prompt or label matches action	Yes, there is connection between user goal and system response
ACTION 4: Export	Yes, the system tells them to	Yes, they would see a call-to-action	Yes, a prompt or label matches action	Yes, there is connection between user goal and system response

prompts the user to insert other blocks. The fact that the words *Actors* and *Resources* are also the names of the two main categories, guides the user to open these categories in the toolbox. Once a category is opened, hovering over a block will cause the block border to glow yellow and the cursor to a hand ready to select, move and release. With this in mind, the group agreed that “It is obvious to the user that the block editor has a drag-and-drop mechanism, and the interlocking on the blocks, similar to that of the pieces of a puzzle, acts as a sort of visual call-to-action”.

ACTION 3: Creation of advanced structures The third activity analysed by the evaluators concerned the *creation of advanced structures*. This may correspond to a generalisation, an aggregation, or an association between two classes; the latter case was examined during the workshop. In the prototype, as well as in traditional UML design software, in order to obtain an association between two classes, both class blocks to be connected must exist. The perplexities of the group of experts during the workshop concerned the insertion of the class name in a text field appearing under the label *Using resource or interacting with actor* of the Custom activity block. The team agreed that “This action requires too much cognitive effort for the user to achieve the right result”. The group thought about alternative solutions. This activity was the subject of a redesign which will be illustrated in the next section.

ACTION 4: Export The last action considered for the evaluation of the prototype during the workshop was the *export of the XMI file* and textual report. For the action analysed in this step, the group was unanimously positive: “The two download buttons are standard and easily visible, and give the idea of being clickable, as their labels make it immediately clear what action will be performed”. When one of the two buttons is clicked, the system responds by starting the download of the chosen file. Opening the start download window in the browser and its progress allows the user to understand that the action was performed correctly and is achieving its goal.

8.3.2 Redesign

The feedback collected during the cognitive walkthrough workshop helped us to redesign critical emerging components. The main change was related to the third action, *creation of advanced structures* which was the only one activity evaluated negatively by the experts. The solution identified consisted of replacing the text field with a selector. During the creation of an association between two classes, it is now possible for the user to choose the class to be associated from a list containing the already existing classes, instead of manually typing the name of the desired class. This contributes to suggesting possible relations without seeking the element name in the diagram while limiting the user’s errors.

8.3.3 Answer to RQ3.1: *How easy is it for a user to model requirements with the ModeLLer prototype?*

The cognitive walkthrough results indicate that users are expected to create basic domain models with the ModeLLer prototype with limited difficulty. Experts judged the

core actions—identifying blocks in the toolbox, constructing models in the workspace, and exporting outputs—as intuitive and well supported by clear prompts, visible call-to-actions, and immediate system feedback confirming progress toward the modelling goal. The only critical usability barrier concerned the creation of advanced structures (e.g., associations), which required excessive cognitive effort due to manual text entry. This issue was addressed in the subsequent redesign cycle by replacing the text field with a selector listing existing classes, thereby reducing cognitive load and limiting user errors.

8.4 Conclusions

In this final section, we discuss the threats to validity and draw conclusions on the cognitive walkthrough, highlighting the research implications emerging from this evaluation. These implications inform subsequent improvement of the tool and motivate further cycles of the design science research.

8.4.1 Threats to Validity

This section discusses issues of the validity of this study, divided into construct validity, internal validity and external validity.

Construct validity The cognitive walkthrough assesses anticipated ease of use based on expert judgement, not actual end-user performance. As a result, RQ3.1 is measured indirectly through learnability heuristics (e.g., visibility of actions, goal–action mapping) rather than through behavioural indicators such as task success rate, errors, or completion time. In addition, focusing on four predefined actions may overlook other relevant modelling activities or breakdowns.

Internal validity Findings may be influenced by how tasks and prompts were framed during the workshop, as well as by group dynamics (e.g., dominant voices, consensus pressure) that can shape the severity and prioritisation of issues. The walkthrough also relied on an initial prototype; some observed difficulties may be due to prototype incompleteness rather than intrinsic limitations of the interaction concept.

External validity Results are based on a limited number of experts and a specific modelling scenario (e.g., associations between classes), so generalisability to the broader population of intended users (domain experts with heterogeneous backgrounds) and to other modelling tasks, domains, or contexts (e.g., field conditions, time pressure) is limited. Moreover, expert familiarity with block-based editors or UML tools may not match that of target users, affecting transferability.

8.4.2 Summary

The third iteration of this design science research is motivated by a set of issues that emerged from the application of the RE method in the CODECS LLs, as well as from literature insights. These include issues that are inherent to modelling with semi-formal

notations, such as the cognitive effort of externalising domain knowledge into semi-formal representations [144], as well as issues associated with modelling tools [193]. In the context of CODECS, we mitigated these issues through action research [229], with RE researchers working alongside LL stakeholders throughout the modelling activities.

In this iteration, we addressed the challenge of empowering LL stakeholders in requirements modelling, so as to support the continued adoption of the method even in settings where the presence of RE experts may not be consistently available. Accordingly, we introduced *ModelLer*, an EUD tool designed to reduce the notational burden of modelling while preserving users' interaction with semi-formal representations. The tool was designed by drawing insights from both modelling-related literature [144, 158, 163] and EUD approaches, which aim to lower barriers for end users through user-friendly interaction paradigms, such as constrained environments, and guided support [23].

We chose a block-based paradigm, as this interaction approach has been widely adopted in EUD [23] and has proven effective and engaging in programming education [181]. In this chapter, we presented the full functionality of *ModelLer*, although its development was iterative and informed by the subsequent evaluation presented in the next chapter.

The chapter also reported an expert-based validation through a cognitive walkthrough. The results confirmed the feasibility and learnability of the block-based approach, while also highlighting targeted improvements needed to better support end users in carrying out modelling tasks. These findings motivated the development of an enhanced version of the tool and a more structured user-based investigation aimed at evaluating its effectiveness with real users.

Implications for AI Support We discuss here some preliminary implications emerging from the design and validation of the first *ModelLer* prototype (V1) with respect to the integration of AI support into *ModelLer*. At the prototype stage, we considered several possible ways of employing AI techniques to enhance the modelling activity. One of the first options explored was the use of LLMs to automatically generate models from textual input. Although this solution appears technically feasible, given the growing availability of tools for automatic model generation [37, 71, 114], in our context, it raised an important methodological concern. In RE, modelling is not only a means of producing a formal output, but also a process of eliciting, articulating, and negotiating knowledge with stakeholders. Within the CODECS LL, the need to externalise domain knowledge directly from situated local practices was primary and fully aligned with the logic of the RE method proposed in this thesis.

For this reason, we deliberately set aside fully automated model generation as the main design direction, and instead favoured forms of AI integration that are more process-centred than solution-centred. This choice is also supported by the feedback gathered in CODECS: although the modelling activity was often perceived as effortful and cognitively demanding, stakeholders still regarded it as useful in itself, as a means to reflect on the case, make knowledge explicit, and support discussion. Accordingly, rather than replacing modelling with automation, we aimed to preserve user engagement in this cognitive activity and to investigate AI-based support as a peripheral aid to modelling. This suggests that, in participatory RE contexts, AI should be designed as a companion that supports users during modelling while leaving agency and knowledge construction firmly in human hands.

■ This chapter provided:

1. A tool to support the appropriation of the RE method in LL contexts beyond the CODECS project;
2. A preliminary feedback on the feasibility of using a block-based interaction paradigm for requirements modelling;
3. Requirements for tool support.

Chapter 9

Tool Assessment through Computational Thinking Framework

This chapter is based on the paper: “End-User Development in the AI Era”, Mannari C., Turchi T., Versino S., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Conati C., Malizia A., resubmitted after revision to the Special Issue “End-User Development in the AI Era” in Behaviour & Information Technology and currently under review [BIT], as an extension of [ISEUD25] [140].

Figure 9.1: Visual summary of tool design and validation iterations, highlighting the portion that addresses: RQ3.2 *Does an artefact-based assessment of ModeLLer reveal insights into computational thinking skills?*, RQ3.3 *Do users’ CT profiles influence their perceived workload when modelling requirements with ModeLLer?* and RQ3.4 *To what extent can interaction log analysis inform the design of intelligent suggestions mechanisms aimed at supporting users’ CT skills while using ModeLLer?*

9.1 Overview

The previous chapter presented ModeLLer, complete with all its functionalities, and began to address RQ₃ (*How can we empower novice and non-technical stakeholders in requirements modelling?*) through a preliminary evaluation using a cognitive walkthrough conducted with experts. This was part of the third design science iteration.

This chapter concludes the third iteration by presenting the first end-user study conducted with ModeLLer. EUD environments play a central role in enabling domain experts to effectively create and adapt digital artefacts to carry out their work [125]. In this scenario, prior research explored evaluation approaches for EUD tools that go beyond traditional usability measures in favour of an assessment that evaluates how well EUD tools align with various levels of users' computational thinking (CT) skills [22] (cf. EUD-ability, in Sec. 2.2.3). A substantial body of literature has addressed the assessment of CT through a range of different strategies, including combined evaluation perspectives to obtain a more nuanced understanding of CT [40] (cf. Brennan and Resnick's framework in Sec. 2.2.3).

In our evaluation study, we address the challenge of CT assessment, building on the close relationship between modelling activities and core CT skills, particularly abstraction and decomposition [34, 63, 144, 200, 231].

To this end, we complement RQ₃ through the second group of sub-questions:

- RQ_{3.2}: Does an artefact-based assessment of ModeLLer reveal insights into computational thinking skills?
- RQ_{3.3}: Do users' computational thinking profiles influence their perceived workload when modelling requirements with ModeLLer?
- RQ_{3.4}: To what extent can interaction log analysis inform the design of intelligent suggestions mechanisms aimed at supporting users' computational thinking skills while using ModeLLer?

To address these questions (cf. Fig. 9.1), we developed the first stable version of the tool and conducted a user study framed within Brennan and Resnick's CT framework, relying on the need for multiple approaches to CT assessment [40] (cf. Sec. 2.2.3).

To answer RQ_{3.2}, we combined three dimensions of evaluation: an assessment of the tool provided by EUD experts, a self-assessment of CT skill levels by participants, and an expert assessment of the artefacts produced with the tool.

To answer RQ_{3.3}, we investigated whether users' CT profiles relate to perceived workload during requirements modelling with ModeLLer.

To answer RQ_{3.4}, we analysed interaction logs and observed behaviours to derive insights into the use and potential value of the AI-assisted features.

■ Compared to prior studies, this evaluation: 1) involves 30 end users performing a modelling task with the ModeLLer, 2) combines multiple approaches to CT assessment, providing insights into the artefacts produced, users' CT profiles, and interaction behaviours, and 3) lays the groundwork for future intelligent suggestions through the analysis of interaction logs collected by the tool.

9.1.1 Methodology

The first stable version of the tool (cf. Version 1, Fig. 9.1)¹ provides full transformation of the blocks into UML, BPMN, and iStar, which are returned to users in graphical form. It also offers dedicated buttons to download the workspace in multiple output formats. At this stage, LLM-based functionalities were not yet integrated; however, the tool includes a logging mechanism that locally records all interaction events generated during modelling. Although this version of the tool already supports multiple notations, the evaluation presented in this chapter focuses specifically on domain models, namely UML class diagrams. This is consistent with the choice made in the first evaluation (cf. Sec. 8.3) and with the rationale of concentrating evaluators' effort on a single type of artefact.

Evaluation Approaches

We framed our evaluation study within Brennan and Resnick's CT framework. Therefore, we adopted a multi-approach strategy with the goal of exploring whether integrating different approaches can inform further development of the EUD modelling tool.

Our strategy combined five evaluation approaches, each characterised by a specific focus, assessment perspective, and evaluation instrument employed. Table 9.1 summarises the approaches.

Table 9.1: Integrated approaches for CT assessment

	Perspective	Instrument
<i>Approach #1: Tool quality</i>	artefact-based, conducted by HCI experts	EUDability inspection checklist
<i>Approach #2: CT profiles</i>	process-based, self-assessed by end users	CTS questionnaire
<i>Approach #3: Model analysis</i>	artefact-based, conducted by SE experts	Model evaluation checklist
<i>Approach #4: Modelling workload</i>	experience-based reported by end users	NASA-TLX
<i>Approach #5: Log analysis</i>	process-based, provided by system	Dataset of user interaction analysis

Approach #1: Tool quality focuses on assessing the quality of ModelLer as the artefact enabling the modelling activity. The evaluation focused on the EUDability dimensions—*concreteness, modularity, structuredness, reusability, and testability* (cf. sec. 2.2.3)—through an external review carried out by HCI experts using the checklist for EUDability predictive inspection-based evaluation.

Approach #2: CT profiles targets users' CT skills from a process-based, self-assessed perspective. This aspect was investigated using the CTS questionnaire (cf. sec. 2.2.3)

¹Version 1 is available at: https://unipisa.github.io/blockly-modeller/demo_v2

to assess participants' CT levels, leading to the identification of CT profiles based on proficiency.

Approach #3: Model analysis focuses on assessing the models as the artefacts produced during the session. A study-specific modelling evaluation checklist was applied by a team of SE experts.

Approach #4: Modelling workload focuses on participants' subjective experience while performing the modelling tasks with the tool, using the NASA-TLX questionnaire [95] to assess the cognitive workload perceived by the modellers.

Approach #5: Log analysis concentrates on users' interactions with the tool during the modelling activity. This approach adopts a process-based, system-provided perspective, as it relies on the interaction logs collected by the tool.

The research questions are addressed by integrating multiple approaches.

RQ3.2 is investigated through Approaches 1, 2, and 3, in which the artefacts produced by users are analysed in relation to their CT skill levels and compared with the evaluation provided by the tool.

To answer RQ3.3, Approaches 2 and 4 are used to analyse whether users' CT profiles relate to perceived workload during requirements modelling with ModeLLer.

Finally, RQ3.4 is investigated through Approaches 2 and 5, by analysing interaction logs and relating observed interaction behaviours to users' CT profiles.

Procedure

Figure 9.2 outlines the study procedure, structured in four steps that involve different participant roles and support the application of all the evaluation approaches. Section 9.1.1 provides details on the instruments used in the study.

Step 1 entails the *EUDability inspection-based evaluation*, in which four HCI experts independently explored the tool and subsequently met in a remote meeting to complete the EUDability checklist.

Step 2 consists of the *CTS assessment*, where a group of end users (n=30) self-assessed their CT skills through the CTS questionnaire.

In Step 3, the end users participated in a *test session using ModeLLer* following the task proposed. Before beginning the session, the end users watched a 10-minute video that

Figure 9.2: Study procedure overview

explained how to model socio-technical systems in agriculture. During the interaction with the tool, a log was produced containing detailed records of user actions. After the user session, the participants answered the NASA-TLX.

Finally, Step 4 consists of the *users' artefacts evaluation*. Each of the five software engineering experts received 12 cases, corresponding to the models developed during the user sessions, which they assessed using the model evaluation checklist. As each case was evaluated by two experts, this resulted in a double evaluation for each model. The two evaluations were then averaged to provide a consolidated assessment of each model.

Participants

The study involved 36 participants, comprising 6 experts and 30 end users, i.e., users without expertise in modelling with semi-formal notations. Among the experts, three had expertise in HCI and five in software engineering and formal languages, with two individuals possessing both areas of expertise.

The end users, who were equally divided by gender (15 males and 15 females), were recruited voluntarily using a snowball sampling technique. Most participants were between 18–24 and 25–34 years old, with smaller groups in the 35–44 and 45–54 age ranges. Educational levels ranged from high school to PhDs, with the majority holding a high school diploma or bachelor's degree. The sample was predominantly composed of bachelor's and master's students (17 out of 30), but also included PhD students and professionals. Backgrounds spanned computer science, engineering, communication, psychology, law, and public administration. No prerequisite knowledge was required to perform the tasks; most of the participants had little to no knowledge of formal notations, and none had prior expertise in the EUD tool. All data were collected and managed anonymously, in full compliance with data protection regulations and with respect for participant privacy. All participants were fully informed about the nature and purpose of the study and provided their informed consent prior to participation.

Setting

The experts conducted individual artefact-based evaluation sessions remotely, whereas the end-user study was carried out in person.

The end users took part in individual test sessions, guided by a moderator. The study was carried out over multiple days, with groups of participants completing the test in successive sessions. The sessions were conducted by three different moderators, including the first and the third author of the paper [BIT]. The initial sessions were co-moderated to ensure consistency in the procedure. Each test session lasted approximately 40 minutes: 10 minutes for the video training, 20 minutes for the interactive session on the tool, and 10 minutes for the post-test questionnaire with demographic data and NASA-TLX. During the test, the moderator provided participants with access to a personal computer containing the online questionnaire and a local installation of the tool. After the test, the moderator saved the system logs along with all materials produced during the session for later analysis.

Table 9.2: User task in ModeLLer

Part 1

Read the process description and create the model. Build the model using the highlighted elements, which are mandatory. You may also add elements based on prior knowledge. Export the structure diagram as an image and save the workspace.
Maximum time: 15 minutes

The farmer aims to modernise greenhouse cultivation to optimise agricultural practices and improve sustainability. The integration of digital tools enhances productivity, reduces the use of inputs such as water and fertilisers, and improves farmers' well-being through automation, saving time.

The new process involves introducing a sensor-based system installed in the greenhouse to measure temperature, CO₂, soil moisture, pH, and light. These sensors are connected through a LoRa Network communication system, allowing data transmission to the AgroSense platform every hour.

The farmer can monitor environmental conditions in the greenhouse by accessing the AgroSense platform from both mobile devices and computers. For example, if the system detects a drop in temperature, the farmer can immediately turn on lamps to prevent plant stress and potential crop damage.

Technical consultants, who work closely with farmers, can also access the data via the same platform and provide personalised recommendations based on the recorded conditions.

Part 2

Import the file POMODORO.json located on the desktop and extend the model by adding a sensor-based technology to monitor the health status of tomato plants and provide recommendations for pest control treatments.
Once satisfied, save the process diagram as an image and the workspace.

Maximum time: 5 minutes

Tasks

Participants were tasked with modelling two digital agriculture scenarios rooted in real-world contexts, using data extracted from materials developed within the project CODECS. The task was exploratory, designed to maintain the open-ended nature of the modelling process. Additionally, it was structured using EUDability as a guiding reference to enable post-hoc observation of all dimensions and to cover the main functionalities of the tool. No strict time limit was imposed; however, users were encouraged to complete the task within 20 minutes.

Table 9.2 presents the modelling task, which is divided into two parts. In the first part, participants are presented with a half-page narrative describing the introduction of a sensor-based system for monitoring greenhouse production. Based on the scenario described, the user is asked to model a small group of entities highlighted in the text and is invited to add any other elements or relations contained in the text or based on their background knowledge. Once the model is complete, the user should save the workspace and export the UML model. In the second part, participants are asked to import a model describing an on-field crop scenario without the use of digital technology, and extend the representation by integrating a sensor-based solution, similar to the one described in the first model, to monitor the health status of the plants and provide pest control recommendations.

Instruments

The study employs a variety of instruments to support CT assessment across the different approaches (cf. Table 9.1, col. Instrument).

Checklist for EUDability predictive inspection-based evaluation To assess the quality of ModeLLer, the inspection-based evaluation technique previously introduced and applied by [24] was employed. The checklist is oriented to experts in HCI and EUD

and contains 15 binary items covering the EUDability dimensions: *concreteness*, *modularity*, *structuredness*, *reusability*, and *testability*. These items capture how domain concepts are represented, how problem-solving elements are organised and guided, and how the outcomes produced can be reused, inspected, and tested within the environment. For each dimension, an overall EUDability level (None, Low, Mid, High) is derived based on the number of positive responses, providing a structured assessment of the extent to which the environment supports EUD.

CTS questionnaire Users' CT profiles were obtained by administering the CTS questionnaire to the end users. The questionnaire was originally proposed by Tsai et al. [213] and consists of 19 self-report items covering five CT skills: *abstraction*, *decomposition*, *algorithm design*, *generalisation*, and *evaluation*. Each item captures attitudes and strategies related to problem understanding, decomposition, solution planning, reuse of solutions, and solution assessment. For this study, the CTS was adopted in the version adapted by Barricelli et al. [24], which uses a 6-point Likert scale, consistent with the EUDability assessment.

Checklist for Expert Evaluation of Models The checklist for expert evaluation of models was applied to assess the models produced by the end users during the test session. This instrument was created specifically for this study, following common practices for artefact-based CT assessments [40, 156]. Accordingly, the assessment criteria are adapted to the characteristics of the tool and the modelling tasks under investigation. The checklist is tailored to the evaluation of UML class diagrams. The rationale behind this choice is to focus evaluators' effort on a single type of artefact. Among the three types of models produced by the tool, namely UML, iStar, and BPMN, UML was chosen being the most prominent modelling notation and the most representative of the task presented to users. The checklist is designed to assess the produced models at the content level, inspecting consistency and quality. It includes 15 questions mapped to CT skills. Table 9.3 contains the checklist. Items 1-3 refer to the *abstraction* skill. These items evaluate the model capability to capture essential entities of the domain and represent them in a meaningful way. The items in this group focus on the inclusion of relevant domain entities, the informativeness of the model, and the representation of meaningful relationships between the elements within the model. Items 4-6 assess the *decomposition* skill. This group investigates how well the model breaks down the system described into smaller components. The items examine whether the model contains multiple element types, avoids redundancies, and provides adequate detail. Items 7-9 refer to the *algorithm design* skill. This item set evaluates whether the user has completed all necessary steps to finish the task and deliver the output. The questions assess the presence of both models, if they contain a sufficient number of elements and whether more advanced elements are introduced. Items 10-12 assess the *generalisation* skill. The group asks to compare the two models produced and evaluate consistency and the presence of recurring elements. Items 13-15 assess the *Evaluation* skill by examining the overall correctness, accuracy and consistency.

NASA-TLX NASA-TLX is a standard questionnaire that assesses user cognitive workload through weighted ratings across six subscales, i.e., *mental demand*, *physical demand*,

Table 9.3: Checklist for Expert Evaluation of Models

CT skill	Checklist items
<i>Abstraction</i>	Model 1: 1. contains relevant domain entities 2. is sufficiently informative 3. represents meaningful relationships between elements
<i>Decomposition</i>	Model 1: 4. contains different types of elements 5. does not contain redundancies 6. is sufficiently detailed
<i>Algorithm design</i>	Model 1 and model 2 7. are both available 8. contain a sufficient number of elements 9. contain advanced elements
<i>Generalisation</i>	Model 2 10. contains a portion equal to that of Model 1 11. is consistent with model 1 12. extends the example model
<i>Evaluation</i>	Model 1 13. is accurate 14. is consistent 15. is correct

temporal demand, performance, effort, and frustration [95]. The questionnaire is adopted within the experience-based approach for measuring the workload perceived by the user while modelling, using a 21-point Likert scale.

Dataset of User Interactions Analysis The use of interaction logs as a source of evidence for CT assessment draws inspiration from recent research [104]. During interaction with ModeLLer, system logs were automatically collected to record users' actions throughout the modelling session. The logs capture time-stamped interaction events related to model construction and modification, such as the creation, configuration, and deletion of blocks, as well as navigation and editing actions within the workspace. This form of behavioural data provides a process-oriented view of users' modelling activity.

9.2 Results

We report our findings following the CT assessment approaches presented in 9.1. Supplementary material is available in the Zenodo repository of the [BIT] study [141].

9.2.1 Approach #1: Quality of ModeLLer

The results of the *EUDability inspection-based evaluation checklist* are the following:

Table 9.4: EUDability score and required CT levels for ModelLer

EUDability	Level	Min. CT Level	CT skill
<i>Concreteness</i>	mid	mid	Abstraction
<i>Modularity</i>	high	low	Decomposition
<i>Structuredness</i>	mid	mid	Algorithm design
<i>Reusability</i>	high	low	Generalisation
<i>Testability</i>	high	low	Evaluation

- The *concreteness* dimension has been assessed as *mid*, as some terms used in the application do not align with familiar concepts in the experts' domain. For example, the blocks *attribute* and *specialisation* in the toolbox panel may not be immediately recognisable, while *actors* and *resources* sound familiar.
- The *modularity* dimension has been assessed as *high*, as the functionality for assembling blocks through drag-and-drop, interlocks, textual inputs, and dropdowns has high affordance.
- The *structuredness* dimension has been assessed as *mid*, since although the single-page interface allows navigation between different phases of model creation, there is no clear indication of the steps required to complete the task. This lack of explicit guidance can make it difficult for users to navigate the task and understand the necessary steps for problem-solving.
- The *reusability* dimension has been assessed as *high*, as export buttons are available, allowing users to export and import the workspace, as well as save models in multiple formats, ensuring interoperability with other platforms.
- The *testability* dimension has been assessed as *high*, as model creation is dynamic, and tools are provided to edit previous actions, allowing for thorough testing and refinement.

Table 9.4, in the *EUDability* and *Level* column, reports the level of support provided by the tool for each EUDability dimension. The scores indicate that, overall, the experts evaluated the quality of the tool as medium to high, while also identifying areas for improvement across *concreteness* and *structuredness*.

Furthermore, following the approach proposed in previous studies [24], the columns *Min. CT Level* and *CT skill* indicate the required CT levels for ModelLer. Since *modularity*, *reusability*, and *testability* received *high* evaluations, the minimum level of *decomposition*, *generalisation* and *evaluation* required to the user is *low*. Instead, since *concreteness* and *structuredness* received mid-level evaluations, the minimum level of *abstraction* and *algorithm design* is *mid*.

9.2.2 Approach #2: CT profiles

Fig. 9.3 presents CT skills distribution across five CT dimensions, showing a general medium-high global perception with higher scores in *decomposition* and *algorithm design*

Figure 9.3: CTS distribution by dimension

(median ≈ 5), and slightly lower perceived skills in *generalisation* (median ≈ 4.5). The box plots show moderate variability within each dimension, with *abstraction* exhibiting relatively wider interquartile ranges. The whiskers indicate the spread of the central data, while several outliers, particularly in *decomposition* and *generalisation*, suggest that some participants reported markedly lower agreement scores, down to 2 on the 6-point Likert scale.

After standardising the data, clustering was applied to the CTS results. K-means clustering was performed, and different values of (k) were explored using multiple evaluation metrics. Considering clarity and robustness, $k=2$ was selected as the most interpretable solution. To visualise the clustering, a PCA was performed to reduce the dimensionality of the standardised data to 2D. The resulting scatterplot (Fig. 9.4a) shows the data points projected onto the first two principal components, colour-coded by cluster. The plot reveals a clear separation between the two clusters, suggesting distinct self-perception profiles in CT skills among participants.

Finally, the bar chart in Fig. 9.4a shows the average self-reported scores for each CT dimension, grouped by cluster ($K=2$). Cluster 0 reports higher average scores across all five dimensions compared to Cluster 1.

Two distinct clusters emerged from the k-means analysis of CTS scores: Cluster 0—*self-confident group*: users with higher self-perceived CT skills. Cluster 1—*cautious*

(a) CTS profiles clusters

(b) clusters by dimension

Figure 9.4: CTS profiles

Figure 9.5: Example of model produced during the evaluation session in ModelLer

group: users reporting lower perceived skills.

9.2.3 Approach #3: Model analysis

All the end users involved in the test session completed the task, producing a first group of 30 diagrams representing the output of Part 1, and another group of 30 diagrams, representing the output of Part 2 (cfr Table 9.2). The average duration for Part 1 was 14.8 minutes out of the 15 available, while Part 2 took an average of 4 minutes out of the 5 available. The average total duration was 18.8 minutes out of 20.

In terms of model complexity, the models contain multiple UML elements, i.e. classes, direct associations, attributes, operations and aggregations. Model 1 contains an average of 11.5 classes, whereas Model 2 has an average of 4.2 classes. The maximum number of classes is 27, and the minimum is 5.

Figure 9.5 presents an example of the output model produced by a user. The model contains 11 classes representing the entities contained in the textual description. All the classes – except two – are connected to other classes through a direct association presenting the relationship between the two elements. One class, i.e. *greenhouse*, contains attributes such as *temp*, *humidity*, *ph*, *co2*, *light*.

Assessment of the models. Figure 9.6 shows the distribution of average evaluation rates across the five CT dimensions. The figure consists of five subplots, each representing a distinct CT dimension: abstraction, decomposition, algorithm design, generalisation, and evaluation. The x-axis contains the violin plots of the single dimensions, while the y-axis reports the evaluation scores, computed as the average of the ratings provided by two independent evaluators.

Overall, the distributions highlight differences in how the various CT dimensions are reflected in the produced artefacts, with some dimensions showing more stable evaluation patterns than others. Abstraction and algorithm design exhibit higher central tendencies, with median values around 2–2.5 out of 3 and a relatively wide spread, indicating variability in participants' performance across these dimensions. Decomposition shows a more concentrated distribution centred around intermediate values, suggesting more consistent outcomes among participants.

In contrast, generalisation and evaluation display lower median scores and greater dispersion, with values extending toward the lower end of the scale. This indicates in-

Figure 9.6: Artefacts evaluation

creased variability and generally lower performance in these dimensions compared to the others.

9.2.4 Combined analysis of Approaches 1–3 (RQ3.2)

Results from the expert evaluation were compared with the CTS scores to explore relationships between artefacts and CT levels. Figure 9.7 consists of five subplots, each representing a distinct CT dimension. The x-axis indicates the average scores of the artefacts discretised into three ordinal categories: low (blue), medium (orange), and high (green), with individual data points overlaid and sample sizes (n) indicated below the boxplots,

Figure 9.7: CTS vs artefacts evaluation bins

while the y-axis displays the corresponding CTS scores on a continuous scale. Dashed vertical lines indicate the lower threshold of CT skill supported by the tool, as identified through expert evaluation.

Visual inspection of subplots reveals a limited alignment between the CTS and artefact-based evaluations. While users' self-assessments of CT skills yielded mid-to-high average results, the results from the artefact evaluation were lower on average. These trends were explored through statistical tests. The Shapiro-Wilk test indicated that CTS scores were not normally distributed for artefact evaluation scores ($W = 0.924$, $p < .001$), prompting the use of a Kruskal-Wallis test, which indicated a statistically significant effect for Algorithm design ($H = 7.964$, $p = .019$). No significant differences emerged for the remaining dimensions. Dunn's post-hoc tests with Bonferroni correction did not identify significant pairwise differences, suggesting a distributed effect rather than a clear separation between individual evaluation categories.

Furthermore, the threshold placement suggests that, for Abstraction and Algorithm Design, effective tool support emerges primarily for users with mid-level CTS scores or higher, whereas for Decomposition, Generalisation, and Evaluation the tool appears to provide support across all CTS levels.

9.2.5 Approach #4: Modelling workload

Fig. 9.8a presents the overall workload score measured using NASA-TLX. Results show a median score of approximately 8–10, corresponding to a moderate perceived workload.

Subscales were analysed individually to explore which contributed most to the overall perceived workload. Fig. 9.8b shows that the subscales with the highest mean scores were *mental demand* and *effort*, followed by *temporal demand*.

9.2.6 Combined analysis of Approaches 1 and 4 (RQ3.3)

The two clusters representing different CT profiles identified through the CTS assessment were compared in terms of perceived cognitive workload, using the average values

Figure 9.8: NASA-TLX results

Figure 9.9: Clusters by NASA-TLX dimension

of the NASA-TLX subscales. The bar chart in Fig. 9.9 displays the average scores for each subscale, grouped by cluster. The subscales include the single dimensions and the overall NASA-TLX score. Cluster 1 reports higher average scores on *temporal demand*, *performance*, *effort*, *frustration*, and the *overall workload score*. Cluster 0 shows higher average values on *physical demand*, while *mental demand* remained approximately constant across clusters. This suggests that participants in Cluster 1—*cautious group* experienced a higher perceived cognitive workload, characterised by increased time pressure, effort, frustration, and lower perceived performance, whereas participants in Cluster 0—*self-confident group* reported a comparatively lower overall workload, with physical demand being the most salient differentiating factor.

9.2.7 Approach #5: Log analysis. (RQ3.4)

The interaction logs comprise over 70,000 entries collected during the modelling sessions. An exploration of the logs was carried out, looking at the process enacted by the modellers. The analysis was inspired by the following sub-questions: *when* should a suggestion be prompted?; *where* should the suggestion appear on the screen?; *what* type of suggestion should be provided?

Interaction timing and pacing. As a preliminary step, the time intervals between consecutive user events were examined to understand interaction pacing and identify natural breaks in user activity. For each session, the time difference between consecutive events was calculated, and the distribution of these intervals was plotted.

The cumulative distribution function in Fig. 9.10 shows the distribution of time intervals (in seconds) between consecutive events across all user sessions. The majority of inter-event times fall within the first few seconds, with a steep increase near zero and a rapid flattening beyond that point. A vertical dashed red line marks the 5-second threshold, which indicates a distinction between short and long pauses in interaction.

Figure 9.10: Cumulative distribution of inter-event times across all sessions. The red dashed line marks the 5-second threshold.

This threshold is later used to group interaction patterns. In particular, 98.2% of all inter-event times fall below this 5-second mark, supporting its use as a meaningful criterion. The data is clipped at 30 seconds to improve visualisation clarity.

To further investigate interaction pacing at the individual level, the distribution of inter-event times per user was analysed. Building on the global view presented in Fig. 9.10, the box plot in Fig. 9.11 displays a user-level breakdown of the time intervals between actions. The y-axis shows the time (in seconds) between consecutive events, limited to 100 seconds for clarity. A dashed red line marks a 30-second threshold, used as an indicator of inactivity or potential breaks in interaction. Each box summarises the distribution for one user, showing the median inter-event time (line inside the box), the interquartile range, and individual data points beyond the whiskers (outliers).

Statistical tests were conducted to explore differences in interaction frequency among users.

To examine whether interaction pacing is associated with specific behaviours, users were grouped into two categories: 1) *fast*, with inter-event time ≤ 5 seconds; 2) *slow*, with inter-event time > 5 seconds. An independent t-test was performed to assess whether the average time between events differs significantly between the two groups. The results were $t=2.48$, $p=0.0133$. This indicates a statistically significant difference in inter-event timing between fast and slow groups.

Figure 9.11: Distribution of time between events per user (without outliers)

Finally, the correlation between users' average inter-event time and their total number of events was examined. The correlation matrix revealed a negative correlation: $r=-0.19$.

This suggests that users who interact more frequently tend to have shorter pauses between actions, reinforcing the link between higher engagement and faster interaction pacing.

9.2.8 Combined analysis of Approaches 2 and 5

The two clusters representing different CT profiles identified through the CTS assessment were used to investigate how users interacted spatially with the modelling interface as well as event-based interaction patterns.

Spatial interaction. To analyse spatial interactions, targeted UI events triggered by user actions (e.g. clicks and drag operations) were selected, and interaction heatmaps based on client X and client Y coordinates were generated and grouped by cluster. Fig. 9.12 shows kernel density estimates of interaction locations for Cluster 0 (left) and Cluster 1 (right). The heatmaps reveal distinct interaction patterns between the two groups. Cluster 0—*self-confident group* displays two main regions of interaction: a primary area of high activity in the lower-right area of the interface (around clientX ≈ 1400 , clientY $\approx 200-400$), likely corresponding to the workspace or modelling canvas; and a secondary hotspot in the top-left (clientX ≈ 100 , clientY ≈ 800), which may relate to interface components such as the toolbox with blocks. Cluster 1—*cautious group* shows a more compact and centralised interaction pattern, with activity concentrated around client X ≈ 1400 , client Y ≈ 400 , and less dispersion overall. The secondary area on the top left is less pronounced compared to Cluster 0.

Patterns behaviours The exploration of the logs was extended by analysing events based on their type. Fig. 9.13 visualises the first 100 interaction events of users, grouped by cluster membership. Each horizontal bar represents a user session, and each coloured segment corresponds to a different event type, such as *create*, *move*, *drag*, *toolbox item select*, *change*, etc. The colour-coded events reveal variation in interaction styles across users: some users (e.g., C0-18 and C23) show repeated toolbox item select events early on, suggesting exploratory behaviour. Other users (e.g., C1-1, C1-2) show early and repeated use of create, change, and input, jumping directly into constructing the model.

Figure 9.12: Interaction heatmaps with cluster 0 (left) and cluster 1 (right)

An analysis by clusters reveals that users in Cluster 1—*cautious group* appear to engage more frequently in *change* events throughout their sessions, compared to those in Cluster 0—*self-confident group*. This pattern suggests that Cluster 1 users may have spent more time adjusting or iterating on existing elements. In contrast, many Cluster 0 users show a greater diversity of actions earlier in the session, often beginning with sequences of *create*, *menu item selection*, and *click* events.

9.3 Discussion

From the results collected during our study, we discuss the research questions concerning CT skills assessment through artefact-based evaluation, the influence of CT profiles on modelling workload, and the potential for intelligent support mechanisms.

Insights from artefact-based assessment

Findings from the combined analysis of artefact-based evaluation and CTS suggest that depending solely on CTS may not reliably reflect end users' actual modelling outcomes.

Figure 9.13: Activity patterns ordered by clusters

The differences between self-assessed and expert-assessed CT levels may indicate that some users have underestimated their skills, while others may have overestimated them. Furthermore, among the factors that contribute to these discrepancies, the EUD tool may represent one influencing element. From the perspective of CT assessment, these findings are consistent with the view that assessing CT is inherently challenging [210], thereby supporting the need for multi-perspective assessment strategies [40, 185]. From an operational perspective, integrating different approaches may inform the design of more granular and targeted strategies for supporting users. For instance, analysing the artefacts with lower scores in Abstraction and Algorithm design, which appear to be dimensions less strongly supported by the tool, may provide insights into how such strategies might be refined.

Influence of CT profiles on perceived modelling workload

The analysis focused on self-perceived CT skills resulted in two distinct user clusters, corresponding to a first, more self-confident group, characterised by higher perceived awareness of their CT abilities, and a second group reporting lower levels of self-confidence in their skills. The two groups exhibited different patterns of perceived cognitive workload. In particular, users positioned at higher CT levels tended to report a lighter overall perceived workload. At the same time, it is noteworthy that, across subscales, mental workload was consistently perceived as the highest, with no substantial differences between clusters. This insight is in line with previous research highlighting the cognitive effort required by modelling [10, 126, 144]

Insights for intelligent suggestions

The exploratory analysis of interaction logs aimed to uncover deeper insights into user behaviours and strategies from temporal, spatial, and event-based dimensions. The insights from this analysis suggest when to prompt, where to place hints, and what content to include. Regarding temporal analysis, findings suggest potential moments during the modelling process at which suggestions may be triggered.

In particular, longer pauses could reflect hesitation, confusion, or cognitive overload. A noticeable slowdown in interaction may represent a suitable moment for AI-driven hints to help users regain momentum or guide next steps. Moreover, interaction timing may serve as an indicator of the type of reasoning applied, distinguishing exploratory/evaluative behaviours from construction/practice-oriented ones.

The spatial analysis associated with the two clusters revealed a distinct behaviour between the groups. Cluster 0—*self-confident group* appears to include users with a more spatially extended approach, as indicated by interactions distributed across multiple interface sections, such as activating buttons, modifying blocks, and navigating between areas. In contrast, Cluster 1—*cautious group* shows a more concentrated interaction pattern, possibly reflecting a more bounded strategy or a tendency to become “stuck” within a specific part of the interface.

These contrasting behaviours may be linked to differing levels of confidence, familiarity with tools, or problem-solving styles. This insight reinforces the value of further investigating interaction patterns.

Finally, event-based analysis provides insights into activity patterns in relation to the two clusters. Notably, users in Cluster 1 appear to engage more frequently in *change* events throughout their sessions, compared to those in Cluster 0. This pattern suggests that Cluster 1 users may have spent more time adjusting or iterating on existing elements, potentially indicating a more cautious or incremental modelling strategy. In contrast, many Cluster 0 users show a greater diversity of actions earlier in the session, often beginning with sequences of *create*, *toolbox_item_select*, and *click* events, which may reflect a more exploratory or construction-oriented approach to the task.

9.3.1 Answer to RQ3.2: *Does an artefact-based assessment of ModeLLer reveal insights into computational thinking skills?*

The artefact-based assessment reveals that while multi-dimensional assessment strategies are necessary for capturing CT skills, the combination of self-reported and expert-evaluated perspectives provides a more nuanced understanding of users' actual modelling competencies and highlights dimensions where the tool may require enhancement.

9.3.2 Answer to RQ3.3: *Do users' computational thinking profiles influence their perceived workload when modelling requirements with ModeLLer?*

Findings from the study demonstrate that users' CT profiles do influence perceived workload, with higher self-confidence in CT skills associated with lighter cognitive load, suggesting the need for differentiated support strategies to requirements modelling, tailored to users' self-perceived competence levels.

9.3.3 Answer to RQ3.4: *To what extent can interaction log analysis inform the design of intelligent suggestions mechanisms aimed at supporting users' computational thinking skills while using ModeLLer?*

The analysis of interaction logs demonstrates considerable potential for informing AI-powered support. By identifying when users hesitate, where they concentrate their activity, and what patterns characterise different problem-solving approaches, the system can provide timely, contextually relevant guidance adapted to individual modelling strategies.

9.4 Conclusions

In this final section, we discuss the threats to validity and draw conclusions on RQ3 (*How can we empower novice and non-technical stakeholders in requirements modelling?*), highlighting the research implications emerging from this iteration. These implications motivate a final cycle of the design science research.

9.4.1 Threats to Validity

This section discusses issues of the validity of this study, divided into construct validity, internal validity and external validity.

Construct validity The constructs considered in the study are the following:

Tool quality (Approach #1), assessed by experts using the EUDability inspection checklist. While expert-based evaluations may be influenced by subjective judgment or by potential misinterpretation of checklist items, this threat was mitigated by involving three evaluators with experience in EUD/HCI systems who were required to compare their assessments and converge toward a shared overall evaluation.

Users' computational thinking skills (Approach #2), assessed through CTS questionnaire. Self-reported measures may be affected by social desirability or miscalibration of self-perception; however, the CTS is a validated instrument widely used in prior CT research.

Quality of the generated models (Approach #3), was evaluated through an artefact-based analysis using a model evaluation checklist specifically developed for this study. While the use of custom evaluation metrics is common in CT-related studies—particularly when the focus is on the qualitative characteristics of artefacts rather than on purely quantitative measures—this choice may introduce threats, such as evaluators not fully understanding the intent of specific items or the overall evaluation scope. To mitigate this risk, the assessment was conducted by five SE experts, and each of the 30 models was independently evaluated by two experts. The final score for each artefact was computed as the average of the two evaluations, reducing individual bias and supporting a more robust evaluation.

Modelling workload (Approach #4), was measured through experience-based self-reports using the NASA-TLX questionnaire. Although workload perception is inherently subjective, NASA-TLX is a well-established and validated instrument. Additionally, this evaluation may be affected by the Hawthorne effect, as the study was mostly conducted by those who developed the tool, and the users may not feel comfortable in expressing negative judgments. However, they are well aware that this activity is oriented to validate the approach and that negative opinions can be beneficial to improve it.

Log-based analysis (Approach #5) captured users' interactions behaviour using system-generated data. While interaction logs provide objective and unobtrusive measures of user activity, they represent indirect proxies of cognitive processes and may therefore introduce construct validity threats if interpreted in isolation. To mitigate this risk, log data were used to explore objective interaction measures and to identify recurring interaction patterns.

Finally, the triangulation of multiple approaches, adopted to obtain a more nuanced understanding of CT-related aspects and tool features, entails a trade-off between interpretative depth and construct robustness due to the heterogeneous operationalisation of the constructs.

Internal validity The study was conducted in a controlled setting using a single, domain-specific modelling task, which may have influenced participants' behaviour and limited the variability of observed strategies. In addition, the relatively small sample size may have affected the stability of the identified user clusters and interaction patterns.

Moreover, participants' self-assessed CT skills, while useful for characterising user profiles, may not fully reflect their actual competencies and could introduce bias in the interpretation of results. Furthermore, the presence of experimenters and the structured nature of the task may have influenced user behaviour, potentially leading participants to act more cautiously or systematically than they would in naturalistic settings.

Future work will address these threats by expanding the empirical sample, involving a broader range of participants, including domain experts and practitioners, and validating the findings in more ecologically valid settings.

External validity The evaluation was conducted with a relatively limited number of participants and focused on a single tool instance, task, and application domain. As a result, the findings cannot be directly generalised to all contexts, domains, or user populations. Differences in domain characteristics, task complexity, and users' profiles may influence both interaction behaviour and CT observation. However, following the principle of case-based generalisability [228], findings can be transferred to contexts that share similar structural and organisational characteristics. In this respect, the study context reflects key features common to other EUD scenarios, such as heterogeneous user backgrounds and CT proficiency. These characteristics support the transferability of the findings to similar cases.

Future work will further strengthen external validity by replicating the evaluation across additional domains and organisational settings, involving a broader range of end users and professional roles, and by comparing results across multiple case instances to assess the robustness of the observed patterns.

9.4.2 Summary

This chapter has concluded the third design science iteration through a user study conducted on a first stable version of ModeLLer (V1). This version did not yet include AI-based assistance. The objective of the evaluation was twofold: i) obtaining insights on the user interaction with the tool to assess whether the proposed solution is effective in supporting end users in modelling requirements, and ii) contributing to methodologies for evaluating EUD tools while also shifting the focus from primarily educational settings to work environments.

Following CT-grounded approaches [22, 40, 185], our structured process combined multiple evaluation perspectives, namely tool assessment, models assessment, CT profiling, workload measurement, and interaction log analysis. Triangulating these approaches has offered a nuanced assessment that is summarised in three main points. First, artefact-based assessment reveals discrepancies between self-reported and demonstrated CT skills, reinforcing the value of performance-based evaluation methods for assessing the effectiveness of the EUD tool. Second, users with different CT profiles perceived distinct cognitive workload patterns during modelling, indicating that the tool should provide differentiated forms of support adapted to different users' attitudes and skills. Third, interaction log analysis provides actionable insights for designing adaptive support strategies that respond to temporal patterns, spatial behaviours, and event sequences. Together, these findings contribute to understanding how EUD modelling tools can be enhanced to better support users with varying CT competencies through intelligent, adaptive mechanisms.

Implications for AI Support The analysis of the artefacts showed that the tool is effective in supporting the creation of syntactically correct models, while the block-to-model transformation process remains fully under human control. However, correctness extends beyond notation compliance: dedicated AI support may be required to strengthen models coherence and accuracy and to help users appropriately apply the full range of constructs supported by the EUD environment.

In addition, through the analysis of interaction logs, we could identify when users hesitate, where they concentrate their activity, and what patterns characterise different problem-solving approaches. This confirms that a recommendation mechanism could provide timely, contextually relevant guidance adapted to individual modelling strategies. For example, a possible support strategy could consist of detecting periods of inactivity and analysing the sequence of actions leading up to them to identify behavioural patterns. Based on these patterns, the system could provide context-aware hints aimed at resolving confusion, encouraging exploration, or supporting task progression. Another aspect worth exploring is the recognition of personalised patterns of actions associated with an analysis of the current status of the artefact, which could be used to prompt contextually relevant suggestions aimed at identifying underdeveloped constructs or incorrect uses.

🔖 RQ3 recap

Taken together, this chapter and the previous one answer to RQ3: *How can we empower novice and non-technical stakeholders in requirements modelling?* Novice and non-technical stakeholders can be empowered in requirements modelling through an EUD tool grounded in block-based interaction. This approach helps lower the entry barriers associated with learning semi-formal notations, while supporting users in the abstraction and decomposition activities required by modelling. This kind of system can benefit from AI-based support, as long as such support is designed to preserve human agency and active engagement, while providing adaptive guidance tailored to different user skill levels.

Chapter 10

Exploring Adaptive AI Support

This chapter is based on: “Assisting Stakeholders in Class Diagram Interpretation with LLMs: a Work in Progress”, Mannari C., Turchi T., Bacco F. M., Malizia A., MoDRE, co-located with IEEE RE (2025) [MoDRE25] [139], and “Designing Adaptive AI Assistance for Block-Based Modelling: A Wizard of Oz Study with Domain Experts”, Mannari C., Turchi T., Bacco F. M., Ferrari A., Conati C., Malizia A. In Proceedings of the 2026 International Conference on Advanced Visual Interfaces (2026) [AVI26] [142].

Figure 10.1: Visual summary of tool design and validation iterations, highlighting the portion that addresses: RQ4.1 *To what extent can large language models perform model-to-text transformation?*, RQ4.2 *To what extent do users follow the suggestions provided by the system?* and RQ4.3 *How do the agronomists perceive the AI-based assistance offered by ModelLer?*

10.1 Overview

The previous chapter completed the third design science iteration through a user study of ModelLer conducted on the first stable version of the tool.

This chapter concludes this design science project by performing the fourth iteration.

Insights from the previous chapter confirmed the feasibility of adopting a block-based approach to alleviate issues related to semi-formal notations. However, the study also showed that modelling remains a cognitively demanding activity. This confirms findings from our field study regarding the application of the modelling procedure (cf. Ch. 5), as well as insights from the literature [55, 193, 220]. To reduce modelling effort, recent research has investigated modellers' assistance needs [126, 193] and has proposed AI-based solutions such as automated modelling [191], intelligent assistants [163], and recommender systems [14]. However, these approaches are mainly oriented to expert modellers, fragmented, and technique-driven (cf. ch. 7). Since novice modellers do not engage with requirements modelling in the same way as professional modellers, they are often not in a position to explicitly articulate the kinds of AI support they need.

This chapter tackles the challenge of exploring the need for adaptive AI support among novice modellers. To this end, it addresses RQ4: *How do domain experts experience requirements modelling with a block-based AI-infused tool?*

This question is addressed through three sub-questions:

- RQ4.1: To what extent can large language models perform model-to-text transformation?
- RQ4.2: To what extent do users follow the suggestions provided by the system?
- RQ4.3: How do the agronomists perceive the AI-based assistance offered by ModeLLer?

We tackled this challenge by incorporating AI-based features into the tool and conducting a second user study. Figure 10.1 outlines the validation phase executed to address the sub-questions. In preparing the study, we were inspired by previous research [122], taking the approach of anticipating the user study through a technical evaluation.

Therefore, to answer RQ4.1, we first conducted a **technical evaluation** of LLM capabilities for model-to-text transformation, to inform the integration of such functionality into the tool. This evaluation is described in Sec. 10.2.

Given the encouraging results of the study, we extended the tool with the LLM-based functionalities described in Sec. 8.2.3 (**AI-Infused Tool v2**). Afterwards, we set up a study with agronomists who performed a task with the tool, while a **Wizard of Oz** (WOz) protocol was used to simulate system suggestions.

To answer RQ4.2, we analysed interaction logs and screen recordings to examine users' uptake of suggestions during modelling.

To answer RQ4.3, we conducted a think-aloud protocol and post-test interviews to capture participants' perceptions and feedback on assistance needs.

This study is described in Sec. 10.3. We refer the reader to the corresponding sections for details on the methodologies adopted.

■ Compared to prior work, this evaluation: 1) involves domain experts performing a modelling task with ModeLLer while a WOz setup simulates adaptive AI assistance, 2) records interaction patterns and Human–AI interaction flows during modelling, and 3) collects feedback on assistance needs after users have explored the AI-infused tool.

Table 10.1: Summary of the UML case studies and available artefacts.

Case	Description	UML	Software	Format	
1	IoT vineyard monitoring system	An IoT monitoring system based on sensors installed on-field that measures several parameters in the vineyard to optimize organic treatments.	No: nodes #9; arches #12. Types: class, aggregation,	StarUML	png svg xmi
2	Soil scanner	A soil scanner with sensors and AI-based software that measures soil parameters to optimise fertilisation.	No: nodes #12; arches #20 Types: class, aggregation, direct association	draw.io	png svg drawio
3	Smart irrigation	An AI-based system to monitor field and weather conditions and manage irrigation	No: nodes #8; arches #9 Types: class, direct association	ModeLLer	png PlantUML xmi

10.2 Technical Evaluation

For convenience, we restate here the RQ addressed in the technical evaluation:

- RQ4.1: To what extent can large language models perform model-to-text transformation?

The technical evaluation assessed the quality of the output produced by LLMs when transforming diagrams into natural language. This was conducted to inform the design of an interactive component that complements the tool by offering natural language descriptions of the diagrams.

10.2.1 Methodology

Consistent with previous evaluations (cf. Sec. 8.3 and 9), we focused on domain models—UML class diagrams—and we executed two prompts in ChatGPT. The first prompt generates a textual description of the model tailored to non-technical users. The second prompt creates a table containing the classes extracted from the diagram, a contextual description of the class role and interaction, a classification of the class, size and coordinates indicating the position of the class within the diagram. Results from the prompts should provide data to enrich future versions of the tool with an interactive layer to overlay the diagram with contextual tooltips with class explanation.

The current version of the tool includes only a subset of the AI functionalities envisioned in this study (cf. Ch. 8). This is due to the limited time available for development and the resources required by the AI services needed to run the tool. The remaining functionalities are planned to be integrated in subsequent studies.

Cases We selected UML class diagrams, which are among the notations incorporated in our RE method. These representations are used to depict the structure of the process to-be, including all involved actors, digital systems, components, and natural resources, as well as the relationships among these entities. As we plan to create an AI-generated web-based layer to integrate into our EUD tool, we selected test data that reflects real-world contexts in which stakeholders may utilise a variety of diagramming tools. In this experiment, we assess diagrams created with: (1) StarUML and (2) draw.io, both recommended in the formalisation procedure 4.2.3, and (3) ModeLLer V1, which incorporates the PlantUML library and generates diagrams in the PlantUML style. We added

a first variant by considering multiple formats supported by the tools: PNG, SVG, XML, PlantUML and drawio.

Table 10.1 summarises the three real-world cases extracted from the CODECS project, detailing UML structure and format specifications. Diagram 1 represents an IoT system for the remote monitoring of vineyard conditions; diagram 2 depicts a scanner system for real-time soil analysis; diagram 3 refers to a smart irrigation system for remote control of irrigation.

Prompts For executing prompts, we selected GPT, a prominent LLM that has recently introduced vision capabilities (gpt-image-1), enabling image input understanding. We ran our prompts using the web user interface and adhered to the prompt engineering guidelines provided in the OpenAI Cookbook¹. In addition, we included a comparative variant by evaluating both GPT-4o – the first model to natively implement gpt-image-1 – and GPT-4.1, which is declared to feature improved instruction following and context examples.

At this stage, we did not use personas, as the objective was to assess the model capabilities through a simple and neutral prompting strategy, without introducing additional guidance. Persona-based prompting is left for future work.

We designed two prompts: the first, a one-shot prompt, was intended to assess GPT baseline ability to describe diagrams with minimal instruction. The second, a chain-of-thought prompt, was chosen to explore whether a more structured reasoning process could improve the extraction of structural and spatial information and support the generation of more context-aware descriptions. The two prompts are as follows:

Prompt 1 “Write a summary that explains the uploaded diagram to a non-technical audience”.

Prompt 2 “First, analyse the uploaded UML class diagram. Then, extract all classes and create a table with a row for each class and a column named NAME with the class name. Then, create a column DESCRIPTION containing a 20-30 word description of the class that explains to a non-technical audience the role of the class within the system and operations performed in association with other connected classes. Then, create a column TYPE containing the type of entity represented, either digital, actor/organisation, natural resource or other type of resource. Then, create additional columns: WIDTH, containing the class width; HEIGHT, containing the class height; X, containing the x-position of the class; Y, containing the y-position of the class. Convert all values into relative values. Return the complete table”.

In prompt 1, we did not impose length restrictions, as diagrams may vary in size; however we specified the target, consisting of users not having knowledge of formal notations.

Prompt 2 is oriented towards the creation of an interactive layer with tooltips, with content returned in the form of a table. The prompt is articulated in 4 steps requiring respectively to (1) extract classes, (2) write short descriptions based on the class role and neighboring relationships, (3) classify classes into human, natural or technological entities, and (4) extract class size and coordinates within the diagram. Following GPT guidelines, we structured and ran prompt 2 as a chain-of-thought in GPT-4.1, whereas in GPT-4o, we decomposed the prompt into separate, sequential instructions.

¹<http://github.com/openai/openai-cookbook> (last accessed: 5 February 2026)

To clarify our objectives, Fig. 10.2 illustrates an example of the intended output for the interactive layer. While the diagram itself is human-generated, the accompanying explanatory content is produced using the designed prompts.

Evaluation criteria We were inspired by previous work from Ferrari et al. [71] and adopted the four quality criteria that are also relevant to our context. We adapted the statements such that they are applicable to diagram-to-text transformation:

- **Completeness:** the text covers the content of all the (main) entities with a sufficient degree of detail to explain the content of the model to potential stakeholders.
- **Correctness:** the text describes a system structure (e.g. domain) that is coherent and consistent with the diagram.
- **Degree of understandability:** the text is sufficiently clear, given the complexity of the diagram, and does not contain redundancies.
- **Terminological alignment:** the terminology used in the generated text aligns with the one used in the diagram, so that textual references can be clearly traced back to the corresponding model elements.

We introduced a fifth criterion to assess the coordinates extracted in *Prompt 2*, which are used to generate the interactive layer:

- **Acceptability** the extent to which the positions of the tooltips in the generated interactive layer align with their correct placement as defined in the UML source model.

Figure 10.2: Example of LLM-generated interactive layer.

Evaluation approach We assessed largely the same criteria across both prompts, introducing minor variations in the evaluation approach.

Prompt 1 to evaluate the summaries generated by Prompt 1, we assessed each criterion individually. Both prompts were independently evaluated by two raters using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “1 – Not fulfilled at all” to “5 – Completely fulfilled”. The ratings were averaged to determine inter-rater agreement. Additionally, a text field (“Notes”) was included to document any observations or comments regarding the evaluations.

Prompt 2 to evaluate the table obtained from Prompt 2, we performed independent evaluations for each column in four steps:

Class extraction this step focuses on completeness, considering the following metrics: true positives (nodes correctly detected), false negatives (nodes missed), and false positives (nodes incorrectly identified). As this evaluation is objective, it is conducted once by a single evaluator.

Tooltip description this addresses three quality criteria: completeness, correctness and degree of understandability, using the same 5-point Likert scale applied in *Prompt 1*, except for completeness, which is assessed objectively as a single accuracy measure based on the ratio of edges mentioned to incident edges. Terminological alignment is not included, as the explanatory and concise nature of tooltips naturally results in terminology differing from the diagram.

Classification this evaluation step is assessed once using a boolean value to indicate correct or incorrect classification, along with a note field for additional observations.

Positioning this evaluation step is addressed through the criterion of acceptability and is evaluated through the 5-point Likert scale applied above, along with the “Notes” field.

10.2.2 Execution and Results (RQ4.1)

We started our prompts with the instruction “Execute this prompt in isolation”, requesting to perform actions without considering previous messages. Both prompts were evaluated independently by two evaluators (the author of the thesis and the second author of the paper [MoDRE25] [139]), and the results from both evaluations were averaged.

Diagram summary

Prompt 1 was repeated on 18 instances, considering all cases and format variants (cf. Table 10.1) and GPT models 4o and 4.1. The average word count for all 18 summaries is 220 words, ranging from 176 to 260. Notably, GPT-4.1 outputs are longer (239 words) compared to GPT-4o (202 words).

The average output quality is *high*. Both GPT models achieve scores between 4 and 5 for all dimensions. Overall, there is no significant difference between cases, formats or

models. Only the correctness dimension shows slightly more variability, with GPT-4.1 generally yielding constantly better results.

The notes added by the evaluators suggest that several outputs included *extra content not present in the original data*. Furthermore, the text frequently exhibited *subjective commentary* and *interpretative statements*, for example, “more sustainable practices”. There were a few *instances of hallucination* (for example, adding unmentioned operations of calibrations), as well as some omissions.

Tooltips table

Prompt 2 was executed on 10 instances, covering all cases and both models, with a focus on input formats of type *image*. Thus, only PNG and SVG formats were considered, while XML, drawio and PlantUML were excluded, as these do not contain the spatial information required for the evaluation. The execution returned 10 tables containing one row for each detected class, and columns with class name, description, classification, size and localisation data (coordinates).

Class extraction Across all cases, GPT-4.1 achieves perfect scores for *precision* (calculated as the number of nodes correctly detected over the number of nodes correctly detected plus the number of nodes wrongly detected) and *recall* (the number of nodes correctly detected over the nodes correctly detected plus the number of nodes missing). In contrast, GPT-4o shows some variability, with lower scores in case 1 for both variants (0.57 and 0.75 for precision; 0.44 and 1.00 recall). For the remaining cases, both GPT models reach perfect scores.

Tooltip description Results for this evaluation step are presented case by case. In *Case 1 - IoT on-field*, GPT-4.1 outperforms GPT-4o across all metrics and formats. For PNG, GPT-4.1 shows higher completeness (0.71 vs. 0.54), correctness (4.22 vs. 2.11), and understandability (4.50 vs. 2.22). In SVG format, completeness is slightly higher for GPT-4.1 (0.54 vs. 0.46), with correctness similar for both (3.67), while understandability remains higher for GPT-4.1 (4.17 vs. 4.22). In *Case 2 - Soil Scanner*, completeness differs significantly, with GPT-4o achieving a much higher score (0.91) compared to GPT-4.1 (0.41). However, GPT-4.1 outperforms GPT-4o in correctness (4.38 vs. 2.69) and understandability (4.69 vs. 2.69). In *Case 3 - Smart Irrigation*, GPT-4.1 consistently delivers higher correctness and understandability scores (around 4) for both PNG and SVG, although completeness remains low (0.30–0.35) and similar to GPT-4o. In contrast, GPT-4o achieves lower correctness and understandability (2.25–2.38). Notes from the evaluators are similar to those observed in Prompt 1, highlighting some recurring issues and tendencies. Among issues, it is reported that *aggregation relationships are frequently not recognised or properly explained* or *important piece of information are sometimes missing*. Among the tendencies, it is reported *content additions*, such as background, contextual, or qualitative information, and the inclusion of positive or promotional language about technology benefits. Occasional hallucinations are present, such as actions not depicted in the diagram.

Classification The overall accuracy of classification is high across all cases, with an average of 91% (9 errors out of 100 instances). GPT-4.1 achieved perfect accuracy (0% error rate), while GPT-4o committed all 9 errors (18% error rate). Analysing by case, GPT-4o error rates are higher for *Case 1 - IoT on-field* (27.8%) and *Case 3 - Smart irrigation* (25%), while for *Case 2 - Soil scanner* are lower (8.3%). The errors made by GPT-4o are mainly due to empty values — stemming from unextracted classes, which were counted as errors. However, two instances within Case 3 — weather station and moisture sensor, were classified as *natural* resources, instead of *digital*. This may indicate a more accurate understanding of domain-specific concepts by the newer model.

Positioning Results of the acceptability of detected class positioning indicate that GPT-4.1 generally achieves higher scores, consistently reaching 4 or above in most instances. In contrast, GPT-4o shows greater variability and generally lower scores, with some values at or near 1. In several cases, all classes were extracted and positioned close to their actual locations; however, overlaps or minor misalignments, especially in y-positioning for crowded areas — were observed, while x-positioning was generally more accurate. Notably, there are exceptions — such as in Case 2, format *svg* — where GPT-4o outperforms GPT-4.1. This output demonstrated precise mapping with boxes aligned with class centres and correct sizing.

Hallucinations Some instances of hallucinations were observed, although these could be related to the tendency to add contextual information and interpretations. A closer look at the hallucinations reveals the introduction of non-existent operations or class relations. For example, in Prompt 1 applied to *Case 2 - Soil scanner*, the generated output includes the sentence: “*The demo farm manager also sends soil samples to a soil lab*”, which is plausible, though it is not present in the input model. This kind of error could stem from the attempt to fill in perceived gaps in the representation, particularly when diagrams are partially structured. This may suggest that the model is leveraging probabilistic inference rather than relying strictly on visual-textual alignment.

10.2.3 Answer to RQ4.1: To what extent can large language models perform model-to-text transformation?

Results from prompt executions indicate GPT capability of producing good-quality content, with neither model consistently outperforming the other across all criteria. GPT-4.1 tends to generate more verbose text and interpretations, while offering greater accuracy in class detection, classification and positioning. Instead, GPT-4o occasionally achieves higher completeness but manifests more variability and reduced quality in other dimensions. We observe limitations in contextual understanding and in the ability to capture granular information, such as aggregations and labels. Additionally, some instances of hallucinations were observed.

10.3 Wizard of Oz Study

For convenience, we restate here the RQs addressed in the WOz study:

- RQ4.2: To what extent do users follow the suggestions provided by the system?

- RQ4.3: How do the agronomists perceive the AI-based assistance offered by *ModelLer*?

To evaluate whether the envisioned RS could benefit novices, we carried out a study with domain experts leveraging a WOz approach.

10.3.1 Methodology

The WOz methodology [52] has proven effective in AI research as a way to prototype future intelligent capabilities before full automation, enabling researchers to study Human-AI dynamics under realistic conditions [49, 93].

Therefore, we set up a WOz workflow to simulate part of the AI-infused system, namely the Recommender System (RS), which complements the tool with notification-based assistance (cf. Ch. 8). This choice was motivated by the fact that recommendations are highly contingent on users' actions, making it difficult to anticipate a priori which suggestions to issue and when.

Participants

The study involved eight domain experts ($n = 8$). We selected this sample size in line with usability-testing guidelines [102], suggesting that approximately 10 ± 2 participants are typically sufficient for identifying the majority of usability issues in think-aloud-style evaluations, while still enabling an in-depth and manageable analysis of behavioural and qualitative data. Participants were adults spanning from young to mid-career, with a majority of females. Most were researchers or practitioners with a background in agronomy. They reported low to moderate experience with modelling notations and tools, while none identified as an expert modeller.

These characteristics were collected through a demographic questionnaire administered after the WOz session. All data were collected and managed anonymously, in full compliance with data protection regulations and with respect for participants privacy. All participants were fully informed about the nature and purpose of the study and provided their informed consent prior to participation. After the WOz session, participants were informed about the simulated nature of the study.

Procedure

The study was carried out over multiple days, with participants completing the test in individual sessions conducted remotely through Teams. The sessions were conducted by the author of the thesis. Each test session lasted approximately 35 minutes and consisted of three main steps:

1. *Training*: participants were introduced to the modelling activity and the tool through a six-minute video.
2. *Interactive session*: this session on the tool lasted 15 to 20 minutes. Participants carried out a modelling task based on a digital agriculture scenario while verbalising their thoughts through a think-aloud protocol. During this phase, a WOz setup

was employed, in which the participants shared their screen, and the moderator simulated the behaviour of the RS by providing suggestions when participants encountered difficulties. During the session, interaction logs were collected and stored by the system for subsequent analysis.

3. *Interview*: After completing the task, participants joined the moderator in a wrap-up session. During this phase, the WOz setup was revealed, and participants provided feedback on their experience in using the tool and reported their assistance needs. Two open-ended questions were posed: (1) *How did you find the AI-enabled features while you were modelling?* and (2) *What kinds of support—AI-based or otherwise—would make modelling easier for you?* Participants were also invited to provide any further comments or reflections on their experience.

Task The task was designed to preserve the open-ended nature of modelling and consisted of an exploration of the tool framed within a scenario of agricultural digitalisation. The scenario was based on data extracted from the CODECS LLs. Participants were tasked with creating a model capturing the key elements and relationships of the scenario, drawing on their own background knowledge, without a predefined solution. The scenario concerned the use of drone technology for crop management and included a remote sensing system collecting agronomic data through drones and a digital platform for data processing. Participants were encouraged to extend the model with additional actors, data sources, or system components and explore the tool functionalities.

WOz Notifications Hints were delivered through a chat controlled by the moderator, resulting in contextual pop-up notifications appearing on the user's screen. This mechanism followed a WOz approach, in which the moderator simulated the RS. Hints were triggered upon the detection of a stuck state, inferred both through think-aloud verbalisations and observed interaction patterns, such as repeated execution of the same actions, frequent undo/redo cycles, or prolonged inactivity.

The purpose was to support the user's intended actions, and guide participants toward modelling goals while preserving exploratory behaviour. Consistent with Repenning's AAA model (cf. AAA model in Sec. 2.2.3 and AI-based functionalities in Sec. 8.2.3), hints were provided at three computational thinking (CT) stages:

- **Abstraction**: aimed at eliciting model entities, e.g., encouraging exploration of the available blocks.
- **Automation**: addressing practical interaction, e.g., drag-and-drop actions or zooming.
- **Analysis**: providing feedback related to the output model or block structure, including suggestions to leverage tool functionalities such as the diagram reader.

Thematic analysis

The think-aloud session and post-task interview were analysed through thematic analysis of the transcripts, following Braun and Clarke's approach [39]. The author of the thesis carried out the coding, and the supervisors subsequently reviewed the resulting codes.

Figure 10.3: Woz notification distribution

10.3.2 Results (RQ4.2-RQ4.3)

We report results from three complementary analyses: interaction logs, recorded sessions of participants, and thematic analysis of the think-aloud session and post-test feedback. Interaction logs are available in Annex 13 [130], the remaining study materials, together with the transcripts and codebook from the thematic analysis, are available in Annex 14 [130].

Adoption of system suggestions

During the exploratory sessions, which lasted an average of 18 minutes and 32 seconds, the moderator sent a total of 34 Woz notifications, averaging 4.25 notifications per session.

Fig. 10.3 illustrates the distribution of the notifications. Each row represents a session, the x-axis contains elapsed time, and the grey background bars indicate session duration. Markers indicate individual notifications, with colours corresponding to the type of notification classified into one of the CT stages: abstraction (blue), automation (orange), and analysis (green). Automation-related hints are the most frequent and appear throughout the sessions, often occurring in the second part. These hints mainly addressed operational issues, such as managing aggregations, associations or drag-and-drop (e.g., “use the selector *is part of* within the sensors block to connect the sensor block to the drone”). Analysis-related hints were delivered in half of the sessions, suggesting revision of the elements created (e.g., “check advisor’s connections”). Abstraction-related hints are less frequent and tend to appear earlier in the sessions, supporting users in identifying model elements through interaction with the toolbox (e.g., “explore blocks on the menu”).

To assess users’ reaction to Woz notifications, we first examined how quickly participants reacted to assistance by closing the alert appearing on the screen. Fig.10.4 shows the distribution of alert-closing times across the sessions. Each boxplot represents one session, illustrating the variability in how long participants took to dismiss system alerts. Substantial between-session variability emerges. Sessions 2, 3, 5, and 6

Figure 10.4: Alert closing time

show short and relatively stable closing times, suggesting that alerts were dismissed in less than 5 seconds. Sessions 1, 4, and 8 exhibit longer median closing times, indicating that participants spent more time reading the alert content. Session 7 presents highly heterogeneous behaviour, with some alerts dismissed rapidly, while others were kept open for extended periods. Overall, the figure highlights that alert engagement was not uniform, varying both across participants and within sessions.

Finally, through observation of the recorded sessions, we assessed whether the received suggestions were successful. We identified three outcomes: *success*, when the user successfully performed the suggested action; *fail*, when the user attempted the action without achieving the suggested result; and *missed*, when a suggestion was ignored by the user.

Fig.10.5 summarises hint outcomes across all sessions. This distribution shows that nearly 80% of users followed the system suggestions, while only a small proportion ignored them. Among all provided suggestions, half successfully supported users, whereas the remaining half did not lead to a successful outcome.

We investigated the variability of suggestion success across sessions. Fig.10.6 highlights session variability. Sessions 2, 3, and 4 show high success rates. In contrast, sessions 6 and 8 exhibit null success, with hints either failing or not being followed at all. The remaining sessions display a more balanced distribution. Overall, there is significant variability across sessions.

To assess whether variability persists at the level of suggestion type, we analysed hint success rate based on the CT stage. The results presented in Fig.10.7 indicate that suggestions related to the automation stage achieve the highest success rate (53%), with minimal dismissal by users. In contrast, suggestions associated with abstraction and analysis exhibit a more balanced distribution of outcomes, with abstraction hints showing a comparatively higher level of dismissal.

Overall, the results indicate a high degree of engagement with the system suggestions, with nearly all suggestions taken into account by participants. Alert-closing times indicate that, while some suggestions were dismissed rapidly, users selectively invested

Figure 10.5: Pop-up notifications success rate aggregated

time in evaluating others. Approximately half of the provided suggestions successfully supported users. Among these, suggestions were predominantly related to the automation stage, which offered immediately actionable guidance.

Feedback on AI assistance

Participants' feedback revealed *a mixed experience with WOz notifications*. The majority of participants perceived the suggestions received as *useful aids*, especially when they addressed practical issues: "Oh, oops. I'm writing too much. Ok, I should use shorter names for activities" (P2). However, other participants reported that such hints were *misaligned with workflow*: "The pop-up works if you take the time to read it. I basically didn't read them and just kept going" (P6). Some notifications were *hard to interpret*: "I didn't understand in the beginning when it tells me to using *is part of*" (P1), and others were perceived as *constraining*: "At the beginning I'd like to enter longer information without being prompted to shorten it, and then streamline it later, so I can check whether the generated text fully reflects what I meant to include in the diagram" (P5).

Among the LLM-based components, the *diagram reader emerged as the most useful*, helping users to reflect on the model under construction: "the AI is kind of trying to help me to describe this system in this diagram reader" (P7). However, one participant considered it *visually less appealing* when compared to other components: "I did not really look at the text that much. I was just focusing on the diagrams and then on the map. I didn't read much the texts" (P2). In some cases, the generated description introduced interactions that were not present in the diagram, resulting in hallucinations. This could foster *reliance on the textual output* rather than on the underlying model structure. As P8 noted: "For me, the system was working because what I had in mind was written there, so from my point of view I was doing relatively well." In some instances, the textual description also *conflicted with WOz suggestions* by suggesting that required elements

Figure 10.6: Pop-up notifications success rate per session

were already present: “I have to write the activities in here. Oh. The activities are already written for me in the diagram reader” (P7). Text-based instructions and contextual hints functionalities remained peripheral, as many participants declared having *low visibility* and having noticed them sparingly: “I focused on the central area, where I was supposed to work, and only at a certain point I realised that there were other elements” (P7) and would *require time to explore* the tool entirely: “I’ll just need to learn more, like get so immersed” (P2). In contrast, for some participants, these features proved *effective*. For example, P4, reflecting on their experience with textual instructions, remarked: “When you ask to build an activity or an actor, it works very well, I think. And then I asked him to link some features, so Ok” (P4). However, they perceived this interaction mode as *less engaging than blocks* and *more appropriate for advanced use*: “Instinctively, I would not use it. I would prefer building my actor, my activity, etc. But maybe then, when you’re used to the tool, maybe it’s faster to ask AI” (P4).

Regarding support needs, participants generally did not request additional theory. In-

Figure 10.7: Hints success rate per CT stage

stead, they expressed *appreciation for a learning-by-doing approach*, where understanding emerges through hands-on exploration. As P6 remarked, “I learn by trying it out”. A clear *need for examples* also emerged, with participants suggesting that worked references could help clarify both the expected output and the use of modelling constructs. As one participant noted, “Maybe it would make sense to include an example, like showing an already completed diagram” (P3). Moreover, participants expressed a preference for *on-demand validation*, which they could actively request at moments of uncertainty: “I was looking how the diagram worked, I don’t know if it made sense or not. Probably then I would have to ask someone who tell me ok, this is the diagram is well conceptualised or not. I don’t know if the AI can do it” (P1). Finally, several participants suggested *conversational support*, enabling them to ask questions in natural language “I think it’s nice to have the possibility to ask some questions. For example, how can I link my drone to my server?” (P4).

Overall, users reported a mixed experience. WOz notifications were generally perceived as helpful when they provided concrete guidance. However, sometimes they were dismissed, hard to interpret, or perceived as constraining. While some LLM-based features were perceived as secondary, the diagram reader was most valued for sensemaking, yet occasionally could foster overreliance on the textual output and conflicts with system notifications. Participants preferred practice-oriented, on-demand support—such as working examples, validation at moments of uncertainty, and conversational help for specific questions—over additional theory or training.

10.3.3 Discussion

Findings from the user session suggest that AI notifications were effective in assisting novice modellers. We observed a process of co-adaptation [77] between the system and the users: the system issued notifications in response to users’ ongoing actions, while users adjusted their behaviour to the suggestions and incorporated them into their workflow. The higher success rate of suggestions provided at the automation stage suggests the value of prompts that help users resolve impasses with minimal interpretation effort, indicating the effectiveness of operational guidance. At the same time, unsuccessful suggestions highlight design space for improving how assistance is delivered and integrated into the workflow. Future work should better scaffold co-adaptation therefore examining why suggestions fail while also assessing users’ satisfaction with the assistance received.

User feedback indicates that, despite sharing a similar background, participants adopted different modelling strategies and perceived AI assistance in different ways. This can be further confirmed by the log analysis, revealing multiple patterns of human-AI interaction. Fig. 10.3.3 reports two representative examples of interaction patterns overlaid on the User–AI interaction flow model illustrated in Fig. 8.6 (cf. *User-AI Interaction Flows* in Sec. 8.2.4). Thicker links indicate more intense interactions, while the circles represent WOz suggestions. Yellow circles denote suggestions that were followed, whereas grey circles indicate dismissed suggestions. A comparison between Pattern 4 (Fig. 10.8a) and Pattern 8 (Fig. 10.8b) highlights differences in user behaviour. Pattern 4 reflects a wide-ranging approach, with users actively engaging with all available AI functionalities. By contrast, Pattern 2 shows a more focused workflow centred on the diagram reader, on which users relied more heavily while largely disregarding other AI elements.

(a) Session 4

(b) Session 8

Figure 10.8: Session patterns

These patterns confirm two distinct behaviours also emerging from the feedback, with P4 exhibiting a more exploratory approach and P8 being more focused on validating the output through the diagram reader and dismissing system suggestions. These findings suggest guiding future AI assistance through the identification of these interaction patterns and enabling adaptive support accordingly.

10.3.4 Answer to RQ4.2: *To what extent do users follow the suggestions provided by the system?*

Findings from the WOz study suggest that AI-based notifications can effectively support novice modellers. Participants frequently adjusted their behaviour by incorporating

these suggestions into their workflow. Overall, the results highlight the value of prompts that help users overcome impasses, underscoring the effectiveness of operational guidance. At the same time, instances of unsuccessful or disregarded suggestions indicate that such assistance is not equally effective for all users, thus pointing to a design space for more effective integration of support into the modelling process.

10.3.5 Answer to RQ4.3: *How do the agronomists perceive the AI-based assistance offered by ModeLLer?*

User feedback indicates that, despite sharing a similar professional background, participants perceived AI assistance in distinct ways. This observation is confirmed by the interaction log analysis, which revealed multiple patterns of Human–AI collaboration emerging during the modelling sessions. Among the AI-based features introduced, the WOz suggestions were perceived as particularly effective, especially when delivered at moments of impasse. In addition, the model-to-text translation feature was actively used to clarify and validate the model under construction.

10.4 Conclusions

In this final section, we discuss the threats to validity and draw conclusions on the fourth design science cycle addressing RQ4 (*How do domain experts experience requirements modelling with a block-based AI-infused tool?*). This design cycle also concludes the thesis.

10.4.1 Threats to Validity

Due to the exploratory nature of RQ4, several limitations must be acknowledged, relating both to the technical evaluation and to the WOz experiment.

Regarding technical evaluation, we acknowledge several limitations, both in terms of the small number of cases evaluated, the number of UML elements contained, and LLMs assessed. The evaluation had a primary scope to preliminarily assess the feasibility of the functionalities to be incorporated into ModeLLer before exposing them to users, as well as to evaluate their potential in supporting future AI-enhanced features. To partially mitigate these constraints, we selected a variety of models representative of those likely to emerge in living lab (LL) contexts. However, this choice may have led us to prioritise ecological relevance over exhaustive coverage of modelling constructs, potentially overlooking other aspects that could influence system performance. Furthermore, among the various LLM-based functionalities envisioned for the tool, the technical evaluation was limited to the model-to-text transformation. The other AI-based features were not subjected to a prior technical verification, as they would require different evaluation settings and appropriate assessment techniques tailored to their specific interaction logic and expected outputs.

Regarding the WOz study, first, the produced models were not validated at the content level, as the goal was to observe interaction patterns rather than assess artefact correctness. Second, we did not collect standard usability or satisfaction measures, given

the exploratory and formative nature of the study, which prioritised exploring functionality and interaction over summative assessment. Third, the limited session duration may have constrained exploration and shaped how participants engaged with assistance compared to more realistic, extended use. Fourth, the specific task design and the chosen scenario may potentially limit the generalisability of the findings to other contexts. Finally, the study did not include baseline conditions or comparisons with alternative tools or assistance mechanisms, limiting causal claims about the added value of specific features.

10.4.2 Summary

The final iteration of the design science project in this thesis evaluated the latest AI-infused version of ModelLer (V2) through a technical evaluation and a WOz study involving domain experts.

LLM-based features

Results from the prompt executions in the technical evaluation indicate GPT capability of producing good-quality content. This confirms the feasibility of using LLMs to assist stakeholders in understanding diagrams created with semi-formal notations.

In line with previous research [71, 111], we observed limitations in contextual understanding and in the ability to capture granular information, such as aggregations and certain labels in associations. In addition, occasional instances of hallucinated content were identified. A primary concern is that such inaccuracies may compromise the reliability of the generated explanations. In the context of supporting stakeholders in model interpretation, hallucinations may lead to misinterpretations and undermine user trust in the system. Despite these limitations, the relatively low frequency and limited severity of the observed issues led us to proceed with integrating the feature, while acknowledging the need for safeguards and further refinement. From a design perspective, a preferable behaviour would be for the model to explicitly signal potential ambiguities, uncertainties, or areas of incompleteness in the diagram, rather than generating plausible but non-existent content.

These findings highlight the need to conduct further research at a technical level to better understand the internal reasoning patterns of the model when dealing with diagrammatic content, for example, constraining outputs through schema-driven guidance that could mitigate hallucinations and inconsistencies and improve the reliability and usefulness of the generated results. This consideration extends to all the LLM-based features integrated into the tool, which did not undergo a dedicated technical assessment comparable to that conducted for the model-to-text functionality. As these features are likewise prompt-based, they remain susceptible to unpredictable errors, inconsistencies, and occasional hallucinations.

At the same time, such LLM-based solutions are increasingly widespread in contemporary digital tools, and users are progressively accustomed to encountering and managing these types of imperfections [15]. Nevertheless, reliance on user familiarity alone is insufficient. In parallel with ongoing prompt refinement and technical optimisation, it is essential to incorporate explicit safeguards, such as clear disclaimers. Ensuring

transparency in how AI-generated suggestions are produced and presented is critical to supporting informed use.

User study

The WOz study provided several insights into how domain experts explored and perceived an AI-based requirements modelling tool in terms of system functionalities and interaction strategies. We summarise these insights into three takeaway lessons that provide a roadmap for future design of modelling assistance for novices:

(1) The agronomists approached the task using different strategies and responded to assistance in heterogeneous ways. An intelligent modelling assistant for novice modellers should therefore adapt to diverse interaction styles and learn from user preferences, rather than being constrained to standard interaction patterns.

(2) Users are more likely to accept suggestions when they struggle, and they are offered concrete solutions. Accordingly, an intelligent modelling system should detect modelling challenges and provide concise, actionable hints that minimise the cognitive effort needed to interpret them and to get unstuck.

(3) Our findings suggest that novice modellers may benefit from a practice-oriented approach to modelling. The interaction fostered engagement by supporting a learning-by-doing workflow, helping users articulate abstraction through block-based construction. In this context, user agency should remain central, while intelligent assistance is peripheral and transparent, being offered primarily on demand to avoid disrupting users' exploratory flow.

📌 RQ4 recap

This chapter has provided an answer to RQ4: *How do domain experts experience requirements modelling with a block-based AI-infused tool?* The agronomists' experience with the AI-infused version of ModeLLer revealed that domain experts can engage with requirements modelling through a block-based tool, as this supports a learning-by-doing approach. At the same time, the user sessions showed that interaction styles and responses to AI assistance vary across users. AI-based aids are most valuable when they are transparent and offered at moments of difficulty, helping users overcome impasses with minimal cognitive effort. The findings suggest that AI can effectively support novice modellers, provided that human agency remains central and assistance is designed to be peripheral and non-intrusive, so as to sustain rather than replace the cognitive processes involved in modelling.

Part IV
Conclusion

Chapter 11

Contributions and Limitations

In this thesis, we addressed the problem of knowledge exchange in agricultural living labs (LLs) by leveraging visual models to support communication and the analysis of process digitalisation. To this end, we selected MoDRE notations for their widespread use throughout the software lifecycle.

These notations are characterised by a defined syntax and partially specified semantics. A first advantage is their dual nature: they provide a graphical representation that is human-interpretable, while also offering an underlying textual encoding that is directly usable by software and AI. In this sense, they can effectively act as a shared “lingua franca” between stakeholders and computational tools. A second advantage is their technical maturity and their ability to provide complementary views, including domain structure, operational workflow, goals, and rationale. Building on this choice, we followed a design science approach [227] to iteratively design and validate two modelling-related artefacts: a method—*PoMeLO*—and a tool—*ModelLer*, generating contributions for both research and practice.

11.1 Summary

The research was grounded both in the practical needs emerging from the community of local practices within the LLs of the European research project CODECS and in theoretical foundations drawn from RE, EUD, and, more broadly, model-related literature across SE, IS and HCI.

The research unfolded through four engineering cycles, each addressing a specific RQ, progressively refining the two artefacts.

RQ1 – How can we carry out process modelling using semi-formal notations within agricultural living labs? The first iteration focused on selecting suitable notations from MoDRE and defining a RE method through an action research approach [229]. We drew on established RE practices and adapted them to the characteristics of open, multi-actor ecosystems such as agricultural LLs. It resulted in a structured procedure for data collection and formalisation, using complementary notations—iStar, UML class diagrams, and BPMN—to provide goal-, domain-, and process-oriented perspectives. The method was validated with pilot LLs and subsequently applied and evaluated across 20 LLs, confirming, through an assessment based on Technology Acceptance Model

(TAM) [56], its suitability for multi-stakeholder settings and its ability to balance methodological rigour with accessibility for non-RE experts.

RQ₂ – How do living lab stakeholders experience comprehending and creating models with semi-formal notations? The second iteration aimed to empower LL stakeholders to autonomously apply the method and create models. This motivated the adoption of an EUD perspective, aimed at lowering entry barriers to requirements modelling. To this end, we investigated through a field study [207] how domain experts—such as agronomists and LL stakeholders—engage with semi-formal models both in model creation and interpretation. The study pointed to the feasibility of requirements modelling by and for end users. It also highlighted that semi-formal modelling languages can effectively support multi-stakeholder settings, enabling a rapid immersion into a case study, fostering a shared understanding of the case under discussion. At the same time, it showed that modelling effort is substantial and further amplified with novice modellers. These findings suggested the need for an entry-level modelling environment to support non-expert participation.

RQ₃ – How can we empower novice and non-technical stakeholders in requirements modelling? The third iteration translated empirical evidence from the implementation of the method and insights from modelling-related literature into design implications for an AI-enhanced modelling tool for novices. The tool was developed following a meta-design approach [77], combined with computational thinking (CT) frameworks [22, 181] for the design and assessment of EUD environments in alignment with users' computational literacy. A block-based approach was chosen, based on a visual language aligned with agricultural concepts, to support users through constrained composition, incremental construction, and immediate feedback. The validation through a user study combined artefact and user-centred assessment, examining both the tool effectiveness in supporting modellers and the technical feasibility of the AI-supported functionalities.

RQ₄ – How do domain experts experience requirements modelling with a block-based AI-infused tool? The last iteration introduced AI-based functionalities following an approach for the development of AI-infused systems [15], in which AI provides assistance while users retain control of the system. A technical assessment anticipated the integration of selected functionalities by testing the capability of LLMs to generate meaningful textual outputs from semi-formal models. The AI-enhanced tool was validated in a user study with agronomists who performed a modelling task based on an agricultural digitalisation scenario. A Wizard of Oz setup [52] simulated additional AI support. Through this user study, we explored the modelling strategies adopted by novice modellers and how they drew on AI-assisted functionalities during the task. Findings indicate the effectiveness of a block-based approach for introducing modelling. Users benefit from a learning-by-doing approach to modelling. Moreover, they adopt heterogeneous strategies, calling for assistance that accommodates different interaction styles and preferences.

Table 11.1: Artefacts produced in this thesis

	Artefact	Description
1	PoMeLO method	Guidelines for data collection in LLS, supporting the collection of process-related data through interviews, workshops, and focus groups. Includes templates and practical examples. Available in Annex 4 [130]
2		Formalisation procedure providing stepwise guidance for transforming qualitative information collected in LLS into semi-formal representations using UML, iStar, and BPMN models. Available in Annex 5 [130]
3		Archive of reports from the CODECS project documenting socio-technical transformations and digitalisation scenarios across the considered case studies. https://zenodo.org/records/16372574
4		Archive of models from the CODECS project, including structural, goal-oriented, and process views of the analysed transformations. https://zenodo.org/records/16372882
5	ModeLLer tool	Open-source block-based modelling environment supporting the participatory construction of semi-formal models and the integration of AI-assisted functionalities. https://github.com/Unipisa/blockly-modeller
6		Dataset of interaction logs from the first empirical study with end users under CT frameworks. Available in Annex 12 [130]
7		Dataset of interaction from the second empirical study with domain experts engaging the AI-assisted modelling tool. Available in Annex 13 [130]

11.2 Contribution

Across the design science iterations, the research progressively moved from artefact design to validation. This empirical study was primarily conducted within the primary sector, namely agriculture, and more particularly, digital agriculture—a field that is currently experiencing rapid growth [84] and bringing disruptive system changes [183]. The thesis focuses on LLS as socio-technical settings that involve a broad and dynamic set of stakeholders, representing different perspectives, interests, and roles in digitalisation processes [121]. Unlike more stable industrial environments, these contexts require approaches for knowledge exchange and co-creation capable of accommodating heterogeneity, openness, and the continuous reconfiguration of actors and practices [121]. At the same time, LLS provide concrete settings in which requirements for digital technologies can be elicited not only from a purely technical perspective, but also in relation to broader sustainability concerns [27].

The thesis contributed a set of artefacts grounded in empirical work. Table 11.1 summarises the artefacts produced throughout the research, including the tool source code, datasets, modelling guidelines, and other supporting materials developed to enable the application, evaluation, and reuse of the proposed approach.

The outcomes of this work both support LL practices and address gaps in the modelling literature. Accordingly, the thesis contributes at two complementary levels: research and practice.

11.2.1 Contribution to Research

This thesis mainly contributes to research by bridging RE and EUD. Both disciplines share a strong stakeholder-oriented perspective, yet the use of EUD approaches to involve stakeholders in requirements modelling actively remains underexplored, especially in multi-stakeholder contexts such as agricultural LLs. Empirically grounded contributions in this area are still limited: existing studies have typically been evaluated on a specific type of modelling language and within more controlled industrial settings [208], while other works have focused primarily on the application of EUD techniques to model-driven development activities rather than to requirements modelling [172]. Moreover, these approaches have not been investigated through procedures involving broad networks of stakeholders in participatory and open contexts.

In this respect, the thesis extended current knowledge by investigating how requirements modelling practices can be opened to non-expert stakeholders within participatory contexts.

The research contributions can be further articulated with respect to the two disciplinary areas involved.

Contribution to RE

First, the thesis contributes to RE through a method (cf. Ch. 4 to 6) for requirements elicitation and modelling that spans the full path from data collection to formalisation. The method is designed for agricultural LLs and explicitly includes stakeholder involvement in the elicitation, validation and refinement of requirements. While prior work has proposed operational approaches [120, 186], the main novelty of this contribution regards documenting the formalisation process (cf. Ch. 5). Indeed, practical aspects of requirements modelling are still only sparsely documented in the RE literature, with much of this knowledge remaining tacit and often confined to the individual expertise of requirements engineers. In this respect, the thesis contributes a more systematic and operational approach for turning distributed domain knowledge into shared semi-formal representations, addressing the lack of empirically grounded RE methods [222].

Second, the thesis contributes through the application of MoDRE in real-world contexts. In doing so, it helps address the lack of empirical studies previously highlighted in the literature [98, 145] and broadens the range of socio-technical settings in which MoDRE has been investigated. More specifically, the thesis provides empirical evidence on how stakeholders from the agricultural domain engage with semi-formal notations, focusing on three modelling languages—iStar, UML and BPMN—with different characteristics and purposes. The empirical validation was conducted in two complementary contexts: first, within LL stakeholders as part of the process modelling activity concerning their own LL (cf. Ch. 6), and second, it took place in plenary settings, where the models were utilised to facilitate external stakeholders' quick understanding of the dynamics of process transformation (cf. Ch. 5). This enabled the identification of specific challenges related to these notations, particularly when they are used by non-experts. The main novelty of this contribution lies in having investigated these modelling approaches with end users in ecological settings.

Third, the thesis contributes to the RE process by promoting a more bottom-up and structured approach to requirements elicitation (cf. Ch. 4 to 6). In common practice,

requirements elicitation is often conducted through conversational and informal techniques, while modelling tends to be introduced only in a subsequent phase [222]. Moreover, software engineering processes often rely on information elicited from the stakeholders, whereas subsequent analysis and modelling are carried out by developers in isolation, with the risk that the resulting representations reflect developers' interpretations rather than users' intentions [169]. The approach proposed in this thesis addresses this separation by integrating modelling more directly into elicitation, within a structured and participatory RE process. Thus, the proposed approach may help mitigate interpretative biases by enabling problem owners to participate more directly in constructing requirements representations and allowing the use of modelling languages as a means to strengthen elicitation [166]. This is particularly relevant in contexts where domain knowledge is distributed across heterogeneous actors and would otherwise remain largely tacit without the direct involvement of practitioners. In this respect, the thesis complements the predominantly textual orientation of mainstream requirements approaches [222] by advancing a more visual, participatory, and stakeholder-centred alternative.

Finally, through the artefacts (cf. contributions in Table 11.1, rows 1–4), we aim to provide the RE community with a basis for experimentation in contexts beyond the specific use case addressed in this thesis.

Contribution to EUD

This thesis advances EUD through the adoption of EUD approaches and principles both in the proposed method and tool. These contributions are relevant to EUD research because they extend EUD practices within RE—an area still only marginally explored from an EUD perspective, despite its close relationship with the HCI landscape [203]. Moreover, the application in agriculture is relevant, as interest in EUD in this domain is increasing, although existing work has so far been predominantly centred on development platforms [94].

At the empirical level, the application of EUD approaches through action research (cf. Ch. 4) and a field study (cf. Ch. 5) contributes to filling the gap of empirical investigations in ecological contexts highlighted in prior literature [23, 211]. Overall, the experience gained through this research strengthens stakeholder involvement as a crucial step for the development of advanced technologies that remain aligned with users' actual needs and practices. This commitment to user involvement was further advanced in the experimental evaluation of the AI-infused modelling tool (cf. Ch. 10), with input from domain experts. In this case, the contribution lies in empirical findings and design implications informing intelligent support for novice modellers.

At the methodological level, the contribution revolves around the development of the tool. Through the design of the tool and its evaluation using CT frameworks, the thesis contributes to extending the application of CT concepts beyond educational environments, where it is most commonly studied, into workforce-oriented settings, which likewise require appropriate approaches to cope with the growing complexity of technological environments [59]. Our methodological contribution is twofold. On the one hand, we proposed an EUD-grounded design approach for integrating AI support into a block-based modelling environment mapping functionalities to CT stages while maintaining user agency (cf. Ch. 8). On the other hand, through the evaluation of the tool

(cf. Ch. 9), we contributed to the emerging EUDability framework [22] by extending prior work [24] where the framework had been used to complement traditional usability metrics with a more nuanced assessment of tool functionalities in relation to users' computational abilities. In this thesis, we further advanced this perspective by implementing a process-based assessment grounded in log-based analysis, which enabled us to examine users' behaviours and modelling strategies during interaction with the tool.

Finally, the release of the tool and datasets as an open-source artefacts (cf. contributions in Table 11.1, rows 5–7) is intended as a contribution to the broader EUD community, enabling further experimentation, adaptation, and reuse in domains beyond the agricultural context investigated in this thesis

11.2.2 Contribution to Practice

From a practical perspective, the thesis delivers two artefacts to support the assessment of digital transformation of agriculture: the PoMeLO method and the ModeLLer tool.

PoMeLO provides a structured yet adaptable procedure that guides stakeholders in collecting data, creating visual models, and validating the resulting representations, even in contexts where RE expertise is limited.

ModeLLer supports the application of the method through a block-based, AI-enhanced approach, designed to lower entry barriers for novice modellers.

Together, these artefacts enable domain experts—such as agronomists, advisors, and LL stakeholders—to externalise knowledge distributed across multiple stakeholders and reason about socio-technical change more systematically. In doing so, the thesis contributes actionable support for improving communication, shared understanding, and decision-making in agricultural ecosystems interested by digital transformation.

11.3 Limitations

This research is still subject to the following limitations. First, the choice of semi-formal notations that constitute the method in Chapter 4 was based on preliminary requirements and pragmatic decisions. Different outcomes may result from using different languages. Comparative evaluation of the appropriateness of different languages in relation to the intended use, modelling goals, and application contexts is still missing. Similarly, the adaptation of the representations in terms of selected constructs, graphical enhancements, and the amount of information included in the models was the result of decisions taken by the requirements engineers together with the stakeholders involved in the action research. These decisions are closely linked to the agricultural LLs context in which the method was developed. Different results might have emerged with a different group of participants or in a different application context.

Second, the field study in Chapter 5 had an exploratory nature, aiming to observe end users in their natural project environment, thus ecological realism was prioritised over experimental control. Regarding the assessment of model creation, this was conducted through expert evaluation and complemented by participants' reported experience. As such, the results were also influenced by the individual attitudes and prior capabilities of the participants. Regarding model interpretation, the results were influenced by the specific study conditions in which the evaluation took place. As a consequence, some deci-

sions concerning the operationalisation of constructs, the aggregation of variables, and the correspondence between the measured variables and the constructs they were intended to represent may limit the precision and interpretability of the findings. However, such limitations are to some extent inherent in naturalistic studies, where higher ecological validity is often achieved at the expense of stricter control [207]. To strengthen the results obtained in the initial validation, we subsequently implemented the method across 19 LLs and evaluated it through focus groups and two TAM-based surveys, as documented in Chapter 6. At the same time, a limitation remains, since these evaluations were still conducted within the CODECS project and with the continued involvement of the requirement engineers who proposed the method. Further studies in different contexts would therefore be needed to consolidate these findings and assess the broader applicability of the method.

Third, although the modelling tool described in Chapter 8 was conceived to accompany the method, it does not yet provide the full range of functionalities required to support the level of detail enabled by the method itself. In developing the tool, priority was given to user experience and to the implementation of a minimum set of functionalities sufficient to enable empirical testing with end users, rather than to achieving full methodological completeness from the outset. As a result, the development of comprehensive models still requires following the full procedure proposed by the method and relying on complementary general-purpose modelling tools. At this stage, ModeLLer should therefore be regarded primarily as an entry point to participatory modelling—lowering the barrier for stakeholders to engage with semi-formal representations—rather than as a complete environment capable of operationalising the method end-to-end. More specifically, only a limited number of constructs are currently supported for each notation, with UML being more fully developed since it was the language adopted in the user studies. In addition, the mechanism for transformation across notations still requires further refinement, both to clarify the extent to which such transformations can be supported semantically and to provide a dedicated evaluation of the effectiveness and reliability of this functionality. Lastly, some limitations may concern the block-based interface itself. In particular, the vertical structure adopted for arranging blocks may become less effective when dealing with larger and more articulated models. This issue may be especially relevant in more prolonged modelling sessions, where representations are likely to grow in size and complexity. As a consequence, further work is needed to investigate the scalability of the interface, identify possible constraints in block arrangement and navigation, and assess whether alternative layouts or interaction mechanisms may be required to better support extended modelling activities.

Fourth, the evaluation study described in Chapter 9 was primarily aimed at obtaining design insights and informing the iterative refinement of the tool. Accordingly, the resulting evidence should be interpreted mainly as exploratory and may therefore be less robust for broader generalisation. Although some validation activities were conducted on the produced artefacts, these focused mainly on syntactic aspects and formal correctness of the representations rather than on the semantics of the modelling languages. A fuller understanding of these dimensions would require more longitudinal studies, capable of examining how the tool and the representations it supports are appropriated over time in real settings. Indeed, within open environments such as LLs, the adoption of the tool may evolve beyond its initially intended use and open up to multiple, more situated

forms of use [77]. In addition, the technical evaluation of the LLM-based functionalities is inherently dependent on the specific model versions and configurations available at the time of the study. Since LLMs evolve rapidly and their behaviour can vary significantly across versions, prompts, and deployment settings, the observed results should be interpreted as indicative of the feasibility of the approach rather than as definitive performance benchmarks. Future evaluations may yield different outcomes as models improve or as alternative prompting strategies and system architectures are adopted. Furthermore, the Wizard of Oz study used to evaluate the AI-infused interaction simulated certain AI capabilities in order to observe how domain experts would engage with such support. While this approach enabled the exploration of interaction dynamics prior to the full technical implementation of the functionalities, it also introduces limitations. In particular, although the WOz mechanism was concealed from participants, the study was conducted in the presence of a moderator, which may have affected the realism of the interaction and may still have influenced participants' behaviour. Therefore, the findings would benefit from further validation through studies involving more naturalistic conditions and longer-term usage scenarios.

Finally, this research prioritised a broad range of activities, employing multiple empirical methods—including surveys, focus groups and log analysis—and alternating technical evaluations with empirical validation in order to advance the design iterations. As a consequence, the sample sizes in some studies were constrained by both the limited availability of participants and the time constraints of the research. Therefore, while the results proved valuable for deriving design insights and informing the iterative refinement of PoMeLO and ModelLer, they may be less robust for broader generalisation.

Chapter 12

Open Research Directions

This chapter concludes the thesis outlining directions for future work. While our empirical work demonstrated the feasibility and usefulness of requirements modelling within agricultural living labs (LLs), several research directions remain open. Future work will concentrate on consolidating the proposed method and tool, while further exploring their theoretical and practical implications for requirements modelling and research on sustainable digital innovation. Table 12.1 summarises three high-level research directions and corresponding research goals outlined in the remainder of this chapter.

Table 12.1: Summary of future works

High-level research direction		Research goal
1	Extending the Application of the RE Method in LLs and Beyond	Application beyond the evaluated scope
		Cross-case and socio-economic analyses
		Longitudinal research
2	Further Experimentation in End-User Requirements Modelling	Measuring tool engagement and effectiveness
		Extending the tool capabilities
		Learning from modelling practice for tool evolution
		Deepen cognitive and theoretical perspectives on EUD-supported modelling
3	Further Exploring AI-Infused RE for Participation and Sustainability	Integration with informal modelling practices
		Exploring additional AI-assisted support
		Exploring multiple grades of AI assistance
		Supporting foreseen activities through requirements elicitation and generative AI

12.1 Extending the Application of the RE Method in Living Labs and Beyond

RE is a research area inherently close to users' needs. In this respect, this thesis contributes to extending its empirical application by investigating the adoption of an RE method in agriculture across >20 LLs.

Application beyond the evaluated scope Future research should address the first two limitations of Section 11.3, namely the bounded scope of the evaluated notations and

the specific empirical settings considered in this thesis. Additional studies are therefore needed to examine the applicability of the approach under different contextual conditions and to better understand the extent to which the results can be generalised beyond the cases considered in this thesis. Accordingly, future research may address questions such as: *What deviations in results emerge when different modelling notations are adopted?; What deviations emerge when the method is applied in contexts other than LLS?*

Cross-case and socio-economic analyses At the time of writing, ongoing activities within CODECS are undertaking cross-case comparisons of the set of models as a basis for cost-benefit analyses. Future work could build on these efforts by using the RE method developed in this thesis as a common analytical foundation for socio-economic analyses. In parallel, further research could investigate the requirements emerging from the cases and evaluate the extent to which existing technological solutions are fit for purpose with respect to such requirements. This would support a more systematic understanding of agricultural systems requirements and technological gaps. This opens up research questions such as: *In what ways can the RE method proposed in this thesis support cross-case comparisons for socio-economic and cost-benefit analysis?; What recurring requirements emerge across cases, and to what extent do existing digital solutions adequately address them?*

Longitudinal research In addition, further evaluations should investigate the long-term adoption of the approach through longitudinal and observational studies. Such studies could analyse how modelling artefacts evolve over time and how modelling practices become embedded within collaborative innovation processes. Extending the empirical evidence across multiple application domains, such as smart cities, energy transition initiatives, or healthcare innovation ecosystems, would not only strengthen the generalisability of the proposed approach but also contribute to the progressive development of a broader theory of RE methods [222]. Example research questions in this direction include: *How do modelling artefacts and modelling practices evolve through the long-term adoption of the approach?; What variations emerge in the application and outcomes of the approach across different socio-technical domains?*

12.2 Further Experimentation in End-User Requirements Modelling

EUD provides approaches that empower end users to take an active role in shaping software artefacts. In this thesis, these approaches have been applied to requirements modelling. EUD and RE share a common grounding in that both are concerned with stakeholders' problems and support.

Measuring tool engagement and effectiveness Another direction for future work concerns further experimentation with requirements modelling approaches for end users beyond the specific context investigated in this thesis. From this perspective, ModelLER can be proposed as an entry point to model-based practices for stakeholders who do not possess formal modelling expertise. Rather than being conceived as an alternative to

existing tools, it may support a gradual engagement with modelling by lowering initial barriers and enabling multiple pathways of learning and adoption towards semi-formal representations through a learning-by-doing approach. Advancing this direction also requires further development of the tool to address the third limitation identified in Section 11.3. This leads to questions such as: *To what extent does the tool engage novice and non-technical stakeholders with semi-formal requirements modelling?*; *To what extent can a learning-by-doing approach lower the initial barriers to semi-formal requirements modelling for end users*

Extending the tool capabilities Another line of work concerns the extension of the modelling capabilities of the tool. Future work could broaden the set of supported modelling notations and explore strategies for enabling more seamless transitions between structural, goal-oriented, and process-oriented perspectives. Such an evolution should be accompanied by improvements in usability, user experience, and scalability. For example, future research could explore alternative visual layouts and strategies to better support longer modelling sessions and the construction of larger and more articulated representations. This direction opens up research questions such as: *To what extent can block-based environments support multiple modelling notations without compromising usability for end users?*; *What visual and interaction design strategies best support the creation and navigation of larger modelling artefacts in participatory modelling settings?*; *To what extent is a notation-agnostic strategy, combining block-based interaction and model transformation, effective in supporting natural requirements modelling within participatory contexts?*

Learning from modelling practice for tool evolution The modelling practice itself can provide requirements for improved approaches to requirements elicitation and modelling for domain experts [77]. This opens up several relevant questions: *Which modelling languages are preferred by different categories of stakeholders when engaging in participatory requirements modelling?*; *Which modelling constructs are most frequently used and explored in practice?*; *How do users navigate across structural, goal-oriented, and process-oriented perspectives during modelling activities?*

Deepen cognitive and theoretical perspectives on EUD-supported modelling On the other hand, future research could include empirical studies investigating questions raised by theoretical work on the cognitive advantages of diagrammatic representations, as discussed in Section 2.2.1. A relevant direction could be to examine the extent to which learning and adoption of semi-formal notations can be supported by EUD approaches while preserving their expressive power. At the same time, such investigations should account for the trade-off identified in the literature [181]: while EUD approaches—specifically block-based ones—reduce syntax-related barriers, they may also be perceived as less authentic than conventional modelling environments. Comparative studies could therefore navigate this trade-off and clarify under which conditions EUD-supported requirements modelling is most beneficial. RQs may include: *To what extent can block-based support improve the effective use of constructs of semi-formal modelling notations?*; *How does the use of block-based modelling environments compare with conventional interfaces in terms of usability, perceived authenticity, and modelling*

performance?; How do outcomes and user experiences differ when an EUD approach is used instead of, or alongside, established modelling practices?

To investigate these aspects more systematically, future research could also consider educational contexts. Such settings could enable repeated and more fine-grained observation of how users appropriate modelling over time. In this way, the research could also extend prior work that has identified modelling as a key activity in the development of computational thinking literacy [158].

Integration with informal modelling practices Finally, a further line of investigation concerns the integration of informal modelling practices with semi-formal representations to strengthen requirements gathering through visual techniques. Prior research has explored how ideas can be externalised through sketches and progressively formalised into more structured representations [232]. Extending this line of work, future environments could support hybrid workflows in which informal artefacts coexist with semi-formal models. In such a layered perspective, semi-formal notations would offer semantic consistency, while the informal layer would preserve the natural fluidity of early ideation. This would enable the investigation of questions such as: *What forms of representation are most effective or preferred by stakeholders during requirements elicitation: informal or semi-formal?; How do informal and semi-formal visual approaches differ in terms of the requirements elicited, stakeholder engagement in participatory contexts?*

12.3 Further Exploring AI-Infused RE for Participation and Sustainability

The integration of AI into modelling is an expanding research area, and further experimentation would contribute to a better understanding of how different AI-based techniques can effectively support modellers. In this thesis, we have explored an AI-infused modelling approach, integrating into ModelLer several functionalities based on LLMs, as well as simulating adaptive assistance.

Exploring additional AI-assisted support Future research could explore alternative forms of AI assistance by also comparing different modelling environments and interaction paradigms. For example, comparative studies could investigate the experience of using ModelLer in comparison with visual whiteboard platforms (e.g., Miro), which are frequently used in co-design workshops. Such comparisons would help clarify the advantages and drawbacks of modelling with more constrained and structured environments specifically designed for semi-formal representations, as opposed to more flexible and informal collaboration tools. This line of inquiry may also help navigate the complexity highlighted by recent work on the difficulties end users encounter when interacting with AI systems through prompting [236]. Example research questions in this direction include: *How does the experience of AI-supported modelling differ between structured modelling tools and flexible whiteboard platforms?; Can structured modelling environments mitigate some of the prompting-related complexity faced by novice users when interacting with AI support?*

Exploring multiple grades of AI assistance Another path worth exploring concerns the use of different levels of AI assistance within modelling environments. Rather than treating AI support as a fixed feature, future work could investigate how different degrees of AI intervention affect the modelling process. For instance, AI support could range from minimal assistance—such as contextual suggestions or explanations—to more proactive forms of support, including automatic model generation from prompts. Exploring this spectrum would help clarify how AI systems can balance automation and user control, avoiding over-reliance on automated outputs while still providing meaningful cognitive and operational support. This opens up research questions such as: *How do different levels of AI assistance influence modelling performance, user control, and trust in AI-supported modelling environments?*

Supporting foreseen activities through requirements elicitation and generative AI A final direction for future research concerns coupling MoDRE with generative AI to support foreseen activities within sustainability-oriented participatory contexts. In these settings, MoDRE artefacts could function as boundary objects, serving both as structured inputs for AI agents and as analytical resources for stakeholders. This would enable the simulation and exploration of alternative socio-technical scenarios, the visualisation of possible impacts, and the analysis of different design options. In turn, this could enrich requirements elicitation and refinement by helping stakeholders early reflection on sustainability implications, negotiate trade-offs, and collectively reason about future systems. This opens up research questions such as: *How can AI-assisted foreseen activities support requirements elicitation in participatory contexts concerned with sustainable digitalisation?*

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